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Proceedings of International Research Conference, Feb 2010 “Services Management – The Catalyst”

Volume 2, Papers on:

- ❖ Current Trends In Service Industry
- ❖ HR Practices In Services
- ❖ Services In Banking, Finance And Insurance

3rd Annual Advertising and Brand Conference

Coming Up

March 27, 2010, 10:00 am onwards

Phoenix 3.0 – *Cosmetics of Advertising*

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- Can advertisement be outsourced?
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- Is Brand Really dead on web?
- A brand = the good+ the bad+ the ugly+ off strategies.
- Understanding the branding aspects through the Creative Directors eye

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- Mr. Kaushik Mitra, Creative Director, Bates 141.
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Foreword

Dear Readers,

A warm welcome to all of you. We are very happy to release this special issue of Spectrum which contains proceedings of the fifth international research conference on Services Management held at Kohinoor Business School and Center for Management Research's campus in Khandala on 20th February 2010.

The theme for this year's conference was Service Management- The Catalyst. In his welcome address at the conference, Dr. Bigyan P.Verma, Director, KBSCMR, highlighted how the service sector contributes to economic growth and has a crucial role in future. He pointed that the East Asian countries have achieved excellence in manufacturing, while India with its vast pool of skilled manpower is poised to leapfrog - building a service sector in sync with global economy. He emphasized how the extensive use of internet and information technology can help us achieve the goal of inclusive growth. Further he elaborated how service sector has maintained a healthy growth rate despite general economic slowdown, and thus having the theme Services Management - The Catalyst, is apt.

Dr.Vijay Khole, former Vice Chancellor, Mumbai University then delivered his keynote address. In his presentation Dr.Khole elaborated on the theme: - how the expectation that reallocation of resources from defense to civilian purposes after the cold war would help the economic development have not been realized. The major reason for this is the rise in terrorism and war activities. In India, health and education are vital for our progress. Service sector in India is growing with rapid urbanization, privatization and emergence of knowledge based economy. Services like micro-credit have the potential to transform our economy.

This was followed by presentation of researchers in the technical sessions dedicated to the following areas:

- Marketing challenges in service industry
- Importance of service quality
- Ethical dilemmas in service industry
- Human Resource practices in service industry
- Strategic role of Information technology in service industry.
- Operational issues in public services management

These sessions were chaired by various moderators from academia and industry.

We are pleased to inform that due to overwhelming response from researchers from India and abroad, this issue of Spectrum is being released in three volumes. Each volume is dedicated has to a set of subthemes:

- Volume 1 contains papers on Marketing challenges in service industry, Strategic role of Information technology in service industry, Operational issues in public services management
- Volume 2 contains papers on services related with banking and finance, HR and current trends in services industry.
- Volume 3 contains papers on service quality, service ethics and importance of management practices.

I am thankful to all the contributors of research papers – the conference delegates from various institutions, moderators, corporate professionals, research committee members and especially Prof. Saravan Krishnamurthy, the coordinator for the Annual International Research Conference 2010 for making this conference a grand success.

Dr. Ajit Gaikwad
Executive Editor, Spectrum 2010

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“India A Land of Opportunities”

-An Analytical Study of India’s Service Sector

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Abstract -

In developing countries like India, each and every sector contributes towards its growth. No matter how large or small that sector is, its importance is in the fact that in India’s GDP, share of service, industry and agriculture is 55.1 per cent, 26.4 per cent, and 18.5 respectively. Earlier it was said that India is an agricultural economy, but now with the LPG (Liberalization, Privatization, Globalization) it has opened its doors for various companies from in and out side the country. With the rapid industrialization, a large pool of talent has occurred for managing different sectors not only India’s traditional sector but highly technological one also. This talent force has many competitive advantages like English fluency, Cheap Labor, Hard work but smartly, Creativity and alike. This flair is being used in many industry and sectors. Service Sector, a major constituent of India’s growth is using this sector as in Technological Services, Education Services, Health-Care Industry, Finance Industry etc. And it would not be exaggeration to say that this talent force has been the catalyst of India’s Service Sector. But only this can not be the factor of Industry’s growth. There are many as improvisation in infrastructure, government policies and customer’s attitude which is changing day by day. For moving towards the pace of growth in the same way, Service Sector has been facing the challenges. For managing these challenges we requires some kind of strategies to deal. The present paper is an insight is the same direction and provides some strategies for sustaining this sector as the opportunity for India.

Introduction

Service sector is the lifeline for the social economic growth of a country. It is today the largest and fastest growing sector globally contributing more to the global output and employing more people than any other sector

Service Sector in India today accounts for more than half of India's GDP. The share of services, industry, and agriculture in India's GDP is 55.1 per cent, 26.4 per cent, and 18.5 per cent respectively. The fact that the service sector now accounts for more than half of GDP marks a watershed in the evolution of the Indian economy and takes it closer to the fundamentals of a developed economy. In the current economic scenario it looks that the boom in the service - sector is here to stay as India is fast emerging as global services hub. The real reason for the growth of the service sector is due to the increase in urbanization, privatization and more demand for intermediate and final consumer services. Availability of quality services is vital for the well being of the economy.

In advanced economies the growth in the primary and secondary sectors are directly dependent on the growth of services like banking, insurance, trade, commerce, entertainment etc.

Services

Before proceeding further, we must have to know that what exactly these services mean. As in categorizing goods there are two types of product, one is goods and other is services. Services, as in basic term is the non-tangible goods. To be more precise - "A service is non-ownership equivalent of a good." Service provision has been defined as an economic activity that does not result in ownership and is claimed to be a process that creates benefits by facilitating a change in customers, a change in their physical possessions, or a change in their intangible assets

Characteristics of Services

Service are different from goods and they can be differentiated as:

- ✓ Services are intangible in nature.
- ✓ These are perishable.
- ✓ The service provider cannot be inseparable from service as he/she must be presented with customer in providing services.

- ✓ Services are having simultaneity because as soon as the services are being requested, they will be consumed.
- ✓ Each service is unique. It is one-time generated, rendered and consumed and can never be exactly repeated as the point in time, location, circumstances, conditions, current configurations and/or assigned resources are different for the next delivery, even if the same service consumer requests the same service.

Service Categorization

Services are distinct in character as they can be 'n' number of services. There can be Health Care Services, Consulting Services, and Construction Services, for our convenience we have categorized them as:

1. Business Functions: It comprises Consulting, Customer Service, Human Resource Administrators
2. Child Care
3. Cleaning, Repair and Maintenance Services: Janitors, Gardeners, Mechanics, Construction, Carpentry, Electricians, Plumbing
4. Dispute Resolution: Arbitration, Courts of Law, Diplomacy, Incarceration, Law Enforcement, Lawyers, Mediation, Military, Negotiation
5. Education
6. Entertainment
7. Fabric Care
8. Financial Services: It includes Accountancy, Banks and building societies, Real estate, Stock Brokerages, Tax Preparation
9. Personal Grooming such as hair dressing
10. Health Care Services
11. Hospitality Industry
12. Information Services: It is what we call Data Processing, Data Services, Interpreting, and Translation
13. Risk Management: Insurance and Security
14. Social Services: Social Work
15. Transport
16. Public Utility: Electric Power, Natural Gas, Telecommunications, Waste Management, Water Industry

Service Management

With the enhancement of service sector ratio in total GDP of a country, there is a need for managing this sector as without management we cannot fully utilize the potential of

this sector. Besides, we cannot sustain current growth pace of this sector. For this we have to know first what service management is.

Service Management is integrated into Supply Chain Management as the joint between the actual sales and the customer. The aim of high performance Service Management is to optimize the service-intensive supply chains, which are usually more complex than the typical finished-goods supply chain. Most service-intensive supply chains require larger inventories and tighter integration with field service and third parties. They also must accommodate inconsistent and uncertain demand by establishing more advanced information and product flows. Moreover, all processes must be coordinated across numerous service locations with large numbers of parts and multiple levels in the supply chain. Among typical manufacturers, post-sale services (maintenance, repair and parts) comprise less than 20 percent of revenue. But among the most innovative companies in Service, those same activities often generate more than 50 percent of the profits.

Components of Service Management

Generally there are six components of management:

- I. Service strategy and service offerings
- II. Spare parts management
- III. Returns, repairs and warranties
- IV. Field Service Management or Field force effectiveness
- V. Customer management
- VI. Assets, Maintenance, Task Scheduling, Event Management

India's Service Sector

In alignment with the global trends, Indian service sector has witnessed a major boom and is one of the major contributors to both employment and national income in recent times. The activities under the purview of the service sector are quite diverse. Trading, transportation and communication, financial, real estate and business services, community, social and personal services come within the gambit of the service industry. One of the key service industries in India would be health and education. They are vital for the country's economic stability. A robust healthcare system helps to create a strong and diligent human capital, who in turn can contribute productively to the nation's growth.

Service Sector in India today accounts for more than half of India's GDP. According to data for the financial year 2006-2007, the share of services, industry, and agriculture in

India's GDP is 55.1 per cent, 26.4 per cent, and 18.5 per cent respectively. The fact, that the service sector now accounts for more than half the GDP marks a watershed in the evolution of the Indian economy and takes it closer to the fundamentals of a developed economy.

Services or the "tertiary sector" of the economy covers a wide gamut of activities like trading, banking & finance, infotainment, real estate, transportation, security, management & technical consultancy among several others. The various sectors that combine together to constitute service industry in India are:

- Trade
- Hotels and Restaurants
- Railways
- Other Transport & Storage
- Communication (Post, Telecom)
- Banking
- Insurance
- Dwellings, Real Estate
- Business Services
- Public Administration; Defense
- Personal Services
- Community Services
- Other Services

India's Journey in Service Sector

There was marked acceleration in services sector growth in the eighties and nineties, especially in the nineties. While the share of services in India's GDP increased by 21 per cent points in the 50 years between 1950 and 2000, nearly 40 per cent of that increase was concentrated in the nineties. While almost all service sectors participated in this boom, growth was fastest in communications, banking, hotels and restaurants, community services, trade and business services. One of the reasons for the sudden growth in the services sector in India in the nineties was the liberalization in the regulatory framework that gave rise to innovation and higher exports from the services sector.

This can further be analyzed as:

(1) Information Technology Industry

Information Technology industry has achieved phenomenal growth after liberalization. The industry has performed exceedingly well amidst tough global competition. Being

knowledge based industry; India has been able to leverage the global markets, because of the huge pool of engineering talent available and the proficiency in English language among the middle class.

(2) ITES sector

The ITES sector has also leveraged the global changes positively to emerge as one of the prominent industries. Some of the services covered by the ITES industry would be:

- Customer interaction services -Non voice and Voice.
- Back office, revenue accounting, data entry, data conversion, HR services.
- Medical Transcription.
- Content development and animation.
- Remote education, market research and GIS

(3) Retailing

Prior to liberalization, India had one of the most underdeveloped retail sectors in the world. After liberalization the scenario changed dramatically. Organized retailing with prominence on self service and chain stores has changed the dynamics of retailing. In most of the tier I and tier II cities supermarket chains mushroomed, catering to the needs of vibrant middle class. This indirectly contributed to the growth of the packaged food industry and other consumer goods.

Year	1998-99	1997-98	1996-97	1995-96	1994-95*	1993-94	1992-93	1991-92	1990-91	1985-86	1980-81
Services of which	569005 (51.16)	537642 (51.24)	498572 (49.91)	463980 (50.08)	423200 (49.15)	108974 (45.62)	102142 (45.34)	97045 (45.35)	92733 (43.69)	66306 (42.25)	50177 (40.99)
Construction	50328 (4.53)	49313 (4.70)	47382 (4.74)	46054 (4.97)	42560 (4.94)	10517 (4.40)	10386 (4.61)	10047 (4.70)	9833 (4.63)	7183 (4.59)	6114 (4.99)
Trade, hotels & restaurants of which	164355 (15.68)	155954 (15.61)	143858 (15.53)	127532 (14.81)	31057 (13.00)	28650 (12.72)	26827 (12.54)	26580 (12.52)	19649 (12.55)	14713 (12.02)
i) Trade	155120 (14.78)	147305 (14.75)	136087 (14.69)	121546 (14.12)	29082 (12.18)	26866 (11.93)	25147 (11.75)	24933 (11.75)	18498 (11.81)	13839 (11.30)
ii) Hotels & restaurants	9235 (0.88)	8649 (0.87)	7771 (0.84)	5986 (0.70)	1975 (0.83)	1784 (0.79)	1680 (0.79)	1647 (0.78)	1151 (0.74)	874 (0.71)
Transport, storage & communications of which	79819 (7.61)	74956 (7.50)	68788 (7.43)	63118 (7.33)	13057 (5.47)	12398 (5.50)	11785 (5.51)	11164 (5.26)	7951 (5.08)	5724 (4.68)
i) Railways	11521 (1.10)	11189 (1.12)	10647 (1.15)	9846 (1.14)	1746 (0.73)	1758 (0.78)	1778 (0.83)	1677 (0.79)	1404 (0.90)	1124 (0.92)
ii) Transport by other means	50144 (4.78)	47895 (4.79)	44513 (4.80)	41706 (4.84)	9209 (3.86)	8735 (3.88)	8275 (3.87)	7853 (3.70)	5309 (3.39)	3680 (3.01)
iii) Storage	655 (0.06)	646 (0.06)	652 (0.07)	621 (0.07)	188 (0.08)	180 (0.08)	175 (0.08)	177 (0.08)	163 (0.10)	122 (0.10)
iv) Communication	17499 (1.67)	15226 (1.52)	12976 (1.40)	10945 (1.27)	1914 (0.80)	1725 (0.77)	1557 (0.73)	1457 (0.69)	1075 (0.69)	798 (0.65)
Financing, insurance, real estate of which	127205 (11.44)	119814 (11.42)	110575 (11.07)	102438 (11.06)	94609 (10.99)	27711 (11.06)	25084 (11.14)	23972 (11.20)	21700 (10.22)	14708 (9.39)	10791 (8.81)
i) Banking & insurance	65814 (6.27)	58034 (5.81)	51343 (5.54)	45190 (5.25)	16111 (6.74)	13861 (6.15)	13107 (6.13)	11169 (5.26)	5828 (3.72)	3408 (2.78)
ii) Real estate, dwelling business	54000 (5.15)	52481 (5.25)	51095 (5.52)	49419 (5.74)	11600 (4.86)	11223 (4.98)	10865 (5.08)	10531 (4.96)	8880 (5.67)	7383 (6.03)
Community, social, personal of which	131047 (11.78)	124341 (11.85)	109705 (10.98)	102842 (11.10)	95381 (11.08)	26632 (11.15)	25624 (11.37)	24414 (11.41)	23456 (11.05)	16815 (10.74)	12835 (10.48)
i) Public admin. & defence	58631 (5.59)	48736 (4.88)	46635 (5.03)	43620 (5.07)	12483 (5.23)	12170 (5.40)	11570 (5.41)	11328 (5.34)	8016 (5.12)	5794 (4.73)
ii) Other services	65710 (6.26)	60969 (6.10)	56207 (6.07)	51761 (6.01)	14149 (5.92)	13454 (5.97)	12844 (6.00)	12128 (5.71)	8799 (5.62)	7041 (5.75)
Total GDP:	1112206	1049191	998978	926412	861064	238864	225268	213983	212253	156566	122427

* Figures for 1994-95 onwards are on a changed base (1993-94=100), so they show huge increases compared to the preceding period.
Source: Studies by Reserve Bank of India

(4) Financial Services-Banking And Insurance

Prior to liberalization these two sectors were controlled and regulated by the government. Nationalized banks and insurance companies had a firm grip over the market. After liberalization the banking and insurance domain have been opened up for private participation.

(5) Banking Sector

The three major changes in the banking sector after liberalization are:

- Step to increase the cash outflow through reduction in the statutory liquidity and cash reserve ratio.
- Nationalized banks including SBI were allowed to sell stakes to private sector and private investors were allowed to enter the banking domain. Foreign banks were given greater access to the domestic market, both as subsidiaries and branches, provided the foreign banks maintained a minimum assigned capital and would be governed by the same rules and regulations governing domestic banks.
- Banks were given greater freedom to leverage the capital markets and determine their asset portfolios. The banks were allowed to provide advances against equity provided as collateral and provide bank guarantees to the broking community.

(6) Insurance Sector

The Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority Act 1999 (IRDA Act) allowed the participation of private insurance companies in the insurance sector. The primary role of IRDA was to safeguard the interest of insurance policy holders, to regulate, promote and ensure orderly growth of the insurance industry. The insurance sector could invest in the capital markets and other than traditional insurance products; various market link insurance products were available to the end customer to choose from.

A graphical representation of India's service sector industry can be as:

Share of the service sector in India's GDP (in Rs. crore).

Figures in brackets indicate percentage share of different sectors and subsectors.

Figures for 1994-95 onwards are on a changed base (1993-94=100), so they show huge increases compared to the preceding period.

Need for Managing Service Sector

The boom in the services sector has been relatively "jobless". The rise in services share in GDP has not accompanied by proportionate increase in the sector's share of national employment. Some economists have also cautioned that service sector growth must be supported by proportionate growth of the industrial sector; otherwise the service sector growth will not be sustainable. In the current economic scenario it looks that the boom in the services sector is here to stay as India is fast emerging as global services hub.

Service sector is the lifeline for the social economic growth of a country. It is today the largest and fastest growing sector globally contributing more to the global output and employing more people than any other sector.

Future Trends of India's Service Sector will pose urgency for managing this sector. These changes can be like:

- Globally outsourcing industry would continue to grow.
- Following the success of US and UK, more countries in the European Union would outsource their business.
- Technological power shift from the West to the East as India and China emerge as major players.
- Political backlash over outsourcing would come down as companies reap the benefit of outsourcing.

Strategies for Managing Different Service Sector

Strategies for Health – Care Tourism

- I. Reliability: Zero defect services are essential for providing reliable solutions. Efforts should be to provide the best quality health services with the highest level of accuracy as it pertains to the life of an individual and any discrepancy leads to negative word-of-mouth, a potent means of promotion in service industry.
- II. Proficiency: Knowledgeable and highly skilled technicians, medical professionals and staff are the backbone of any health-care centre. They need to be carefully selected, developed and retained in the organizations. As the new gamut of job opportunities in the medical sector is opened by this sector; there should be some short term, full-time courses. Say for example, recently Indian Clinical Research Institute (ICRI) has launched a full-time course on medical tourism. The course from ICRI would offer training on hospital and health services financial management, marketing, OR techniques, costing, budgeting, Pricing techniques, hospitality and Patient relation and conflict resolution, healthcare laws and regulations, health insurance, business ethics and corporate governance. There should be some more efforts like this. Since, in any organization People are the key to success of the organization or we can address them as the back bone of the organization. Well-trained and skilled— doctors, nurses, technicians and support staff are the prerequisite for the success of any organization.

- III. Modernization: With the rapid advancement in the field of medical sciences, there is a need to use the state-of-the-art technology and equipment. It's true that India is following this but she should also continuously upgrade and modernize her medical infrastructure and facilities to provide superior services. We should also provide modern diagnostic services and these services centers should be sufficient enough to offer the basic as well as advanced diagnostic solutions. A wide variety of health checkup plans should be offered to cater to the different segments of the target market.
- IV. Professionalization: Developing a culture of excellence is the responsibility of the key personnel in the organization for promoting healthy workplace habits and developing a professional approach. Employees need to learn to be effective and efficient in all areas of their performance. People are most precious resource. They need to be nurtured and managed with special care. Best human practices related to training, development, performance evaluation, motivation and retention should be adopted to develop a team of professionals.
- V. Price Competitiveness: Organizations should offer the best value in terms of price to its customers. Prices should reflect the quality levels and services offered, and comparable to the industry trends. Pricing can be effectively done to suit target customer's purchasing power. Pricing strategy should be according to individual customer, type of products/services and place, time and duration of consumption.
- VI. Accessibility: health-care should be located at convenient places with long working hours and emergency facilities. Value added services should be identified and offered to the customers. As health-care tourism is combination of medical services with tourism, the destination or Place of service delivery assumes great importance. Most of the modern super specialty hospitals are located in metropolitan cities or state capitals to facilitate easy accessibility and transportation facilities while Spas, Yoga, naturopathy and meditation centers are usually located away from the cities and in natural surroundings like sea shores, hill/mountains/desert.
- VII. Event Management: A series of mini or mega events can be planned to attract medical fraternity or general public to educate them about preventive healthcare and staying healthy. Special packages or prices can be offered, experts can be invited or camps can be organized to make a special health related occasion.
- VIII. Medical standards: There should uniform medical education standards which should be followed strictly. These standards should be mandatory and accreditation of all Colleges and Hospitals. It should be started from the service creation and delivery of

service and is the called the Process. Design of process begins with the 'inquiry generation' and 'appointments' to 'discharge and send off'.

- IX. Networking: In the era of collaboration and outsourcing, health-care service providers should develop partnership with a well-defined group of institutions and individuals for mutual benefit.
- X. Quality control and Accreditation: There is an urgent need to bring in standard procedures and equipment to maintain the hallmark of quality.
- XI. Government measures: Government should provide soft loan to private players to increase the efficiency of their working. There should be greater industry and government interaction so that India can walk with the world. Government of India should also promote India as Health Tourism Destination. Policy measures taken by government are now holding a great significance as Private hospitals can do nothing in strict bureaucratic bottlenecks. Initiative has been taken by some state governments like Kerala, Karnataka, Goa (Go Goa), Himachal Pradesh, Uttaranchal (Dev Bhoomi), Maharashtra and Delhi. With the Government's support combining medical expertise and tourism, India can become "global health destination".
- XII. Promotion: As today's era is of technology and internet and you can avail the entire world to your computer. We should also connect our Cost Advantageous Land through this internet. There are websites like www.health-tourism-india.com and www.healthtourismindia.com. Healthcare organizations now-a-days have many advantages and can use modern marketing tools to promote their service for informing, image building, differentiating and attracting potential customers. Advertising in print media and broadcast media is found to be very effective in creating awareness about the services and facilities just as "Incredible India" is being promoted by Government of India. Advertising in related programs on television channels such as DD India, Travel and Living, Discovery, National Geographic, Animal Planet, BBC, CNN etc. allows marketers to reach to a considerably number of target audiences and show the facilities and offered to them.

Thus, an insight into these strategies reveals that effective management of these elements would enable the healthcare professionals to tap the vast potential in global health tourism and it can achieve this dream. It can shine in the sky of World Health Tourism only by customer satisfaction as customer delight is the core of service industry

Strategies for Telecommunication Industry

- **REDUCE THE PSYCHIC COSTS OF THE CUSTOMER:** The services are generally more difficult to evaluate than the products. For this, customers should be informed about the offers and options to let them make a better choice.
- **CREATION OF CREDIBILITY:** Credibility must be created in the minds of the customers before the customers can be persuaded to choose them.
- **VALUE DESCRIPTION:** It is difficult for the customers to determine the economic value derived from the purchase of services. Therefore, the customer should be convinced about the benefits and the value.
- **POSITIONING:** In order to win over the customers from other competing service providers, the advertising must create a new position through perception in the mind of the customer.
- **NEW SERVICES:** In the case of new services introduction, the marketing strategies play a very crucial role in informing the customers about the availability of such services, the benefits it creates for the customers, and how to switch over to such a service.

Strategies for Financial Service Sector

- **Marketing Activities:** Direct marketing, like advertisements, fosters a key element: name recognition. To target customers, advertisements can be placed in a variety of trade publications, regional business newspapers or narrow in on a select group in niche newsletters. Aside from getting the firm's name in circulation, the advertisement promotes its value.
- **Enhancement of Firms' capability:** The advertisements can establish integrity quickly, but firms also need to cultivate trust and relate to customers who entrust the company with their money. The firms must demonstrate capability and credibility. A firm can also provide a wide range of services not just concentrating on few.
- **Training for Brokers:** When brokers are a part of the community, they can network by informing people of their firm's specializations. Passing out cards to colleagues and friends will hopefully create branches that lead business back to the firm. Publishing articles on topics in the industry further illustrates the competency of brokers and managers.
- **Research and Analysis:** Every time there is an opportunity for the firms to introduce new services to their customers, what these opportunities are, how they can be followed, and others answers can be found through only research and analysis.

Strategies for Managing Education Services:

Over the last decade, education is increasingly being seen as an avenue to success. Education and training have not only helped develop human capabilities, but have created social opportunities for those who until then had little access to them. The numbers crowding our schools and colleges indicate this growing demand for educational services.

- Improving the Knowledge of Knowledge Providers: Teachers in the Educational Institutions are the only source which can make you sustain in the industry. Hence if their growth is bunged, the growth of students will also be bunged. For this, teachers should be motivated for doing research work, further education and alike.
- Expansion into different areas: Education institutes can also go ahead in introducing different courses into colleges so that students get choices of their own.
- Development of Students: Not only is the development of teachers necessary but the all round development of students, is also mandatory for educational institutions. For this, there can be different competition like Debate of Current Issues, Cultural Fest, and Personality Development.
- Practical insight to Theoretical: It is said every time that bookish knowledge is none of use in practical life, but this is not truth. Somehow, so called bookish knowledge is based on practice world but the difference is how to apply the theory into practical. Students can be learned this by Case-Study, Presentation, Projects etc.

Strategies for Managing IT Services:

IT infrastructure — that diverse collection of hardware, software, and services used to create, process, store, transmit, and display information — is the critical facilitator of the modern enterprise. IT enables business processes and decision making; it fuels organizational efficiency and growth and enables an explosion of collaboration, communication, and new business models. However, with these benefits come challenges: IT can be expensive to acquire and at times frustrating to maintain, and it regularly seems to need replacement or expansion. Business leaders routinely struggle with IT life-cycle management practices — the critical process of evaluating, funding, and retiring IT equipment. In the last few years IT services is being increased day by day as the human became high-tech. latest technologies needs latest service standards and highly trained technocrats. Although basic strategies for it will be:

- Improve technical stuff: with the increase in technologies a company needs certain technocrats that perfectly deal with all the problems in order to maintain service standards. For which in-house upgradation plans as well as outside special training plans will be carried out smoothly. Also as a strategic planner we need certain plans to retain our technocrats from switch over.
- Efficient Interaction: Service industry is mainly based on minimum response time and manages clients efficiently. For this a company provides maximum interfaces

through which a client can interact and remove its problems in minimum time. Interfaces like online chat rooms, toll free helpline numbers, onsite service programmes etc.

- Increase Clientage: Company uses the CRM activities to stay in touch with the clients on any special day on any special day eg. Birthday, Anniversaries, Holi, Diwali, Id, Christmas. Company convert their clients into friends i.e. energetic friends those encourage another of there personal friends to attach with company. Also invite all of the best clients in company meetings / parties

Conclusion

As the India is in growing / developing stage, it provides the platform for each and every industry to grow and mature. The paper is concluded with the possibilities to enhance the share of service sector using strategies for managing these services. But keep in mind, another sectors are also there. In order to make India Developed will grow every sector unbiasly. India is emerging as a land of opportunity despite insurmountable challenges faced by the country land. Its success now depends on how it overcomes them. As one Indian author said "If India just develops and pollutes the environment, thinking we'll clean this up later, it will become unlivable. Describing India as the 'new America'-- a land of opportunity-- she said "The vibe is that anything is possible. In India you have a multicultural, multi-religious democracy in a developing country that is an open and free society that has embraced capitalism. It's exciting and scary to think of the possibilities of that.

Table 1 Age -wise classification of respondents

Sample – Target	Sample Size
Age Group 20 to 40	100
Age Group 41 to 60	75

Table 2 Income wise classification of respondents

Income	No of respondents
Less than 50,000	27
50,001-1,00,000	33
1,00,001-2,00,000	63
2,00,001-3,00,000 and above.	52
Total	175

Table 3 Reasons (in percent) for switching brands

Product Category	Not Available	Offer/ Price	For a Change	Quality
Toothpaste	32 %	28 %	30%	04 %
Toothbrush	06 %	Nil	59 %	12 %
Bathing Soap	49 %	17 %	05 %	21 %
Talcum Powder	27 %	Nil	29 %	17 %
Detergent Bar	08 %	15 %	63 %	12%
Detergent Powder	43 %	3%l	46 %	08 %
Hair Oil	23 %	16%l	67 %	06 %
Shampoo	28 %	27 %	10%	30 %
Deodorant	70 %	Nil	20%	20 %
Health Drink	22%	77 %	12 %	10%
Average Percent	30%	16 %	34 %	14 %

Growth And Poverty
In
The Era Of Globalisation

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ABSTRACT:

Since India become part of the global economy and underwent economic reforms in 1991, its economy is growing at a faster rate of nearly 10 per cent per annum. The economy of India, measured in USD exchange-rate terms, is the twelfth largest in the world, with a GDP of around \$1.2 trillion (2010). It recorded a GDP growth rate of 9.1% for the fiscal year 2007–2008 which makes it the second fastest big emerging economy, after China, in the world. At this rate of sustained growth many economists forecast that India would, over the coming decades, have a more pronounced economic effect on the world stage. In the last two decades, a significant proportion of the population across the country has reaped the benefits of this economic growth. They have become the part of global economy and market, and their lives have transformed into one of global citizens with all the comforts and luxury in life. Analysts such as the founder of Forecasting International, Marvin J. Cetron writes that an estimated 300 million Indians now belong to the middle class: one-third of them have emerged from poverty in the last ten years. India is adding 40 million people to its middle class every year. Growing at the current rate, a majority of Indians will be belonging to the middle-class by 2025.

This research paper examines the impact of globalization on growth and poverty in India and shows how to help poor through globalization. The paper has been divided into four sections.

Section I presents introductory part of the paper and also focuses on objective, methodology and literature review of the paper. Section II presents meaning of globalization, economic growth rate and poverty in India. Section III suggests policy measures which need to be addressed to help poor in the era of globalisation. Section IV focuses on findings of the paper, limitations and concluding remarks.

Key words: Economic growth, Poverty, Globalisation.

“Our primary concerns are that globalisation should benefit all countries and should raise the welfare of all people throughout the world. This implies that it should raise the rate of economic growth in poor countries and reduces world poverty, and that it should not increase inequalities or undermines socio-economic security within countries”.

– World Commission on the Social Dimension of Globalisation (2004).*

INTRODUCTION:

Globalisation is something of a buzz word today. Trade and investment barriers between countries are rapidly breaking down. Companies are spreading their operations across the globe. Consumers are able to access an ever-growing basket of goods and services. Countries, companies and individuals are increasingly beginning to take into account what is happening across the world, rather than in only the country in which they are based. All of these advances are part of globalisation – which, at its simplest, means crossing borders.

Globalisation is not a new phenomenon. From the mid-1800s to the late 1920s, the world saw a frenetic pace of globalisation. If we look at the volumes of trade and capital flows across borders, relative to GNP and the flow of labour across borders, relative to populations, the period of globalisation preceding World War I was quite similar to what we are seeing today. Countries like Great Britain were huge investors in emerging markets. There were few currency controls and people migrated freely. Other than in wartime, countries did not require passports for travel before 1914. Immigrants moved into America without visas. The inventions of the steamship, railroad, telegraph and eventually telephone, all helped to shrink the world significantly.

If we look at Indian history then we will realise that Globalisation in a fundamental sense is not a new phenomenon for Indian economy too. The Indus civilization had one of the most globalised economies of that time. Even Hindu epics like, Ramayana and Mahabharata indicate that business operations existed across countries even in those days. Some cities specialized in the production of copper, others in beads and textiles-all meant for the export market. Once again the period of Gupta Empire saw huge exports from India. India is known as the "golden bird" though little gold is found in the country. The wealth of India in the past may be said to be substantially due to our having adopted an outward oriented trade policy. Globalisation is, so to say, in our blood.

But there are some important difference between the pervious era of globalisation and the current one. The degree and intensity of today's globalisation is much higher. What is also new is the sheer number of people and countries who can take advantage of the globalised economy and information networks. The previous era of globalisation was built around falling transportation costs, due to the invention of the railroad, the steamship and the automobile. Today's globalisation is being driven by falling telecommunications costs – thanks to microchips, satellites, fibre optics and the Internet.

OBJECTIVES:

The main objectives of this research paper are as follow;

1. To study the impact of globalisation on economic growth.
2. To study the impact of globalisation on poverty.

METHODOLOGY:

The present study basically being secondary data based exclusively relies on the publications and the reports of the study teams and committees of the government of India and from individual researches. Along with, the various journals of education have been taken into consideration for the purpose.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

1. Bardhan Pranab, writes in his paper entitled "Poverty and Inequality in China and India: Elusive Link with Globalisation", that reduction in poverty in these both countries is not due to globalisation only (Economic and Political Weekly, 22nd September, 2007).
2. Tuteja Usha, writes in her article entitled "New Concerns over rising poverty", that education and skill-building or rural poor are big challenges. In the absence of these attributes the rural poor will not be able to compete in the skill-based market economy and would remain at the bottom of the pyramid (The Economic Times, 8th November 2008).
3. Gaiha R & Kulkarni Vani, writes in their article entitled "Losing the war against poverty?" that at the all-India level, the calorie deficient population rose from about 68% to about 76% (The Economic Times, 31st December 2009).

4. Desai Ashok, writes in his article entitled "The Indian Cycle", that different sector of Indian economy are bouncing back (Businessworld, 4th January 2010).

SECTION II

GLOBALISATION:

Many scholars have attempted to define globalisation from their own respective perspective. Consequently, close to one hundred definitions of globalisation – some simple while others elaborate – exist. Given the degree of interest in the phenomenon, it is not surprising. Some of the definitions are given below

- According to Stiglitz, (Noble Prize winner for Economics (2001) and Chief Economist of the World Bank) "Globalisation is the closer integration of the countries and peoples of the world which has been brought about by the enormous reduction of costs of transportation and communications, and the breaking down of artificial barriers to the flow of goods and services, capital, knowledge, and (to a lesser extent) people across borders."
- International Monetary Fund defines "Globalisation as the growing economic interdependence of countries worldwide through increasing volume and variety of cross border transactions in goods and services and of international capital flows and also through the more rapid and widespread diffusion of technology."¹
- According to World Bank, "Globalisation means (a) gradual abolishment of import control over all items including consumer goods: (b) reducing the rate of import duties and (c) privatising public sector enterprises".²

The term 'globalisation' has, therefore, four parameters:

- Reduction of trade barriers to permit free flow of goods and services among nation-states;
- Creation of environment in which free flow of capital can take place among nation-states;
- Creation of environment, permitting free flow of technology; and
- Last, but not the least, from the point of view of developing countries, creation of environment in which free movement of labour can take place in different countries of the world.ⁱ

The advocates of globalisation, more especially from developed countries, limit the definition of globalisation to only three components, unhindered trade flows, capital flows and technology flows. They insist on developing countries to accept their definition of globalisation and conduct the debate on globalisation within the parameters set by them. However, several economists in the developing world believe that this definition is incomplete and in case the ultimate aim of globalisation is to look upon the world as a 'global village', then the fourth component, unrestricted movement of labour cannot be left out. But the entire issue whether debated at the World Bank, IMF or World Trade Organisation (WTO) blacks out 'labour flows' as an essential component of globalisation.

GLOBALISATION AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN INDIA:

It should be noted here that the average rate of gross domestic product during the first three decades of planning had remained at a level around 3.4 percent. It was static and stagnant growth rate, which was termed as a 'traditional growth rate' or 'Hindu Growth Rate' by economists like Prof. Raj Krishna.

There is no doubt that globalisation has been able to promote a relatively higher growth. After the teething troubles of the first two years viz., 1991-92 and 1992-93, the growth rate during 1993-94 to 1997-98 has averaged to more than 7 per cent per annum. The growth rate during the Eighth Plan (1992-97) period works out to be 6.8 per cent. While the growth rate during the ninth plan (1997-2002) period remained 5.5 per cent a bit below than the growth rate eighth plan period, but in the tenth five year plan (2002-2007) India grew at 7.9 per cent rate. India achieved record annual Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth, averaging 8.45%, in the five years, 2004-2005 to 2008-09. The economy of India, measured in USD exchange-rate terms, is the twelfth largest in the world, with a GDP of around \$1.2 trillion (2010). It recorded a GDP growth rate of 9.1% for the fiscal year 2007–2008 which makes it the second fastest big emerging economy, after China, in the world. At this rate of sustained growth many economists forecast that India would, over the coming decades, have a more pronounced economic effect on the world stage.

Finance Minister Pranab Mukherjee on 8th January, 2010 said that he was optimistic that India, which along with China is leading the drive out of a global recession, could return to annual growth of 9-10 per cent in a few years time. The Indian economy grew an annual 7.9 per cent in the second quarter ending September 2009 (The Economic Times, 7th January, 2010). Clearly, the Indian economy has emerged quickly and relatively unscathed from the Global Liquidity Crisis (GLC), much faster than the global economy.

GLOBALISATION AND POVERTY IN INDIA:

The standard argument by pro-globalisers has been that the opening up of the economy leads to dynamic benefits, which improve the growth rate, and the latter in turn reduces poverty. The static allocation effect may also be pro-poor as it expands job opportunities for unskilled labour, which is plentiful in poor countries. Now let us we look at the link between growth and poverty reduction in India. Official poverty estimates show that the poverty percentage declined from 44.5 per cent in 1983 to 27.5 per cent in 2004-

05. Again the international financial press often attributes this significant decline in poverty is due to globalisation. But no one has yet convincingly demonstrated that this decline is mainly due to globalisation. There is no convincing statistical demonstration of this, as no one has yet tested a causal model where, controlling for other factors and applying a suitable identification strategy, global integration has been found to be the main cause of the dramatic decline of poverty in India (see Bardhan, Pranab 2007). In the absence of such a demonstration, a careful eyeballing of the data suggests that the more important reasons for the large decline of poverty over the last three decades may actually lie elsewhere. Rural poverty reduction in India may be attributable to the spread of Green Revolution in agriculture, large anti-poverty programmes or social movements in India, and not the trade liberalisation of the 1990s. National Sample Survey (NSS) data actually suggest that the rate of decline in poverty has somewhat slowed down in 1993-2005, the period of intensive opening of the economy, compared to the 1970s and 1980s. It may not be unconnected with the fact that agricultural output (and total factor productivity in agriculture) grew at a slower rate in the last decade compared to the earlier decade. This may be largely on account of the decline in the public investment in rural infrastructure (like irrigation or prevention of soil erosion), which has little to do with globalisation. Some disaggregated studies across districts in India have also found trade liberalisation slowing down the decline in rural poverty. Such results may indicate the difficulty of displaced farmers and workers in adjusting to new activities and sectors on account of various constraints (for example, in getting credit or information or infrastructural activities like power and roads, large incidence of school dropouts, and labour market rigidities), even when new opportunities are opened up by globalisation.

This high rate of poverty can be attributed to:

- High level of dependence on primitive methods of agriculture
- Rural urban divide
- 75 per cent of Indian population depends on agriculture whereas the contribution of agriculture to the GDP was 22 percent
- While services and industry have grown at double digit figures, agriculture growth rate has dropped from 4.8 per cent to 2 percent
- High level of inequality arising from rural-urban divide
- High population growth rate
- High Illiteracy, about 35 percent of adult population
- Unemployment and under-employment
- Protectionist policies pursued till 1991 that prevented high foreign investment

SECTION: IIIMAKING GLOBALISATION PRO-POOR:

1. Link urban markets with rural farming hinterlands:-

India's economic growth has been concentrated almost exclusively in urban centres, while rural areas remain largely mired in appalling poverty. Since 70 percent of India's population lives in rural countries, the vast majority of Indians find themselves cut off from their nation's economic boom. Rural Indians generally depend upon agriculture for a livelihood and are trapped by a political system that privileges sharp-toothed middlemen over poor farmers. A law requiring farmers to sell produce through state-run markets encourages bureaucracy, waste and high consumer prices. The farmer continues to be beholden to the local monopolist for distributing his produce. One study suggests that tomato farmers in Karnataka, for example, received rupees 2 per kilogram, compared to the end-user price of rupees 8.20. A 2003 report in Delhi states that while the tea price in the retail market was around Rs. 160 per kg, in the auctions it was less than Rs. 50 per kg (and while auction prices have fallen, retail prices of tea continue to rise). Well-placed foreign investment working closely with India's entrepreneurs, however, could give farmers direct access to urban markets-and thus allow rural Indians to share in their country's economic growth (see Khanna, Tarun 2008).

2. Agricultural growth:-

For reducing rural poverty, agricultural growth is important. The Indian evidence clearly shows that the growth of food grains production in the post-reform period has been lower than those for earlier periods despite successive good monsoons for the last ten years. It is true that the area under coarse cereals and pulses has been shifted to oilseeds. But, the yields of rice and wheat have been more or less stagnant. Even the growth rate of non-food grains has been lower in the post-reform period. The growth rate in agriculture has been low in spite of increase in terms of trade and private investment in agriculture. Increasingly, a favourable term of trade for agriculture is supposed to attract private investment into agriculture, thereby leading to growth in output and demand for rural labour. In a simple neoclassical framework, since agriculture is more labour intensive, a rise in the relative price of its output (i e, food) leads to an increase in real wages and investment into agriculture.

3. Labour absorption in agriculture and rural non-farm employment as an escape route:-

Any strategy for reducing poverty has to concentrate both on employment intensity as well as labour productivity. The survey suggests that effective measures are needed for raising agricultural labour

productivity without compromising on the employment intensity of agriculture.

4. Urban planning:-

Rapid urbanisation is one of the indicators of development. However, efficient urban planning is needed to absorb some of the rural workers and to reduce urban poverty.

5. Reduction in regional disparities:-

We have seen above that rich states have benefited from economic reforms because of better physical infrastructure and human development. There is a need for higher investment for improving physical and human capital in poor states.

6. Information technology:-

It is argued that information technology would increase employment potential of the economy. However, initially mainly skilled workers will benefit from information technology. This technology should be made friendly to the poor. Because of scale economies, the unskilled workers may also benefit over time.

7. Direct Poverty Alleviation Programmes:-

The programmes which are aimed at directly helping the poor instead of the entire population are termed as targeted poverty alleviation programmes. The main objective of these programmes is to directly help the poor to improve their economic, physical (nutrition, health) and social conditions. These schemes are supposed to protect a person or household in the case of both chronic as well as transient poverty (see Yesudian 2007).

8. Some other measures:-

It, of course, does not absolve the responsibility of international organizations and entities in helping the poor of the world (see Bardhan Pranab 2008). This can be achieved by -

- Working toward a reduction of rich-country protection on goods produced by the poor,
- Energetic anti-trust action to challenge the monopoly power of international (producing and trading) companies based in rich countries,
- Facilitating international public-private partnerships in research and development of products (for example, drugs, vaccines, crops) suitable for the poor,
- Organizing more substantial (and more effectively governed) financial and technology transfers and international adjustment assistance for displaced workers and farmers, help in (legal and technical) capacity building for poor countries in international trade negotiations, and

SECTION: IV

FINDINGS:

- Globalisation has helped to achieve higher growth rate.
- There is no convincing statistical demonstration that global integration has been found to be the main cause of the dramatic decline of poverty in India.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

This paper is based on primary data, so limitation of primary data is the limitation of this research paper.

CONCLUSION:

Nothing is an unmixed blessing. Globalisation is also neither good nor bad: it offers both opportunities and risks. This means that we must seize the opportunities and, at the same time, limit the risks. The world needs more not less globalisation, but it must be a better globalisation.

Notes

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Sustainable Development of Renewable Energy and Its Opportunity in India (Job Opportunity)

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Abstract:

India is facing an acute energy scarcity which is hampering its growth of industrial and development of economic. Apart from increasing the energy supply, renewable energy resources will help India in extenuating climate change. Energy is a necessity and sustainable, renewable energy is a vital link in industrialization and growth of India. A transition from conventional energy systems to those based on renewable energy resources is essential to meet the ever-increasing demand for energy and to address environmental concerns. However today's the global challenges in the form of population growth, source consumption and environmental deprivation. The environment is endangered by the perils of climate change, global warming, and energy crises. There is a need to protect the environment and at the same time to provide people with opportunities for sustainable livelihoods. This article looks at employment opportunities in the renewable energy section. This section has many eco-job opportunities. As a positive step towards understanding their role in solving the problem of the energy crisis, it is essential that people first understand what the problem is, where the solution lies and how some organizations have already started working on this issue. Working towards creating an environmentally sustainable world, while also providing employment opportunities.

Keyword: Renewable Energy. Job Opportunity. Job Creation. Sustainable Energy.

Introduction:

India is the fifth major consumer of fossil fuel energy in the world, and it is projected to exceed Japan and Russia to become the world's third largest energy consumer by 2030. At the same time, India is facing a serious energy scarcity which is hampering its industrial expansion and economic development. India is trying to stopping the lack of energy resources through a judicious consumption of renewable energy resources, such as solar energy, biomass energy, geothermal energy and wind energy. India has seen a 12% rise in investment in the renewable energy region with an investment of \$3.7 billion in 2008. That's a magnificent investment indeed in absolute terms, though a 12% growth does scant justice to the big needs the country has from renewable energy. It is expected that this growth rate will be much higher in future.

India is facing an acute energy scarcity which is hampering its growth of industrial and development of economic. Setting up of new power plants is unavoidably dependent on import of highly unstable fossil fuels. Apart from increasing the energy supply, renewable energy resources will help India in extenuating climate change. India is heavily dependent on fossil fuels energy for its energy consumption needs. Most of the power production is carried out by mineral oil-based and coal power plants which give heavily to greenhouse gases emission. The standard per capita consumption of energy in India is approximately 500 W, which is much lower than that of residential countries like USA, Australia, Europe, Japan, Australia, Japan etc. However, this is expected to rise roughly due to high economic development and rapid industrialization. The consumption of electricity is growing on the worldwide basis. Energy is a necessity and sustainable renewable energy is a vital

link in industrialization and growth of India. A transition from conventional energy systems to those based on renewable energy resources is essential to meet the ever-increasing demand for energy and to address environmental concerns. However today's the global challenges in the form of population growth, source consumption and environmental deprivation. The environment is endangered by the perils of climate change, global warming, and energy crises. Unless some direct remedial measures are taken, things are only expected to get worse. There is a need to protect the environment and at the same time to provide people with opportunities for sustainable livelihoods. If people get involved with conserving the situation by producing clean energy, then we will concurrently address the problems of unemployment and environmental degradation (Bureaus, 2009).

This article looks at employment opportunities in the renewable energy section. This section has many eco-job opportunities. As a positive step towards understanding their role in solving the problem of the energy crisis, it is essential that people first understand what the problem is, where the solution lies and how some organizations have already started working on this issue. Working towards creating an environmentally sustainable world, while also providing employment opportunities.

Sustainable Development and Renewable energy:

The economic growth of modern societies is critically dependent on energy. Energy is very important for sustainable growth. It is used to create electricity for a diversity of needs, among which are transport needs, industrial needs and domestic needs. The methods of supply, production and consumption of energy are key issues in sustainable growth because they strongly influence the local and global environment. However, the existing methods of energy production are mainly by the use of fossil fuels. These fossil fuels are mostly responsible for the greenhouse effect and global warming, as they are accompanied by enormous emissions of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. These methods of production are not sustainable in the long run and therefore do not give to sustainable growth (Asifa & Muneer, 2007).

However, the use of fossil fuels to produce energy is not favorable to achieving sustainable growth. Oil, coal, and natural gases are all fossil fuels. Over millions of years, the decompose of plants and animals resulted in the configuration of fossil fuels, with these fuels lying covered between the layers of the earth. While underground heat and pressure these days are still creating more fossil fuels, they are being consumed faster than they are created. When fossil fuels are burned, they release enormous amounts of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere, adding to climate change and global warming. Given that energy utilization will continue to increase with the demands of increasing population, with the gap between the supply and demand of energy growing wider than before, the use of fossil fuels has two different disadvantages. The first is that they are environmentally damaging since they release greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. The second is that they are actually unsustainable, as they will eventually get exhausted as the demand for them surpasses the supply, leaving the world searching for substitute methods to manufacture energy. We need a resolution to this problem. Firstly, communities and governments must collectively choose to change their ideal of energy use. Secondly, more sustainable sources of energy must be tapped. This would not only mean moving away from the current condition in which most humanity energy is supplied by fossil fuels but a decrease in the energy and contamination intensity of economic actions. Preferably, we need perpetual energy sources. Renewable energy systems offer the solution. Renewable energy, as the name suggests, makes use of sources that do not get depleted by usage. This has three broad implications.

The energy shaped is "clean" as opposed to fossil fuels that produce massive amounts of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. Thus it protects contributes and the environment to the alleviation of climate change. Renewable energy utilizes natural sources like sunshine, water and wind. It is not dependent on

restricted supplies of petroleum, coal, diesel, etc. that will ultimately get exhausted, resulting in a fuel lack. Renewable energy is thus sustainable in the long run, as it can be continual for an indefinite period into the future as long as there are natural resources like flowing water, sunshine and wind. Energy is a vital factor in bringing about enlargement in poor countries and these countries frequently face a constant shortage of energy. Most of these developing countries are not in a situation to import enormous supplies of fuel or coal to meet their energy requirements, so the shortage persists. Thus these countries should give confidence the acceptance of renewable energy to meet their growing energy needs. This will not only cut their dependence on imports of petroleum to produce energy, but will also ensure a sustained local source of energy (Paul, 2009). There is a growing amount of awareness on renewable energy today, and many countries have set up renewable energy initiatives, which are estimated to grow in the future.

Renewable Energy and Job Opportunity:

Renewable energy is a way to join the goals of job employment (then income creation) and environmental safety, thus contributing to sustainable growth. One process to implement this prospective relation between environmental and employment defense is to develop job-led enterprises to create and market renewable energy to off-grid consumers. Job-led renewable energy enterprises are a viable means of achieving sustainable growth, as they encourage technologies that are less damaging to the global vicinity, while at the same time as long as sustainable income-generating opportunities for people.

Tapping the energy for promoting renewable energy will have a three-fold effect.

It will release new energy in accomplishing many of the goals set by the global community for climate change
 It will move people into creative and long-term nation building actions, away from nonproductive searches
 It will straight people to income generating actions in this sector.

Thus renewable energy projects proffer capable results and should be adopted on a worldwide level. Eventually, the need is to encourage employment in renewable energy activities in as many national settings as possible. The growth of renewable energy can transport encouraging and touchable effects on employment because this energy is local in nature and can frequently be made accessible without the existence of serious infrastructure. Developing countries have huge potential for renewable energy, particularly in rural areas. It is usually rural areas that are not linked to the network for electricity. Urban areas are usually well linked to the network, even if the power generated is by conventional fuels such as coal. Rural inhabitation is frequently dispersed non-uniformly, with many rural communities situated far away from other rural communities. In such cases, it is not economical to try to connect these rural pockets to the network. At the same time, these communities do need contact to electricity. Renewable energy provides the answer to this. Thus it is in the rural areas of increasing countries that renewable energy is supposed to be focused (Education development Center, 2002).

Apart from rural areas, a new area that holds promise is the tourism zone. This sector offers especially excellent opportunities for the improved use of renewable energy. If a region enjoys tourist passage, then the region's environment needs to be conserved while providing for the increased energy require during peak periods due to the steady inflow of visitors. In addition, there is growth in tourism ensuring the attendance of a valuable advantage needed for growth – dynamic and hard working people. Evaluate this to the contrast of the people that migrate to the cities hopeful for jobs, and become aggravated, discontent, and disenfranchised, intimidating political and economic constancy. Consisting principally of small and medium sized enterprises, the renewable energy sector is known as a main source of new employment opportunities (Heinberg, 2009).

The renewable energy production can be termed a “sunrise” industry. It has been predicted that

internationally, jobs in the renewable energy and energy effectiveness industries will rise to more than 3 million over the next twenty years and lead to the opening up of a new range of career opportunities. The global profits of promoting off network renewable energy projects are indirect if measured alone. These projects contribute to a global initiative to catalyze markets for rural renewable energy applications that jointly will serve huge shares of the two billion people in developing countries presently without electricity. These markets will also be the opportunity for people to earn their livelihoods and protect the environment.

The use of renewable sources of energy and renewable energy industries should therefore be a significant factor for supporting entrepreneurial ideas and employment. In order to generate a positive climate for the utilization of the renewable energy industries and its diverse applications it is important to teach the men and women who would implement them. Thus, important components of any developmental attempt are education and training. The early interest of individuals and community organizations benefiting from the accomplishment of renewable energy projects is an important march towards its success. The signs are positive already. The Oil Company announced that by 2050, 50% of its entire business is likely to be through renewable energy industries.

Trained staffs are wanted at the technical and professional levels to meet the existing and predictable increase in jobs. With the comprehension and proficiencies to develop, promote and apply new methods of sustainable energy manufacture, they are expected to improve the efficiency of accessible systems and appliances. Opportunities for job in the renewable energy sector can be generated by nongovernment institutions, government institutions and the private sector or can be purely self-employment. Several organizations and governments have identified ways and means of conserving and preserving renewable sources of energy (McKee, 2002).

Expected job opportunities in renewable energy lie in the following areas: ☐

Design and Planning, Assessment of Social and Environmental Impacts of Energy Systems, Energy Economics and Energy Management, Energy Policy Analysis and Development, Energy Efficiency Consulting, Research and Development

The organizations that could offer such employment opportunities are: Universities and private industry research organizations, International aid organizations, Energy efficiency and environmental consultancies, Energy companies exploring possibilities of alternative forms of energy, Renewable energy manufacturing and installation companies, Non government organizations.

Job Creation and Renewable Energy (Type of Job Examples)

Biogas Energy Mechanic	Bio-plant Mason
Community Recycling Manager	Eco-Campaigners
Eco-Infomediary	Energy Mechanic
Energy Specialist Manufacturer & Marketer of Solar Lanterns and	Energy Specialists
Energy Specialists (Solar Water Heating Systems) Mechanic	Entrepreneurial Development
Entrepreneurial Development & Funding	Geothermal Geologist
Manufacturer & Marketer (Solar Lanterns, Woodstoves)	Manufacturer & Marketer (solar PV, biogas systems & accessories and wind turbines)
Plant Architect & Designer	Plant Architect & Designer, Wind Meteorologist
Recycling Engineer	Resource Economist
Solar Energy Based Systems.	Solar Energy Mechanic
Wind meteorologists	Wind Turbine Engineer
Wind turbine engineers	

Renewable Energy and it Regional Require:

A range of renewable energy technologies accessible are not uniformly grown-up or cost efficient. However, most forms of renewable energy still have an important way to go before they become competitive with fossil fuel technologies, particularly for power production. This needs concentrated R&D efforts. Unsuccessful attempts in the combination of social and environmental considerations into the economic resolution making development can be identified as one of the main bassettes for the unacceptable outcome of sustainable growth efforts. Issues such as poverty mitigation and equity should be addressed in the light of energy and environmental factors.

The importance that is being placed on global renewable energy requires a considerable dedication of financial and human resources. The rising role of renewable energy forms the policy goal of a number of countries. However, at present many renewables are in a classic chicken and egg condition - manufacturers and financiers are unwilling to invest the capital needed to decrease costs when demand is low and doubtful, but demand stays low because potential economies of level cannot be realized at low scales of production. Act is required in key areas, which, requiring on the energy sources and the needs of the country in problem can cover the way for substantial role to the world energy supply. An apparent mismatch has been recognized between the significance of renewables in the international energy and environmental scene and the resources at present being exploited for their process and development. Here, the government needs to step in. Delivering and producing energy to the customer involves environmental costs and energy prices should reflect them in a better way. Investments in new energy contribute plants and the compulsory infrastructure should be optimized from both environmental and economic stand points. Greater investment in development, research and demonstration should aim at bringing down the costs of renewable energy industries. Attracting private investment in renewable energy, in both developing and developed countries require initiatives such as guaranteed initial markets for the production of renewable energy. Raising public's

consciousness of renewables should be high priority. International financial support bodies, private and public organizations, and development assistant agencies should engage themselves in the action of promoting international cooperation (Wohlgemuth & Missfeldt, 2000).

The energy trade is poised to turn out to be a service industry. It must be well equipped to respond to the diverse service needs of enterprises and households. In order to promote entrepreneurial risk-taking and competition, governments should set up lawful and regulatory environments, and ensure access, accountability and transparency to information that will help in the development of decision-making. A special position should be accorded to renewable energy, since it is environmentally friendly. It is possible to decrease the environmental impacts of conservative energy use by promoting renewable energy. Also, renewable energy sources save foreign exchange since they are domestically accessible. While this is a rapid growing industry, it opens up opportunities for export industries as well. Therefore, giving preferential treatment to renewable energy and energy effectiveness projects would promote sustainable growth by maximizing social and environmental advantages like creating new jobs and decreasing air pollution.

The Implementation of Renewable Energy Projects in developing countries delivers clear benefits for energy capable industries. The potential to meet the needs of the customers, the convenience of maintenance and service spare parts, the contribution of financing agencies and local stake holders, the ability to retain skilled employees, and established cost recovery have been recognized as some of the driving values in the implementation process of these sustainable energy projects.

In the case of most of the less developed or developing countries, the technical-know-how is always transferred from the experienced urbanized countries. The transfer of industries should meet three basic criteria: the presence of locally suitable technologies and processes, they must reflect the best practices at the time of the project in order to avoid the dumping of obsolete ones and of course, they should be very low emitters of greenhouse gases. The recognition of the role-players and stakeholders in the local renewable energy sector is a precondition for the successful implementation of local to worldwide renewable programs. First is the government, which must offer a policy framework and provide various incentives and measures to promote renewable energy industries. Then there is the renewable energy service industries and the renewable energy manufacturing industry, including distributors, retailer, installers and consultants (Wiser & Bolinger, 2005). Traditional energy companies can also be well-known as potential vehicles of development. Trade union organizations, environmental NGOs, and consumers who need energy services can drive market forces.

Renewable Energy Development in India:

In India, major efforts have been made towards the propose, growth, field demonstration and among the rural energy programmers, large-scale use of biogas plants and improved cook stoves (Chulhas) is promoted as part of the general Program. Over 3 million biogas plants and nearly 31 million improved cook stoves have been installed. These rural energy programs efficiently save about 22 million tons of petroleum and forest every year and help in creating important employ opportunities in rural areas (Swaminathan, 1999).

In the area of solar energy operation, solar thermal technologies and solar photovoltaic are finding ready reception for a variety of commercial and industrial applications, in addition to in rural areas without electricity. More than 700,000 PV systems aggregating to 57 MW and covering over 30 diverse applications have been deployed. Home lighting and solar lanterns systems are now being used in nearly 390,000 homes and are contributing to considerable savings of kerosene. About 500,000 square meters of solar collector area has so far been installed for solar water heating systems in domestic and industrial sectors. About 190,000 rural radiotelephones are also being powered by solar energy (Ottinger & Jayne, 2000).

More than 1600 MW capacity of network power is now based on renewable energy sources. Major achievements have been made in wind electric generation with 1170 MW installed capacity. 217 MW capacities is set up throughout small hydropower and another 222 MW capacity throughout biomass power. A 140 MW Integrated Solar Combined Cycle Power Project, to be set up at Mathania near Jodhpur in Rajasthan has been approved by the Government. It will have a 35 MW solar thermal power component based on parabolic trough collectors, and a 105 MW combined cycle component using gas turbines and naphtha as fuel. To support power production from renewable energy, 14 States have so far announced policies to provide planning for banking, wheeling, third party sale and buy back of power for non-conventional energy based power production. In line with those policies, the State Electricity Boards enter into remunerative Power Purchase Agreements for renewable energy projects.

The increase of different renewable energy industries has been aided by a range of fiscal and other support measures. The policy is clearly directed towards a larger thrust on overall growth and encouragement of renewable energy industries and applications. The current policy measures provide well opportunities for augmented investment in this sector, technology up gradation, induction of new industries, market growth and export encouragement (Liminga, Haqueeb, & Barg, 2008). Indian Renewable Energy Development Agency, the commercial financing arm of the Ministry for Non Conventional Energy Sources, is the only agency of its type in the world dedicated to financing of renewable energy projects. Interest rates vary from 0% to 15%, with special concessions being obtainable for projects in the hilly areas, Northeast, islands, and desert areas, and for special categories of borrowers.

The institutional organization for Research & Development is being strengthened. A National Institute of Renewable Energy is being established by the Ministry near Jalandhar in Punjab as an apex autonomous institution to support R&D, human resource development, training and commercialization activities. A Wind Turbine Test Station is being set up as an integral part of this Centre to undertake standardization, testing and certification of wind turbines. The Centre for Wind Energy Technology has recently been established in Chennai. The Ministry is finalizing a Renewable Energy Policy Statement that will focus on policy interventions and creation of a conducive environment to accelerate diffusion of renewable energy in the country and set a goal for power generation from renewables in the energy sector.

Conclusions:

The current global situation warrants immediate and effective action. The need for a co-ordination of activities to ensure a simultaneous approach to environmental and employment sustainability cannot be overstated. The links between protecting the global environment while providing employment opportunities to the people is critical in promoting sustainable growth in the twenty-first century. People must be trained in the growth of renewable energy businesses. Energy needs are among the most basic needs of rural communities and the accessibility of adequate energy can act as the driving force behind the transition from a rising economy to a developed one. Renewable energy is today one of the most promising opportunity for combining the goals of employment and sustainable growth. Civilian involvement in renewable energy will offer rural communities with important benefits. People will benefit by the income generating opportunities and the social benefits that they will bring to their societies. The economic benefits will improve the standard of living of the entire community.

The massive potential of renewable sources can meet the world energy demand several times over. Globally, the potential that exists in renewable sources can contribute to long-term sustainability, while it can also be harnessed effectively to create new employment opportunities. The renewable energy industry is in its nascence. Companies, in the long run, can benefit from the momentum of an early start. Enormous market

potential in the field of renewable energies is a reality. For the unemployed youth, that means jobs, careers and business opportunities.

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Reverse Innovation the success mantra during Turbulent Times

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ABSTRACT

Innovations, over the millennia have driven us to where we are today. Innovations along with inventions have since paved the way for the growth of business. First it was reverse engineering, reverse positioning then and now reverse innovation! The paper examines the concept of reverse innovation, strategies for corporate reverse innovation. This paper has covered the Interview with Vijay Govindrajan who is regarded as one of the world's leading experts for strategy on innovation. It further explores the moral of the moment: A perfect time for reverse Innovation economics.

Finally, the paper dwells on concluding remark. The business model, labeled 'Glocalization' wherein MNCs develop products in first world countries and then produce and distribute them worldwide, has proven to be unsustainable. MNCs are now pursuing, 'reverse innovation', whereby products are developed in the individual markets and then ultimately scaled globally. Tony Davila said, " Building a deep innovation capability requires a systematic approach... Over time your company can make the transition too, if it's prepared to patiently assemble all the components that are critical for making innovation a ubiquitous capability."

QUOTES:-

1. Never before in history has innovation offered promise of so much to so many in so short a time.
Bill Gates.
2. Innovation is not the product of logical thought, although the result is tied to logical structure.
Albert Einstein.
3. The world leaders in innovation and creativity will also be world leaders in everything else.
Harold R. McAlindon
4. Innovations come from the producer, not from the customer.
W. Edward Deming.
5. Entrepreneurs innovate Innovation is the specific instrument of entrepreneurship. It is the act that endows resources with a new capacity to create wealth.
Peter F. Drucker.

I. INTRODUCTION

Innovations, over the millennia, have driven us to where we are today. Gaining prominence in the wake of the industrial revolution in 18th and 19th centuries, innovations along with inventions have since paved the way for the growth of business. Basically, behind any major industry we see around us today are chronicles of inventions and innovations.

Academics argue that innovations were the ones that helped nations develop as major economic powers. As strategy guru Michael Porter rightly said, "Competitiveness of a nation depends on the capacity of its industry to innovate and improve."

The current prolonged global economic downturn has revealed what economists and other design thinkers have asserted for years: economic imperialism, sometimes labeled 'Glocalization,' wherein multinational corporations develop products in first world countries and then produce and distribute them worldwide, has proven to be unsustainable. Multinational corporations are now pursuing 'reverse innovations' whereby products are developed in the individuals markets and then ultimately scaled globally. While this model may succeed, it also indicates that the time has come for national companies to engage in successful innovation and meet the needs of their local and regional markets without external ownership or direction.

Regardless of the existing economic environment, protracted, successful innovation is essential for corporate competitiveness. There is no universal template guaranteeing successful corporate innovation, there are specific attributes present in all organizations that successfully innovate. Five important strategies that help ignite and focus corporate innovation are now explored.

II. STRATEGIES FOR COPORATE REVERSE INNOVATIONS

A. BUILD NIMBLE INNOVATION TEAMS:-

- Corporate strategist Gary Hamel noted," Because we live in an increasingly non linear world, only non linear ideas have the power to change customer and redefine the basis for competitive advantage. "The key to successful reverse innovation is to release the innovative potential already existing in the organizations employees. This most often is achieved by developing small (twelve or fewer members), highly diverse teams, focusing them on specific needs, and then encouraging them to engage in many inexpensive experimental projects.
- Their goal now and when a member of an innovation team, is to achieve "small wins", advances that are continuous in character and driven by opportunism and dynamically changing market situations.

B. LEVERAGE INTIMACY WITH CUSTOMERS:-

- Every innovative idea starts and ends with current or prospective customers in mind. Futurist Watts Wacker noted, "focus on the consumer at the end of the channel, and you will immerse yourself in your own possibilities."
- Proximity to customers allows innovative team members to observe for themselves What customers want and need. Heather Fraser of the university of Toronto noted, " if you begin with the users and set out on a path to look at the broader context of their lives and activities, you will suddenly see a whole new set of opportunities to be tapped."
- Quantitative emphatic research translates into a rich body of lore to be systematically shared with co-workers. Ultimately leading to helpful hypotheses and ideas that can be subsequently incorporated into future incremental changes or entirely new products.

C. APPLY APPROPRIATE INNOVATION METRICS :-

- The companies must formulate and consistently use metrics that are clearly stated, valid, reliable and expansive. A historical business rule of thumb is, "what get measured gets done."
- As Tony Davila has said, "the fundamental idea behind innovation metrics is to develop a measurement system that captures the logic behind and innovation, strategy and facilitates agreements in terms of what is important, how day to day activities add value and how each person contributes to the mission."
- To spur successful innovation, development and successful use of innovation metrics that support both creativity and value creation is essential to individual, team and corporate success.

D. EXTEND INSTITUTIONAL LEARNING:-

- Fresh ideas, concepts and knowledge are the foundations of successful corporate innovation. Ongoing innovation requires workable mechanisms that encourage fresh ideas to be duly recorded and disseminated to others in the organization.
- As Professor Ikeyiro Nonaka of Hitoksubhashi University in Tokyo said, "Making personal knowledge available to others is the central activity of the knowledge - creating company. It takes place continuously and at all levels of organization." This process is known as institutional learning.
- New formal and informal communication networks should be developed for effective sharing of information in the organization.

E. ENCOURAGE EXPERIMENTATION AND CONSTANT SMALL FAILURES:-

- To achieve truly valuable breakthrough in the long term, it is necessary to accept and learn from failures in the short term. Regular and methodical failure is essential to eventual innovative success and yet most corporations brutally sanction failure.
- An important role for leader of innovation is to clearly signal the propriety of failure and to distinguish between 'good failure' and 'bad failure'. 'Bad failure' is that which is repeated, and nothing new is learnt. 'Good failure' happens often, but same event is not repeated because it is recorded and shared with others in the organization.

III. FEW GLIMPSES FROM INTERVIEW WITH VIJAY GOVINDRAJAN WHO IS WIDELY REGARDED AS ONE OF THE WORLD'S LEADING EXPERTS ON STRATEGY ON INNOVATION AND REVERSE INNOVATION

Vijay Govindrajan was the first professor in Residence and Chief Innovation consultant at General Electric.

Q.1. Can you give us the background for this path breaking idea, what prompted GE to embark upon his journey of reinvigorating and disrupting itself?

AnsVG:.. We introduced the concept of reverse innovation in our HBR article, "How GE is disrupting itself (Oct 2009). Historically, American multinationals innovated in the US and sent those products to emerging markets. Reverse innovation is doing the exact opposite. Going forward, multinationals must innovate in emerging markets and bring those products into developed markets. This is what we mean by reverse innovation.

Q. 2. How does reverse innovation enable GE to disrupting itself?

AnsVG:.. Let me illustrate how GE is pursuing reverse innovation by taking the portable ultrasound example. In China GE introduced a portable ultrasound to cater to the needs of rural customers. In rural areas there are hospitals. Therefore, you cannot ask the patient to go to the hospital, rather than a hospital has to come to a patient. That is why a portable machine is critical. This low cost portable machine is creating new applications for GE in the US.

Q. 3. Why do you say that days of glocalization are over and reverse innovation are isn't optional.... Its oxygen. Does it mean that developing countries never get to see the products / services developed in developed countries?

AnsVG:.. While reverse innovation is critical, Glocalization will continue to be important going forward. MNCs must innovate both in their home markets as well as in emerging markets. Thus the developing countries will continue to see the cutting edge technologies and cutting edge innovations from the west coming into their markets while sustaining that, MNCs must also innovate from the ground in emerging markets.

Q. 4. What kinds of companies are best suited to pursue reverse innovation impeccably?

AnsVG:. Companies which are ideally suited for reverse innovation would be consumer products companies like P&G, Unilever and Nestle. Consumer companies obviously are most affected by the unique characteristics and income disparities in country like India.

Q. 5. What is the role of leadership in nurturing a futuristic and impending culture of reverse innovation, especially for MNCs from developed countries?

AnsVG:. Leadership has to play a critical role. CEO must travel to emerging markets, see first hand what is possible, and convince the organization about the potential of reverse innovation.

Q. 6. What do you think are the challenges and precautions for MNCs seriously looking at reverse innovation as their next growth driver?

AnsVG:. The reverse innovation is as much as cultural transformation as it is a strategic transformation. Therefore the biggest barrier would be organizational barrier. In order to overcome this MNCs must develop leaders with a different orientation and global mindset. In order for reverse innovation to be successful, the CEO needs to play a role showing 100% commitment to this concept.

The interview was conducted by Dr. Nagendra V. Chawdary, Consulting Editor, Effective Executive Dean, IBSDC, www.ibsdc.org.

Source:- Effective Executive, Jan. 2010. Page: 36 – 40.

IV. THE MORAL OF THE MOMENT: A PERFECT TIME FOR REVERSE INNOVATION ECONOMICS

- The world has been in an economic free fall for quite sometime. It seems like every business has suffered in its own way. But there are few companies that have flourished which would be referred as, 'reverse innovation companies.' These companies do not necessarily cater to the wealthy but rather the less privileged.
- The poster child for 'reverse innovation companies' is Walmart. You will be greeted in a friendly manner, you will have an enormous assortment of items to choose from and the price will be low.....very low. Incomes are down and that means conditions are right for innovation that offer acceptable quality at low price.
- The moral of the moment centers an embracing the economic lessons taught to us by reverse innovation. There are lots of things written about dangers to reverse innovation and how to battle against it.

V. FINANCING INNOVATION IN TOUGH TIMES

- Business leaders who recognize that innovation is not a luxury reserved for good times, but rather the life blood for driving growth valuation and strategic renewal, will discover that incredible achievements does not necessarily require a massive budget.
- Innovation can actually cost a lot less than most think. The implicit assumption that big breakthroughs requires big budgets is kind of like the Gershwin lyrics articulate, "It ain't necessarily so."
- Many organizations have also discovered the wisdom of this approach. Take Procter & Gamble co's, Open Innovation Program – "Connect and Develop"- which is aimed at sourcing half the company's innovation from the outside. This program produced a slew of successful new products. It has simultaneously helped P&G slash its own R&D investments around 20 percent, boosting productivity tremendously.
- A close related way to multiply a firm's available resources is to keep its innovation commitments consistent. Instead of going "full speed ahead in all directions," it's wise for the investments to compound – to be cumulative overtime. Consider Apple. The company has produced a steady flow of exciting innovations over the last decade – imac, ipod, & iphone along with iTunes and retail stores – but a close look shows a coherent logic; they compound and reinforce each other.

CONCLUDING REMARK

- 1) Reverse innovation by massive multinational corporations may be the model de jour , and their size and wealth may render their efforts successful.
- 2) Courageous corporate leaders initiate and support nimble innovation teams to experiment and develop ideas with current and prospective customers to meet lofty company goals and to diffuse innovation learning throughout the organization.
- 3) The time has never been better for national corporations to engage in successful innovation so that they can survive and thrive in the economically turbulent years ahead and provide members of the society respect, choice, self-esteem and welcomed future they so richly deserve.
- 4) For many companies in the west, the domestic markets are pretty much saturated. What they attempt or consider as innovation in the name of reverse innovation or bottom of the pyramid, is what emerging market leaders like China and India had been doing for a long time.
- 5) While writing an editorial page article, R.Gopalkrishnan, Executive Director, Tata sons in Business line, "Destiny Awaits Innovation India", November 21, 2009 said that, "...innovation requires 4 C's: Chaos, Creativity, Communication to generate ideas and Channelization to convert them into real products.

India has the first three, but needs to strengthen the fourth". What it takes to strengthen the fourth element of successful innovation.

- 6) Innovation does not only spring from spending billions of dollars understanding the consumer, innovation is about creating a product, a service or a process that is difficult to replicate.

"The challenges of the current economy offer a unique opportunity to push innovation to a new level. Wholesalers have become more creative, more strategic and more efficient, allowing us to do business smarter and faster with greater result" ..

Rocky Wirtz, Chairman of (WSWA) The Wine & Spirits Wholesalers of America and President of Writz Beverage Group.

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Retail-The Catalyst to weed out Insurgency an Anathema in Assam

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Introduction

As the theme of this conference very aptly suggests I do believe that the service industry can be the catalyst which provides a way out to some of the problems faced by the Indian economy in particular and the global economy in general. From the various industries that can be included to make up the fabric of the service industry this paper focuses on retail. 'Retailing is the set of activities that markets products or services to final consumers for their own personal or household use. It does this by organizing their availability, on a relatively large scale and supplying them to consumers, on a relatively small scale' (Andrew J Newman and Peter Cullen). Retailing is defined to include all the business activities relating to the selling of goods and services to the final consumers. It is the final link in the product supply chain. In India, retailing is one of the fastest growing industries. It is estimated to be the largest single sector (after agriculture) both in terms of turnover as well as employment. After leading the IT bandwagon, India is poised to grow as a retail hub. From a 2 billion industry in 2002 it grew by leaps and bounds to its current status. According to consultant KPMG, the sector has an annual turnover of \$ 37 billion, while the retail industry is at about \$ 350 billion (Dec 2009). This year consultant AT Kearney ranked India as the most attractive emerging retail destination in the world.

The backward and forward linkages of large organized retail sector, using sophisticated technology and communication networks, offers several benefits to the consumers in the form of availability of quality products at lower prices; wider choice to the customers; shopping with convenience, space and entertainment etc. It is also beneficial for the growth of the economy as a whole because it provides forward linkages for mass-marketing of processed and packaged goods. Its expanded reach and increased volumes translates into backward linkages such as more manufacturing units, more jobs, better standard of living and hence more prosperity. One can also see a direct correlation between development of retail and the mushrooming growth of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME's) in India. Thus encouraging the development of a vast network of SME's which can act as a catalyst which will lead to faster growth of modern retail by building a World Class Supplier Base.

With the western economy back on the road to recovery the New Year has good news for India. Due to the huge demand for gifts in the Christmas, New Year season in the US and Europe, gems and jewellery, handicrafts and apparel are showing an uptrend in exports. Global retailers such as Wal-Mart, Macy's, Tesco, Marks and Spencer's too have increased their sourcing from India for the festive season. The world's largest retailer Wal-Mart has increased its sourcing from India for the festive season. It sources products like towels, shower curtains, bed sheets, apparel, leather accessories, fine jewellery and house ware from India. The senior director of international corporate affairs Kevin Gardner says that India is an important market for Wal-Mart Global Procurement due to the fact that the Indian suppliers provided high quality products at competitive prices. Globalised retailing has helped the economy to expand, by increased local competition resulting in enhanced production, increasing employment and per capita wealth as well as reduced poverty.

This paper suggests a two pronged strategy as to how Retail can be used as a solution to bringing a turnaround in the insurgency afflicted state of Assam.

1. To develop a world class supplier base of products, specifically of those that are unique to Assam.
2. To also encourage financial inclusion at the grass root level by forming an alliance between Retail and Banking by adopting the model developed by Wal-Mart in Mexico.

There is something very unique about Assam as far as diversity is concerned, as this is one state which has been endowed with natural resources such as oil, coal, natural gas and can also boast of fertile alluvial soil and agro-climatic conditions best suited for agriculture,

This state can pride itself on facts such as being the state to have the first oil company in the world at Digboi and also the first tea company in the world (now known as Assam Company Limited). Therefore one can say that it is oil, coal and tea for which the state is famous in India and globally. What I would like to highlight is a fact that is not known to many in India, about the fruits that grow here, the different kinds of flowers and orchids that are native to this region or the cloth that is woven in Assam which is very different from what is available in the rest of India.

More than 50 percent of the state's income is derived from agriculture and more than 3/4th of state's population is dependent on agriculture for livelihood. More than 90 percent of the area under agriculture is rain fed. This by itself is what should have made it one of the most prosperous states in India but unfortunately the reverse is true for this state as far as per capita income is concerned.

The areas where Assam can add to the supply chain are:

1. Rice varieties such as 'komal' which need no cooking and are ready to eat, hence can be a nutritious substitute to breakfast cereals marketed by MNCs, there are rice varieties like 'bora' which is similar to the sticky rice eaten by the Japanese, Chinese and Koreans and thus can cater to the growing number of expatriates within the country other than having an export potential too. They also produce aromatic rice strains such as 'joha' and 'kalajoha' which should be commercially exploited.
2. Spices such as turmeric and ginger are grown commercially but they should be grown on a larger basis, especially because the type of ginger grown is the kind which has a lot of demand in the global market. Hence over and above adding to the supply chain in India, it also has a huge export potential. Other spices like clove, cinnamon, pepper, cardamom etc are also grown here.
3. Vegetables which have a novelty value such as bamboo shoots, baby corn, bell peppers, various types of cabbage, mushrooms, peas, squash etc, are native to this state. Broccoli too grows well in the agro-climatic conditions here. Green leafy vegetables are also available in plenty and the people in this state also consume wild edible plants. One kind of wild leafy vegetable consumed all over the state, is nutritious and tasty is the dhekia, which actually belongs to a weed family commonly known as bracken. Assam holds the world record of having the hottest chili on earth known as Bhut Jalakia (*Capsicum Chinensis* Jacq.) with Scovelli Heat Unit (SHG) of 10, 41,047.

4. This region has one of the largest varieties as far as fruits grown are concerned. One can find mangoes, jackfruit, litchis, oranges, plums, peaches, custard apples, guavas, jamun (java plum), pani jamuns (syzygium syzygioides), mulberry, grapefruit, poniaol commonly known as Coffee Plum (botanical name being Flacourtia jangomas), and pineapples of at least two distinct varieties etc. These should be grown on a commercial basis. While living in Assam very often when I would want to buy some fruit such as custard apple or peaches during the season it used to be available, the standard answer I got from most people was you eat it if you grow it.

5. The region is also home to various rare kinds of orchids so much so that it is customary to wear the koapu flower an orchid during the festival of rongali bihu. It is normal to see orchids being grown in many homes here. Most of the bungalows and gardens have a huge variety of flowers growing but very little is cultivated on a commercial basis. Out of the total 1350 species of orchids, as many as six hundred species are presently available in the region and several high value species can be commercially exploited. These orchids have vast potential as far as retail is concerned and also from the export angle. It is necessary to take up the activity as a commercial venture. The other potential crops as far as flowers are concerned are marigold, tuberose, gladiolus, orchids, rose, dendrobium, gladiolus, anthurium, tuberose, chrysanthemum and gerbera.

6. Textile from this region should be marketed more strongly. The cloths uniquely indigenous to the region are endi and eri, both these are used as cloth for making garments and also as warm clothing for winters. Assam is the home to several types of silks. The climatic condition in Assam is well suited for the growth of the sector. Traditional varieties of silk cultured include eri, muga and mulberry. However, now a variety known as Tassar is being cultured on an experimental basis. Muga silk, known for its fine shine and golden colour is also very long lasting and used by the local silk weaving industry. This has contributed to the development of the muga culture in the State. It is produced only in Assam in the world. With further infusion of capital and modern methods, the State offers a tremendous potential for the development of a large-scale industry based on silk. Besides, Assam has the largest concentration of handlooms and weavers in India. Traditional handloom silks have a prominent position in the world markets and score over factory-made silks in the richness of their textures and designs. The number of looms in the State stands at around eight lakhs which works out to around 16 per cent of the looms in the entire country. Cotton, muga, paat (mulberry silk) and endi are the basic raw materials for hand-woven fabrics in Assam.

7. Another area which offers scope for large scale cultivation is the formulation and preparation of medicine and perfume from native herbal wealth in the State. Although a large number of medicinal and aromatic plants can be cultivated in Assam, the crops which have significant economic importance with sizeable demand in national and international markets are patchouli, safed musli, geranium, citronella, lemon grass, vetiver, palma rosa, etc. About 300 types of medicinal herbs and plants are known to exist in abundance in the state within the Brahmaputra valley itself having 150 varieties of herbs and plants of commercial value.

8. Artifacts whether it is products made from bamboo, bell metal or the traditionally jewellery made and worn by the women of Assam. Cane and Bamboo are used to make large varieties of products. Cane furniture of Assam is much sought after both in the national and international markets. Brass-work is an important traditional handicraft of Assam. Brass articles are produced not only for day-to-day use, but also for interior decoration.

9. One of the byproducts of having a large petroleum industry in the state is the availability of good quality wax and the existence of small scale units making excellent perfumed candles which is a fad in most high end shopping malls.

10. Assam is the largest producer of tea in India. Assam tea is well known for its distinct quality, especially for its strong liquor, rich taste and colour. It is sold as a single estate tea and used in tea blends bearing many distinguished labels. Assam accounts for nearly 53% of the all India production and about 1/6th of the tea produced in the world. This is one of the success stories from Assam and with the establishment of the Guwahati Tea Auction Centre. Assam tea is very much a part of the supply chain in tea in India.

11. This state is also native to various types of lemon such as gul nimbu, elachi nimbu, which we rarely see in the rest of India, and therefore has the potential to be cultivated commercially. Hatkora is an exclusive export item belonging to the citrus family that is native to this region. Its peel is used for tenderizing meat and enhancing flavour in culinary dishes.

12. Good quality timber and also furniture is another product that can be manufactured on a large scale and supplied from the state.

Case studies

To present my point of view I would like to first quote Devangshu Dutta who is the chief executive of Third Eyesight, a specialist-retail and consumer products consulting firm.

“To my mind, retail developments need to be seen as part of urban infrastructure and also, more importantly, as part of the social fabric of a town or city. Government at all levels, especially state, district and municipal level, need to understand that the presence of successful retail developments in their population centres are an indication of the social and economic health of their localities. A well-planned retail centre not only creates income for the local population and the local government, but also provides a very important socio-cultural platform for interaction between the different segments of a community. The presence of successful brands and retailers acts as an attractive beacon for other businesses, small or large.”

Second I would like to highlight the case of Wal-Mart founded by Sam Walton. This was started in 1962, the same year that TARGET, Woolworth's and K-MART opened their first stores in America. His strategy for success was very different from these other early retailers. While they all focused on urban areas, he chose to focus on rural areas. His goal was to raise the standard of living for people living in rural areas to equal that of those living in urban areas. At that time his “rural retailing” strategy was perceived to be quite radical. Nobody could understand how he could possibly succeed when he was opening such large stores in such small towns. He boldly opened big stores in towns with a population of only 2000 or 2500 inhabitants which at the time went against conventional wisdom and people thought that he was downright foolish. Bankers, suppliers, his competitors and even his customers thought he had “lost his marbles!” But Sam Walton continued to believe in his vision when no one else did, and he remained steadfast under scornful criticism. The key to his success turned out to be that his stores drew rural customers from a 50 mile radius surrounding his stores. His rural

discounting strategy worked so well that he eventually used his rural success to fund his expansion into urban areas where he would take on his bigger discount retailing rivals and beat them at their own game (Michael Bergdahl).

Third I would like to put forth the case of Woolworths in Australia which has supermarket as its core business, though it later diversified into general merchandising, liquor retailing and wholesaling groceries to third party supermarkets. In 1986 Woolworths started facing heavy losses. To overcome this crisis it undertook extensive market research and found that it was mostly system driven and not customer driven in its work culture. Woolworths adopted a multipronged approach to tackle the problem such as starting campaigns like "Woolworths-fresh food people", "Every day low prices", "Crazy store", 'Project Refresh', and starting an online shopping portal called "Homeshop.com" and "Greengrocer.com.au" among other things. The innovations it introduced were to start Petrol retailing in 1996 and tying up with Caltex to provide discounted fuel to its customers which helped it increase its sales by 9.8%. Another novel campaign it started was its Ezy Banking service which was a joint venture between Woolworths and Commonwealth Bank, provided to customers in 60 supermarkets in September 1999. In 2003 it entered into an agreement with Cashcard a leading ATM service provider in the country. This service also facilitated collection of movie tickets to customers a service which was provided by Movieline a joint venture of 3 major cinema groups in the country. Pharmacy in supermarkets was also first introduced by the Woolworths. These were some of the strategies adopted by Woolworths to get back their standing in the market.

Fourth I would focus on the fact that there are many youth from the north east who are employed in the organized retail sectors in metros in India. From small boutique stores to stores of big brands such as Adidas, Reebok, Nike, United Colors of Benetton, to high-end luxury brands such as Emporio, Armani, Gucci, and Christian Dior, retailers across the spectrum are hiring the talent pool from the north east to man their stores. Every employer speaks highly of their commitment, industriousness, loyalty, good taste in clothes and music, politeness, natural friendliness, and language and communication skills.

Fifth case I would like to call attention to is the strategy Wal-Mart adopted in Mexico. In November 2006 Wal-Mart's subsidiary in Mexico received approval to open a bank in Mexico and became the second retail chain in Mexico to operate a bank. The first Grupo Elektra has been operating a full service bank since 2002. The goal of both Wal-Mart's and Elektra's banks is to provide banking services to low income individuals who have traditionally faced barriers to loans from commercial banks or have chosen not to maintain savings accounts due to high maintenance fees. In 2007 Citigroup's Banamex charged a flat monthly fee of 30 pesos on its Cuenta Perfiles account, or per transaction levies and required a balance of at least 1000 pesos to pay interest. BBVA's Bancomer charged an annual fee of 109 pesos plus tax on its flagship savings El Liberton and required a minimum balance of at least 3000 pesos to pay interest. To cite an example of how Wal-Mart helps with financial inclusion at the grass root level I put forward the case of a Mr. Rojas, a cab driver who makes 2000 pesos a week and needed credit to furnish his house. Banamex rejected his application and Bancomer demanded too many documents but banco Wal-mart needed only two days, to talk to his neighbours as he could not provide proof of his income, before approving his loan. The success of this form of banking can be gauged from the fact the number of customers it serves. The number of customers served was 484 millions in 2001 which increased to 1073 million in 2008 and to 1,174 millions in 2009. The strategy adopted by Wal-Mart is to first tap the people who have traditionally avoided the banking sector and after wards expand to middle income consumers.

CONCLUSION

1. The reasons for which retail will do well in the state is because there is a large segment of the middle class people who do a lot of their shopping in the metros especially in Kolkata. Most industries have active club houses that encourage a lot of socializing, so much so that before Insurgency started every district party would entail a small chartered flight coming in from Kolkata with all that was required for the event. Even today executives from tea companies do a lot of their shopping during the month long paid vacation that they get. If the government encouraged retail there would be a decrease in money flowing out of the state. The fact that even a small town like Kakoajan and Dhekiajuli do have people making a livelihood by resorting to MLM especially of products from companies such as Amway, Avon and Tupperware is proof of the fact that consumption pattern is not affected by insurgency and that retail in Assam does have a chance of doing very well.
2. There are a lot of people from other states in the North East coming to Guwahati, Dibrugarh, Tinsukia, Tezpur etc to do their shopping. Many people from the princely nation of Bhutan also do come to Guwahati and other cities in Assam to do their shopping.
3. Organised retailing has been the harbinger of growth, as it can with modern technology guide the economy along, cut costs, curbs avoidable losses, increase production and employment as well as make available products to consumers at competitive prices. If the state of Assam concentrates on the production of products in which it has a natural competitive advantage this would also go a long way in helping to have large number of small and medium enterprises. The backward and forward linkages of this alone are enough to help get the unemployed youth get a means of livelihood and will also be a deterrent to these youth turning to insurgency. Therefore I would suggest that the people of Assam should take their governments help to revive industry in the state and not resort to getting an income from joining insurgent groups. Here parliamentarian P.A Sangma's line on Insurgency most appropriately says it all "Insurgency has become a cottage industry in North East India".
4. Therefore if policy makers in the state focused on promoting collective farming along with contract farming it would go a long way in helping the state economy get on to a better path of growth. One of the methods adopted by the Assam government to rehabilitate the surrendered ULFA members is to give those who surrender a sum of Rs 2 lakhs and a gun. Instead of this the government should make it mandatory that the surrendered ULFA (SULFA) is given some compulsory training and helped to start his or her own SME. It would be better still if the government itself started manufacturing units in the above mentioned products and the SULFA be put to work in these units.
5. The Assam government's main losses due to 30years of insurgency in the state has been damages to roads and bridges, flight of capital and businesses, maintaining paramilitary forces besides compensation to victims of terrorism. Therefore in January this year the Assam government is seeking from the central government a compensation of a whopping Rs 250 billion. Apart from this there is an additional demand of Rs 200 billion towards infrastructure development, healthcare, and police modernization. Even if half of this said amount is sanctioned to the state then there can be hope of a

turn around as far as the state economy is concerned. Having said this I also do believe that the state has enough resources which is employed judiciously are enough to get the state out of the situation it is now.

6. If we take the example of Wal-mart it is easy to see that one can implement the same strategy that was adopted by Sam Walton namely that of focusing on the setting up of stores in rural areas and to use that money to fund the setting up of urban stores. This is also highlighted by the fact that this is one of the reasons for the turnaround in Indian retail as there has been a definite shift in focus on tapping the rural customer since last few years.
7. The example of Woolworths highlights the fact that it is usually a multipronged approach that has to be adopted to achieve success as far as retail is concerned. Here too they could adopt a tie up between retail and petrol to start petrol retailing.
8. There being lack of opportunities in Assam and the north east is what prompted the youth to go out of the state to get jobs outside. The silver lining in this case being that if the retail sector in this region takes off then these youth will definitely come back and would be much sought after by this industry as they already know the ropes of the trade.
9. The last point I would like to make is that of financial inclusion as this is the focus of the RBI and policy makers at present. There is even talk of financial inclusion by tying up the telecom companies and banking institutions to deliver cost effective financial services in the under banked areas in the country. Bharati Airtel CEO Sanjay Kapoor speaking at the Economic Times Financial Inclusion Summit 2009 said there are several rural customers who are accustomed to using a cell phone but do not have a bank account and mobile banking could help provide them access to financial services. Therefore there is a need to adopt the Wal-Mart example of financial inclusion which is commercially viable and implement it in India. In a state like Assam where the a large segment of the low income groups irrespective of gender tends to indulge in substance abuse, it would be better if they get into some form of forced savings due to the acquisition of consumer durables with help from a retail bank.

The above mentioned points emphasise the fact that there is huge potential for the retail sector to do well in Assam. It could be one of the ways in which the state could have a turnaround in its economy and therefore Retail can become the Catalyst the state needs to get on to the road which leads to prosperity and peace.

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India, The Land Of Opportunities For Services Industry Of Rental Machines In Construction Business

Submitted by

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Abstract

The upswing in the Indian Economy has enhanced the demand for the Construction and Material Handling equipments. The demand for Construction and Material Handling Equipments is correlated with the growth of other segments like Infrastructure Construction, Ports, Pipelines, Roads, Steel, Power Projects, Mining, Building Construction etc. Increase in foreign investment (FDI/FII) and technology has led to a tremendous growth in requirement of mobile cranes and construction equipments. The size of Indian construction industry is over US\$25 billion and it accounts for over 6.5% of GDP. With the GDP growth likely to be around 8% for 3 to 5 years going forward, the demand for construction equipments will continue to grow with core sectors like construction, cement, steel chemicals, petroleum, mining etc.

Construction equipments forms major portion of construction cost though its share differs by the construction segments.

This paper is an attempt to bring out realities of the scope and new trends of this service industry of Rental machines in construction business

Keywords: construction machinery, earthmoving, Rental machines

Introduction

Infrastructure is the backbone of any economy and India is no exception.

The construction equipment rental business is at a nascent stage and is a mere 2% of the total equipment market. However, this is projected to grow to 25% by 2010, thanks to the rising demand for machinery from the infrastructure sector

The country's construction, housing and real estate sector has been growing at 10% in the last five years, employing more than 30 million people. Global demand for construction machinery to jump 6% per year to \$130 billion in 2011 ... "The services segment in the construction equipment business is still the major industrial market

The sector, which covers rural and urban infrastructure, roads, airports, sea-ports and commercial and residential establishments, has got a major impetus in the last five years, thanks to a host of government

projects, such as Bharat Nirman, Pradhan Mantri Grameen Sadak Yojana and airport modernization.

The Eleventh Five Year Plan (2007-12) envisages the total investment in the infrastructure sector to touch 9% of GDP towards the end of the Plan period, from 5% of GDP in 2006-07, according to the Economic Survey 2007-08. Based on this projection, the Survey adds, the investment in physical infrastructure alone from 2007-2012 is estimated to be \$500 billion. Massive construction projects would translate into multiple downstream opportunities for several other sectors, such as cement, steel and construction equipment.

Market Demand (\$ billion) 1

This research basically is an desktop research, the statistics company profiles and written material available to the researcher is utilised to study as well as frame objectives that led to certain questions like :Do you use rented equipment?, Are any innovations applied by the companies about renting machines in a recent project?, what are the Challenges of growth in current scenario?. How much is the Progress of the rental ratio? Etc.

Birth of Indian Construction Equipment Industry

The Evolution of Indian Construction Equipment (CE) Industry can be broken up in a time frame of five decade on bases of Industry trends, market and products.

- 1 1960-70's Domestic production began with setting up of BEML Government being the main producer and buyer Dozers, Dumpers, graders, scrapers, graders etc.
- 2 1980's Private sector entering the sector with likes of L&T, Telecom Growth of market due to increase in mining/infrastructure activities Hydraulic excavators, mining equipment etc
- 3 1990's Joint Ventures with global player Liberalization of economy with increase construction activities Pavers, loaders, backhoe etc
- 4 2000's Demand moving northward leading to capacity doubling Infrastructure development gains momentum with investments pouring Equipments of latest technology with increase load handling capacity
- 5 Current scenario & Future Sectorial reforms and boost to infrastructure development Increase in budgetary allocation, The increase in international finance institution funding for infrastructure Emerging as a manufacturing hub for designing and developing products for global markets Prior to

1960's, domestic requirements of construction equipment were entirely met by imports. Domestic production began in 1964 with manufacturing of bulldozers, dumpers, graders, scrapers etc by Bharat Earth Movers Ltd (BEML) a PSU unit under Ministry of Defense. In the private sector, the Hindustan Motors established its Earthmoving Equipment Division in 1969 at Tiruvallur, near Chennai. In 1974, L&T began to manufacture hydraulic excavators under license from Poclain, France. In 1980, Telcon began production of hydraulic excavators under license from Hitachi, Japan and in 1981, Escorts JCB started production of backhoe loaders under license from JCB, UK. Escorts JCB was taken over by JC Bamford Excavators Ltd. U.K. in 2003 and is now called JCB India Ltd. Volvo and Terex Vectra are the newest entrants to the market. Volvo has set up their manufacturing unit in Bangalore.

The Rental Business

Large construction projects require deployment of heavy equipment such as cranes, bulldozers, loaders and dumpers. Purchasing such equipment only adds to the costs of construction companies, who are already battling soaring commodity prices, particularly those of cement and steel. Many construction companies thus look around for such equipment on lease. This has helped in the growth of construction equipment banks, which provide machinery on rent and make it easier for developers to curtail project costs. The statistics discussed in introduction does show that the investments worth \$500 billion to flow in infrastructure between 2007-12 which is an typical progress ratio of rental equipment service business as well as the future face of rental business can be explained as rental equipment has become one of the leading end-use markets for construction and industrial equipment, and one of the hottest subjects of study. The industry has grown tremendously over the last half-decade. "The equipment rental market is not yet fully developed but there are a number of companies who have entered this business encouraged by the low interest regime. This will give a further boost to the demand for small and medium-sized equipment. The growth of this sector is interlinked with the growth of the Indian economy and indirectly with the growth of infrastructure. The last few years have witnessed a phase of restructuring in the industry through acquisitions and joint ventures. This reflects the active interest of international majors in the domestic markets. The future prospects of this industry are directly linked to the Indian economy which is expected to do well in the future,

Industry Profile

Construction equipment is one of the key segments of any manufacturing sector. India today is, by and large self sufficient in the production of construction machinery. The industry has evolved over last four decades from primarily catering to the army's requirement in to a stage where it spans all major equipment categories such as Earthmoving and Road Construction Equipment, Concrete Equipment, Material Handling Equipment etc. During the last decade, industry has made enormous progress and has grown both in terms of size and diversity. With investment projections of more than \$350 billion in infrastructure sector over the next few years, prospects of the construction equipment industry appear to be dazzling. International majors have unveiled ambitious plans for India, and leading Indian firms are also strengthening their existing operations, and even foraying. The industry is poised for a growth trend in order to realize India's growth momentum with

sustained competitiveness.

India's Construction equipment consists of the following key categories:

- Earth Moving Equipments: Its the largest segment and includes products like excavators, backhoe, loaders, Bulldozers.
- Construction Equipments: Includes key equipment like concrete mixer, hot mix plant, road making machine, concrete breakers, stone crushers etc.
- Material Handling Equipment: It includes mobile cranes, forklifts, truck cranes, tower cranes and conveyors etc.
- Construction Vehicles: These include dumpers, trippers, tankers, trailers etc.

Construction equipment product range

Earthmoving Equipment	Concrete Equipment	Material Handling Equipment	Material Preparation	Road Construction Equipment	Construction Vehicles	Tunnelling and Drilling
Backhoe Loaders	Concrete Breaker	Telescopic Handlers	Crushing Plants	Construction Equip	Dumpers	Rotary / DTH Drilling
Excavators	Paver Finisher	Crawler Cranes	Jaw Crushers	Vibratory Rollers	Articulated Haulers	Hammer Track Drill
Loaders	Concrete Batching Plants	Mobile Cranes	Pavers	Boring Equipment		
Bulldozers	Concrete Pumps	Truck Cranes	Demolition Equipment			
Skid-steer Loaders	Concrete Mixers	Forklifts				
Wheeled Loading	Hot Mix Plants	Pick & Carry Cranes				
Shovels	Slew Cranes					
Wheel Loaders	Tower Cranes					
Motor Graders	Conveyors					
Motor Scrappers						
Dump Trucks						
Wheel Dozers						
Draglines						

Current Scenario

The construction industry is the primary users of the heavy earthmoving equipments in India. The organized construction sector accounts for 50-55% of the total construction equipment industry which is growing at around 25% per annum, amidst sustained economic development with special emphasis on infrastructure development by the government and private organizations.

➤ Size of the market

The Indian construction equipment sector is estimated at USD \$2.25 billion, a fraction Of global market which is over \$75 billion. The global industry is growing at the pace of 5% per annum compare to India's robust growth of around 30% per annum.

➤ Demand

Due to the robust growth in the infrastructure development, the demand for the construction equipments is expected to exceed to 10,000 units from current 6,000 units.

➤ Exports

Exports currently constitute 2-3% of India's construction equipment industry. Many factors contributed to the low level of exports, including a lack of complete product range, the need to avoid competition with JV partners and relatively low levels of technology & quality. But now, exports are expected to grow rapidly. Increased outsourcing of manufacturing to low-cost countries and improvements in technology and product range are expected to boost Infrastructure Equipment (IE) exports from India.

➤ Growth Drivers for the Industry

India has demonstrated strong growth across all sectors, with Indian economy moving In top gear we are set to achieve exponential growth in coming years. The India Infrastructure development has been on a high agenda for the Indian government over past few years as it is a key driver for the overall economy development. Construction spending as a percentage of GDP has been increasing steadily over last 4-5 years from 5.70% in 2000 to 6.83% in 2006 and it is estimated to touch 6.85% in 2007. It is expected to grow significantly in the coming years as well.

The above plan of the government for developing infrastructure in the country to fuel overall economic growth has a huge positive impact on the sector.

The Market

Construction equipment rental is one of the emerging growth areas of the Indian construction equipment industry, besides exports, and refurbishing of used equipment and services. The major customers range from large EPC contractor firms executing BOT projects like highways and bypasses to small contractors involved in road resurfacing or housing construction

Advantages to construction companies in taking rented equipment rather than buying them

As per the findings and analysis of data it can be stated, the average utilisation of any equipment is not more than 30 per cent so they remain idle for long. Two, most of these equipment are expensive and three, we are supplying trained manpower along with the equipment to run and maintain them. We are have strong team of over 450 skilled and technical people to run these equipment. Availability of international standard equipment in the country will considerably bring down the cost of equipment, which can subsequently be passed on to the clients. Entry of organised players into the segment is expected to significantly increase penetration of rentals in the coming years. Immature market, non-availability of new machines and lack of trained operators clearly outlines that the rental industry holds huge potential, specifically for smaller equipment and also for small to medium size contractors. Challenge for equipment

rental companies: The Indian infrastructure sector is booming. Despite the boom in the business there are certain regulatory issues for the equipment rental companies, which have to be addressed. One of the major impediments to the popularity of equipment rental model is logistics since transporting these equipments over longer distances is an issue, especially so when we do not yet have a nationwide presence. Customers generally tend to hire equipments for three to six months in variety of options depending on the project and requirements. The rental period could also last for just a few hours to tide over the peak demand and this explains the flourishing unorganised market for equipment rentals. Larger equipments are rented out for longer duration as compared to smaller capacity equipments for comparatively shorter duration in developed countries as equipments here are primarily deployed in infrastructure building or developmental efforts. Different states adopt different rules governing RTO, taxes and octroi. Smooth operations of pan-Indian equipment rental are possible only when the rules are uniform and there is no roadblocks for inter state movement of the equipment. Also the equipment rental industry does not get any custom duty benefits by importing the equipment even though it may be the latest and most viable solution on the block for the capital-intensive infrastructure industry. Another problem affecting the use of equipment is availability of trained manpower. Equipment is as efficient as the operator. The equipment rental companies need to join hands with vendors and also large construction companies in creating training centres for operators. Unless such facilities come up, Indian infrastructure sector will continue to lag behind advanced economies.

SWOT Analysis of the Sector

- Strength

Construction Equipment sector is estimated at USD\$ 2.25 billion in 2006 and is growing at 25% per annum against 5% per annum of global market. Indian market is estimated to be USD\$ 4 billion by 2010. The vast talent pool gives India a comparative advantage, with high quality of engineering, software and IT talent. India's labor cost per hour is amongst lowest compare to other developing countries.

- Weakness

Weak organized market currently. It is necessary to have a strong organized market for the industry to grow fast, because it offers substantial benefits. It will allow customers to upgrade to newer, more sophisticated equipment faster, and also help players to retain customers. To develop India as a major manufacturing hub it is necessary to focus on R & D. But in the case of construction equipment the focus on R & D is less compare to the global counter parts. With few exceptions, technology is imported from global partner or parent companies, rather than developing it indigenously here.

- Opportunities

Many global companies have brought in world-class technology, processes and systems. Few big names like JCB, Ingersoll Rand, Komastu, Caterpillar have there presence in India. With India's talent pool of skilled labor, adequate R & D, low cost of labor India has the potential to manufacture similar equipments at a much lower cost.

- Threats

Unorganized segment is estimated to be at 16-18% which varies across different equipment categories. High end equipments are manufactured by organized players with large R & D facilities. Hence, unorganized sector does not pose a big threat. Government have drawn robust plan for infrastructure development but still poor

Quality of existing infrastructure acts as a bottle neck as significant resource is utilized for its repairs and maintenance. This acts as a hurdle for implementation of new projects, which also hampers the overall economic development of the economy and the sector.

Conclusion:

After the study of available statistics of this sector it can be stated that, the demand for construction machinery will jump 6% per year to \$130 billion in 2011 in the world, The study says that China, India, Mexico and Russia will register some of the largest sales increases, The demand will be fuelled by healthy economic growth, ongoing industrialization efforts, rising population and higher standards of living in a developing world leading to increase in spending on construction. While India is on an upswing, the US, however, could see a slump in its construction equipment rental business. This is because of the fears of recession looming large over the world's largest economy and the ongoing trouble in its housing market. Less construction of houses translates into lesser demand for cranes and dumper trucks among other earthmoving machinery. New machines drive the rental market. Rental companies sell off used machines, as soon as they get the price to recover their investments. This keeps the fleet young, ensuring higher uptime and lower requirement of parts. It also adds to productivity. Penetration of rentals in the Infrastructure Equipment Industry in India, has been low. In the case of cranes, rental penetration is estimated to be higher (around 60%); but overall, it was 2% in 2004. Renting has a strong potential in India, particularly for smaller equipment. It is already becoming the preferred option for small and medium sized contracting firms. Penetration of rentals could go up to 20-25% by 2010. A 20% penetration in a USD 4.25 bn industry would put the rental market at USD 800mn plus by 2010. To end up the results show that rentals offer multiple benefits to the end user, it is preferred model in Indian construction industry. Having equipments on rentals have few benefits such as: Avoid large capital expenditure, Saves on maintenance and storage cost and offers access to broad selection of equipments and also It allows best equipment for the job and tests it before take a decision to buy.

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Service Sector: Boost To Economy

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Abstract:

The rise of investment in service industry has emerged as one of the most important aspects of Indian economy. The attempt has been made to review the recent trends and pattern and tries to identify determinants of such investments. The paper explores the human development approach and marketing approaches of service companies. It also examines various drivers in service sectors and the challenges in front of the service industries.

Introduction:

The service sector is increasingly gaining momentum in Indian economy. The change in India's approach towards trade and investment liberalization in services is clearly due to the growing importance of the services sector in India's economy and its trade and investment flows in the recent years. Service sector can create more jobs at low cost since majority of the services are knowledge and skill based.

The services sector continues to remain the favorite destination for foreign investors as it attracted \$3.12-billion FDI in the first seven months of 2009-10.

Services, which contribute the largest chunk to the country's gross domestic product (GDP), attracted 22 per cent of the total Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows of \$17.64 billion in the April-October period.

In 2008-09, the services sector, including financial and non-financial segments, attracted the maximum foreign direct investment worth \$6.11 billion.

Lead indicators suggest that the pace of expansion in the services sector activity is likely to be sustained even in the next financial year.

Foreign tourist arrivals (FTAs) during January to August 2009 were 3.26 million.

Railways freight traffic increased to 833.03 million tonnes during fiscal 2008-09 from 794.21 million tonnes carried during 2007-08, an increase of 4.89 per cent.

- Approximately 14.25 million telephone connections, including wireline and wireless, were added during July 2009, taking the total number of telephone connections at the end of July 2009 to 479.07 million.
- Cargo handled at major ports during April–December 2008–09 has been 391.80 MT as against 378.82 MT in the corresponding period last fiscal.

The prospects for growth in the Indian services sector over the next year continues to be robust, according

to a survey by KPMG, conducted across the BRIC (Brazil, Russia, India and China) countries in spring 2009. The survey revealed that 31.3 per cent Indian companies saw their activity levels improving. Around 37 per cent forecast new order growth in one year's time, compared with 16 per cent that anticipate a fall. Even capital expenditure at Indian services firms is anticipated to rise in the year ahead, with 43 per cent of companies saying they plan to increase spending on fixed assets. Revenues are expected to grow by 31.1 per cent of firms, while 32.5 per cent believe their profits will increase.

Drivers of India's services sector:

IT industries:

The impressive growth in the Information technology sector has been feasible because of low cost of operations, high quality of product and services and readily available skilled manpower. The ITES-BPO industry has witnessed significant growth in 2005-06, driven by increased off shoring by firms in America and Europe. Within ITES service lines, customer care and finance have been the two fastest growing segments. Apart from these two, some other important segments in the outsourcing industry include human resources, payment services administration and content development. While presently customer care remains the largest service line, finance and administration services are expected to grow significantly over the next few years.

The global ITES and BPO market is growing at around 9 per cent. With the industry structure undergoing change, established software service companies have entered into ITES-BPO arena driven by factors such as cross selling opportunities, critical mass and strong balance sheets, end-to-end service offerings. Even as Indian service providers continue to strengthen their position as providers of Information Technology Outsourcing (ITO) and Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) services to companies around the world, the possibility now exists for India to add new stream of services export growth i.e., Engineering Services Outsourcing (ESO).

Most economies are getting increasingly skill-scarce in a relative cost-effective sense, and professionals in India could meet this gap effectively. Each year, India's universities, technical colleges and other tertiary institutes produce nearly 100,000 engineering and science graduates. India presently accounts for 28 per cent of IT and BPO talent among 28 low-cost countries in the world. India has emerged as a major software exporting country with a level of US \$ 23.6 billion in 2005-06, growing at a steady rate of over 30 % in the recent past. While this cost advantage due to cheap skilled labor and the fluency in English is a major strength for India, the pool is not big enough. Currently only about 25 per cent of technical graduates and 10 to 15 per cent of general college graduates are suitable for employment in the offshore IT and BPO industries, respectively. There is a shortfall of nearly 0.5 million qualified employees in the IT and BPO sector. The potential shortage of skilled labors has already led to an increase in wage. Wage costs are rising by around 17 - 20 per cent per year. India will need a 2.3 million IT and BPO workforce by 2010 to maintain its current market share.

Hotel and restaurants:

The tourism industry that includes hotels and restaurants has witnessed good times on account of increased passenger traffic (business and leisure). The same has been the result of government initiatives such as 'Incredible India' campaign, signing liberal agreements with various nations in the recent past that increased international traffic, increased investments to develop and open new tourists destinations and increased focus on development of infrastructure such as modernization of airports and ports; all of which helped the industry to flourish.

Banks & insurance:

One must note that reforms have taken place in the banking sector since 1991 despite changes in the government. The Finance Ministry continuously formulated major policies in the financial sector such by giving licenses to private sector banks as part of the liberalisation process, opening of the insurance sector, designing measures to increase financial soundness like introducing capital adequacy requirements and other prudential norms for banks, limiting the entry of foreign banks etc.

While the policy changes have led to the development of the financial sector, growth has also been backed by the radical change in the Indian consumers' mindset regarding credit. The banking system has evolved from the traditional banking practices of lending and deposits to other avenues such as investment banking, insurance services etc. Going forward, banks that have ensured sufficient capital to sustain credit growth will increase focus on non funded income to sustain margins. A few domestic banks like ICICI Bank and SBI are likely to be impacted by the financial turmoil witnessed globally and will have to make provisions but the fact that they are dependant largely on the domestic business, the impact may not be that severe.

Communication:

The communication sector is one of the fastest growing sectors domestically. The changing demographic profile and increased disposable incomes are few factors that have driven growth of the sector. India's teledensity has improved from under 4% in March 2001 to over 26% by the end of March 2008; however, it is still low as compared to other developing nations. At the end of FY08, India's mobile subscriber base stood at 261 m registering a growth of 58% YoY. The low penetration levels leave a lot of scope for growth in this sector. Further, low tariffs that are likely to boost volumes and higher usage will continue to give a further fillip to growth. However, increased competition is likely to pressurise revenues in the near term.

The accelerated economic growth of both India and China in recent years has been a focus of significant policy discussion and analysis. On one hand, this growth is led by the IT industry in India, and on the other, it is the manufacturing industry based in China. However, service sector has played a very different role in both the countries. The share of service sector in India's GDP is 54% while its share in China's GDP is 40.7%. Since the 1990s, China and India have witnessed spectacular average annual growth rates of 10.2% and 6.2% respectively (for the period 1992-2005). In India, service sector has become a dominant contributor, such that the success in this regard has been called as 'India's services revolution'. However, in China, the service sector has lagged behind the manufacturing sector.

One of the drawbacks of the Chinese service sector growth is the constant threat of intellectual property rights violation. There is rampant piracy which is constantly contributing to the smaller and weaker size of China's software firms. Despite the differences in the Indian and Chinese service sectors, most of India's lessons can be applied to ensure the success of the Chinese service sector. Both India and China have earmarked two different development paths. Each has leveraged its strengths to develop its own industries. While India has been hugely successful in its service sector, it has fallen short of the manufacturing sector. As a result, China looks towards India for lessons learned and vice versa.

Service sector and economic development: A human development approach

Majority of the services are centered around a human. Many services required technical expertise, skills and knowledge of human beings. So, economy need to be developed which is service oriented with human focus. Population is actually our strength, provided we should improve the quality of people. To make a better use of large human resources we really need to develop HRM techniques. Deliberate efforts are to be made to link human development with economic development through service sector.

Marketing Approach of Service Companies:

Companies engaged in service must continue to reinvent themselves in order to survive the global market. Service companies must constantly instill competitive change in their organization to stay alive. Many business gurus believe that change is no longer optional but inevitable. Big companies that went down in the past failed to recognize important trends in their internal and external environment that were affecting their business. As a rule, decision makers of service companies must be well informed on the different trends in their internal and external environment so that they will be guided on what corporate changes they will

Below are some trends that are shaping the marketing approach of service companies:

- Focus on Customer Service and Customer Satisfaction. Companies of the past focused too much on their internal being. Their capital expenditures were geared towards expansion of network, technical superiority, and market domination by size or scale. These companies failed to recognize that unless customer needs are taken to account, these initiatives will not bring success or profit.
- Focus on the Service Value. Customers want value for their money and they expect that company's offerings must be of prime quality at the least possible price. This is opposite to the principle of business operations. Companies will need more money to execute first-class service because it requires investment on well-experienced employees which eventually require higher salaries, high-end facilities, additional employee trainings which all boils down to an increase operational expenditures. Managers of service companies are tasked to design a service model that are valuable to their customers but priced reasonably. In the past, companies believe that as long as they are "big" in terms of scale, size, and resources, their perceived value is high. This is no longer true today. The best judge of your company's value is your customers.

Focus on Information Technology. One of the best contributions of technology is information. Technological advances led to the availability of information in all sectors of the organization. Examples of information are consumer's purchasing behavior, consumer's consumption pattern, consumer's data information and so on. Information made the decision making process of top executives easy and later resulted to further innovation and improvement on the company's strategic direction. Companies who failed to use information also failed to understand their customers.

- Focus on Globalization. Globalization has swept companies from all over the world by storm. Local markets are already saturated by local players and the best way to expand their sales is to tap emerging international markets. However, internationalization approach is not as simple as transporting your service to another country. If your company's service model is effective in your local market, it is not a guarantee that it will also be effective in other countries. Culture, social behavior, and customs of the foreign country must always be taken into account. Many companies who jumped in the globalization band wagon failed to adjust their service approach when setting-up a foreign franchise. In the fast-food industry for instance, MC Donald's beef burger may not be a hit in countries like India because cows are sacred in this country. Some American fast-food chains that established franchise in the Middle East or some parts of Asia changed the ingredients of their food products and modify the service orientation of their staff in order to adapt to the taste and customs of the locals.

These are just some of the emerging trends that managers of service companies must consider. Companies that did not recognize these signs and failed to adapt to these trends have suffered and send millions or even billions of their resources in to the trash bin.

Challenges Faced by Services Oriented Industries:

The service industry can be very subjective in nature due to the fact that you are trusting people to perform skills. Trust may not be the biggest issue, however value in the service can be perceived as very high or very low. A lot of that perception has to do with the individual selling the service. This can be a big hurdle to overcome.

Though the service sector has brought number of opportunities for the society, consumers, Govt. Producers and suppliers. It has the number of challenges. Some major challenges are as follows:

How to get and retain the:

- 1) -Productivity
 - 2) -Competitive difference
 - 3) -Service quality
- -How to manage Cost, Customer, Change.
 - -How to tangible the intangible.
 - -How to standardized the services.

If we could succeed in managing these challenges and finding solutions to it, there is every reason for the success in future.

Conclusion:

The outlook for the various segments of the services sector is positive from a long term standpoint despite short term jitters. The sectors discussed here directly and indirectly generate huge employment, which results in increased income in the hands of the people and in turn increases consumption, which is likely to get impacted in the short run. However, as the economy is relatively insulated from the global financial meltdown, India's growth remains on track from a long term perspective.

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India's Logistics Vision

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ABSTRACT

This paper on "India's Logistics Vision" portrays India's infrastructure facilities in the present era, outlines government of India's proposed investments, new policies etc. It also envisages the constraints in investments of various infrastructure investments. The paper gives a bird eye view of our major infrastructures like Highways, Railways, Civil Aviation and Ports, the way they have connected the every nook and corner of India and how they have provided the base for the Indian Economic Growth. The focus is to highlight the present structure vis-à-vis various investments proposed by the Government of India.

India is emerging as a modern economy and is witnessing scorching Growth. India's economic performance, particularly over the past three years, has been robust on several counts. Economic growth has accelerated and is now averaging over 8 percent per annum. In order to sustain this rate of economic growth, India's Planning Commission has estimated an investment in infrastructure - defined broadly to include road, rail, air and water transport, electric power, telecommunications, water supply and irrigation. It would need to increase from 4.6 per cent of GDP to be 7 to 8 per cent during the Eleventh Plan period (2007-2012), which would entail an outlay of almost US\$ 320 billion over the Plan period.

An indicator of India's emerging importance on the global logistics scene is the growth and expansion of logistics service providers in the country. India is a fast-growing, market-driven economy. As India emerges as an economic superpower, the elements critical for success on the global scene will continue to be speed to market, quality, cost, and efficiency. In turn, India offers logistics and transportation service providers' ample opportunity to tap into an emerging marketplace. India's existing inland transportation network is considerably more developed than China's. Its 39,289 miles of railroad track rank fourth in the world closely behind China -- despite the fact that China is three times larger in total land area. Also, India's 2.4 million miles of roads more than double China's total. The Indian government is quietly amending its economic policies, reducing trade barriers, and inviting more private sector investment to help alleviate these transportation gaps and create better synergies between its ports and inland transportation networks.

India's Logistics Vision

India is emerging as a modern economy and is witnessing scorching Growth. India's economic performance, particularly over the past three years, has been robust on several counts. Economic growth has accelerated and is now averaging over 8 percent per annum. In order to sustain this rate of economic growth, India's Planning Commission has estimated an investment in infrastructure - defined broadly to include road, rail, air and water transport, electric power, telecommunications, water supply and irrigation. It would need to increase from 4.6 per cent of GDP to be 7 to 8 per cent during the Eleventh Plan period (2007-2012), which would entail an outlay of almost US\$ 320 billion over the Plan period.

Investment requirements in some key sectors are:

- US\$ 50.8 billion for modernization and up gradation of highways
- US\$ 9.25 billion for civil aviation
- US\$ 11.5 billion for ports
- US\$ 69.39 billion for railways

There are several indicators in the economy today which point to the huge investments being made by both the Government and the private sector in infrastructure development.

- India's construction equipment sector is growing at over 30 per cent annually
- The order books of the 10 largest construction companies in India have swelled by over 50 percent year-on-year
- Annual cement consumption has breached the 150-million tonnes mark for the first time.

Infrastructure Growth to Surge on the back of Government Initiatives

Driven by government initiatives, investments in India's infrastructure development are surging. Political parties, across ideologies, have realized the criticality of a very good infrastructure in sustaining economic growth. The Government recognizes the need to improve infrastructure and has stepped up investments in this direction. Despite rising deficits, the Government has been trying to push infrastructure development in the country.

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opportunity to tap into an emerging marketplace. India's existing inland transportation network is considerably more developed than China's. Its 39,289 miles of railroad track rank fourth in the world closely behind China -- despite the fact that China is three times larger in total land area. Also, India's 2.4 million miles of roads more than double China's total. The Indian government is quietly amending its economic policies, reducing trade barriers, and inviting more private sector investment to help alleviate these transportation gaps and create better synergies between its ports and inland transportation networks.

Present India Infrastructure –Policies & Programmes :

HIGHWAYS -

Size of Indian Roads

India has an extensive road network of 3.3 million kms - the second largest in the world.

Roads carry about 61% of the freight and 85% of the passenger traffic Highways/Expressways constitute about 66,590 kms (2% of all roads) and carry 40% of the road traffic. The ambitious National Highway Development Project (NHDP) of the Government is at an advanced stage of implementation.

Structure

National Highways Authority of India (NHAI) is the apex Government body for implementing the NHDP. All contracts whether for construction or BOT are awarded through competitive bidding.

Private sector participation is increasing through:

- Construction contracts
- BOT for some stretches - based on either the lowest annuity or the lowest lump sum

Payment from the Government

Policy

100% FDI under the automatic route is permitted for all road development projects

Incentives:

- 100% income tax exemption for a period of 10 years
- NHAI agreeable to provide grants/viability gap funding for marginal projects
- Model Concession Agreement formulated
- IIFCL to provide funding up to 20% of project cost.

A Rs.41,200 crores (US \$ 5 billion) project plans to lay 6 lane roads over 6,500 kms of National Highways on the Design Build Finance and Operate (DBFO) basis - in Golden Quadrilateral and other high traffic stretches. For a country of India's size, an efficient road network is necessary both for national integration as well as for socio-economic development. The National Highways (NH), with a total length of 66,590 km, serve as the arterial network across the country. The ongoing programme of four-laning the 5846 km long Golden Quadrilateral (GQ) connecting Delhi, Mumbai, Chennai and Kolkata is nearing completion. The ongoing four-laning of the 7,142 km North-South East-West (NSEW) corridor is to be completed by December 2009. In its third meeting held on 13 January, 2005, the Committee on Infrastructure adopted an Action Plan for development of the National Highways network. An ambitious National Highway Development Programme (NHDP), involving a total investment of Rs.2,20,000 crore upto 2012, has been established. The main elements of the programme are as follows:

Four-laning of the Golden Quadrilateral and NS-EW Corridors (NHDP I & II)

The NHDP Phase I and Phase II comprise of the Golden Quadrilateral (GQ) linking the four metropolitan cities in India i.e. Delhi-Mumbai-Chennai-Kolkata, the North-South corridor connecting Srinagar to Kanyakumari including the Kochi-Salem spur and the East-West Corridor connecting Silchar to Porbandar besides port connectivity and some other projects on National Highways. Four-laning of the Golden Quadrilateral is nearing completion. Four-laning of 7,166 km under NHDP-I and 2,440 km under NHDP-II has been completed upto December 2008. The contracts for projects forming part of NS-EW corridors are being awarded rapidly for completion by December 2009.

Four-laning of 12,109 kms (NHDP-III)

The Union Cabinet has approved the four-laning of 12,109 km of high density national highways, through the Build, Operation & Transfer (BOT) mode. The programme consists of stretches of National Highways carrying high volume of traffic, connecting state capitals with the NHDP Phases I and II network and providing connectivity to places of economic, commercial and tourist importance. Up to December 2008, NHAI has awarded contracts of 2,075 km.

Two laning of 20,000 km (NHDP-IV)

With a view to providing balanced and equitable distribution of the improved/widened highways network throughout the country, NHDP-IV envisages upgradation of 20,000 kms of such highways into two-lane highways, at an indicative cost of Rs.27,800 crore. This will ensure that their capacity, speed and safety match minimum benchmarks for national highways.

Six-laning of 6,500 kms (NHDP-V)

Under NHDP-V, the Committee on Infrastructure has approved the six-laning of the four-lane highways comprising the Golden Quadrilateral and certain other high density stretches, through PPPs on BOT basis. These corridors have been four-laned under the first phase of NHDP, and the programme for their six-laning will be completed by 2012. NHAI has already awarded contracts for 1,030 km till December 2008.

Development of 1000 km of expressways (NHDP-VI)

With the growing importance of certain urban centres of India, particularly those located within a few hundred kilometers of each other, expressways would be both viable and beneficial. The Committee on Infrastructure has approved 1000 k.m. of expressways to be developed on a BOT basis, at an indicative cost of Rs.16,680 crore. These expressways would be constructed on new alignments.

Other Highway Projects (NHDP-VII)

The development of ring roads, bye passes, grade separators and service roads is considered necessary for full utilization of highway capacity as well as for enhanced safety and efficiency. For this, a programme for development of such features at an indicative cost of Rs.16,680 crore, has been approved.

Accelerated Road Development Programme for the North East Region

The Accelerated North-East Road Development Project has been approved, which will mainly provide connectivity to all the State capitals and district headquarters in the north-east. The proposal would include upgrading other stretches on NH and state highways considered critical for economic development of the north-east region.

PORTS

Size of Indian Ports

Indian ports handled cargo of 519 mn tonnes in 2004-05, a 11.8% increase over 2003-04

70% of the traffic at major ports by volume is dry and liquid bulk, remaining 30% is general cargo, including containers.

- Containerized cargo has grown at a rate of about 14% p.a. over the last 5 years
- India has 12 major ports and 187 minor ports along 7,517 km long Indian coastline
- Cargo handled by Major Ports has increased by 9.5% p.a. over last 3 years
- Major ports handle nearly 75% of the total traffic

Of the 12 major ports, 11 are run by Port Trusts while the port at Ennore is a corporation under the Central Government. These ports handled 383.75 million tonnes of cargo in 2004-05.

Major Government projects underway:

- Project

“Sethusamundram”: Dredging of the Palk Strait, in Southern India to facilitate maritime trade through it

- National Maritime Development Programme for modernization and expansion of port capacities

Structure

- Government of India dominated maritime activity in the past. Policy direction is now oriented to encourage the private sector to take the lead in port development activities and operations
- Many Major ports now operate largely as landlord ports - International port operators have been invited to submit competitive bid for BOT terminals on a revenue share basis.
- Significant investment on BOT basis by foreign players including Maersk (JNPT, Mumbai) and P & O Ports (JNPT, Mumbai and Chennai), Dubai Ports International (Cochin and Vishakhapatnam) etc.
- Minor ports are already being developed by domestic and international private investors: Pipavav Port by Maersk and Mundra Port by Adani Group (with a terminal operated by P&O).

Policy

100% FDI under the automatic route is permitted for port development projects

100% income tax exemption is available for a period of 10 years

Tariff Authority for Major Ports (TAMP) regulates the ceiling for tariffs charged by Major ports/port operators (not applicable to minor ports)

A comprehensive National Maritime Policy is being formulated to lay down the vision and strategy for development of the sector till 2025.

Initiatives

The experience of operating berths through PPPs at some of the major ports in India has been quite successful. It has, therefore, been decided to expand the programme and allocate new berths to be constructed through PPPs. A model concession agreement is being formulated for this purpose.

The Government has also decided to empower and enable the 12 major ports to attain world-class standards. To this end, each port prepared a perspective plan for 20 years and an action plan for seven years. International experts were engaged for assisting the Ports in this exercise.

A high level committee has finalized the plan for improving rail-road connectivity of major ports. The plan is to be implemented within a period of three years. Further, changes in customs procedures are being carried out with a view to reducing the dwell time and transaction costs. The government has also delegated powers to the respective Port Trusts for facilitating speedier decision-making and implementation. At the same time, several measures to simplify and streamline procedure related to security and customs are being initiated.

The National Maritime Development Programme is expected to bring a total investment of over Rs.50,000 crore in the port infrastructure. Such improvement in the scale and quality of Indian port infrastructure will

significantly improve India's competitive advantage in an increasingly globalized world.

RAILWAYS

Size of Indian Railways

Indian Railways, the largest railway system in Asia, has been the prime mode of transportation in India. Railways have been an integral part of the Indian economy and operate more than 11,000 trains per day, of which around 7,000 are passenger trains.

Over the past few years, Indian Railways has engineered a dramatic turnaround. The dynamic pricing policy for freight traffic introduced in the year 2006-07 has yielded encouraging results. The strategy has been the cornerstone for ensuring optimal capacity utilization. At 20 per cent, the Railways' return on net worth is now the highest in the organization's 155-year history. Besides, it has generated a cash surplus of US\$ 4.7 billion (EBIDTA) and a net surplus of US\$ 3.5 billion.

Initiatives

The rapid rise in international trade and domestic cargo has placed a great strain on the Delhi-Mumbai and Delhi-Kolkata rail track. Government has, therefore, decided to build dedicated freight corridors in the Western and Eastern high-density routes. The investment is expected to be about Rs. 22,000 crore (US \$ 5 bn). Requisite surveys and project reports are in progress and work is expected to commence within a year.

- With increasing containerization of cargo, the demand for its movement by rail has grown rapidly. So far, container movement by rail was the monopoly of a public sector entity, CONCOR. The container movement has been thrown open to competition and private sector entities have been made eligible for running container trains. 14 applicants have submitted the application seeking permission for container train operation, which have been approved.
- Tariff rationalization and effective cost allocation mechanism are also on the anvil. This includes a methodology for indexing the fare structure to line haul costs. Efforts aimed at introducing commercial accounting and information technology systems are also underway.
- Technological upgradation and modernization for higher operating efficiency
- Transformation from bulk transporter to multi-modal transporter
- PPP envisaged in new routes, railway stations, logistics parks, cargo aggregation and warehouses etc.
- It is estimated that Indian Railways will need at least 500-600 electronic freight locomotives, besides the same number of diesel locomotives for dedicated freight corridors in the first phase. The investment required for manufacturing electronic freight locomotives is around US\$ 2.3 billion.

AIRPORTS

Size of Indian Airports

India has 125 airports; of these 11 are designated as international airports.

In 2004-05, Indian airports handled 60 million passengers and 1.3 million tonnes of cargo

- Passenger traffic grew at over 22% in 2004-05 over 2003-04; Cargo grew at 21.6% over the previous year.

Structure

Currently, all 125 airports are owned and operated by the Airports Authority of India (AAI). The Government aims to attract private investment in aviation infrastructure.

- Privatisation of the Delhi and Mumbai airports is in progress – concessions have already been awarded. Expected investment of about Rs.15,700 crores (US \$ 3.5 billion)

- New international airports at Bangalore and Hyderabad are being built by private consortia with a total investment of about Rs.4000 crores (US \$ 600 million)

- 25 other city airports are being considered for private investment.

Air India and Indian Airlines are Government owned international and domestic flag carriers respectively.

Indian private airlines – Jet, Sahara, Kingfisher, Spice jet - account for around 60% of the domestic passenger traffic. Some have now started international flights.

Policy

100% FDI is permissible for existing airports; FIPB approval required for FDI beyond 74%.

100% FDI under automatic route is permissible for green field airports.

49% FDI is permissible in domestic airlines under the automatic route, but not by foreign airline companies.

- 100% equity ownership by Non Resident Indians (NRIs) is permitted

- AAI Act amended to provide legal framework for airport privatization.

- 100% tax exemption for airport projects for a period of 10 years.

- 'Open Sky' Policy of the Government and rapid air traffic growth have resulted in the entry of several new privately owned airlines and increased frequency/flights for international airlines.

Opportunity

Development of airport infrastructure is a focus area for the Government

There has been a significant uptrend in domestic and international air travel

- Currently there are 454 airports / airstrips* in India
- Airports owned by Defence Department - 138
- Airport owned by Airports Authority of India (AAI) - 97
- Airports owned by State Governments - 158
- Privately Owned Airports - 61

*Including operational, non-operational, abandoned and disused airports

The Airports Authority of India (AAI) manages 127 airports (86 operational airports, including 28 civil enclaves and 41 non-operational airports)

- 13 International airports (excluding Delhi and Mumbai and including three civil enclaves)
- 7 Customs airports
- 28 Civil enclaves
- 80 Domestic airports
- 2 Joint Venture airports (Delhi & Mumbai)

Initiatives

The Committee on Infrastructure has initiated several policy measures that would ensure time-bound creation of world-class airports in India. A comprehensive civil aviation policy is on the anvil. An independent Airports Economic Regulatory Authority Bill for economic regulation is also under consideration. The policy of open skies introduced some time ago has already provided a powerful spurt in traffic growth that has exceeded 20% per annum during the past two years.

Greenfield international airports at Bangalore and Hyderabad have been approved and are currently under construction. These are likely to be commissioned by middle of 2008. Modernization and expansion of the Delhi and Mumbai airports through PPPs has been awarded, based on a rigorous and transparent competitive bidding and evaluation process. Other major airports such as Chennai and Kolkata are also proposed to be taken up for modernization through the PPP route. Similarly, to ensure balanced airport development around the country, a comprehensive plan for the development of other 35 non-metro airports is also under preparation. These measures are expected to bring a total investment of Rs. 40,000 cr. for modernization of the airport infrastructure.

On the analogy of the highways sector, a Model Concession Agreement is also being developed for standardizing and simplifying the PPP transactions for airports. In addition, proposals for revamping the Airports Authority of India are to be finalized soon. This would include upgrading of the ATC services at the airports. Issues relating to customs, immigration and security are also being resolved in a manner that enhances the efficiency of airport usage.

Obstacles to Growth

Like most countries in transition, India is not without obstacles to growth. But India's greatest impediment is its inability to quickly and efficiently move product from inland facilities to its ports, a problem directly linked to outdated and disconnected transportation infrastructure.

As per recent study, Connecting India: Transport Challenges and Opportunities "India risks missing out on an additional one to two percent of annual GDP growth led by its emerging manufacturing sector unless the country can improve transport connections to meet the just-in-time requirements of complex international supply chains. Cargo transportation expenditures in India are among the highest in the world, accounting for 11 percent of total landed cost, the report says. As a result, foreign direct investment over the past two years has been stifled. Most industry insiders point to India's lax attitude toward economic reform -- especially compared to China -- as the primary reason for its sluggish response to these problems.

Forward Path -

1. The Government has announced commitments to build large infrastructure projects through significant public expenditure and with the help of private partners - including, for the first time, foreign investors. Despite of these efforts, well planned resource allocation by government is required for financial support. Public private participation needs to be strengthened further for both qualitative and quantitative developments. The well defined phases of developments should be divided into various mini projects and each mini project should be awarded to competent private contractors / construction companies with a time line to execute the project. These projects has to be implemented strictly as per the specified time table in the tender for the contracts. Precautionary steps should be taken so that projects are not delayed due to the red tape.
2. A central monitoring group should be created to monitor all the projects & should be given authority for resolving the obstacles in the path of implementation of the projects. They should be given powers to arrange for resources – financial, human, equipments & other shortages with in a short period of time. This group should consist cross functional authorities like cabinet rank secretaries, ministers, private sector visionaries etc. to guide the projects up to final execution.
3. Along with all these developments at macro levels, rural infrastructure development can not be left out as maximum population of India still lives in villages. For their economic upliftment, connectivity to the major

growing network is required. The government has also taken steps in this direction through implementation of Bharat Nirman Programme for Rural Infrastructure.

4. Though there has been improvement in infrastructure development in transport sector in recent years, there are still significant gaps that need to be bridged. The current economic slow down provides an opportunity for countries like India that substantial degree of unmet infrastructure requirements. This is reinforced by the understanding that spending on infrastructure has large multiplier effects. Development of infrastructure would not only improve the supply side bottlenecks but also will also improve demand side stimulus to growth.

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Public Private Participation in Indian Infrastructure by KPMG

Discover Opportunity Indian Infrastructure by India Brand Equity Foundation

India: The Land Of Opportunities

Submitted By
Anita Natekar

“There is a broad recognition of the enormous benefits flowing from greater integration between India and ASEAN.... The India-ASEAN Car Rally...will dramatically symbolize the effort to forge new linkages, while embodying the spirit of our cooperation.”

Dr. Manmohan Singh
Prime Minister of India

“India's highly educated workforce, management talent, rule of law, transparency, cultural affinity and regulator environment are more favourable than China's.”

A T Kearney
FDI index report

There are plenty of exciting business opportunities in India. India is the largest democracy in the world. In terms of population it ranks second in the world. The policy of liberalization pursued by the government after 1991, has transformed the prospects for the Indian economy. Today India is one of the favored destinations for global service offerings, investments etc.. Let us have a look on the following table, which shows the picture of GDP and Per-Capita GDP of India

Period	GDP Growth (%)	Per-Capita GDP Growth (%)
1972-1982	3.5	1.2
1982-1992	5.2	3.0
1992-2002	6.0	3.9
2002-2009	8.4	5.9

Source: Business Today, December 27, 2009, Page No. 13

Almost all the sectors have contributed to the fast growth of Indian economy, the main intension of penning this article is to show the various opportunities the India have with, so by going through this paper, we will understand the enormous business opportunities in India specifically with respect to Service and Knowledge sector.

Business Opportunities in India:

There are several factors which create favorable business opportunities in India.

- India has a huge middle class, with improved purchasing power, due to the high growth in the economy. Increasingly Indians have become more brand conscious, resulting in increased growth for the retail sector.
- Presence of vibrant trade links with South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) nations like Bangladesh, Bhutan, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka.
- Improved infrastructure available for business ventures. India's competitive advantage in Information Technology, ITES can be used to enhance productivity in Industries.
- Availability of huge pool of technical manpower has heralded the expansion of manufacturing base across different industries.
- India is rich in natural resources and self sufficient in agriculture.
- A well established banking system consisting of public and private banks and other financial institutions.
- The capital markets in India are one of the fastest growing markets in the world, attracting huge investments from FII's.
- The economic reforms have brought in policy changes in terms of freedom of entry, investment, location, usage of technology, import and export. These changes have created an investment friendly environment.
- India is a well established democratic country, with free and fair judiciary.
- A considerable section of the population is proficient in English.

Let us discuss about some of the vital opportunities in India:

➤ Performance of telecom sector (during the month of November 2009)

The expansion of the telecom sector was further consolidated with an increase of 175.41 lakh in the number of telecom subscribers during the month of November 2009. As a result, the total number of telephones in the country is 5,432.00 lakh as on 30th November 2009; as compared to 3741.26 lakh as on 30th November 2008.

The Wireless (GSM+CDMA) segment has registered an increase of 176.39 lakh. The Wire-line segment has declined by 0.98 lakh respectively during the month of November 2009.

Tele-density

The overall tele-density improved further to 46.32% in November 2009 as compared to 32.34% as on November 2008.

Growth trend – Circle wise

In the Wireless (GSM+CDMA) segment, only UP (East) telecom circle added more than nineteen lakh subscribers during November 2009.

In the Wire-line segment, only Delhi telecom circles added above ten thousands subscribers during November 2009.

Broadband Connections

The growth of broadband connections improved further and at the end of September 2009, 7.21 lakh broadband connections were provided. Further, the total number of existing ISP licences is 370 at the end of October 2009.

Rural Telephony

Under Bharat Nirman Programme, 408 VPTs were provided in the month of October 2009. Thus, out of the targeted 62,302 villages, a total of 60,208 villages have been provided with VPTs till October 2009.

➤ Performance and Opportunities in Insurance sector

Insurance in India has its history dating back until 1818, when Oriental Life Insurance Company was started by Anita Bhavsar in Kolkata to cater to the needs of European community. The pre-independent era in India saw discrimination among the life of foreigners (English) and Indians with higher premiums being charged for the latter. In 1870, Bombay Mutual Life Assurance Society became the first Indian insurance company covering Indian lives at normal rates.

At the dawn of the twentieth century, many insurance companies were founded. In the year 1912, the Life Insurance Companies Act and the Provident Fund Act were passed to regulate the insurance business. The Life Insurance Companies Act, 1912 made it necessary that the premium-rate tables and periodical valuations of companies should be certified by an actuary.

Currently (2007-08), in India the insurance industry is US\$ 41- billion, and grew by 36% in 2006-07 over the previous year, i.e., Life Insurance - US\$35 billion industry with US\$24 billion accounting for First Year Premium (inclusive of Single Premium) and Non-Life Insurance - US\$5.6-billion industry; motor and health segments account for 56% of total business.

Indian Insurance market was opened to private and foreign investment in 1999-2000, as of now the Indian Insurance industry consists of a total of 34 players, i.e., Life: 1 public sector player; 16 private players and Non-life: 6 public sector players; 11 private players. Major international players like AIG, Aviva, MetLife, New York Life, Prudential, Allianz, Sun Life, Standard Life and Lombard are already present with minority stakes in joint ventures with Indian companies for both Life and Non-life segments. The Life Insurance market is still dominated by Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) - a public sector company which had 75% share of first year premium in 2006-07.

In non-life, private sector companies (almost all are joint ventures with foreign insurers) accounted for 34% of the market in 2006-07 only two million people (0.2 % of the total population of 1 billion) are covered under Mediclaim, whereas in developed nations like USA about 75 % of the total population are covered under some insurance scheme. With more and more private companies in the sector, the situation may change soon.

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) up to 26% is permitted under the automatic route subject to obtaining a license from the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA). Intention to increase FDI up to 49% by the Government of India Potential:

- Largely untapped market with 17% of the world's population
 - Nearly 80% of the Indian population is without Life, Health and Non-life insurance
 - Life Insurance penetration is low at 4.1% in 2006-07
 - Non-life penetration is even lower at 0.6% in 2006-07
 - The per capita spend on Life and Non-Life Insurance is US\$33.2 and US\$5.2 (2006-07), respectively compared to a world average of US\$330 and US\$224
 - Strong economic growth with increase in affluence and rising risk awareness leading to rapid growth in the insurance sector
- Innovative products such as Unit Linked Insurance Policies are likely to drive future industry growth
- Investment opportunities exist in both life and non-life segments
 - Total estimated investment opportunity of US\$14-15 billion.

➤ Performance and Opportunities in Banking and Financial Services:

India has a rapidly growing Banking and Financial Services sector based on sound fundamentals (low NPAs, Basel I compliance). Total banking assets of about US\$16 billion in 2007: CAGR of 24% over last year. Liquid and well regulated equity markets, with Market capitalisation (NSE) of over US\$1.6 billion on December 2007. Turnover has grown at a CAGR of 24% in 2007. Mutual funds assets under management of US\$130 billion in CY 2007; growth of 70% over previous year with 44 Venture Capital and over 100 Private Equity Funds are in India.

Public sector (government-owned) banks account for 75% of the assets; however, Indian private banks and foreign banks are growing rapidly and gaining a larger share. Standard Chartered Bank, Citibank and HSBC are the 3 largest foreign banks in India with more than 65% of the total assets of foreign banks. Most global players in Banking & Financial Services – including Goldman Sachs, Morgan Stanley, Merrill Lynch, JP Morgan, Deutsche Bank, UBS, Lehman Brothers, ABN Amro, Barclays, Calyon etc. are active in India.

The Mutual Funds industry has both domestic and foreign companies - UTI Mutual Fund, Prudential ICICI, HDFC, Franklin Templeton, Birla Sun Life Mutual Fund, Tata Mutual Fund.

As per the RBI, all foreign investment in this sector must seek the approval; and as per RBI guidelines Foreign banks can do business in India either by setting up branches or through a wholly owned subsidiary. Indian private banks can be 74% foreign owned, with a 5% cap on ownership by any one entity.

Potential

Several factors favour high growth of Indian Banking and Financial Services, like:

- Demographic profile favours higher retail offtake - 54% of the population is in the 15-35 years age group
- Capital expenditure by the government and private industry expected to grow at a high rate
- Economic growth of about 14% p.a. in nominal terms

- SME lending, a largely untapped market, presents a significant opportunity - SMEs account for 40% of the industrial output and 35% of direct exports
- Regulatory and technological enablers leading to high growth
 - The banking system is technologically enabled with RTGS and cheque truncation in place
 - Improved asset management practices - Gross NPAs to Advances ratio reduced from 24-25% in 1993 to 2.5% in 2006-07
- Investment opportunity across all segments in the banking and financial services sector
 - Low penetration in the pension market makes it a lucrative business segment
 - Foreign banks likely to be allowed to acquire local banks after March 2009 when the next stage of banking reforms is proposed

➤ Performance and Opportunities in Tourism Sector:

In India, Travel and Tourism is a US\$41.8-billion industry in India, 5.3% of GDP, 4.9 million international tourist arrivals in 2007, an increase of over 9% from the previous year, 382 million domestic visits estimated in 2006; the domestic tourism market grew at about 12% CAGR in the last 5 years, Only 1,09,000 rooms in 1,980 hotels across the country registered in 2006. Five-star hotel rooms constitute 27%, four-star 7.5% and three-star 22%. All India industry wide occupancy of over 66.9% in 2006-07. Scarcity of rooms in several cities such as Mumbai, Delhi and Bengaluru has resulted in rates of over US\$300 per night.

The industry is dominated by 4-5 large Indian hotel owner-managers – The Taj Group, Oberoi, ITC, Leela and Bharat Hotels. Most major international chains like Sheraton/Starwood, Inter Continental, Hyatt, Marriott, Hilton, Le Meridien, Carlson, Shangri-La, Four Seasons are represented by management or franchise contracts. Aman and Accor plan to own hotels as well. Others such as Ritz Carlton and Mandarin are in the process of establishing their presence in India, primarily through management contracts. The branded segment represents approximately 30,000 rooms or 30% of the total hotel stock. Compounded growth in the last 5 years, in terms of rooms added, was the strongest in the five-star deluxe category at 6%

100% FDI is permitted in Hotels and Tourism, through the automatic route. Hotels in Delhi set up before 2010 have been granted infrastructure status with special tax concessions

Foreign tourist arrivals are targeted to grow to 10 million in 5 years, Domestic tourism is expected to increase by 15% to 20% p.a. over the next 5 years and Rapid growth in average room rates is expected to continue until sufficient new supply comes on stream (Average room rates increased by over 15% in 2007; the fastest growth rate was in 4-star and 5-star segments).

Potential

- Favourable demographics and rapid economic growth point to a long-term secular uptrend in the domestic demand for hotels – for business and leisure
- International inbound traffic is expected to grow rapidly with increasing investment and trade activity
 - WTTC has identified India as one of the fastest growing countries in terms of tourism demand
 - India has benefited from an aggressive promotion campaign and an out-performing economy
- The growth momentum in domestic and international travel is expected to receive a further boost with more budget airlines/lower air-fares, open sky policies and expected improvements in travel infrastructure (roads, airports, railways)
- There are opportunities in all price and value chain segments due to the shortage of hotel stock; plans are on to increase quality accommodation from the current 110,000 rooms to 200,000 rooms by 2011
 - Hotel-asset construction and ownership
 - Low penetration of brands (about 30%) provides opportunities for management contracts and franchising with local hotel owners/developers
 - Serviced apartments in major cities – no chain operating in all cities, very little stock
 - Need for world-class MICE infrastructure in major Indian cities
 - Significant requirement of hotel stock and tourist infrastructure for the Commonwealth Games in New Delhi in 2010

➤ Performance and Opportunities in IT and ITES Sector:

India is the leading destination for providing IT and IT-Enabled Services (ITeS), with revenues of about US\$40 billion in 2006-07 of which:

- IT Services and Software constituted 58%, ITeS about 21%, and the domestic market about 21%
- Exports constituted 79% of the total IT and ITeS revenues

The industry has 3 broad categories of companies:

- Indian IT and ITeS companies ranging from large companies (Tata Consultancy Services, Infosys, Wipro, HCL) to small niche companies
- Global IT companies such as IBM, Dell, Microsoft, HP, Accenture, etc. all of whom have set up development centres in India
- Captive back office operations of large global corporations like JP Morgan, American Express, GE, HSBC, British Airways, etc.

Policy:

- 100% FDI is permitted in this sector under the automatic route
- SEZs, EOUs and Software Technology Parks have been set up across India – income tax exemptions are available for units in these designated areas/zones
- IT Act, 2000 legalises the acceptance of electronic records and digital signatures providing a legal backbone to e-commerce

Major IT & ITeS Companies in India

	Revenues ¹ (US\$ million) (FY 07)	Nos. of Employees
Domestic Private Companies		
Tata Consultancy Services	5,676	85,582
Wipro Technologies	4,970	67,800
Infosys Technologies	4,144	59,831
Satyam	2,103	40,000
International Private Companies		
IBM (CY 07)	98,786	386,558
Accenture (CY 07)	19,696	170,000

Source: www.investmentcommission.in

Potential

- India's inherent IT capabilities - talented workforce and world-class companies
 - Availability of technically skilled and English-speaking labour force at a fraction of the costs in USA and Europe
 - Quality orientation, project and process management expertise
 - Enhanced global service delivery capabilities of Indian companies through a combination of greenfield initiatives, M&A, alliances and partnerships with local players
- International recognition of India's strengths
 - Increasing awareness among global companies about India's capabilities in higher, value-added activities and in the Global Delivery Model
 - Leading international companies have identified custom application development and maintenance as priority areas due to a high offshoreable component
- High growth of domestic IT & ITeS market due to several regulatory and technological factors:
 - Increased investments by enterprises in IT infrastructure, applications and IT outsourcing
 - Demand for domestic BPOs has been largely driven by faster GDP growth and by sectors such as telecom, banking, insurance, retail, healthcare, tourism and automobiles.
- Opportunity to supply to the global market in addition to serving the growing domestic demand

While investing in India one should know about the Investment Policy (FDI) in India. The procedure for FDI in India has been simplified through the automatic route.

All items/activities come under the purview of automatic route, except the following.

Any proposal that requires an Industrial license. An Industrial license is required if

- The said industry is covered by the Industries act 1951.
- The proportion of foreign equity is more than 24 per cent of the equity capital of units manufacturing products set aside for small scale industries.
- All applications, wherein the foreign collaborator has a previous business tie up in India (except IT sector).
- All ventures to acquire shares by a foreign investor in an existing Indian company.

Any investment in public sector units. Export Oriented Units (EOUs), units in Export Processing Zones (EPZs), Special Economic Zones (SEZ), Software Technology Parks (STPs) and Electronics Hardware Technology Parks (EHTPs) come within the purview of automatic route.

Conclusion:

The above mentioned facts and figures shows us the tremendous opportunities the India have with respect to Indian Service and Knowledge industries. It is not like we have only opportunities in these above mentioned sectors. Even India have a plenty of opportunities in various sectors. Ex: Agriculture, Automobile, Infrastructure, FMGC, E-commerce, Export Animations, Multimedia, Graphics or Other Content Products etc. So, the one who is looking for doing good business the India is the destination.

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“A Study Of Job Satisfaction Of Women Employee In Educational Institution” In Pune Region

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INTRODUCTION

Nowadays women are participating in all spheres of activities. The development of any nation depends on economic development which makes rich contribution to the growth of a nation. The economic role played by women cannot be isolated from the framework of development. The role of women in socio-economic development has undergone a marked change over the years the world of women is no longer confined to household activities. Today, they contribute to the promotion of economic development in different capacities. The women are the citadels of excellence in the academic field, politics, administration of business and so on. Now its no longer the exclusive prerogatives of men. Growth and development of an organization depends on its employees / workers. They perform better in the organization, if they are satisfied with their job. If not it leads to low productivity, poor labour turnover, absenteeism and low job performance. Nowadays women have entered all walks of life. Job satisfaction can affect physical health and possibly longevity. It may be related to mental health and adjustment and plays a casual role in absenteeism and turnover. It may affect other types of behavior as well. Who could dispute the fact that women are becoming more and more important in shaping the world we live in?

This study is an attempt to look into one corner of one industry that seems yet unexplored, job satisfaction of women in the educational institutions. The reason for studying job satisfaction in this group, which is growing in both sizes and influence, are related to the know effects of being satisfied or dissatisfied with one's work.

LITERATURE REVIEW :-

Human resource management (HRM) practices are being increasingly treated as dependent rather than independent variables. Whereas in the past researchers focused almost exclusively on how changes in HRM practices affect employee performance or satisfaction, researchers is now beginning to ask how organizational conditions shape HRM practices (e.g., design, staffing, performance appraisal, compensation, and training and development). (Hambrick and Snow 1987; Snow and Hrebiniak 1980; Olian and Rynes 1984; Lawler 1984; Hambrick and Mason 1984; Gupta and Govindarajan 1984a, b; and Miller, Kets de Vries and Toulouse 1982), Baron's found that Job Satisfaction is an attribute held by employees about their work and also he explains that it is "the extent to which a worker is content with position, conditions, cooperation and general treatment relative to others in organizations."

SCOPE FOR THE STUDY:-

The present study involves the analysis of Job satisfaction of women employees in Educational Institution in Pune region. 56% of women prefer to work in educational sector then others. Therefore, this study concentrates on the women working in educational institution situated in Pune city. The job satisfaction of the women workers in these organizations is measured in terms of various job satisfaction factors.

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH:

- To make a preliminary determination of overall job satisfaction among women in educational institution.
- To identify specific characteristics of educational jobs that make women more or less satisfied.
- To study colleagues (male) behaviour with respondent.
- To understand the basis on which performance is evaluated.
- To analyze the attributes on which increment is based.

5. Methodology:-

The study covers both primary & secondary data to fulfill the above objectives. A structured form of questionnaire was distributed to 100 employees of age group 18 to 55 in Pune City, from various educational institutions.

The secondary data was collected from the published records, journals, magazines & web portals.

6. Tools Used:-

- The data collected was tabulated & analyzed with the help of simple percentage (%) technique.
- Chi square test was applied for testing the hypothesis.

7. Limitations of the Study:-

1. Due to time factor only 100 employees were surveyed.
2. The study is limited only to Pune City.

8. Hypothesis of the Study:-

1. There is significant association between satisfaction level and status of women.
2. There is significant association between Salary increment and status of women
3. There is significant association between income & status of women.
4. There is no significant association between performance and status of women.

Married : 53 Unmarried : 47

Q1. Status wise analysis for working years?

Attributes	0-1 year	1-2 year	3-5 years	More than 5 yrs	Total
Married	11	14	15	13	53
Unmarried	18	16	11	02	47
Total	29	30	26	15	100

From the above table it is concluded that 30% of the women are working between 1-2 years whereas 15 % of the women are more than 5 years.

Q2. Age –wise classification

Attributes	18 - 20 year	21-25 year	26-35 years	Above 36	Total
Married	04	19	17	13	53
Unmarried	17	27	03	--	47
Total	21	46	20	13	100

From the above table it is concluded that 46% of the women are under the age group of 21-25 years whereas 13 % are above the age group of 36.

Q3. Which industry from the following would you like to prefer?

Attributes	Education	KPO	BPO	Hospitality	Total
Married	29	4	7	13	53
Unmarried	27	8	03	09	47
Total	56	12	10	22	100

From the above table it is concluded that majority of the respondent i.e 56% would like to prefer educational sector than other.

Q4. Status –wise analysis

Attributes	Yes	No	Total
Married	53	--	53
Unmarried	47	--	47
Total	100	--	100

From the above table it is concluded that 56% are unmarried women and 47% are married women selected for the study.

5. Income –wise analysis

Attributes	Less than 1,00,000	1,00,000 to 2,00,000	2,00,000 to 3,00,000	3,00,000 to 5,00,000	More than 5,00,000	Total
Married	11	16	17	09	--	53
Unmarried	14	13	16	04	--	47
Total	25	29	33	13	--	100

From the above table it is concluded that 33% of the respondent fall under the income category of 2-3 lakhs.

Q6. Satisfaction with your present employment?

Attributes	Yes	No	Total
Married	28	25	53
Unmarried	29	18	47
Total	57	43	100

From the above table it is concluded that 28% of the married respondent & 29% of unmarried respondents are satisfied with present employment

Q7. If yes, please specify the reason

Attributes	reward recognition &	career development	training program	Others (recreational activities)	Total
Married	09	17	11	16	53
Unmarried	06	14	08	19	47
Total	15	31	19	35	100

From the above table it is concluded that 31% of the respondent are satisfied due to career opportunities whereas 35% are satisfied for other reasons such as recreational activities, industry- interface etc.

Q8. If no, please specify the reason

Attributes	salary	working environment	work pressure	Lack of motivation	Total
Married	13	11	17	12	53
Unmarried	14	08	13	12	47
Total	27	19	30	24	100

From the above table it is concluded that 30% of the respondent are not satisfied due to work pressure whereas 27% are not satisfied due to salary .

Q9. Spirit of cooperation in your organization?

Attributes	Yes	No	Total
Married	34	19	53
Unmarried	26	21	47
Total	60	40	100

From the above table it is concluded that 60% of the respondent feel that there is a spirit of cooperation in their organization whereas 40% does not feel the same .

Q10. Training and seminars organized by Organization in a year

Attributes	Once	Twice	thrice	more than 3	Total
Married	11	22	12	08	53
Unmarried	09	20	11	07	47
Total	20	42	23	15	100

From the above table it is concluded that 42% of the respondent said that the training & seminar is organized twice in a year while 15 % of the respondent said that the training & seminar is organized more than twice in a year.

Q11.Satisfaction level with personal workplace ?

Attributes	fully satisfied	satisfied	partial satisfied	not satisfied	Total
Married	13	18	12	10	53
Unmarried	14	13	09	11	47
Total	27	31	21	21	100

From the above table it is concluded that 79% of the respondent said that they are satisfied with their personal workplace whereas 21% are not satisfied.

Q 12. Colleagues (male) behaviour with Respondent ?

Attributes	excellent	good	appropriate	not appropriate	Total
Married	14	18	12	09	53
Unmarried	15	14	11	07	47
Total	29	32	23	16	100

From the above table it is concluded that 84% of the respondent feel that the male colleagues behaviour is

appropriate., whereas 16% does not agree

Q13. Traveling Distance to reach at work place

Attributes	1- 3 km	3-5 km	5-10 km	more than 10	Total
Married	12	18	14	09	53
Unmarried	15	14	11	07	47
Total	27	32	25	16	100

From the above table it is concluded that 59% of the respondent are comfortable with the distance they travel to reach their work place, whereas 41% of the respondents travel the more than 5Km.

14. Organization opportunity for career enhancement

Attributes	Yes	No	Total
Married	39	14	53
Unmarried	35	12	47
Total	74	26	100

From the above table it is concluded that 74% of the respondent feel that there is an opportunity for career enhancement in the organization, whereas 26% does not feel the same.

Q15. How is your performance evaluated?

Attributes	Productivity	extra-curricular	Sincerity	others	Total
Married	22	9	12	10	53
Unmarried	18	11	10	08	47
Total	40	20	22	18	100

From the above table it is concluded that 40% of the respondent feel that their performance is evaluated on the basis of productivity, whereas 22% feels its on sincerity.

Q16. Salary increment based on .

Attributes	Productivity	Performance	Experience	others	Total
Married	14	17	18	04	53
Unmarried	12	16	16	03	47
Total	26	33	34	07	100

From the above table it is concluded that 34% of the respondent feel that their salary increment is based on the experience , whereas 33% feels it is on performance.

Hypothesis Test:

1. To find out the significant association between satisfaction level and status of women.

Calculated Value	Tabulated Value	Result
0.93	7.82	$X^2 < V = 3, X^2 0.05$

The calculated value is less than the table value; hence the formulated hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is significant association between satisfaction level and status of women.

2. There is no significant association between performance and status of women.

Calculated Value	Tabulated Value	Result
10.52	7.82	$X^2 > V = 3, X^2 0.05$

The calculated value is greater than the table value; hence the formulated hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded that there is significant association between performance and status of women

3. To find out the significant association between Salary increment and status of women.

Calculated Value	Tabulated Value	Result
2.9	7.82	$X^2 < V = 3, X^2 0.05$

The calculated value is less than the table value; hence the formulated hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is significant association between Salary increment and status of women

4. To find out the significant association between income & status of women .

Calculated Value	Tabulated Value	Result
2.9	7.82	$X^2 < V = 3, X^2 0.05$

The calculated value is less than the table value; hence the formulated hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that there is significant association between income & status of women

FINDINGS :

1. 18% of unmarried women are working in 0-1 year category, whereas 15% of married women are working 3-5 years category.
2. 27% of unmarried women are in the age group of 21-25 years whereas, 17% married women are from the group 26-35 years.
3. Majority of unmarried and married women are in the income level of 2-3 lakhs whereas, no one is earning more than 5 lakhs.
4. 28% of the married respondent are satisfied with their present employment whereas, 29% unmarried respondents are satisfied with their present employment.

5. Reward & Recognition, Career development, Training Program are the main factors of Job satisfaction among employees whereas due to salary, working environment, work pressure and lack of motivation are the reason of dissatisfaction .
6. Majority of the respondents feel that there is a spirit of cooperation in their Organization.
7. out of the total, 42% of the respondents said that training & seminars is organized twice in a year.
8. Majority of the respondents are satisfied with their personal workplace.
9. Majority of the respondents feel that their colleagues (male) behaviour is appropriate with them.
10. Majority of the respondents are traveling between 3-5 km per day to reach their work place.
11. Productivity is the major tool for evaluating performance.
12. Performance and experience are the major criteria for salary increment.

CONCLUSIONS:-

From the analysis we conclude that there is a significant association between satisfaction level. Performance, salary and income with status of women. Performance and experience are the major criteria for the increment of salary, whereas productivity and sincerity helps in evaluating performance.

In educational field, there is no women having the income level above 5 Lakhs. When women provided with proper working environment as well as opportunities for career enhancement they are more satisfied.

Every Educational Institutions are organizing training & seminar program for the growth of the faculty, staff and students.

SUGGESTIONS:-

Educational organization should provide fair compensation, good working environment, less work pressure , coordination with co-workers. Also provide opportunities for career enhancement and learning. Their work should get recognized and appreciated. There should be a two-way communication between management and the employees and there should be a spirit of cooperation among the employees. They should be involved in decision making process.

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An Overview Study Of Current HRM Practices As An Indispensable Building Block In Service Sector Virtual Organization.

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Abstract:

Globalization and technology have been two major forces that have brought about change in organizations as well as in HRM system. In response to these forces service sector industries are now transforming into virtual organizations to sustain in the global market and have incorporated many change processes like, outsourcing, downsizing and reengineering, to ensure the continuous growth of these Industries. To sustain in the market, service industries are also not an exception to become virtual in nature. Hence they also function virtually. In this paper the focus will be on the service sector VO (Virtual Organization). Virtual Organization refers to a flexible network of independent entities linked by information technology to share skills, knowledge and access to others' expertise in nontraditional ways to work as a unified organization for achieving common goal. It requires integration of individuals, groups and organizations in a Virtual Organization (VO). This implies greater levels of common understanding, cooperation, flexibility and trust among the teams, popularly known as Virtual Teams (VT). To a great extent the integration of virtual teams is a part of the Human Resource Management. Virtual HR Department allows virtual team to think strategically towards achieving common goals, this call for new roles of HR Professionals in functioning of HR Department in Virtual Organizations.

This paper aims at Defining Virtual Organization, determining the problems of virtual team in action and hence the importance of HRM in service sector Virtual Organization, and pointing out important practices of HRM which need to be considered for creating effective virtual teams in Service Sector VOs.

Key Words: Virtual Organization, HRM, Virtual Teams

- Introduction:

"The growing integration of world economy into a single, huge marketplace is increasing the intensity of competition in a wide range of service industries" (C.S.Venkata Ratnam and B.K. Srivastava, 1991) Globalization and technology have been two major forces that have brought about change in organizations as well as HRM system. Some of the change processes which have been incorporated are, outsourcing, downsizing, reengineering and in all flexibility to ensure the continuous growth of these companies. This has definitely made the organizations to restructure their organizations which are more flexible in nature to deal with these incorporated changes.

Virtual Organization is one of the products of this restructuring of the organizations. Today, the virtual working world has evolved to the point where no physical means are required to conduct business and instead virtual teams can conduct business from various points around the globe and serve customers from locations that are just as remote. (Robert. L Heneman, David B Greenberger, 2002)

Some stimuli that are driving the development of virtual organizations, this includes:

1. Increasingly dynamic markets – having to react quickly to market demands; not all Organizations /enterprises have the core competencies to react to changing demands.
2. Changing value chains – more services led as opposed to manufacturing led growth, particularly important in the western world. Convergence between technologies, services, products etc are changing value chains.
3. Customers are more knowledgeable and demanding, expectations are very high.
4. Personalization – customers/end-users increasingly seeks differentiation or individually developed products and services.
5. One-stop-shop and end-to-end service – some customers/end-users seek one all encompassing solution from one company
6. Shrinking margins – the manufacturing industry is particularly vulnerable to this and will seek new ways of delivering value to customers/end-users
7. Eco-system partnerships or alliances, some, will evolve into virtual organizations. (TekPlus, 2001)

In connection to these above mentioned stimuli various authors have defined virtual organizations taking into consideration one or more features of these organizations. Following are definition of virtual organization.

- 1) A temporary network of independent companies linked by information technology to share skills, costs and access to one another's market. (International Business Week)
- 2) Bradt (1998) describes "The alliance organization, in which functions previously carried out within the boundaries of one organization are conducted by linked partners which concentrate on their core competencies".
- 3) Virtual organizations will be reliant on the medium of cyberspace; will be enabled via new computing and communications developments; [and] will initially only exist across conventional organizational structures. (Christopher Barnatt)
- 4) A virtual organization is a temporary network of independent institutions, businesses or specialized individuals, which work together in a spontaneous fashion by way of information and communication technology, in order to gain an extant competitive edge. They integrate vertically, unify their core-competencies and function as one organization (or organizational unit). (Fuehrer, Votalk, 1997)
- 5) Whatever the virtual corporation turns out to be, flexibility will be its defining characteristic. (Society of Management Accountants of Canada)

The above definitions can be summarized by various characteristics as under:

- 1) Technology: As these are networked organization, the functioning of VO is highly impossible with the frequent communication and information flow. This is only possible through equipped Information Technology.
- 2) Location: Team members work in unconventional locations and this is the prime feature of VO. They work boundary less
- 3) Interdependences: VO call for cooperation and synergy in autonomous units who are working for common purpose, those seemed scattered.
- 4) Decentralization of Power: As location of VO are unconventional , there need to be devolution of power for right decision making since VO tasks work on restricted time frame.
- 5) Common Goal: Virtual Teams in VO need to have common understanding of the mean end while working for the said task, here as the risk of misinterpretation of goals and time of achieving these goals is very high.
- 6) Adaptive: Virtual teams working in VO must have flexibility as one of their basic function.

With above description of the main features of VO, based on the definitions, it can be made clear that for operating and justifying these above features like interdependence, adaptive , devolution of power , Virtual Teams plays a vital role . Having said so HR Department in VO should be able to change is traditional passive outlook to highly proactive partner playing a leadership role in helping to create effective Virtual Teams for meeting corporate strategic objectives.

Here current paper focuses majorly on the importance of Human Resource Management and its functions which are necessary to be considered for creating effective virtual teams in virtual organization.

- Virtual Teams and Arising problems

In general, a group of people becomes a team if all the members of that group consider the goals of the group (team) to be their own goals, as well; if the members of the group manage to create a common approach or method of action whose only purpose is to accomplish the mutual goal, and finally, if every single member of the group holds themselves responsible for the results they achieve. The creation of groups, that is, teams, "is a normal part of human social behavior". Their importance for the organization lies in the fact that teams can make the organization "more flexible, quality-conscious and competitive. Accordingly, "the organizations that recognize the impact of teams on productivity can use that knowledge to their advantage" (Roberts, 1999).

Virtual team is defined as under:

"a group of people who interact through interdependent tasks guided by common purpose", that "works across space, time, and organizational boundaries with links strengthened by webs of communication technologies" (Lipnack, Stamps, 2000, 113).

It is precisely in this definition that Lipnack Stamps give four essential dimensions of the basic model of VT-a (that make it possible) "to hold something as distributed as a network and something as immediate as a virtual team-people linking with purpose over time" (figure 1). These are the following dimensions (Lipnack, Stamps, 2000, p. 115):

Figure 1 Four-Dimension Model (VT)
Source: Lipnack, Stamps, 2000, p. 116.

Following are the characteristics of a virtual organization:

1. Complementary core competencies of team members
2. Boundary crossing
3. Participant equality
4. Changing participants
5. Geographical dispersion
6. Electronic communication

Team members do not necessarily need to be in the same location and might not meet physically.

- Problems of Virtual Team in Action:

The effective and smooth functioning of virtual team for realization of common goal is of prime importance. The definition and characteristics mentioned above makes it clear that VT cannot function or execute any activity as it is seen in traditional working environment so there bound to have various problems when these teams are into action for execution of task. Following are the problems which are primarily seen in VT.

1. Unstable work structure:

As mentioned before, team members can be geographically dispersed and they might work at different times. Thus, teams no longer have the same structure as in a traditional working environment. Apart from the traditional working environment even if we look upon the working of team in Virtual organization, they do not sustain for longer period of time in the defined adhoc structure, which is designed for accomplishing the current said task or project. This can confuse the team members when they are working simultaneously for more than two projects or tasks at a time. Each team member must have a well defined his core functions which allows him to execute his assigned task on his own.

2. Communication:

Different problems concerning communication represent the serious problem in the functioning of the virtual team. One of such problems is the inability to view the whole project. The members of the virtual team know what they as individuals do, but they are not always quite certain whether and how the results of their work "fit" in the total, overall picture of the team task. Consequently, there sometimes can arise problems like the delay of the information needed for accomplishing certain tasks, and accordingly, the delay of completing the

whole work. This certainly can hamper integration and synergy of team members which is required for the realization of common goals of VT. Even the specific communication inside the virtual team may even create some situations in which a member of the virtual team does not understand the received message completely (especially in case of ambiguous information).

3. Un trust :

It is supposed that the essential problem of the virtual team is not the physical, but, the so called, psychological distance, among the members. The all present danger in most virtual teams is that the members who are from different places, belonging to different cultures and possessing different level of technological knowledge feel some kind of fear concerning the way in which their information will be used, or whether other members of the team will give the same contributions to the realization of the mutual task, etc. Sikka Jarvenpaas, 1998), that "trust is the artery of the virtual organization". (Aspin, 1999,) It is the trust which prevents the physical (space) distance from becoming the psychological barrier in the communication of the team members. It takes some time to develop the "on-line" trust, although a little time is usually spent on that.

4. Cross- Cultural Sensitivity:

As stated earlier the members in the VT are not located at one identified place. They are geographical dispersed. This makes it clear that, they are the origin of various regions within or outside the nation with different cultural strata. Understanding our team member cultural background is very essential. This will certainly help in reducing misinterpretation of information, clearly understanding the role of each member, and a healthy communication where they can avoid cross cultural insensitivity.

- Role and Importance of Human Resource Management in Service Sector Virtual Organization:

Having learned the problems of Virtual Team in Action, the current study tries to identify the role of HRM and its various functions which can create the effective VT in Virtual organization.

In era of globalization the Human Resource organization is an important strategic partner in developing the goals and implementing the tactics of the firm. Through a mixed model of centralized and decentralized functions, the corporate HR functions are now viewed as

"Centers of Excellence," Fundamentally HR Department in VO needs to rethink and radically redesign HR Processes for bringing out drastic improvement in the efficiency of VT (Michael Hammer & Steven Stanton, 1995)

In this connection the changing role of Human Resource Management can be summarized as under

1) Recruitment for Trust based team members:

People in different teams working on different projects, in different organizations in different places need to be managed. These people can no longer be controlled. So a new HRM style is required. It is based on giving guidelines, motivating people and most of all: trusting the employee.

Thus, future managers will have to take a different position within their working group. Before all, they need to be good communicators. The leader in a virtual organization must be able to rely on his staff without wanting to control it. He knows that his people will do their assigned work. It is needless to say that the information flow between leader and employee is at least as important as between employees. As trust is so critical, recruitment of the right people becomes extremely important.

Identification of required (KAS) Knowledge, Ability and Skills of each member of Virtual Team should be done to reduce the close monitoring and tight control on employees.

On this ground ideally following are the few (KAS) which are required in VT.

- be self-supervisory
- be able to manage time
- be willing to take extra responsibility
- Track record of virtual work
- Good work habits
- Discipline in staying focused on work when working alone
- Self-sufficiency
- Self-awareness
- Independence
- Comfortable using technology to reach out to others (e.g. Group IM)
- Previous experience working virtually is a bonus

Traditional HR Department certainly carries out the recruitment procedure with the help of technology, but to pool out liable team member for the project is a crucial task. With the help of effective identification of KSA for VT proceeding Recruitment will help to avoid leaders role in settlement the disputed matters , overlapping of various unnecessary work which has arise due to misinterpretation leading to sever un trust among the team members.

KSA will also help in pooling knowledge based Human Resource which are required to think strategically towards achieving the strategic goal in the organization.

2) Cross Cultural Training:

Virtual Organization recognize that Virtual Team play an important role in developing and sustaining a competitive advantage in global business environment (Brewster, 2002; Schuler, Budhwar and Florkowski' 2002; Dowling, Welch and Schuler, 1998; Stroh and Caligiuri,1998a and Napier, 1996).The effectiveness of VT is largely determined by team members' cross cultural adjustments as team members are exposed to different laws and customs, interaction with local bodies and customers, dealing with foreign language etc when they are in action.(Black and Mendenhall, 1990 Sappinen , 1993)hence there is a need for cross cultural training for these teams in VO.

Cross Cultural Training is defined as any planned intervention designed to increase the knowledge and skills of the employees to live and work effectively and achieve organizational goals effectively. (Kealey and Protheroe, 1996).

Here in this context of Virtual organization the Human Resource Department have to customize the training module as per the members in the team who are likely to communicate frequently for a particular task. Training should touch the basic cultural trends of each member if they are majorly responsible for misinterpretation of information. Research has shown that a well designed CCT program can enhance the learning process of the employees and thus facilitate effective cross cultural adjustment while interacting with other team members in VT. (Black And Gregersen, 1991; Caligiuri et al. 2001) The process of determining Cross Cultural Training module may consist of five distinct phases in respect of VT Training:

1. Identify the type of assignment / Project for which CCT (Cross Cultural training) is needed.
2. Determine the basic CCT needs. (This will include the cultures of not only the client for whom the VT is working but importantly will include the training for knowing the culture of the team all the Virtual team members.)
3. Establish the goals and measures for determining training effectiveness.
4. Develop and deliver the CCT program
5. Evaluate whether the CCT program was effective.

3) Designing effective Reward Systems:

Rewards are the important element of any organization. Here there is a need for correct reward strategies for organization that adopt virtual teams, as the 'control approach' in reward system is losing ground and more involvement or high performance approach is need by the management in respect of virtual teams. Reward system should also entirely depend on the degree of virtuality needs to be taken into account in decision about how virtual teams are rewarded. This approach will help the management to achieve more team integration and High level of self management. Also for implementing high performance approach, the management should be very liberal in sharing the following things:

1. Information about the performance of the organization
2. Knowledge that enables to understand and contribute to organizational performance.
3. Power to make decision that influence organizational direction and performance.

The challenge here with the HR Department is to create a 'fit' between the characteristic of the reward system and characteristic of the VT, because team differs in their purpose, structure and virtual characteristics.

Apart from these major HRM practices the HR Department can also practice following techniques for creating effective VT.

4) Encourage camaraderie.

HR Department can start with these initiatives by holding virtual celebrations, using technology and imaginative ways to bridge distance and culture. Some organizations hold virtual birthday parties and special holiday celebrations, even to the extent of giving "virtual gifts." This can increase the VT morale and will have the sense of togetherness as we generally experience in Traditional working environment.

5) Start off with a face-to-face meeting.

In-person meetings are especially good for:

- Getting to know team members and their style of communicating
- Solving problems, such as discussing technical matters that are unclear
- Transferring knowledge.

Hence HR Department should take the initiative to encourage VT for direct (face-to-face) contacts at the very inception at formation or structuring of VT. It is often suggested to the virtual team managers to organize at least one initial meeting for the virtual team members, so that they can meet one another in person and develop some personal contacts. Such meetings, if they are possible at all, make interpersonal contacts and relations among the virtual team members stronger.

Distant teams need regular, structured team meetings. In addition, you need to schedule 1:1s and keep to the schedule. Have a regular cadence for team meetings and 1:1 meetings between managers and employees, and treat these as immovable events. This practice will also help in leveraging conflicts amongst the team members as the leader can ask how the team members are feeling, not just what they're doing. This will help to deal with issues before they escalate.

- Conclusion:

Service sector Virtual organization is has emerged dynamically due to various global changes in market. Understanding these changes and the role of virtual teams working in these organizations is important as virtual teams are been considered as basic unit in VO. Virtual teams need to be very efficient in execution of the action for achieving the end result this calls for defining the role of HRM and changing HRM practices for creating effective Virtual team. HR practices can be restructured by initially defining problems faced by Virtual Teams in action.

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The Role Of Cultural Differences In Workplace: How To Manage People In Global Economy

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ABSTRACT

Global business presents a tremendous opportunity but is also a challenge. Nowadays, in a totally connected world, it is not possible to have a successful business without being aware of cultural differences. It is important to have a multicultural work environment, because it allows the development of different perspectives and powerful brainstorming about the solutions of problems. People with different cultural backgrounds, usually, have different mental models and different approaches to problem solving, which creates a great potential and leverages the team work and results. It is important to keep an open mind and treating people fairly based upon what they do or don't do are the keys to bridging whatever cultural gaps exist. Since the average workforce is much more diverse than twenty or thirty years ago, employers need to keep their employees' cultural differences in mind. The understanding of cultural differences can mean success or losing the deal at the first meeting. It can create a huge impact on your reputation and the way your business is viewed by the rest of the world.

With the growth in global business, more attention is also being paid to cross-culture service encounters. This study helps to understand the effect of intercultural sensitivity on the cross-cultural performance of service employees. This paper focuses on how much it is important for organizations to understand and accept cultural differences, if they want to work around the world and experience working life in different countries. This paper discusses how to manage people in global economy.

KEYWORDS: - Culture, Culture Differences, Culture Sensitivity, Culture Diversity, Work Culture Global Culture.

INTRODUCTION

It is an apparent fact that there is a great need in understanding cultural differences in the workplace. Being that most societies are factually multicultural, and many organizations and individuals pool their resources to break geographic and cultural limits. Cultures, values, attitudes and behaviors are characteristics in a society that ultimately and unfortunately reflects our actions towards others despite how subtle. Nowadays, in a totally connected world, it is not possible to have a successful business without being aware of cultural differences.

We have two important aspects to analyze, that are related of cultural differences. The first one is the analysis of the internal business environment, and the second one is the approach to the external environment, local and global. It is important to have a multicultural work environment, because it allows the development of different perspectives and powerful brainstorms about the solutions of problems. People with difference cultural background, usually, have different mental models and different approaches to problem solving, which creates a great potential and leverages the team work and results. Also, it helps to avoid misunderstandings, when dealing with particular issues, about a product or service that doesn't satisfy clients' needs in a specific region or country. The second aspect is related with doing business globally .What induce more noise in international negotiations are the cultural aspects, which are misunderstood and confused with Ethical differences .The cultural aspects that need to be highlighted are: the protocol, the religion, the use of colors and their meaning, the corporal language, eating habits and gifts.

Good businesses that are multi-national and global players will always keep abreast of the important cultural differences. It has never been easier to research how other countries citizens live and their general beliefs. It is also important to understand how foreign businesses work every day, developing the multi-cultural organizations to manage diversity or respecting differences.

Today's business and service organizations face a three-fold challenge. With management and employees of a variety of national and cultural backgrounds, they must enable this heterogeneous workforce to work together harmoniously toward their common goals; maximize the contribution of each member of what is in fact a large team; ensure fair treatment for all, irrespective of background. Meeting this challenge demands systematic efforts on the part of these organizations, as many of them have come to realize. Whether the multi-cultural character of the company arises from its internationally mobile workforce and its local operations in various countries, or from the mixed backgrounds of a workforce in a single location, the organization must address this diversity if it is to be successful.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY:- This paper discusses the importance of sensitivity to cultural differences. This paper also tells that how can you reduce the risk and reap the benefits of culture difference. This study helps to understand the effect of intercultural sensitivity on the cross-cultural performance of service employees. This paper focuses on how much it is important for organizations to understand and accept cultural differences, if they want to work around the world and experience working life in different countries. This paper discusses how to manage people in global economy. The paper will cover many important aspects like the Importance of Cultural diversity and Sensitivity, Understanding Cultures, Creating a Fair and Respectful Workplace, communicating Across Cultures.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: The study of paper is based on secondary data. The secondary data is collected from various resources like internet, newspaper, journals and magazines, press announcements etc.

Let us then ask ourselves the question; what is culture & characteristics?

Culture has actually been studied in more ways than one. Culture is a set of beliefs that a group of people share. And as such it is important wherever a number of people get together. And the business environment is no exception. Culture comes in many shapes and sizes. It includes areas such as politics, history, faith, mentality, behavior and lifestyle. Culture is a distinctly human means of adapting to circumstances & transmitting this copying skill & knowledge to subsequent generations. Culture gives people a sense of who they are, of belonging, of how they should behave & what they should be doing. Culture is often considered the driving force behind human behavior everywhere. Culture impacts behavior, morale, & productivity at work & includes values & patterns that influence company attitudes and actions.

A culture of Dialogue:

In order to actively participate in culturally diverse societies, every individual should be supported in efforts to develop an attitude that is receptive to intercultural exchange, consisting of several components.

Knowledge- Accurate information about the values, norms, historical experiences and cultural reality underlying the words and actions of others serves to increase mutual understanding.

Respect- While tolerance means not to interfere with others' ways of living or thinking, respect actually attaches a positive value to what one is or does, thus going beyond mere tolerance. This respect, of course, can be extended only if a person's actions and ways of thinking do not limit the rights and freedom of other persons.

Dynamism- No culture is static, but changes over time, so awareness of the dynamism of cultures is important. Keeping in mind that neither one's own nor the culture of others are static lays the basis for an open exchange that includes changing the perception of one's own cultural values and norms.

Readiness to transform- The recognition of differences alone does not yet lead to mutual understanding, but has to be accompanied by a genuine receptivity to other viewpoints. Ultimately, one should be prepared to transform one's own world views by integrating other perspectives into one's ways of thinking.

KEY CONCEPT FOR MANAGING PEOPLE IN GLOBAL ECONOMY

An understanding & utilization of these concepts is critical to successful global performance.

1. **Global leadership:-** being capable of operating in a global environment while being respectful of cultural diversity. This is an individual who can manage accelerating change & differences. The global leader is open & flexible in approaching others can cope with situations.

2. **Cross cultural communication:-** recognizing what is involved in one's image of self & one's role, personal needs, values, standards, expectations, all of which are culturally conditioned. Such a person understands the impacts of cultural factors on communication & is willing to revise & expand such images as part of the process of growth. He/she is aware of verbal & non verbal differences in communication with persons from another culture. Not only does such a person seek to learn another language, but he or she is cognizant that even when people speak the same language, cultural differences can alter communication symbols and meanings and result in misunderstandings.

3. **Cultural sensitivity :-** Knowing that cultural differences as well as similarities exist, without assigning values,

i.e., better or worse, right or wrong, to those cultural differences. A fair and respectful workplace is the hallmark of a modern and productive organization. Successful businesses welcome diverse personnel and maintain a fair and respectful workplace to reap the benefits of fresh perspectives and increased vitality. With the benefits of a diverse organization, there also come risks associated with the multitudes of cultures with different beliefs, standards for communication and other stereotypes. So, how can you reduce the risk and reap the benefits? The solution is training all staff on cultural sensitivity. Understanding Cultural Sensitivity will help all employees to recognize the differences in your diverse workforce and how to be understanding and work through those differences to maximize the productivity of the organization. The cases of Microsoft, McDonald demonstrate how a lack of cultural sensitivity led to failure and result into downfall of company, individual or product.

- When coloring in 800,000 pixels on a map of India, Microsoft colored eight of them a different shade of green to represent the disputed Kashmiri territory. The difference in greens meant Kashmir was shown as non-Indian, and the product was promptly banned in India. Microsoft was left to recall all 200,000 copies of the offending Windows 95 operating system software to try and heal the diplomatic wounds. It cost them millions.
- The fast food giant McDonald's spent thousands on a new TV ad to target the Chinese consumer. The ad showed a Chinese man kneeling before a McDonald's vendor and begging him to accept his expired discount coupon. The ad was pulled due to a lack of cultural sensitivity on McDonald's behalf. The ad caused uproar over the fact that begging is considered a shameful act in Chinese culture.

4. Acculturation :- effectively adjusting and adapting to a specific culture, whether that be a sub-culture within one's own country or abroad. Such a person is alert to the impact of culture shock in successfully managing transitions. Therefore when operating in an unfamiliar culture or dealing with employees from diverse cultural back grounds, this person develops the necessary skills and avoids being ethnocentric.

5. Cultural influences on management :- understanding that management philosophies are deeply noted in culture and that management practices developed in one culture may not easily transfer to another. In global market place, all management is multicultural.

6. Effective intercultural performance :- applying cultural theory and insight to specific cross cultural situations that affect people's performance on the job. Such a person's make provisions for the foreign deployment process overseas adjustments and cultural shock and the reentry of expatriates.

7. Work culture: - applying the general characteristics of culture to the specifics of how people work at a point in time and place. In the macrosence work can be analyzed in terms of human stages of development. The work cultures of hunter, farmer, factory worker and knowledge worker. In the micro sense work culture can be studied in terms of specific industries, organizations or professional groups.

8. Global culture: - understanding that while various characteristics of human culture have always been universal, a unique global culture with some common characteristics may be emerging.

9. Global organizations:-the corporate culture of global organization copes with competition and change, whether in terms of technology, economics, or people. People in global businesses are triply socialized –to their culture, their business culture & their corporate culture.

CULTURAL DIVERSITY IN THE WORKPLACE

Cultural diversity in the workplace provides strengths as well as challenges to businesses today. Diversity issues can be related to race, gender, age, disabilities, religion, job title, physical appearance, sexual orientation, nationality, multi cultures competency, training, experience, and personal habits. Businesses today are working on an international level and it is important for your company to understand the true meaning of diversity when managing an increasingly growing diverse group of people.

Establishing diversity in the workplace has become an important component in today's organizations. When defining diversity in the workplace, it means company has the ability to acknowledge, accept, value, and recognize the worth in celebrating the many differences which exist in all people. When establishing diversity initiatives in an organization, there may be some challenges to overcome. The best way to alleviate most potential issues which can arise is to establish a firm approach to diversity and develop a clear organizational diversity policy.

Businesses have different approaches and policies regarding diversity. Some organizational policies are highly successful and fully defined while others are merely made up of "fluff". On paper they sound good, but in reality contain no substance. When you manage diversity initiatives you want to ensure you don't fall into the latter category. If you have run into challenges managing diversity in the workplace, you are not alone. Many businesses experience degrees of challenges when trying to integrate cultural diversity in the workplace. Establishing diversity in your organization will not come without challenges, but with determination and motivation any obstacles you run into can be overcome. The way they can be overcome is by having a firm grasp in understanding diversity, what it represents, what it can do and what the challenges are. Many negatives can arise if you don't understand how to manage diversity. Weak mismanagement of diversity and snowball into many workplace challenges such as:

- Discrimination. When diversity is not accepted in an organization, much of the time this is due to varying levels and kind of discrimination. Some types of discrimination which exist are gender, race, sexuality, religion, disability, economic class or cultural background.
- Stereotypes and preconceptions. When people assign an identity to an entire group, rather than judging each individual on their own merits, this presents challenges because these conceptions are typically inaccurate and are based off wrongful stereotypes.
- Harassment. Negative attitudes can arise which may lead to harassment of others who are different from the person(s) provoking this behavior.
- Exclusion. In order for diversity initiatives to be successful, you need to eliminate organizational tendency to exclude people for reasons which have nothing to do with the job.

The companies who do not invest in solid diversity policies are often plagued with problems such as:

- High turnover rate. This is costly because each time someone leaves the company, time and money have to be spent on recruiting potential new hires, interviews and subsequently, training new employees.
- Absenteeism. This is another problem which afflicts organizations who lack diversity initiatives; this ends up being expensive because morale goes down which results in less productivity due to low spirits and absenteeism.

- Lawsuits. When discrimination and harassment occur in the workplace, this opens up the organization to costly lawsuits which do not benefit anyone; not the victim, or the employee.

These problems which can occur are directly related to a non-investment in strong diversity initiatives. It is in your company's best interest to promote diversity, but overcoming these challenges sometimes takes effort. One way to overcome these challenges is to promote awareness and acceptance; providing diversity training is good way to accomplish this. This should start on the managerial level and then works its way down through the organization.

Promoting diversity brings about positives such as improving marketplace understanding, and your company's employees reflecting its customer base which leads to better relationships. Also, creating a diverse staff will stimulate innovation and bring different backgrounds of ideas and creativity to the proverbial table.

There are many strong arguments for promoting organizational diversity. When you have a diverse team of employees, this usually results in higher degrees of innovation and better problem solving. A diverse team reflects a larger talent pool of which ideas and solutions can be derived from. If you put forth effort to rise above the challenges, you will realize the true value of diversity in the workplace.

Why Does Cultural Diversity In The Workplace Matter?

Cultural Diversity matters to every single one of us, both professionally and personally. When a group or segment of our population is excluded or oppressed, all of us are denied. For our businesses and communities to not only survive, but to thrive, each of us needs to be aware and sensitive to all the members of the community. Our communities are rich with human resources. When all segments are respected and utilized, it benefits everyone involved. We all need to learn to accept what is different from us and respect it. Realities of cultural diversity:

- Global level
- More than 225 official languages spoken around the world point to at least as many different
- Cultural groups, multicultural societies
- With the increasing intermixture of members of different cultural groups within (national) societies, the exposure to different cultures is no longer limited to a few people who travel abroad, but has become a fact of everyday life at all levels of society.

Search for unity in diversity

1- As every person or social group reflects a multiplicity of traditions and cultures, all individuals differ in some respects, but in other regards have much in common. The search for what one has in common with members of other cultures, religions, and ethnic, social or political groups should always be part of intercultural exchange.

2- The lack of appropriate means of exchange or self-expression can lead to an alienation from the process of globalization and a retreat into a narrow sense of cultural identity.

3- Often, this process is accompanied by a tendency to reinterpret and idealize one's cultural heritage, ignoring the cultural realities of past and present.

4- Such a narrowly defined cultural identity can be the basis for a translation of various root causes of conflict into cultural terms: "difference" is used as an excuse for intolerance.

Developing the multi-cultural organization: managing diversity or respecting differences?

Today's business and service organizations face a three-fold challenge. With management and employees of a variety of national and cultural backgrounds, they must: enable this heterogeneous workforce to work together harmoniously toward their common goals; maximize the contribution of each member of what is in fact a large team; ensure fair treatment for all, irrespective of background.

Meeting this challenge demands systematic efforts on the part of these organizations, as many of them have come to realize. Whether the multi-cultural character of the company arises from its internationally mobile workforce and its local operations in various countries, or from the mixed backgrounds of a workforce in a single location, the organization must address this diversity if it is to be successful.

Defensive or Developmental

Every organization has a strategic choice to make in how it will face this issue, between a fundamentally defensive approach, and one that is developmental in nature and effect. An organization which adopts the defensive approach treats cultural differences as hazards - a series of weak links between people in which there is great potential for misunderstanding, conflict, mistrust and even resentment. It assumes at the start that certain people are inherently culturally insensitive to others. Handling 'cultural diversity' therefore means avoiding giving offence to groups or individuals, preventing harassment, and managing grievances. It may have an implicit political objective as well, to reduce the alleged dominance of one 'culture' or another. The developmental approach, on the other hand, first of all sees cultural differences for what they are - potentially different values, assumptions, expectations, and behavior which people bring to business as a result of their differing backgrounds. Culture is "the way in which a group of people solves problems" Moreover, the developmental approach recognizes that these collective tendencies reveal themselves as individual differences. Members of a team are not there to represent a 'culture' or particular ethnic group - they represent themselves.

Acknowledging The Difference

Handling cultural differences means recognizing that these differences can have a significant impact on how people of different national or ethnic backgrounds approach the day-to-day issues of business and professional life, and that people want those differences, where they exist, to be acknowledged. The developmental approach begins with the more positive assumption that while people may sometimes be unaware of these differences, they are not automatically insensitive to them. The outcome of the developmental approach is recognition of these different perspectives as alternative ways of handling particular situations. Cultural differences are no longer hazards - they are opportunities to strengthen the organization through shared learning, better communication, and new perspectives. How can one tell whether an organization has adopted the defensive or the developmental approach? After all, any organization can use terms such as 'diversity,' 'culture,' 'differences,' or even 'inclusiveness' to its general goals in this area, whatever the reality. For a start, the defensive approach often arises as a reaction to grievances or conflicts. The organization may

define it through policies, procedures, and public relations statements, and make it visible through initiatives and 'programmes.' 'Training' is preoccupied with reducing insensitivity, often by trying to induce certain subjects to admit how insensitive they are. To the extent that such efforts are presented positively (or in the words of one company's website, "leverage[d] for competitive advantage"), it is as a question of equal employment opportunity. Employers need to keep their employees' cultural differences in mind when planning interviews or investigation. Since the average workforce is much more diverse than twenty or thirty years ago, employers need to keep their employees' cultural differences in mind when planning interviews or investigations. , there are a few general principles to keep in mind that can help interviews go more smoothly with a diverse group of people:

Approach each interviewee with an open mind - do not form an opinion before meeting and talking with the individual, but rather let the interview shape your opinion. Put yourself in the interviewee's place - imagine yourself as an employee being faced with your own questions.

Prepare yourself before interviewing each employee on your witness or party list. If you need more information about general cultural attributes of people from certain countries or religions, research the issue (using sources such as the public library or the Internet), reviewing at least two or three different sources for each different cultural type involved. Try to find out as much as you can about a particular culture's stance toward things such as the amount of physical space between people who are talking with each other, the amount of eye contact that is appropriate, the significance of voice inflections when asking questions, and the significance, if any, of head movements and other body language during a conversation. Be sensitive to the role that gender can play in cultural dynamics. For instance, in some cultures, it may be inappropriate for a male interviewer to be alone in a room with a woman who is being interviewed. A general practice of always having an opposite-gender witness present would come in handy for such times. Another example might be that male employees from certain cultures might react very adversely, or may "clam up" altogether, if forced to answer pointed questions from a female interviewer. Whether it's right or wrong to have such an attitude in our country is beside the point if the goal of getting full and accurate information is not being achieved. Remember that one can be easily deceived by generalities and stereotypes. Just as there are significant differences between the longtime citizens of your own neighborhood, town, county, and state, and between the members of your church, there are equally significant differences between the people of other countries and religions. Refer back to point 1 above.

Regardless of cultural differences, there are some constants:

Every person appreciates being treated with respect.

Even those who come from cultures noted for self-sacrifice and community thinking has a sense of self-value and appreciates being treated as individuals.

Every person appreciates feeling as if their opinion matters to you.

Everyone appreciates an opportunity to explain themselves, so be sure to allow enough time to let people "get things off their chests."

Every person from every culture understands the basic concept of fairness: that people should be treated consistently according to known rules or standards, based upon things that were within their power to control.

Every employee comes to an interview with a certain amount of trepidation and uncertainty and will appreciate whatever you can do to reassure them that they will at least be treated fairly.

Remember, while it is important to know your employees and to have basic familiarity with their backgrounds and cultures, you will mislead only yourself if you believe that you have them all figured out based upon cultural generalities. Keeping an open mind and treating people fairly based upon what they do or don't do are the keys to bridging whatever cultural gaps exist.

FINDINGS and RECOMMENDATIONS:-

- : Be sensitive to the fact there are basic differences in the ways people of different cultures communicate, such as through the different use of words, voice & body language.
- : Be persistent in maintaining open communication. If miscommunication occurs, view it as a problem to be solved & an opportunity to be finding new ways to communicate.
- : Openness, caring & mutual respect of the dignity of individuals are essential qualities for effective communication regardless of cultural differences.
- : Take an active interest in the culture & norms of the other person. The more you know about a certain culture, the better chances for effective communication.
- : Being culturally sensitive means being nonjudgmental & recognizing that although differences may exist based on culture, communication can still continue.
- : Think about & examine the cultural bias of your own belief system when trying to understand the culture of another person.
- : Avoid making comparisons, think about them as individual.
- : Active listening includes listening fully, without interrupting, clarifying, acknowledging, reflecting or expanding & building on what being said.
- : With each culture there are individual differences in the way people communicate.
- : Be honest & willing to take risks & make mistakes.
- : Valuing diversity.
- : Valuing & recognizing the importance of one's own culture.
- : A willingness to adapt one's communication & behavior to be compatible with another's cultural norms.
- : A Willingness to learn about the tradition & characteristics of other cultures.
- : Effective communication is enhanced when empathy is conveyed. Empathy can be developed by consistently trying to put yourself in another's shoes.
- ; Become flexible in your communication style.

SUMMARY:-

Here are parallel reasons why all managers should advance their culture learning or why global organizations should include it in their human resource development strategies:-

1. Culture gives people a sense of identity, whether in nations or corporations, specially in terms of the human behavior and values to be encouraged. Through it organizational loyalty and performance can be improved.
2. Cultural knowledge provides insight into the people. The appropriate business protocol can be employed that is in tune with local character, codes, ideology & standards.
3. Cultural concepts and characteristics are useful for the analysis of work culture in the emerging global industrial work environment.
4. Cultural awareness and skill can be useful in influencing organizational culture. Furthermore, subsidiaries, divisions, departments or specializations have sub culture that can foster or undermine organizational goals and communication
5. Cultural insights and tools are helpful in study of comparative management techniques so that we become less culture bound in our approach to leadership and management practice.
- 6 .cultural competencies are essential for those in international business trade.
7. Cultural understanding is relevant to all relocation experiences whether domestic or international. This is valid for individual managers or technicians who are facing a geographic transfer, as well for their families and subordinates involved in such a culture change.
8. Culture understanding and skill development systems. Acculturation to different environments can improve the overseas experience and productivity and facilitate reentry into the home and organizational culture.
9. Culture capacities can enhance one's participation in international organizations and meetings. This is true whether one merely attends a conference abroad, is a delegate to regional or foreign association, is a member in a world or professional enterprise, or is a meeting planner for transnational events.
10. Cultural proficiency can facilitate one's coping with changes of any transitional experience.

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The challenges of diversity in the workplace-Leigh Goessl

Workplace Diversity: Prepared by Susan Woods, Tammy Bormann and Deborah Joseph Schmidle; updated by Deborah Schmidle, currently maintained by Chris Miller

Leadership-Emotional Intelligence For Positive Results

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Abstract

Since the time of Thorndike (1920), a number of different conceptualizations of Emotional Intelligence have appeared which have created an interesting mixture of confusion, controversy and opportunity regarding the best approach to defining and measuring this construct. In an effort to help clarify this situation, the Encyclopedia of Applied Psychology (Spielberger, 2004) recently suggested that there are currently three major conceptual models: the Salovey-Mayer model (Mayer and Salovey, 1997) which defines this construct as the ability to perceive, understand, manage and use emotions to facilitate thinking, measured by an ability-based measure (Mayer et al., 2002); the Goleman model (1998) which views this construct as a wide array of competencies and skills that drive managerial performance, measured by multi-rater assessment (Boyatzis et al., 2001); and the Bar-On model (1997, 2000) which describes a cross-section of interrelated emotional and social competencies, skills and facilitators that impact intelligent behavior, measured by self-report (1997) within a potentially expandable multi-model approach including interview and multi-rater assessment (Bar-On and Handley, 2003).

Key Words: Emotional Intelligence, Leadership, Checklist for Effective Leaders, Neuropsychological Model

Introduction - Emotional Intelligence

Broadly EI embraces two aspects of intelligence:

- (1) Understanding its goals, intentions, responses and behaviours.
- (2) Understanding others, and their feelings.

Some basic principles to satisfy these two aspects are:

- All humans have basic emotional needs
- Each of us has similar, but different emotional needs

- Emotional needs vary more in degree than in type
- Emotional needs vary more than physical needs
- Emotional needs are more basic and more important than “rights”
- Negative feelings are indications of our unmet emotional needs (UEN’s)
- Feelings are real and are not debatable.
- Invalidation destroys self-esteem
- High self-esteem is needed for productivity, job satisfaction, and customer service
- Group harmony requires both mutual need satisfaction and mutual respect of feelings.

Importance of Emotions

- Our bodies communicate with us and others to tell us what we need
- The better our communication, the better we feel
- Emotions help us establish our boundaries
- Emotions have the potential to unite and connect us
- Emotions are essential for good decision making

Emotional intelligence has as much to do with knowing when and how to express emotion as it does with controlling it. For instance, consider an experiment that was done at Yale University by Sigdal Barsade (2002). He had a group of volunteers play the role of managers who come together in a group to allocate bonuses to their subordinates. A trained actor was planted among them. The actor always spoke first. In some groups the actor projected cheerful enthusiasm, in others relaxed warmth. In others depressed sluggishness, and in still others hostile irritability. The results indicated that the actor was able to infect the group with his emotion, and good feelings led to improved cooperation, fairness, and overall group performance. In fact, objective measures indicated that the cheerful groups were better able to distribute the money fairly and in a way that helped the organization.

Emotional Intelligence embraces and draws from numerous other branches of behavioural, emotional and communications theories, such as

- NLP (Neuro-Linguistic Programming),
- Transactional Analysis and empathy,
- Neuropsychology and
- Neurophysiology.

By developing Emotional Intelligence in these areas and the five EQ domains one can become more productive and successful at what to do, and help others to be more productive and successful too.

- Motivations and Emotions:
- Before we begin to look in detail at what emotion is and how it is expressed in organizations, we ought to look first at social interaction and the reasons why we participate in it. What motivates us to relate

to other people? Most of us spend a good deal of our time in organizations engaging in some kind of social interaction. Why? The main reason seems to be that we get some fundamental personal benefit – for example, to be approved of by or to help others, to dominate them or to depend on them. Research tells us that there are at least seven different drives of this kind, a drive being defined here as a persistent tendency to seek certain goal. Drives are usually the result of previous experience, often from childhood, and some may derive from our own innate tendencies. It is also clear that, in animals at least, the social behaviour that results from these drives is important for the survival of species.

The significant point to make for us as executives today is that, apart from the essential biological drives, all the other drives (Table 1) identify either responses from or types of relationships with people. And if this is what truly motivates us in our social interactions in organizations, it is in the expression of these drives that the strongest emotions will be expressed as we achieve our goals or are frustrated in the search.

The effects of and interrelationships between the different drives are complex – the same person can behave in very different ways on different occasions, and we still don't really know why. But while motivation is a huge topic, well beyond the scope of this article, it is worth exploring in a little more detail. In the interests of brevity we have summarized the key drives in Table 1.

Table 1: Drives and social motivations

Type	Drive	Description	Comment and observations
VALUES-LED	Other Motivations	Including the need for achievement or money, for example, interests and values.	These higher level motivations depend in large part on the interaction between our own values and sense of identity (e.g. 'I believe in ethical investments') and the values and identify espoused by other individuals and organizations (e.g. 'We believe in ethical trading');
	Esteem & Identity	The need to have approval from others self-image as valid.	uncomfortable conversations at this level affect our sense of who we are as individuals and may be perceived as personal attacks.
COMPETITIVE	Aggression	The need to harm other people physically or verbally.	Sarcasm and apparently mild banter can be intended and perceived as acts of aggression.
	Domination	The need to be accepted as task leader, to take decisions and be acknowledged as leader by a group.	Senior executives having this drive often find it difficult to cede control to other managers and subordinates

COLLABORATIVE	Sex	The need for physical closeness and sexual intimacy	For many people work is a place to find short or long-term life partners; inappropriate or unwanted attention can be difficult to deal with
	Affiliation	The need for warm responses and acceptance.	Unusually from peers, but also also with senior executives around the organization; unless managed well this can create the impression of a ‘crawling’ executive.
	Dependency	The need for protection, support, guidance or help	From parents, siblings, friends and life partners,, but also from people in positions of power or authority at work; unless the dependency is appropriate in the eyes of all parties this can create difficult relations

BASIC	Biological Needs	Eating, drinking and bodily comfort.	For some, the overwhelming time pressures of work can affect eating and voiding patterns leading to stress-related illnesses and poor health; in addition to the illness itself, this may lead to resentment in a wider pool of people.
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The key point worth bearing in mind in this brief exploration of drives and motivation is the earlier point about how significant these drives are for us. It is no surprise, then, that when we meet someone who is driven in a different way from us, first of all we simply cannot understand him or her. Second, it is also very confusing when what our colleague needs or wants appears totally at odds with our own needs and wants. This can take place when we both ostensibly have the organization's best interests at heart – we're both on the same side, as it were. The outcome inevitably is conflict, and the conversations around the issue are invariably two one-sided conversations that rarely take account of the other person's perspective.

It's worth noting that these drives, as well as motivating us towards certain goals, act as a source of energy which sustains us on the journey. In other words, the drives are self-sustaining and it is extremely difficult to let them go. It's also worth pointing out that it is usually the process of seeking the goal that motivates us – actually achieving the goal may remove their motivation, or in fact may not satisfy us. Let us bear in mind that things change over time. What motivated a colleague last week may not be the same today, but it might return next week.

Sometimes, on the other hand, as we get closer to our goal, a greater motivation may surface actually to prevent the goal from being realized. A child seeing a dog for the first time, for example, may want to pat the dog, but as the dog gets closer a fear of the animal sets in and at some point the child halts in its tracks. The fear of rejection had become greater than the need for closeness.

This brief description of the approach-avoidance conflict (Figure 1) is one example of the complexity involved in getting a grips with motivation, and illustrates well the dangers involved in outlining these ideas in this brief format. The field is huge and we do not intend everyone to become pop-psychologists. We can't hope to know exactly what lies behind someone's behaviour but perhaps now, when faced with what appear to be the peculiar actions or statements of a colleague, you may be less afraid of or less concerned about talking with that colleague. Because it is only in exploring the true goals that people hide behind their emotional smokescreen – consciously or unconsciously – that we can move beyond uncomfortable conversations and towards constructive change for the future.

What are Emotions

Now we can begin to look at exactly what emotions are. We know that many managers dismiss them – and their effects on us – simply because of their intangible and ephemeral nature. 'It's just fancy and whim; an excuse not to get on with the job'. If the intangible and ephemeral nature of sub-atomic particles hasn't kept nuclear physicists from investing time in practical research, then the scientific research into emotions is equally worthy – if not more so – for practical everyday reasons.

First, emotions should be seen as a state of mind, and they have real meaning for the people experiencing them. Extreme emotions such as fear, joy, anger and love, but also subtle emotions such as suspicion and disquiet, are all accompanied by bodily responses – flushes, increased heart rate and sweating, for example. And science can measure these physiological differences. One interesting question, though, is the matter of which comes first. Is it the emotional response or the physiological? Do feelings of fear trigger the release of adrenaline in the muscles ready for fight or flight? Or are our emotions a response to the physiological changes? Is our emotional response nothing more than a signal to the brain that something's changed and that we've noticed it?

Early research on emotion suggested that this second ideas was correct, that emotion was the consciousness of some bodily disturbance. In other words, our emotions were perceived as just another form of behaviour. When, at the end of our tether, we can think of no other way of getting what we want,

frustration boils over into anger, and we shout and stamp and throw things. This actually reduces our own stress level, because it's far easier than staying in the conversation and trying to reason a way out of the frustration – a new way that we've never thought of before. You could describe this kind of emotional response as a behaviour of defeat, a defensive reflex.

Other research suggests that emotion is much more complex than a primitive reflexive behaviour. It doesn't appear to explain, for example, why we may react to sudden aggression with anger or fear. And there's a thread of research that suggests that emotions are a more or less conscious behaviour. The conscious mind chooses to have us burst into tears precisely because it cannot or will not pursue a conversation that has become distasteful. In other words, anger with a subordinate – for example – is neither an instinct or a habit, nor a calculated action. It is an abrupt solution to an internal conflict. Being unable, in a state of stress, to find a delicate and precise answer to a problem, anger reduces the tension for some of us. Of course, that anger then may trigger another reaction in the audience.

While this view has merits in explaining why we can have subtle emotions, it largely fails to satisfy us as an effective explanation for why we have emotions at all.

There is another approach, this is the conception of emotion as a state of mind triggered by an interruption. Initially we are aware that we are frightened, for example, and it's important to realize that we are frightened of something. Indeed, the emotion is triggered by and becomes fixated on that 'something'. Or someone – a manager, a subordinate or an important shareholder, for instance. The emotion feeds on the fixation and is either heightened, as the relationship becomes even more tense, or lessens over time as the immediate significance of the relationship fades.

Let's turn for a moment to this relationship we have with the object of the emotional response. (Table 2) shows two forms of emotional response. In the first or primary emotional response, the state of mind of the subject experiencing the emotion is intimately involved in the relationship with the object of the emotion: 'I hate you' (Table 2). The locus of emotion is internal; it is inside 'me', the person experiencing the emotion. The emotion in this instance reflects our attitude – an intensely personal one – to the object. In the other form, the secondary emotional response – 'the world is beautiful' – the locus of emotion is external. It is out there, in the world. We appreciate the things that make the world beautiful, but our relationship is a symbolic relationship with the whole of the beautiful world. The emotion we feel here still reflects our attitude but it is a slightly impersonal one, hence we call it a secondary emotional response: 'I am touched [primary response] that the world is so beautiful [secondary response].' Of course, we may not always be reflecting on the whole world, but we may be reflecting on a complete situation.

In summary, then, the locus of emotion can be either internal (my perception of something or someone) or external (my perception of the world out there – a symbolic perception that the world is good, bad, hateful).

In the next section we'll look at some examples to clarify how this affects leadership on a day-to-day basis.

Table 2: Analysing emotional grammar

Traditional Grammar	Subject	+Verb	+Object	=sentence
Emotional Expression	'I...	...hate...	...you'	
Emotional Grammar	emotional subject	+ expressed emotion	+ emotional object	= emotional relationship
	(indicating where the emotion is located or harboured)		(indicating what triggers the emotion)	(in this instance indicating the emotion is harboured internally – an internal locus of emotion)

Emotional Intelligence: There has been much debate, over the past decade, over the concept of emotional intelligence. Originally academics developed the concept as a simple, single construct associated with how well we interpret and make sense of emotional information. In this way, it is believed that emotional intelligence is an element of intelligence, in much the same as spatial intelligence or verbal intelligence. Furthermore, as elements of intelligence they are also associated with learning and growing.

By 1999, the formative definition of emotional intelligence had developed to encompass two elements: the appreciation and understanding of emotions – our own and others – and their appropriate expression or use.

Emotional intelligence refers to an ability to recognize the meanings of emotions and their relationships, and to reason and problem solve on the basis of them. Emotional intelligence is involved in the capacity to perceive emotions, assimilate emotion-related feelings, understand the information of these emotions and manage them.

The Key to Emotion Intelligence: EI as a single construct located in the Knowledge Stores.

- 1) Emotional Intelligence as a single construct, located in and focused on the Knowledge Store, and how it relates to intrinsic and extrinsic drives and motivations, its unifying theme is that emotion enhances thoughts and that the person is intelligent about emotion.
- 2) The Knowledge Store perceives emotion from the drives and motivations,
- 3) Sometimes the drives and motivations activate concepts in the Knowledge Store.
- 4) Learning occurs in the Knowledge Store as the Role Playing Mind experiments with emotion-laden actions.
- 5) Over time, through attempts at self management from the Conscious Executive Mind, the most appropriate emotional responses for the individual can be identified and encouraged.

Emotions and Organizational Change: It's clear to many researchers that business leaders must strive for emotional awareness – awareness of both their own and others' emotions. Goleman defines emotional awareness as: 'The recognition of how our emotions affect our performance, and the ability to use our values to guide decision making'. He adds:

Emotional awareness starts with attunement to the stream of feeling that is a constant presence in all of us and with a recognition of how these emotions shape what we perceive, think, and do. From that awareness comes another: that our feelings affect those we deal with.'

He goes on to describe the way we influence each other's emotions as being like a 'social virus' that we catch from each other. This idea that we transmit emotions – that emotions are contagious – is worth thinking about. It taps into a stream of research on body language and non-verbal communication skills that has no place here, but that is well worth exploring by the interested reader.

One business leader who recognized the value of emotional awareness was Andy Grove, chairman, co-founder and former CEO of Intel. He suggests that executives' emotions determine whether a company can successfully get through a crisis or not.

Leaders – Dealing with Emotion: Business leaders are all too often unaware of the effect their behaviour can have on their employees, and therefore on corporate performance. People's emotional reactions to particular behaviours in the CEO, for example, can have a serious effect on the company's potential. Keith McCambridge of Whitehead Mann, the consultancy firm that specializes in executive assessment and development, explains how this can happen:"

There are some people [CEOs] who say: 'This lot are awful. I need you to give me some data so I can go to them and say they're awful, because at the moment it's just intuition. So just assess them, will you?' And then we have to do some education, to say: 'Well, we can do that, but we need to make sure that the individuals know why you're doing this. Would you be prepared to say what you've just said to me to them?' They say 'no' or 'yes' and that's when we start to design the communication process. Where we can, we make sure that people participate in it [the assessment process] rather than being subject to it.

An important point for business leaders to recognize is that even those processes introduced to help executives with their own personal development can be traumatic for those involved. As McCambridge points out: 'It's a stressful process being assessed – even if it's for a development purpose, or with the intent of making you better. It's a hard process for some people to go through – though an exciting process for others.' Sadly this vulnerability is one that some managers are frightened to expose themselves to, for fear of being found wanting in some way. And so the organizations, that succeed in developing themselves in terms of emotional character will have a distinctive advantage over those organizations that exclude interpersonal and emotional development of their workforce. Thankfully, there are mechanisms for beginning to develop this aspect of leadership and management and make it less overtly threatening.

Emotional Capability within Organizations: A researcher at the French Business School, Insead, suggests that in the same way as individuals may have emotional intelligence, organizations may well have something similar. He calls it 'emotional capability'. But this is more akin to a set of organizational routines and doesn't

suggest there is some form of collective organizational brain, says Quy Nguyen Huy:

Unlike emotional intelligence, emotional capability is not innate ... it can be developed over time and doesn't necessarily require a large number of emotionally intelligent individuals in influential positions to make it work.

The concept of emotional capability sits well within the Leadership philosophy, and it's worth exploring here. Emotional capability is thought, overall, to be driven by three critical process:

- Receptivity – how receptive the organization is on the whole to exploring emotions.
- Mobilization – how capable it is of mobilizing and using that emotional information
- And finally learning – how quickly and how well the organization can learn about its emotions.

Neurolinguistic Programming

NLP consists of a set of powerful techniques for rapid and effective behavioural modification, and an operational philosophy to guide their use. It is based on four operational principles, which below these headlines are explained in more detail.

- Know what outcome you want to achieve.
- Have sufficient sensory acuity (acuity means clear understanding) to know if you are moving towards or away from your outcome
- Have sufficient flexibility of behaviour so that you can vary your behaviour until you get your outcome.
- Take action now.

NLP is first and foremost an attitude of curiosity and wonderment. NLP-trained people ask lots of 'how' questions. From these questions we discover how we are doing the process of living and use a well-defined methodology for understanding the structure of our experiences. From noticing specifically how we apply language to our experiences, we can change the way we use our neurology and physiology to produce different results. This process assists us to develop what is called our 'emotional intelligence'. People with high levels of emotional intelligence have been demonstrated to be more successful leaders and managers in every context of life.

The attitude, methodology and techniques of NLP form the basis for modeling excellence in ourselves and in others. By being able to define the structure of excellence we can learn how to have behaviours of excellence in all areas of our life by re-coding our neurology. NLP is a process for re-coding, re-patterning and re-programming the way we do things to achieve mastery in our lives.

It is important to have specific outcomes. Many people do not have conscious outcomes and wander randomly through life. NLP stresses the importance of living with conscious purpose. In order to achieve outcomes it is necessary to act and speak in certain ways. NLP teaches a series of linguistic and behavioural patterns that have proved highly effective in enabling people to change the beliefs and behaviours of other people.

Transactional Analysis and Empathy

There's a very strong link between EQ and TA (Transactional Analysis). To understand and explain EQ one can refer to the 'adult' aspect of the TA model (for example, the child becomes less emotionally intelligent/mature when slipping into other negative child or negative parents modes). In this way we can see that one's strength in EQ is certainly linked to personal experience, especially formative years.

Empathy is a particularly important aspect of emotional intelligence, and researchers have known for years that it contributes to occupational success. Rosenthal and his colleagues at Harvard discovered over two decades ago that people who were best at identifying others' emotions were more successful in their work as well as in their social lives. More recently, a survey of retail sales buyers found that appeal sales representatives were valued primarily for their empathy. The buyers reported that they wanted representatives who could listen well and really understand what they wanted and what their concerns were.

Neurophysiology of EI

According to Psychoneurologists moods and behaviours are largely influenced by the ratio of five CNS chemicals known as amines. The secretion of these amines, as controlled by CNS, in turn, regulate the emotional intelligence of the person. These include non-epinephrine (non-adrenalin), Epinephrine (adrenalin), Serotonin (5 – HT), Dopamine and Phenylethylamine (PEA).

Adrenalin – Triggers anxiety – flight and fright responses in animals – needed under severe stress. But if abundance under ordinary life circumstances – it may include paranoid symptoms – hence lowered EQ.

Norepinephrine – Triggers hostility and irritability – triggers aggressive behaviour. Helpful to assert for extremely docile personality – otherwise lowers EQ.

Serotonin – Normal level makes feel good, released and even sleepy – increasing level stimulate nervous tension, heart palpitations, water retention and inability to concentrate and perform. The body turns serotonin into melatonin at night. Melatonin is the peptide that enables us to sleep.

Phenylethylamine (PEA) Elevates mood that helps to feel euphoric at low level and paranoid at high level.

Moods and behaviours are largely influenced by the ratio of five nervous system chemicals known as amines. The ideal state is to have to have a ratio of amines such that the inhibitory modulating amines (dopamine and PEA are in greater abundance than the excitatory amines (adrenalin, noradrenalin and serotonin).

Brain research

The concept of Emotional Intelligence is based on brain research. Research shows that these skills are different from technical and purely cognitive abilities because they involve a different part of the brain – the emotional center rather than the neocortex.

According to affective neuroscience, there is a vast discrepancy between cognitive intelligence and emotional intelligence in brain circuitry. The components of IQ, like, abstract reasoning, vocabulary, spatial logic etc. based primarily in specific areas of the neocortex. Damaging of this area is the result of mental retardation in various degrees. On the other hand, the neural circuitry for the behavioural manifestation of emotional intelligence links primarily the limbic areas for emotion and then centering on the amygdala extends networks throughout the brain – to areas in the prefrontal cortex and the executive center of the brain. The dorsolateral, ventromedial and orbitofrontal sectors of prefrontal cortex as well as amygdala and hippocampus of this circuitry. Moreover, researchers also notice important functional differences between left and the right sides in each of these sectors. Lesions in these areas produce deficits in the hallmark abilities of EI-Self-Awareness, Self-Management including Motivation.

Controversies arise on the point of use of the construct of intelligence for intelligence for emotional

intelligence by amygdale. There is no reason to consider amygdale totally devoid for cognitive capacity and neocortex is the exclusive seat of cognition and rationality. For example, if the amygdale generates “fear”, it must of necessary have the cognitive capacity to interpret something to be a “threat”. Again, how could the neo-cortex think or pursue a rational line of thought if it were not emotionally in touch with our goals, values, desires, fears, etc.? For either we grant that the amygdale has some cognitive capacity, or that it has none. If we believe it to have some, we should not conclude that the neo-cortex is the exclusive seat of “cognition” and “rationality”. If we believe that the amygdale lacks all cognitive capacity, there would be no reason to believe the amygdale capable of generating specific emotions – all of which presuppose specific cognitive definition. To conclude, researchers come up with the metaphor of “balancing” the rationality of the neo-cortex with the emotionality of the amygdale.

So, a can be postulated that the neo-cortex has nothing but higher motivation, desires, and values and the amygdale nothing but lower modes of cognition.

Recent brain researches suggest that increased connectivity between the amygdale and the cortex could result in more harmonious balance between reason and emotion – as it is the intersection of these two processes that makes us uniquely human.

Neuropsychological Model

The Neuropsychology of Self-Discipline teach a seven-step process to build the power of self-discipline and motivation into ones own life. The first three steps are motivational – they provide with the fire, the drive, the emotional energy (for fourth step) to complete goal. The final three steps are actionable – they detail the things that must be done to succeed.

The model can be explained as –

1. Create a Purpose: Define exactly what you really want to accomplish. This gives you a cause, a reason for making the effort. It lights a small spark inside you that will soon begin to burn as your emotion and drive increases.
2. Find Role Models: In order to believe that you can reach your goal, it is important for you find others who have achieved a similar goal. These models provide you with two key ingredients – the belief that your goal can be accomplished, a sense of possibility – and a template or plan you can follow. They’ve achieved it, why can’t you. This sense of possibility combined with a defined purpose further feeds our emotional fire.
3. Sensory Vision: You can vividly see yourself reaping the rewards of achieving your goal. The vision comes alive. You can see, touch, smell, and feel it, you go from “I think I can do it” to “I know I can do it.”
4. Emotion: Your vision becomes atomic in nature, every cell of your body is charged with emotion and passion. With this passing you are now motivated to complete action steps four, five, and six.
5. Planning: You determine exactly what you need to do to reach your goal and how long it will take. This step further fuels your passion and kindles your emotional fires by turning your vision into a concrete plan.
6. Knowledge and Skills: Once you have a plan to reach your goal, you have to acquire the skills and knowledge necessary to implement the plan. You must develop the confidence that you can learn. Each time you master a skill, your confidence in your ability to succeed increases, you get closer to your goal, and the passion from which you draw your motivation energy further increases.
7. Persistence and Perseverance: Persistence is staying with your vision, seeing it through to its completion no matter how long it takes or how difficult it is. Perseverance is persisting in spite of physical and emotional pain, setbacks, and hardships.

MODEL OF MOTIVATION FOR LEADERS
(THE NEUROPSYCHOLOGY OF SELF DISCIPLINE)

"I know what
what I want to achieve"

"If they can do it then
it's possible for me too"

"I see & feel myself doing
it. Now I know I can do it"

"I know what I have
to do to achieve it"

"I can learn the skills
and knowledge I need
to achieve it?"

"No matter how long it
takes or how hard it is,
I can do it"

Components of EQ – GOLEMAN

Self-awareness – The ability to recognize an emotion

Emotional awareness – Your ability to recognize your own emotions and their effects.

Self-confidence – Sureness about your self-worth and capabilities.

Self-confidence – Sureness about your self-worth and capabilities.

Self-regulation.

Self-control – Managing disruptive impulses.

Trustworthiness – Maintaining standards of honesty and integrity.

Conscientiousness – Taking responsibility for your own performance.

Adaptability – Handling change with flexibility.

Innovation – Being open to new ideas.

Motivation.

Achievement drive – Your constant striving to improve or to meet a standard of excellence.

Commitment – Aligning with the goals of the group or organization.

Initiative – Reaching yourself to act on opportunities.

Optimism – Pursuing goals persistently despite obstacles and setbacks.

Empathy.

Understanding others – Discerning the feelings behind the needs and wants of others.

Service orientation – Anticipating, recognizing and meeting clients' needs.

Developing others – Sensing what others need to progress and bolstering their abilities.

Leveraging diversity – Cultivating opportunities through diverse people.

Political awareness – Reading a group's emotional currents and power relationships.

Social skills.

Influence – Wielding effective persuasion tactics.

Communication – Sending clear messages.

Leadership – Inspiring and guiding groups and people

Change catalyst – Initiating or managing change.

Conflict management – Understanding, negotiating and resolving disagreements.

Building bonds – Nurturing instrumental relationships.

Collaboration and cooperation – Working with others towards shared goals.

Team capabilities – Creating group synergy in pursuing collective.

Effective Leaders: The role of Emotional Intelligence (EI)

With business and the economy shifting from an industrial to a service or knowledge-based economy, the fall of the dot-com boom, job losses and outsourcing, the traditional "slash and burn" strategy and the old autocratic, top-down management approach doesn't have a place on the playing field. Today, more than ever before, executives need to revise their game plans in order to adapt to constant change, reduce errors and play "smarter".

In addition to learning how to adapt to rapid change and eliminating common errors in leadership, learning to "play smarter" is just as critical to stay at the top of one's game. One of the most innovative tools executives can use to accomplish this goal is to principles of EI in the corporate environment and in their own professional development.

The term "emotional intelligence", which was coined by psychologists John Mayer and Peter Salovey in 1990, came out of research conducted by Harvard professor David McClelland on comparing exceptional employees

to mediocre ones determining the distinguishing competencies between the two groups. McClelland suggested that organizations look for these competencies in their employees and train employees lacking in them. Then, in 1995 Daniel Goleman published Emotional Intelligence, a bestseller that describes how EI, or the qualities enabling employees to excel, is superior to IQ in determining success. In 2002, Goleman continued his thought innovation with Personal Leadership, which “explores the role of emotional intelligence in leadership”. According to Goleman et al. the importance of EI lies in the obvious but ignored fact that the mood of the leader and how it impacts the mood of the team are inter-related.

EQ fundamentals

1. Build emotional literacy
2. Recognize patterns
3. Apply consequential thinking
4. Evaluate & rechoose
5. Motivate yourself
6. Choose optimism
7. Create empathy
8. Commit to noble goals

Excellence for Leadership - Components

Know Yourself: What makes you think, act and feel the way you do? What parts of your reaction are habitual (done without conscious thought) and which parts are intentional? What are you afraid of?

Self-awareness: the recognition of the causes and effects of your own feelings and reaction.

Self-honesty: the acceptance of your own qualities and faults, your own experiences and emotions and your own power.

Independence: the recognition of your own rights and responsibilities as a free person.

Choose Yourself: How do you know what is right for you? Can you increase your awareness of your actions so that you see their effects/ If you were not afraid, what would you do? Can you live with doing less than what is right?

Delay gratification: take “right” action even though there may not be immediate reward.

Prioritize: to the forefront of your mind a “checklist” of what is most important so you can weigh decisions and actions.

Manage feelings: use simple techniques, like a pause for reflection, to act – not react.

Optimism: recognize that you have choice, that you can make a difference, that you are an important part of a living whole.

Accountability: hold yourself to high standards and do what is right... even when it seems hopeless.

Give Yourself: Am I leaving a legacy of good? Am I healing or hurting? Do I live the golden rule? Will I die knowing I lived well?

Interdependence: the recognition of an individual’s place in the larger community; awareness and decision making that takes into account the short & long term consequences of our actions.

Empathy: use your awareness to guide your choices.

Noble Goals: commit to action that serves ideals & serves others, but does not hurt anyone and does not profit one over another.

Positive Role by Leaders:

Thinking strategically: 'You need to look beyond the horizon'

'I always need to have alternative options ready and to have thought ahead so I'm able to use them'

Making a personal impact: Intellectual skills are not enough to achieve success, you also need resilience, determination and personal effectiveness.

Giving purpose and direction: We always know where we stand and where we are going. It is essential to have commitment to diversity and inclusive policies.

Geeting the best from people: We need to recognize and celebrate a job well done. Makes real effort to get to know people and understand what makes them tick.

Learning and improving: I value comments, ideas and opinions to improve our work. Most people have something to teach me and I have a passing to learn.

Focusing on delivery: We need a relentless focus on delivering results. 'I am not going to walk away until it is sorted out.'

Summary

A. Importance of Emotions

- Our bodies communicate with us and others to tell us what we need
- The better our communication, the better we feel
- Emotions help us establish our boundaries
- Emotions have the potential to unite and connect us
- Emotions can serve as our inner moral and ethical compass
- Emotions are essential for good decision making

B. Motivation

Achievement drive. Your constant striving to improve or to meet a standard of excellence.

Commitment. Aligning with the goals of the group or organization.

Initiative. Readyng yourself to act on opportunities.

Optimism. Pursuing goals persistently despite obstacles and setbacks.

Critical Skills Leaders will need in the New Millennium:

1. Cognitive Ability – both raw "intellectual horsepower" and mental agility.
2. Analytical Ability, especially the ability to sort through diverse sources of information and sort out what's most important.
3. The ability to make sound decisions in an environment of ambiguity and uncertainty.
4. Personal and organizational communication skills.
5. The ability to learn from experience.
6. The ability to manage in an environment of diversity managing people from different cultures, genders, generations etc.

Emotional Intelligence Test

Yes/No

- 1. Do you understand both your strengths and your weaknesses?

- 2. Can you be depended on to take care of every detail?
- 3. Are you comfortable with change and open to novel ideas?
- 4. Are you motivated by the satisfaction of meeting your own standards of excellence?
- 5. Do you stay optimistic when things go wrong?
- 6. Can you see things from another person's point of view and sense what matters most to him or her?
- 7. Do you let clients' needs determine how you serve them?
- 8. Do you enjoy helping colleagues develop their skills?
- 9. Can you read office politics accurately?
- 10. Are you able to find "win-win" solutions in negotiations and conflicts?
- 11. Are you the kind of person other people want on a team?
- 12. Are you usually persuasive?

If you answered "yes" to six or more of these questions and if people who know you well would agree with you, then you have a high degree of emotional intelligence.

(Source: Daniel Goleman, *Working With Emotional Intelligence*, Bantam Books, New York, 1998.)

Conclusion – (EI)

So is there anything new about emotional intelligence? In some ways, emotional intelligence really is not new. In fact, it is based on a long history of research and theory in personality and social, as well as I/Q, psychology. Furthermore, Goleman has never claimed otherwise. In fact, one of his main points was that the abilities associated with emotional intelligence have been studied by psychologists for many years, and there is an impressive, and growing body of research suggesting that these abilities are important for success in many areas of life.

However, rather than arguing about whether emotional intelligence is new, it is easier to believe that EI is more useful and interesting to consider how important it is for effective performance at work. There now is a considerable body of research suggesting that a person's ability to perceive, identify, and manage emotion provides the basis for the kinds of social and emotional competencies that are important for success in almost any job. Furthermore, as the pace of change increases and the world of work makes ever greater demands on a person's cognitive, emotional, and physical resources, this particular set of abilities will become increasingly important. And that is good news for I/Q psychologists, for they are the ones who are best situated to help clients to use emotional intelligence to improve both productivity and psychological well-being in the workplace of tomorrow.

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A Study Of The Training Programs In
Yash Birla Group & Wipro Industries

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INTRODUCTION

PETER DRUCKER, the late management guru, had said that “in order to succeed, every organization will have to turn itself into a change agent”.

Change is everywhere, it is inescapable. Hardly a day goes by without the news of world economy or shift from a production to survive in an uncertain world. As also today's business environment is highly competitive because of sweeping efforts of change & competition, a deal of interest has been placed on higher education & lifelong learning.

Consequently business is turning to TRAINING in order to cut costs & increase productivity among employees.

Training refers to the methods used to give new/present employees the skills they need to perform their job. Training might mean showing a new web designer the intricacies of your site, a new salesperson how to sell your firms product. Training is a hallmark of goal management and task managers ignore at the peril.

Training can contribute to the success of the organization by enabling employees to:-

- Improve their performance in the job & thus improve the performance of the organization.
- Achieve promotion & follow a chosen career path.
- To improve the quality of their work & reduce waste & errors.
- Achieve job satisfaction.

Employee training is needed to add value to the organization in terms of increased productivity, heightened morale, reduced cost & greater organizational stability & flexibility.

Training is the most important activity or plays an important role in the development of human resources. To put the right man at the right place with the trained personnel has now become essential in today's globalised market. No organisation has a choice on whether or not to develop employees. Therefore training has nowadays became an important and required factor for maintaining and improving interpersonal and

intergroup collaboration.

Human resource is the life blood of any organisation. Only through well-trained personnel, can an organisation achieve its goals.

At a glance, we find that training gives the following results:

- Growth, expansion and modernization cannot take place without trained manpower. It increases productivity and profitability, reduces cost and finally enhances skill and knowledge of the employee.
- Prevents obsolescence.
- Helps in developing a problem solving attitude.
- Gives people awareness of rules and procedures.

Training can be either on the job or off the job. In the first case, the worker is trained under the guidance of a supervisor whereas off the job training is usually through lectures, conferences, case studies, audio visual etc.

Training is required for the following reasons:

- Training makes people more competent.
- Personnel become committed to their job resulting in proactiveness
People trust each other more.
- Finally, approach to training must be to increase productivity and profitability and secondly to initiate personal growth and development.

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

“Training is a very important priority for us. Training and developing people is a strategic focus. We’re talking about winning in a highly competitive business. It is the central concept around getting the best people to come to work for you, and it is the central concept around moving to the next level. It can’t be overemphasized.”

Training basically is a short term program for improving ability to perform particular tasks. Many people feel that training programs are fad & do not really improve either production or services. However it is not true. It depends upon the top management attitude & organizational culture to make the training program a success and contribute to overall development of the employee. So it important to study the effectiveness of training on employee performance.

In spite of very well designed system of higher education in the country one observes that the business organizations have to spend a huge amount on training programs. This calls for attention on the gap between education environment & training programs. The study would like to concentrate on the need for training programs.

It is found that most of the B-schools impart knowledge, convey valuable information but lack in providing the essential "SKILL TO PERFORM" Same is the case with many training & development institutes, as such when employees are recruited, they lack practical skills though they possess enough theoretical knowledge. There is an urgent need to reorient the methods of Training programs so that the employees become performance-oriented and not merely bookish- knowledge-oriented.

The need for training program can be emphasized in various work situations, such as in developing skills for existing jobs, planning out one's future job profile, elevating employee's performance, Thus, there is an urgent need to study the impact of training on avenues of skill development and suitable training methods to take care of anticipated changes in process and jobs.

Hence the study aims to investigate whether accidents, scrap & damage can be avoided or minimized through training. Even dissatisfaction, complains, absenteeism and turnover can be reduced if employees are well trained.

OBJECTIVES:

The objectives of the present research study can be spelt out with reference to Yash Birla Group of industries & Wipro industry:

1. To understand training programs of above organizations.
 2. To study the need & purpose of training.
 3. To analyze the impact of training on employee retention.
 4. To study and evaluate impact of training on employee efficiency and productivity.
- Justification for objectives:

The above objectives are selected since the research is time bound. The researcher feels that the above objectives are satisfactory to study the training programs.

HYPOTHESIS

The study proposes to work on following hypothesis:

1. Employers are keen to develop their employees as per their requirement through training programs.
2. Employees least consider training program as a vital part in improving their overall efficiency.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is an empirical study. It is analytical and descriptive. For this purpose researcher uses primary as well as secondary method of data collection. The attempt was made to collect data from all the employees as well as employers with the help of questionnaire and proper interview schedules, though all the efforts were taken to get feedback. Secondary data was collected by referring training manuals of organization, journals on training and development and books.

Sampling method was applied. The size of sample will be 4 HR executive, 2 training managers/appraisal persons and 10-15 employees. The sample is selected as per convenience.

Sample size

Universe:

This research proposal will be considered as a comparative study of training policies In Yash Birla and Wipro. Due to limitation of time, the research is restricted to these companies.

Sample Size

<u>Company</u>	<u>Population Size</u>	<u>Sample Size</u>	<u>Sample %</u>
Yash Birla	900	45	5 %
Wipro	800	40	5 %

Methods of data collection:

Questionnaire method:

Questionnaire method was used to collect information pertaining to training policies of organizations to get first hand information.

Interview schedule:

An interview method was used to collect specific and relevant information.

Primary data collection:

For the purpose of research, researcher used primary as well as secondary method of data collection. The attempt was made to collect data from all the employees as well as employers with the help of questionnaire and proper interview schedules, though all the efforts were taken to get feedback.

Secondary Data collection:

Secondary data was collected by referring training manuals of organization, brochures, journals on training and development and books.

Sampling Techniques:

Random Sampling method was applied. The sample size taken for the research work was 5% of population size, which comes to around 85 respondents in total.

Expected Contribution

The study would enable the reader to understand and explore the need and importance of training in today's competitive world. At the same time it will also reveal suggestions for any improvements

Researcher feels that this study will motivate other organizations to frame ideal training policies in future. In case if, further study is made in employee training then this study will serve as basic study. The main purpose of the study is to convey to the reader the whole results in detail and so arranged as enable each reader to determine the validity of conclusion,

INTRODUCTION TO TRAINING

In simple terms, training & development refer to the imparting of specific skills, abilities and knowledge to an employee. A formal definition of training& development is

...it is any attempt to improve current or future performance by increasing an employee's ability to perform through learning, usually by changing the employee's attitude or increasing his or her skills & knowledge. The need for training & development is determined by the employee's performance deficiency, computed as follows:

Training & development need = standard performance – actual performance¹

“Training in a work organisation is essentially a learning process, in which learning opportunities are purposefully structured by the managerial, personnel and training staff, working in collaboration, or by external agents, acting on their behalf. The aim of the process is to develop in the organization's employees the knowledge, skills & attitudes that have been defined as necessary for the effective performance of their work & hence for the achievement of the organizational aim & objectives by the most cost-effective means available”²

1) K.Aswathappa, 2007, HUMAN RESOURCE AND PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT, bangalore, tata McGraw Hill publishing company limited¹

2) S.K.Ghosh, 1996, HRD IN THE THIRD WORLD QUEST FOR EMPOWERMENT, Vikas Publishing House PVT. LTD²

The training strategies are developed and backed by training system that equips and empowers individuals to cope with change. Management and employees committees are charge with the responsibility of periodical examining what additional training will be helpful to the organization. In addition as new and better methods are discovered. A scheme is developed to disseminate them throughout the organization.

Every individual has certain number of talents and skill sets. This may need to be developed further. For some these skills may help them in their day-to-day activities. Which are job related? Such skills therefore help to be enhanced to perfect the execution of any job. Enhancement can be brought about with the help of various training programs are not aimed a improving just some skills but at improving the self as a whole.

Thus to know the actual story of an organization a kind of survey was done which gave an insight to actual of organization and its training programs. This survey was done with the reason to know whether the person really requires training and. If so, what the training should achieve which further determines what training is required.

WHAT IS TRAINING?

Training involves learning, but it is rather more than training that implies learning to do something and when it is unsuccessful, it results in things being done differently. Much of what people learn during their lives is a result of unplanned experience. Training should be a planned process rather than an accidental one. Within organization, the investment in training is intended to result in increased effectiveness at work.

Thus, board definition of training is:

“Training is an enabling process to help an individual think, act and behave differently in accomplishing the set goals”.

This definition is broad enough to include activities such as on-job training, team development, and action learning and performance management.

Purposes of training:

- To improve quality of work force
- To enhance employee growth

- To prevent obsolesces
- To assist new comers
- To motivate personnel
- To increase productivity
- To bridge the ever increasing gap between planning and implementation of projects
- To meet the challenges posed by changes in work environment both socially and technologically.
- To develop and maintain a good employer-employee relations.

Areas of Training:

Training can be provided in the following areas:-

AREAS OF TRAINING

- Knowledge: Training in this area aims at imparting information and guidance to do a job better.
- Attitudes: People develop attitudes towards their job and organization. Training is imparted to develop positive attitudes towards the job and the organization.
- Administrative and conceptual skills: Training is provided to managerial personnel to develop administrative and conceptual skills.
- Social/human skills: The employees are trained in inter personnel skills. Members work as a team rather than just mere individuals
- Technical skills: Candidates are imparted with technical knowledge require for their work. Thus, training is costly investment, which must survey business goals. Thus, it is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of the training programmer.

WHY TRAINING?

Training means of equipping employees to perform competently in their present or future jobs so as to increase the efficiency of the organization and their own job satisfaction. It is the planned provision of the means of learning on the job or in a training centre. The benefits training can give include the following:

- Reduction of learning time and cost. People learn the job quickly, to required standards, safely, and with minimum waste of materials or damage to equipment.
- Improved job performance. Increased output, improved quality, work done on time.
- Less supervision through reduction of problems such as absenteeism, lateness, accidents.
- Better recruitment and selection. Training opportunities help attract right type of employees.
- Reduced labor turnover by developing employees' potential and their job satisfaction.
- Reduced costs resulting from above benefits.
- Increased customer satisfaction through improved goods and services.

Training is a line management responsibility from the top executive to the first line supervisor. Those responsible for the successful accomplishment of the work are also responsible for maintaining the effectiveness of the employees undertaking that work.

WHAT TRAINING IS TO BE GIVEN?

In order to train effectively, it is necessary first to decide in some detail what specific knowledge and skill the jobs involve, what the individuals already possess, and what gaps in such knowledge and skills training can fill.

A systematic approach to the identification of training requirements is described briefly below .to

undertake such an approach, the manager will probably need to enlist the aid of a specialist, e.g. a training officer, or consultant identification of requirement

➤ Examine the job:

Make a preliminary examination of the job to find out what is involved in its satisfactory performance. Managers may well think they already know all the jobs in their department. This will be of particular importance when training new entrance, since the previous holder of the job may have modified the way the job is done to suit his or her own strengths and weakness-such variation may not suit either the new entrant or the managers' requirements.

➤ Describe the job:

Prepare a job description, i.e. a document stating the job title, where located, job relationships, purpose, activities-or overall objective, main objectives and performance standards.

➤ Analyze the training requirements:

Examine the main activities given in the job description so as to identify heavy task involved and the knowledge/skills required for their efficient performance. The extent and depth of this examination depends upon the complexity of the job. There are a variety of analytical techniques, of which the job instruction breakdown is the simplest and can be applied to a variety of jobs.

➤ Assess individual performance:

The process so far has taken no account of the individual who is to do the job. The new entrant's degree of competence to perform the job should have been assessed when he or she was selected. Existing job holders need regular appraisal to determine how they are measuring up to required performance standards, and what training they need to make good their deficiencies or develop their potential. This assessment will give a detailed statement of what the trainee needs to learn, i.e. a training specification.

➤ Corporate training needs:

Identification of training requirements is not related solely to individual's performance. Managers need to be alert to the training implications, both for their own departments and the organizations as a whole, of such matters as technical developments, new systems and procedures, market forecasts, changes in employment policies and practices, financial results, etc. Such changes may call for a 'one-off' program to meet a temporary situation or emergency. But if the organization is to achieve its objectives, there must be a continuous review of manpower resources to ensure their effective use throughout the organization.

WHO IS TO BE TRAINED?

New entrants:

School-leavers and graduates are unlikely to have any knowledge or experience either of the type of work done, or of the conditions under which it is carried out. Adults may have previous work experience, though not necessarily of the kind they are about to undertake, nor in the particular organization.

All new employees therefore require induction training in order to familiarize them with the organization, its products/services, its personnel policies, and practices. Some part of this training may be carried out by the personnel department. But it is the responsibility of the manager to introduce newcomers to the department, to train them from the start in the department is run and the standards of performance and behavior expected from them.

New employees seldom bring to the job the full range of knowledge and skills required. In addition to induction, they must therefore be trained in the necessary job knowledge and skills. The selection procedure, whereby the applicant is matched against the requirements of the job, should have shown the gaps which training needs to fill.

Employees needing improvement in present job:

If performance standards are to be maintained, it is essential that employees are appraised regularly so that any weaknesses, whether owing to deficiencies in the employees themselves, or to changes in the job, can be made good. Identification of such training needs is the duty of manager no one else is so well placed to do this.

Employees preparing for promotion:

If performance standards are to be maintained, it is essential that employees are appraised regularly so that any weaknesses, whether owing to deficiencies in the employees themselves, or to changes in the job, can be made good. Identification of such training needs is the duty of the manager no one else is so well placed to do this.

Employees needing retraining:

An important factor in achieving success, whether as an individual or an organization, is the ability to recognize and respond to change. Changes in products, technology, markets, legislation and so on, can affect the way jobs are done and may mean that some, if not all, employees must acquire new knowledge and skills. Responsibility for meeting operational changes is a major part of every manager's job since retraining is vital to achieve this.

Employees nearing retirement:

In the interests of both the organization and the employees, it is necessary to decide how to maintain their performance at an adequate standard, how best to utilize the knowledge and experience they have, while at the same time enabling them to 'run down' in preparation for retirement. Some may learn new skills, e.g. as job instructors; or apply their experience to special projects which are necessary, but difficult to fit into the normal routine; some may have to be trained to accept lower-level jobs for a period to retirement.

HOW TO TRAIN?

Not only are managers responsible for training their staff but, in many respects, they are the best people to do the training. They know the jobs, they know their staff, and have a direct interest in their successful performance. But the way training is carried out will depend upon the numbers to be trained, the complexity of the work to be done, the difficulty of the training process, and the facilities at the manager's disposal. Training can be done:

- On the-job (on-site, desk training), e.g. assignments/projects, coaching, job instruction, job rotation.
- Off the-job (in the organization), e.g. internal courses, programmed instruction, packaged program.
- Off the-job (out side the organization), e.g. external courses, special duties, correspondence courses, guided reading, T.V and radio program.

The training program

A training program may employ any one or more of these mean e.g. an on the-job instruction program for a new packer; an internal course for a group of supervisors with common training needs; a combination of external courses, coaching and counseling by a manager for a former sales representative newly supported to supervision.

Planning the program

This should contain all the items in the training specification and give of the order in which they should be taught, the methods to be used, instructional staff, location, time table. In planning the program it is helpful to ask-and answer-the following questions:

- Who is to be trained-number and type of employees?
- Why are they to be trained-training objectives?
- What should be taught-knowledge and skills?
- How should training be done-methods?
- Who should do the training-instructors?
- When can it be done-length and frequency?
- Where will it be done-location?
- How will it be assessed-evaluation?

Designing the program

In the program, consideration should be given to the following points:

- Sequence: Chronological order of priority; common/related items.
- Load and pace: How much information trainees can absorb and how quickly they can learn.
- Feedback: To test learning, e.g. by setting targets, exercises.
- Follow-up: If training is to improve job performance, it is essential that the manager gives trainees an early opportunity to practice their newly acquired knowledge and skills in the job. This may be done by a period of practice under supervision, by coaching and counseling, by assignments or projects, by temporary settlement or job rotation. Whatever means are employed, the manager must continue to check to see how well the information is retained and used, until he or she is satisfied that the trainees can perform their jobs competently on their own.

IMPEDIMENTS TO EFFECTIVE TRAINING

There are many impediments which can make a training program ineffective. Following are the major hindrances:

1. Management commitment is lacking and uneven:

Most companies do not spend money on training. Those that do, tend to concentrate on managers, technicians and professionals. The rank-and-file workers are ignored. This must change, for, as a result of rapid technological change, combined with new approaches to organizational design and production

management, workers are required to learn three types of new skills:

- i. The ability to use technology,
- ii. The ability to maintain it, and
- iii. The ability to diagnose system problems. In an increasingly competitive environment, the ability to implement rapid changes in products and technologies is often essential for economic viability.

2. Aggregate spending on training is inadequate:

Companies spend minuscule proportions of their revenues on training. Worse still, budget allocation to training is the first item to be cut when a company faces a financial crunch.

3. Educational institutions award degrees but graduates lack skills:

This is the reason why business must spend vast sums of money to train workers in basic skills.

Organizations also need to train employees in multiple skills. Managers, particularly at the middle level, need to be retrained in team-playing skills, entrepreneurship skills, leadership skills and customer-orientation skills.

4. Large-scale poaching of trained workers:

Trained workforce is in great demand. Unlike Germany, where local business groups pressure companies not to poach on another company's employees, there is no such system in our country. Companies in our country, however, insist on employees to sign 'bonds of tenure' before sending them for training, particularly before deputing them to undergo training in foreign countries. Such bonds are not effective as the employees or the poachers are prepared to pay the stipulated amounts as compensation when the bonds are breached.

5. No help to workers displaced because of downsizing:

Organization are downsizing and de-layering in order to trim their workforces. The government should set apart certain fund from the National Renewal Fund for the purpose of retraining and rehabilitating displaced workers.

6. Employers and B schools must develop closer ties:

B schools are often seen as not responding to labor-market demands. Business is seen as not communicating is demand to B schools. This must change. Businessmen must sit with Deans and structure the courses that would serve the purpose of business better.

7. Organized labor can help:

Organized labor can play a positive role in imparting training to workers. Major trade unions' in our country seem to be busy in attending to mundane issues such as bonus, wage revision, settlement of disputes, and the like. They have little time in imparting training to their members.

ABOUT TRAINING PRACTICE AT WIPRO

Wipro Technologies is a global services provider delivering technology-driven business solutions that meet the strategic objectives of clients. Wipro has 55+ 'Centers of Excellence' that create solutions around specific needs of industries. Wipro delivers unmatched business value to customers through a combination of process excellence, quality frameworks and service delivery innovation.

The Information Technology (IT) and the IT-Enabled (ITES) sector is now recognized as the sunrise industry worldwide and is generally growing at a rate of around 25% - 30% every year. A growth rate of this dimension needs a very robust and flexible support in the learning and development function to keep the parameters of growth always above the curve. Most of the leading organizations worldwide have adopted a flexible and blended approach, using the advancement in technology and behavioral sciences to great advantage.

WIPRO TECHNOLOGIES

- IT Services for the Corporate, Technology Provider and Service Provider segments
- Operations in North America, Europe and Japan

Training Process

To face the new challenges that the current business scenario often throws up, it is important for practitioners to have the knowledge and skills to implement a strong process framework.

The organization provides process and quality training, coaching and facilitation as follows:

- Providing a total training approach which focuses on imparting specific skills to people, aligned with the business goals and process vision of the organization
- Using a training methodology which touches all the essentials of intended process and quality

improvement initiatives, with focus on practicality and implementation

- Creating a training package that enables participants to immediately apply learning's in their respective quality environments

The approach is designed to facilitate active participation from attendees. The trainings are complete with cases studies, sample artifacts and tips on practical implementation.

Key features of process training are:

- Training needs aligned to the client's business goal/process vision
- Workshops designed to be customized to meet specific needs
- Delivered by instructors with hand-on field experience in relevant areas

TALENT TRANSFORMATION

Talent transformation is Wipro's training and development initiative that works towards creating an environment that enables, encourages and empowers employees to learn. This constant learning continuum results in the addition of value all around: for employees as well as for the customers they serve. Technology training is done to keep the employees abreast with the latest technologies. Regular training sessions are held to match the individual needs of employees on a regular basis. Different groups in Talent Transformation focus on different technologies. For example, the Rational Focus Group provides training on different Rational tools like Rational Rose, Rational Unified Process, Rational Test Manager, Rational Purify Plus, Rational Clear case etc. which are used across different verticals in Wipro Technologies at various stages of software development lifecycle.

Wipro Talent Transformation Landscape

The Talent Transformation Landscape

Talent Transformation – A snapshot

- 120+ Trainers with an average teaching exp of 5+ years
- 10+ Doctorates and another 5 pursuing research
- Vast curriculum ranging from Technology to Leadership programs
- Capacity to train 5000 employees every day
- 18000 employees on e-learning with 24X7 mentoring
- State of the art classrooms, assessment Center and labs
- Virtual Classrooms connecting all employees across the Globe

Talent Transformation at Wipro Technologies caters to the need of 'transforming the talent' in the organization to meet the needs of the business. This wing caters to the training needs of over 27000 employees of Wipro Technologies by providing training on technology, line behavioral skills, and business skills, cross culture, project management skills and domain skills. Assessment Center supports Talent Transformation by helping customize courses and measure the effectiveness and the skill levels of employees.

Whether working with global start-ups or enhancing the effectiveness of groups that work across the aisle, this training program gives all the resources team leaders, coaches, managers, and human resource experts need to uncover a team's problem-solving, communication, and conflict management styles, and help people work together to achieve extraordinary results.

Wipro focusing on below strategic five initiatives for training

Grooming Project Managers

Training of project managers at wipro focuses on imparting specific skills to people, aligned with the business goals and process vision of the organization. Here training process starts with identification of potential project managers which requires inputs from existing managers, these potential project managers are sent for Behavioral training.

Further training is divided into two parts part I technical training and part II technical training interventions, technical training is provided as per the capabilities of the employees & as per the organizational goals. At the initial stage in technical training, evaluation of trainee is made where the minimum score of 60% is required. Then, role model talk/chairman talk is arranged further project managers are sent for simulation, a simulation is a kind of equipment or technique that duplicates as nearly as possible the actual conditions encountered on the job. After simulation techniques trainees level assessment is conducted, then they are assigned to project which is kind of on the job training, for the assigned project they need to acquire skills, perform & improve their performance. During the course of their training, project managers need to get inputs from customers & supervisors and finally performance on the project is measured.

In part II-technical training interventions is made, wherein their performance feedback is given on project managers' score card. Then once they scores are up to the mark, then to accelerate their performance, again after one year their performance is evaluated, if their performance is good, it proves that they are improving.

THE ROLES OF A TRAINER-LEADER

A trainer's job, like a leader's, has some critical roles to ensure that participants reach the objectives of learning and change. The

Following are the six major roles of a trainer-leader:

The 6 roles of a trainer-leader in the process of training

1. Envisioning and setting goals of the training initiative.
2. Designing the program.
3. Communicating objectives to participants.
4. Aligning participant expectations with the objectives.
5. Encouraging, inspiring and motivating trainees.
6. Ensuring outcomes and results.

TRAINING PROCESS AT YASH BIRLA GROUP

The Yash Birla Group is a part of the Birla legacy, one of India's oldest, largest and most reputed business groups. The Yash Birla Group, continuing in the nation building tradition of the Birla's has always been a catalyst to India's economic growth. Today the Yash Birla Group (YBG) is a conglomerate of 14 companies in diverse businesses.

- Auto-components & Engineering
- Power Solutions
- Textiles
- Lifestyle
- Infrastructure & Real Estate

Birla family

The Birla family is one of the foremost business houses in India. Their businesses vary from commodities and textiles to automobiles, Information Technology and telecom. The founder of the Birla Group was Baldeo Das Birla, a member of the successful Maheshwari Marwari community from Pilani, in the westerly state of Rajasthan.

For the purpose of research, Zenith Birla (a division of Yash Birla) was taken for study.

Zenith Limited was incorporated in the year 1960. Its Steel Pipes Division located at Khopoli, 80 kms from Mumbai, went into production in a record time of eighteen months. This Division ranks as one of the pioneers amongst Steel Pipe manufacturers of India. Till 1971, Zenith manufactured Steel Pipes by ERW process. Thereafter, the manufacturing Process was converted to the latest technology of High Frequency Induction Welding (HFIW) process.

Training at Zenith Birla Limited

The training program enables to train people to use interpersonal communication skills that leverage subtle distinctions that make the difference between an ordinary employee and an exceptionally effective professional.

Training program gives the techniques that enable employees to increase their effectiveness both professionally and personally. The three main areas are:

- Managing attitude
- Managing goals
- Managing stress
- The training program provides techniques for individuals in an organization to resolve workplace conflict and build a common understanding and framework for working through challenging conflict situations.

Training process

TRAINING PROCESS:

The research reveals that a very innovative & acceptable process of training is followed, where at the beginning of the year all the respective heads of department understand their employees' needs & assess the training needs of each individual. The details of the training topic & trainees is given to Human Resources Department, thereafter HR Department collects the information about various institutes, availability of resources. And accordingly prepare training calendars. As per the availability of resources & training calendars training schedules are prepared and training is conducted as per needs of employees and finally training program is evaluated.

Researcher learned that a very innovative method of training is used by Zenith birla group, where instead of involving only HR department for selecting trainees & designing training program for overall organisation. A very smart move has been taken of delegating the Heads of respective department for selecting trainees & understanding their needs & according manage the program for them.

Findings of the study

The study helped the researcher to come upon the following findings:

- 1) It was observed that in Birla group, 11 respondents fall in the age of 50-60 years, which shows that the company maintain the experienced people & consider them as an asset for organisation.
- 2) There was no respondent in the age of 50-60 years in Wipro, which states that the company looks forward for young, dynamic & talented people since it is a young company of just 28 years, whereas the company is also involved into technology sector which requires constant rejuvenation of knowledge on the part of employees.
- 3) Research stated that maximum size of population i.e. 66% of the sample size, have attended training program during last 6 months – 2 years, Out of which the ratio of males as compared to females is more at Wipro whereas ratio of females is more in case of Birla. Which proves female employees at Birla is more interested & concerned towards training program. Whereas at Wipro trainees of all the age group equally participate in training which states that employees are highly concerned about the training policies and considers training as a vital aspect.
- 4) It has been noticed that all the employees of both the organisation i.e. Wipro & Birla group considered training is a need of an hour. This proves that employees of any age group consider training as an important aspect for the development of skills & improving their performance.

5) This study proves that the training programs of Birla group were quite motivating to the employees at all age group.

It was noticed that at Wipro more efforts are provided towards online training, since the organization is in technological sector, which is constantly engaged in software development & IT service provider.

6) In case of Wipro overall 18% of employees were dissatisfied with the contents of program, which provokes that contents of training are quite competent to satisfy the 82% of respondents.

It can be analyzed that in case of Birla the overall contents of training programs are effective as 71% of respondents were satisfied, which shows that the organisation is concerned & dedicated towards the design of contents of training program

At Birla, out of 30% of dissatisfaction 28% of respondent, were the age group of 40-50 & 50-60, which reflects that as the age grows the interest of the employees towards training program declines. It is important to notice that there was not a single respondent from the sample size who strongly dissatisfied from the contents of the training program. It can further be suggested that there is a need to reframe the contents of the training program at Birla.

7) Overall 18% of the respondents from Birla were dissatisfied from the trainers' knowledge on the content of training program. While 28% of the respondent were dissatisfied with the knowledge of trainer. Hence Wipro needs to consider the same for better results.

8) The study proved that overall 13% of respondents at Birla group were dissatisfied, with the type of training they have attended, whereas in case of Wipro 41% of respondents were dissatisfied, which proves that the type of training provided at Birla group was much accepted as compared to Wipro, hence there is a need to redesign the type of training as per individual needs of trainees for Wipro company

9) The study revealed that at Birla only 11% of the respondents were dissatisfied with the training methodology, on the hand at Wipro 46% of respondents were dissatisfied, which requires a crucial investigation to find out why the employees were dissatisfied. Hence there is need to study their existing methods of training & evaluate & review the same to adjust with the employees' needs.

Both company put together 80% of the Respondents were satisfied which indicates that company are putting more efforts towards training their employees.

It is observed that senior age group respondents are not so satisfied with the training program with the overall training program as compared to young generation; this may be due to difference in their perception towards training program. However this dissatisfaction is seen more in wipro's respondents. Wipro score least i.e. 2.8

in Training Methodology which indicates that Wipro needs to more focus on modification of training program.

10) Wipro needs to concentrate on the training inputs, since 23% of the respondents conceived that trainer had minimal knowledge of the instructional design Wipro requires to concentrate on the training inputs, since 23% of the respondents conceived that trainer had minimal knowledge of the instructional design

11) The survey stated that at Birla group the trainers, knowledge of subject matter was moderate, so company needs to concentrate on training their trainers, thereby increasing their knowledge. The group needs to train the trainer regarding training program, its contents & general guidelines for the smooth conduct of training program.

The researcher observes that in Birla group out of total senior respondents (40-50 age & 50-60 age) 45% of respondents(10 respondents) disagreed that training brings positive change in their performance, this may due to their "I KNOW EVERYTHING" attitude or may be they are not ready to change with the change.

12) From the research it was noticed that only 9% of the respondents from Birla group strongly agree that training programs helps them to organize themselves & reduces the cost of doing unwanted work, whereas 35% from Wipro respondents strongly agree that training programs helps them to organize themselves & reduces the cost of doing unwanted work

This throws a light that at Wipro training program had effectively worked more than Birla group in helping employees to organize themselves

13) Out of 36% of the respondents from Birla Group who disagree that training programs helps to improve interpersonal relationship & raises their morale,68% were the senior respondents, which proves that senior employees at Birla are not much convinced that training boosts their morale.

14) It was evaluated that only 29% of the respondents from Birla group disagree that training programs motivates them to work towards the betterment of organization, whereas 23% of the respondents from Wipro disagree that training programs motivates them to work towards the betterment of organization this proves that training program are motivating employees in improving their performance matrix.

15) Overall 73% and 71% of respondents from Birla group and Wipro respectively agrees that training

programs helps them to develop their personality and it can be noticed that in Wipro 23% strongly agree with it, so it can be stated that Training helps in improves individual personality

16) The study stated that 58% and 60% respondent in Birla Group and Wipro feels that attending training program is important. This proves that employee are interested in training, but in Birla 31% of respondent feels it's a compulsion on analyzing there age group research reveled that out of the 14 respondent 13 were in senior age group (40-60 years) which accounts for 59% of total senior respondents of Birla Group.

17) Research states that company inputs for training program Birla group average was 3.8, but analysis employee involvement for training program, average of responses for Birla group was only 3.2, 3 being the mid point and both the averages are greater than 3 So Hypothesis would be.

“Employers are keen to develop their employees as per their requirement through training programs and even employees consider training program as a vital part in improving their overall efficiency”, but as the average for company inputs on training program is 3.8 much higher than 3.2 i.e. average of employee involvement for training program so it can also be stated that Employer inputs are much greater than the employee interest for getting trained.

Further it states that at Wipro average of company inputs for training program is 3.2 and average of employees' involvement is 3.5, the Gap between the both is less and both the responses are greater than 3 Hypothesis for Wipro group will be

“Employees consider training program as a vital part in improving their overall efficiency and even employers are keen to develop their employees as per their requirement through training programs.”

Suggestions and Recommendations:

Researcher proposes to give the following suggestions and recommendations for the smooth conduct of training programs. These suggestions are quite general in nature which may be adopted for any organization.

- 1) Organizations should create Assessment centers for training and development. These centers should be able to assess the need for training in jobs and impart the required training to the various categories of employees.
- 2) Organizations should set up suitable training and development units for skill and knowledge development with competent persons.
- 3) Business schools should modify their curricula to include programs related to the following:
 - a) Communication management
 - b) Time management;
 - c) Resource management;
 - d) Conflict management;
 - e) Office- management, record keeping, report writing. etc;
 - f) Self- management, finance, health, work and family;
 - g) Human Resource policies, social security and welfare measures; and
 - h) Integrating organizational and individual aspirations.
- 4) The management should initiate action for the following:
 - a) Remuneration and reward system related to training and development activities;
 - b) Transparent personnel policy;
 - c) Policy regarding retention, growth, separation and succession planning;
 - d) Training and development plan short term and long term; and
 - e) Skills and knowledge transfer scheme for core jobs.
 - f) Communication Departments in Training the Trainers
 - g) Suggestion System Assessment which will help in in-depth assessment for suggestion program, identify the strengths and areas for improvement and helps to develop a business plan that helps to achieve goals.
 - h) Suggestion Program Certification must be designed exclusively for suggestion programs comprehensive measurement and analysis covering all aspects of suggestion program operations.
 - i) Arrangements should be made to train the trainers.
- 5) The training program must have an ambience that is conducive to employee motivation.

The role of training and development in human resources has gained prime importance. From the time of conception of any organization, there is need for training and development of manpower. With more and

more outsourcing of jobs, the role of training and development program is getting extended. The stereotyped process of training and development is becoming obsolete with the tremendous growth in technology. It is time that organizations plan a more dynamic system of training and development by equipping employees to deal with change and transforming.

From time to time, review meetings should be held to measure the gain through training and development schemes. Organisations should be open to suggestions and active participation of employees should be encouraged for decision-making. They may even arrange for competition in order to encourage creativity and innovation.

Further scope of study

Since research aimed at studying the training programs through assess over the employers and employees point of views on training programs. The study indents to open up the door for further research to understand the management commitment towards training, training as an important policy of organization and recognizing the future of training in India and motivation as an important tool in training.

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A Study Of Job Satisfaction And Its Impact On Life Satisfaction Amongst Tea Executives In Assam.

Submitted by

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Introduction

Job Satisfaction or Employee satisfaction is one of the most used variables in Organizational Behavior. The worker attitude of job satisfaction is clearly one of the most researched concepts in the business literature. Hundreds, if not thousands, of studies have examined the various dimensions of the job satisfaction and the relationships between job satisfaction and a vast array of other variables. The amount of energy spent studying job satisfaction is implicitly based upon the idea that satisfied workers, at all organizational levels, are important contributors to an organization's effectiveness and ultimately to long-term success. Conversely, dissatisfied workers are implicitly thought to make less of a contribution to the organization. Following this logic, one of the major areas of behavioral research has focused on the relationship between job satisfaction and life satisfaction or subjective well – being sometimes used interchangeably. Job satisfaction is thought to play a key role in the subjective well- being.

Job Satisfaction is the fulfillment and the gratification that comes from work. It is not the money, the benefits or the vacations. It is the general good feelings we receive from doing the work itself.. It is achieved daily by digging out satisfier's wherever they can be found. Many people get considerable satisfaction from doing ordinary jobs. They make quality time out of their working hours no matter what their assignments may be. It is thus a topic of wide interest for both people who work in organizations as well as people who study them. It is one of the most frequently studied variables in Organizational Behavior. It is one of the central variables in both research and theory of organizational phenomenon. There are important reasons why we should be concerned with Job satisfaction. First, the humanitarian perspective is that people deserve to be treated fairly and with respect. Job Satisfaction to some extent is the reflection of good treatment. It can, also considered as an indication of emotional well-being or the psychological health.

Job Satisfaction is also considered as a part of life satisfaction. The nature of a worker's environment off the job indirectly influences his or her feelings on the job. Similarly, since a job is an important part of life for many workers, life affects work and work affects life.

Literature Review

Job satisfaction and life satisfaction has been studied and researched by many scholars all over the world. Primarily, satisfaction falls in the domain of psychology. However the scholars in management have shown keen interest in studying satisfaction of their employees. The research paper published in different international and national journals have been reviewed to identify the research gap and problem.

Job Satisfaction:

Speroff, B.J.(1955) in their study found out inter correlations between the variables – job satisfaction , age of worker and interpersonal desirability values . Significant correlations were found between one’s job satisfaction score and one’s age as well as one’s interpersonal desirability value score and one’s age but no significant correlation between one’s job satisfaction score and one’s interpersonal desirability value score. Similar studies by Weaver, Charles,N.(1974) measured Job satisfaction across the dimensions of selected independent variables like satisfaction with family income, satisfaction with family housing, education, occupation, race, religion, church, attendance, and number in the household and concluded with findings that there is positive relationship between income and satisfaction, housing situation, important variation among the reports at different levels of education, higher satisfaction in blue collared skilled employees in professional firm, no consistent pattern of association between employee age and job satisfaction, church attendance lacks important association with job satisfaction and males living in smaller households report higher levels of job satisfaction than living in larger households.

Fisher, Cynthia,D.(1980) revealed that the relationship between job satisfaction and performance appears to have some intrinsic appeal. The study asserted that performance is measured at one point of time and as a single act, single observation criterion is obtained, such relation becomes weak, one of the ways to strengthen them would be to obtain a patterned or multiple- observation criterion of behavior, repeated observations of performance measured in several ways. Bartel, Ann, P.(1981) studied job satisfaction amongst blacks and concluded that racial differential in job satisfaction cannot be predicted a priori. While blacks do earn lower wages than whites and should therefore be less satisfied, discrimination may have caused blacks to be less satisfied.

Caston , Richard,J., Braitto, Rita.(1985) did an empirical research on nurses and concluded that much more variance can be explained in job satisfaction among workers who value increased job satisfaction highly, than can be explained among workers do not value it highly. There was no relationship between job satisfaction and its importance when it is ranked against other employment goals.. Another research and study by Watson, Larry, W., Hillison,John.(1991) amongst agricultural teachers support that there is a relationship between personality temperament and job satisfaction. Teachers of the sensing – perceiving temperament type exhibited the lowest satisfaction scores. The results show a definite pattern of job satisfaction by temperament type, which led credence to the theory that personality patterns may be a logical way to view job satisfaction.

Pool, Steven,W. (1997) studied American adults between ages 20 to 46 years. The study revealed that all but subordinate substitutes were significant predictors of Job Satisfaction . Task substitutes, organizational substitutes, consideration leadership behavior, initiating structure leadership behavior and work motivation were significant and together accounted for 54% of the total variance of job satisfaction more than any other variables. Tietjen, Mark,A., Myers, Robert,M(1998) had opined in one of their surveys of Job satisfaction that if managers understand the theories propounded by Frederick Herzberg and Edwin Locke , they can focus on strategies of creating job satisfaction. Although aspects of one’s personal life as well as non –job factors at work influences the behaviour and eventually, the satisfaction of the worker, it is the work itself which brings fulfillment and job satisfaction.

Syptak, Michael, J., et al (1999) researched amongst physicians and applied Herzberg's two dimensions of Job satisfaction: Motivation and Hygiene. Their survey revealed that family physicians who created environments that attracted, motivated and retained hard-working individuals created a positive workplace for their employees and could increase their job satisfaction as well. Ramayah, T., et al (2001) studied all the managers, supervisors and operators employed in the manufacturing sector in Penang. The Job Descriptive Index (JDI) developed by Smith, Kendall and Hulin (1965) was chosen to measure the job satisfaction of the employees. This study proved that individuals do not place the same degree of importance for all facets of JDI. Instead, each individual will have his or her own needs and will rank the importance of the different in regard to them.

The study of Hellgren, Johnny, Sverke, Magnus (2001) resulted in an indication that job insecurity that resulted from downsizing is a significant and negative predictor of job satisfaction and well-being because dissatisfied employees are likely to be less productive and look for alternative employment. Okpara, John, O (2002) surveyed IT managers and concluded that ethical environment might help to enhance job satisfaction. Research from the survey indicated that an instrumental climate has a negative influence in overall job satisfaction in organizations. The findings of the study revealed that organizational ethics influences overall job satisfaction.

Pascobe, Celina, et al. (2002) focuses on the role played by job satisfaction and morale in collaborative learning. The competitive advantage requires a 'knowledge edge' and this cannot be achieved unless employees engage in behaviours that will result in generative learning. The researcher reported in the paper and pointed out that various factors enable generative learning and high level of job satisfaction/ positive morale, is one of these. In their study, Krueger, Paul, et al. (2002) entailed six health care organizations and the result showed that job satisfaction is a multidimensional construct and is a product of the global evaluation of one's work place and context. Specific predictors of job satisfaction were identified and the reports provided, valuable information, about the implications of these findings and deliberated their relation to improve Quality of Work life.

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Another interesting study was conducted by Chandraiah, K., et al (2003) where Occupational Stress and Job satisfaction among managers were studied and concluded that individuals under excessive stress tends to find their jobs less satisfying. Some of their intrinsic or extrinsic needs may be thwarted or not met sufficiently. The subjects with lower job satisfaction were found to experience more stress in the form of overload, role ambiguity, role conflict, under participation, powerlessness and low status compared to those with higher job

satisfaction. In 2003, another study by Lather, Anu, Singh., Goyal, Shilpa(2003) studied job satisfaction amongst managers and engineers in relation to personality and psychopathology. The personality structure of Extremely Satisfied(ES) and Extremely Dissatisfied (ED) is similar and that of Very Satisfied (VS) and Not Satisfied (NS) is similar. Only Moderately Satisfied(MS) employees showed different personality structure.

Turner, James H., Brown, Gene (2004) through a survey found that amongst sales representatives- feeling safe, career advancement, networking, meaningfulness of the job is important for overall job satisfaction. An interesting study was done amongst Indian academicians and Haque, Israrul, Mohd(2004) suggested that both intrinsic and extrinsic factors affect a teacher's satisfaction. The satisfied persons are inclined to enhance the productivity of their organization. The relationship between age, gender has a direct bearing on the job related behavior such as productivity and employee turnover, motivation, contribution to production are significant factors for the study of job satisfaction.

Another study by Steijn, Bram. (2004) showed whether commitment and participation of workers in the public sector has any relation with the determinants of job satisfaction. It has been observed that the extent of use of Human Resources Management (HRM) practices does not have a direct effect on overall job satisfaction but has important indirect effects. HRM practices is especially related to higher satisfaction, with the management of the organization, and with career support. It is positively associated with task and pay satisfaction. The findings also illustrates that workers who feel underutilized are dissatisfied with the management, career support and their tasks, and these variables adversely influence job satisfaction. The study by Benarjee, D.B.R.N.K., Rani, Roja, E.(2004) revealed that there is an influence of Quality of Work life(QWL) on job involvement. Where there is less menial work the jobs tend to be more autonomous, employees get involved in decision making and makes the job more interesting and meaningful and hence more Job Satisfaction was found.

In this research .Okpara, John, O.(2004) studied American and Nigerian managers employed in the United States and compared them with job satisfaction and organizational commitment levels. The results showed that American managers have higher levels of job satisfaction and commitment than their Nigerian counterparts. In another study by Carlson, Jessica,H., Mellor, Steven.(2004) resulted that gender and relational self- definition may jointly moderate the influence of job design variables on job satisfaction. The job-design-job- satisfaction relationship may be the strongest when design variables relate to relational self definition of women and men are taken into account. The study proposed how autonomy and individual responsibility in the form of self- actualization opportunity may relate to satisfaction and in contrast, to propose how ethics of care opportunity may relate to satisfaction.

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Alder, Stoney, G., Ambrose, Maureen, L. (2005) made a study amongst undergraduates data entry workers and examined how the design and implementation of Computerized Performance Monitoring (CPM) system affects individual's performance and attitude. Thus prediction was made that procedural fairness and monitoring fairness was positively related to job satisfaction. Kim, Sangmook. (2005) studied a central paradox of gender and job satisfaction as women's job satisfaction is not lower than men's, given that women's jobs are often inferior in terms of pay, autonomy and promotional opportunity. The revealed that women emphasized intrinsic rewards whereas men emphasized extrinsic rewards and that can be an obvious reason as to why women are more satisfied with their jobs than are men.

Sharma, R.D., Jyoti, Jeevan (2006) found that amongst university teachers the various dimensions of job satisfaction are positively correlated but the extent of exerting the influence by them in determining the overall level is different and elements of work, idealness of job influence the determination of the level of Job Satisfaction the most. Lim, L.S., Yager, J., Cope, D., Leake, B. (2006) compared academic and clinical faculty and found no significant differences between the two physicians groups on job satisfaction, total stress, anxiety or depression scores. Academic physicians experienced more conflict between work and personal life, burdened with time pressure, less satisfied with finance.

Life satisfaction :

Diener, Ed. (2000) studied people's cognitive and affective evaluations of their lives, when and why people are happy and what are the processes that influences Subjective Well-Being. Temperament and personality appears to be powerful factors influencing people's SWB, cultural and societal factors also influence SWB in several ways. Some countries are better able to meet people's desires and on the other hand, variations in cultural influences on mean levels of SWB appear to result from variations in optimism and positivism.

Clark, Andrew, E., Oswald, Andrew, J. (2006) in their paper showed that subjective Well Being follows a U-shape through the life course. The article is concerned with a body of work on happiness and age. The study also aptly states that Life-Satisfaction and General Health Questionnaire (GHQ) measures of subjective well-being seem valuably complementary. Libran, Chico, Eliseo. (2006) in their work, examined, the association of well-being with neuroticism and extraversion. 44% of the variance of subjective well-being was accounted by neuroticism and extraversion only explained 8% of the variance.

Krueger, Alan, B., Schkade, David, A. (2006) in their paper used Day Reconstruction Method (DRM) where participants were required to think about the preceding day, break into episodes and describe each episode by selecting from several menus. It was found that overall life satisfaction measures and affective experience measures, derived from DRM, exhibited test-retest correlations in the range of .50-.70. A key factor behind the results are that answering a life satisfaction question explicitly invokes a nonsystematic review to one's life

which leaves such measures vulnerable to transient influences that draw attention to arbitrary or incomplete information. Kahneman, Daniel., Krueger, Alan, B.(2006) in their paper, discusses how individuals' response to subjective well- being questions vary with their circumstances and other factors. This line of research suggests that the intensity of pain and pleasure that arises during an experience can be plausibly measured in real time and that retrospective assessments are not necessarily a good measure of the sum total of individual's actual experiences.

The relationship between Job satisfaction and Life satisfaction:

Subjective well- being (SWB) is a term used by (Diener, Ed. et.al,1997) for how people evaluate their lives. People can evaluate their lives in terms of a global judgment such as life satisfaction or feelings of fulfillment. Thus SWB is an umbrella term, that includes several different components and these components are somewhat independent. People who work for their goals, and achieve them, they experience subjective well-being.

The result is there is a spillover effect that occurs in both directions between job and life satisfaction. (Davis, Keith, 2002). Wilson (1978) defined Quality of Work Life as enriching the nature of work experience, grappling with issues of efficiency and satisfaction. On the whole Life Satisfaction (LS) is often conceptualized as one of the key aspects of psychological well- being.

In the year 1983, Chacko, Thomas,I.(1983) studied the causal relationship of Job and Life Satisfaction and the results indicated that job satisfaction influence occurred more often than did life satisfaction influence. The results are more supportive of the notion that job satisfaction has a greater influence on life or non work satisfaction than vice versa. The study by Chiu, Randy, K.(1998) revealed that job satisfaction directly effects work/family conflicts, job, marital and life satisfactions as the study was done. The findings indicated that work and family conflicts as well as inter role conflict affected job satisfaction and marital satisfaction. Likewise , life satisfaction reported by the respondents was affected by their level of job satisfaction and marital satisfaction as well.

Similar studies by Cramer,Duncan (1995) studied a time related relationship between job and life satisfaction in a two way panel study amongst professional employees of a British engineering company, showed that a Test- retest coefficients for both variables were moderately positive showing that relative ranking of individuals on these variables was fairly stable.

Diener,Ed., Suh, Eunkook., Oishi, Shinehiro.(1997) in their paper attempted to understand people's evaluation of their lives. These evaluations may be primarily cognitive (e.g. life satisfaction or marital satisfaction) or may consist of frequency with which people experience pleasant emotions e.g., joy, and unpleasant emotions e.g., depression.. In another survey, Judge, T.A., et.al.(1998) had studied that core self evaluations ,which were hypothesized to comprise self- esteem , generalized self efficacy, locus of control and non neuroticism had a model hypothesized that core self- evaluations would have direct effects on job and life satisfactions .It also was hypothesized that core self- evaluations would have indirect effects on job satisfaction.

Rain, Jeffrey,S., Lane, Irving,M., Steiner, Dirk,D.(2004) reviewed that theoretical work is too often characterized by repeatedly confirming the spillover hypotheses to the exclusion of advancing theoretical developments. They focused on theoretical and methodological developments which is needed in future research and areas of multiple links ,between job and life satisfaction, life stages, and satisfaction as a disposition which can be developed as potential areas for theoretical advances.

In their study Theodossior, Ioannis., et.al. (2006) studied and found that job satisfaction is the top factor in employee's overall life satisfaction. This is over, and above satisfaction with family, leisure time, health,

finance and social life. They also found that the highly educated have a higher level of job satisfaction and concluded that link between career fulfillment, and life satisfaction cannot be underestimated and is an issue of policy concern and deserves attention. Similar results was revealed by Sharma, R.D., Jyoti, Jeevan (2006) found that University teachers were happy with their jobs as well as life and the results indicated that the individuals satisfied with job are more satisfied with their life and life satisfaction in turn positively influences job satisfaction . Both are reciprocal in their effect on each other.

Yelamanchili, Venkat, Dr.(2006) found that satisfaction with the amount of leisure, environment and with housing come last in the pecking order of happiness and well- being, Career fulfillment provides workers with the means to maintain life satisfaction according to results found by them.

India is the world's largest tea producer followed by China, the north eastern state of Assam is considered the heart of India's tea industry with the state accounting for 55 percent of the country's total annual tea production. There are about 850 big gardens in Assam employing around 30,000 to 40,000 workers. The production last year was a record high of 955 million kilograms, up by 27 million kilograms , compared to 2005, while exports have gone up by about 8 million kilograms to 200 million kilograms in the same period (Economic Survey of Assam 2005-2006). The Tea cultivation occupies a little less than a tenth of the cultivated area of Assam and 75 percent of the tea gardens are located in the Brahmaputra districts of Darrang, Sibsagar and Lakhimpur. Cachar district accounts for 20% of the balance and remaining 5% being accounted by the lower Brahmaputra valley. Tea gardens are categorized into big, medium and small sized gardens depending on the area of land used for cultivation .The land area from one hectare to nine hectares approximately are termed as small gardens, middle sized gardens are of an area ranging from nine to sixteen hectares of land and the big gardens has an area of sixteen hectares to forty hectares approximately. Guwahati Center in Assam has become the biggest center of auction of CTC (Cutting . Tearing and Curling) tea in the world. Basically the hierarchies in the tea organizations consist of three distinct layers, the top executives, the middle management level consisting of the managers and executives and the workers who consist the lower level and are of the largest section.

Economic histories of Western colonialism amply testify to the overriding presence of plantations in colonial economies, and in India it was tea. The tea industry in India has steadily prospered all through these years and is making huge profits even in the days of downturn. In 1998-1999, India produced more than 850 million kgs. of tea whose market value was Rs. 6000 crores and exported 21.3 % of the total produce earning a foreign exchange equivalent of Rs. 2000 crores. Tea plantation industry of Assam and West Bengal, together constituting the most productive region in the world.

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Alder, Stoney,G., Ambrose, Maureen,L.(2005) made a study amongst undergraduates data entry workers and

examined how the design and implementation of Computerized Performance Monitoring (CPM) system affects individual's performance and attitude. Thus prediction was made that procedural fairness and monitoring fairness was positively related to job satisfaction. Kim, Sangmook.(2005) studied a central paradox of gender and job satisfaction as women's job satisfaction is not lower than men's , given that women's jobs are often inferior in terms of pay , autonomy and promotional opportunity. The revealed that women emphasized intrinsic rewards whereas men emphasized extrinsic rewards and that can be an obvious reason as to why women are more satisfied with their jobs than are men.

Sharma, R.D., Jyoti, Jeevan (2006) found that amongst university teachers the various dimensions of job satisfaction are positively correlated but the extent of exerting the influence by them in determining the overall level is different and elements of work, idealness of job influence the determination of the level of Job Satisfaction the most. Lim ,L.S., Yager,J., Cope, D., Leake,B(2006) compared academic and clinical faculty and found no significant differences between the two physicians groups on job satisfaction , total stress, anxiety or depression scores. Academic physicians experienced more conflict between work and personal life, burdened with time pressure, less satisfied with finance.

Objectives:

The proposed study would have the following objectives:

1. To study the job satisfaction level and life satisfaction level of the executives.
2. To establish the cause and effect relationship between Job satisfaction and Life satisfaction.

To study the association of individual characteristics with job satisfaction via-a-vis life satisfaction.

Hypotheses:

- H1: Age Group is a significant determinant in affecting job satisfaction relating to pay
- H2: Hierarchical level is a significant determinant in affecting job satisfaction relating to pay.
- H3: Job satisfaction factors are significant determinants in influencing life satisfaction of executives.

Research Methodology:

The study is a research work based on both the primary and secondary sources of information. The primary data has been collected by distribution of questionnaire . The secondary data required for the study will be collected from several published reports, books , journals, magazines ,bulletins and published reports of Government of India.

The sample used for the study will consisted of 69 executives in selected tea organizations.

The questionnaire was based on , The Job Descriptive Index (JDI) and Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) and Job Satisfaction Scale (JSS) for Job Satisfaction and Satisfaction with life scale (SWLS) for Life satisfaction. The Job Descriptive Index was developed by Smith, Kendall, and Hulin (1969) and the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire was developed by David J. Weiss, Rene V. Dawis., George W. England and Lyod H.

Lofquist (1967) and Job Satisfaction Scale by Spector(1997). A comprehensive questionnaire will be designed to study the data for job satisfaction.

The survey for SWLS (Satisfaction With Life Scale) was used to access the satisfaction with the respondent's life as a whole (Pivot and Diener 1993) and consisted of introspective questions designed to determine life satisfaction , a quality that impacts job satisfaction.

The data was tabulated and analyzed through statistical tools To test each of the hypothesis developed for the study, chi square analysis was done.

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Basic Details of sample employees:

Age Group	20-30 (21)	31-40 (19)	41-50 (18)	Above 50 (11)
Service Experience	Below 5 years (25)	5-10- years (23)	10-15 years (14)	Above 15 years (7)
Salary benefits	10-15(thousand) (23)	15-25(thousand) (19)	25-30(thousand) (18)	Above 30 thousand (9)
Qualification	Graduates (38)	Post Graduates (22)	Prof. Qualified (9)	
Hierarchical level	Lower level (24)	Middle level (28)	Senior level (17)	

Table 1: Showing the satisfaction level of tea executives with respect to the 9 broad dimensions of job satisfaction:

	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very satisfied
Pay	0	17	15	31	6
Supervision	11	19	12	20	7
Promotion	7	15	10	26	11
Security	5	9	13	23	19
Recognition	9	21	14	18	7
Benefits	8	13	28	17	3
Work environment	12	11	17	18	11
Authority	13	14	18	15	9
Co workers	6	7	27	19	10

Table 11: Showing the % of people in satisfaction, neutral and dissatisfaction level with respect to the 9 broad dimensions of job satisfaction

<u>Job satisfaction factors</u>	% of people in dissatisfaction level	% of people In neutral level	% of people In satisfaction level
Pay	24.6	21.7	53.6
Supervision	43.4	17.3	39.1
Promotion	31.9	14.5	53.6
Security	20.3	18.8	60.9
Recognition	43.5	20.3	36.2
Benefits	30.4	40.6	28.9
Work environment	33.3	24.6	42
Co Workers	18.8	39.1	42
Authority	39.1	26	34.8

Percentage of people in satisfaction zone is highest with respect to security and is closely followed by pay and promotion.

Table1: Showing the ranking given by the executives on a scale of 1 to 9 to the various job satisfaction factors

Rank	Pay	Work Env	Supervision	Benefits	Recognition	Authority	Security	Promotion	Co-workers
1	32	11	-	-	-	-	18	-	4
2	21	16	-	-	-	-	29	-	12
3	11	31	4	-	-	-	11	-	17
4	5	5	17	-	-	5	7	1	33
5	-	4	23	5	4	3	4	10	1
6	-	2	12	9	6	2	-	30	2
7	-	-	13	28	17	2	-	11	-
8	-	-	-	15	24	17	-	17	--
9	-	-	-	12	18	40	-	-	-

Table: Showing the calculation on the basis of which ranks have been allocated to the 9 job satisfaction factors in order to find out their relative importance as perceived by the tea garden executives.

Job satisfaction factors	Calculated value	Rank allotted
Pay	$32*1+21*2+11*3+5*4 = 127$	1
Work Environment	$11*1+16*2+31*3+5*4+4*5+2*6 = 188$	3
Supervision	$4*3+17*4+23*5+12*6+13*7 = 358$	5
Benefits	$5*5+9*6+28*7+15*8+12*9= 503$	7
Recognition	$4*5+6*6+17*7+24*8+18*9 = 529$	8
Authority	$5*4+3*5+2*6+2*7 +17*8+40*9=557$	9
Security	$18*1+29*2+11*3+7*4+4*5= 157$	2
Promotion	$1*4+10*5+30*6+11*7+17*8=447$	6
Co-workers	$4*1+12*2+17*3+33*4+1*5+2*6=228$	4

Relative importance of job satisfaction factors as perceived by the tea garden executives:

Rank	Marketing mix
1	Pay
2	Security
3	Work environment
4	Co workers
5	Supervision
6	Promotion
7	Benefits
8	Recognition
9	Authority

In this study we will find out whether age group and hierarchical level have any impact on the satisfaction level relating to the most important job satisfaction factor i.e. Pay of the executives

H1: Age group is a significant determinant in affecting job satisfaction relating to pay

H0: There is no significant difference among age group of executives in affecting job satisfaction relating to pay

ANOVA table for impact of age on job satisfaction relating to pay

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F Ratio	p
Between Groups	70.7	4	17.68	1.76	>0.050
Within Groups	90.2	9	10.02		
Total	160.9	13			

From the above table, it can be clearly inferred that there is no significant difference among age group of executives in affecting job satisfaction relating to pay. Hence H₀ is accepted for age group and hence age factor has significant impact on job satisfaction relating to pay

H₂: Hierarchical level is a significant determinant in affecting job satisfaction relating to pay

H₀: There is no significant difference among organizational hierarchy of executives in affecting job satisfaction relating to pay

ANOVA table for impact of organizational hierarchy on job satisfaction relating to pay

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F Ratio	p
Between Groups	68.4	4	17.1	1.83	>0.050
Within Groups	46.5	5	9.3		
Total	114.9	9			

From the above table, it can be clearly inferred that there is no significant difference among organizational hierarchy of executives in affecting job satisfaction relating to pay. Hence H₀ is accepted for organizational hierarchy and hence organizational hierarchy has significant impact on job satisfaction relating to pay

In this study, we will also find out whether job satisfaction factors such as pay, security and work environment have any impact on the life satisfaction of executives:

H₃: Job satisfaction factors are significant determinants in influencing life satisfaction of executives

H₀: There is no significant difference among job satisfaction factors in influencing life satisfaction of executives

Job satisfaction factors	Source of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	Statistical inference
Pay	Between groups	40.98	4	10.25	F = 2.5 p>0.050
	Within groups	265.2	6	44.2	
	Total	306.18	10		

Security	Between groups	142.04	6	23.7	F = 1.89 p>0.050
	Within groups	124.84	10	12.49	
	Total	266.88	16		
Work environment	Between groups	56.4	6	9.4	F = 1.84 p>0.050
	Within groups	56.1	11	5.1	
	Total	112.5	17		

From the above table, it is found that there is no significant difference in pay, security and work environment of tea garden executives' in determining life satisfaction. Hence H₀ is accepted for all the above factors and hence all the above job satisfaction factors have significant impact in determining the life satisfaction of executives.

The relationship or the impact of job satisfaction on life satisfaction will be studied by using 'correlation technique'.

Following values have been assigned to Likert's 5 point scale

Scale of job satisfaction: Very Dissat (-2) Dissat (-1) N (0) Sat (1) Very sat (2)

Scale of life satisfaction: Very Dissat (-2) Dissat (-1) N (0) Sat (1) Very sat (2)

The following data relates to job and life satisfaction of executives belonging to different age groups

Age group	Job satisfaction(X)	Life satisfaction(Y)
20-30	-22	72
31-40	-15	353
41-50	40	379
Above 50	54	684

By calculating the correlation coefficient from the above data, it comes to (r= 0.83)

The positive correlation coefficient evaluated above indicates a high degree of association between job satisfaction and life satisfaction for executives belonging to different age groups i.e. higher the job satisfaction, higher would be the life satisfaction. It shows that both move in the same direction.

The following data relates to job and life satisfaction of executives belonging to different organizational levels

Organizational level	Job satisfaction(X)	Life satisfaction(Y)
Lower level	-16	370
Middle level	23	572
Senior level	55	1176

By calculating the correlation coefficient from the above data, it comes to ($r = 0.94$)

The positive correlation coefficient evaluated above indicates a high degree of association between job satisfaction and life satisfaction for executives belonging to different organizational levels i.e. higher the job satisfaction, higher would be the life satisfaction. It shows that both move in the same direction.

Conclusion :

The study concluded with the findings that with the 9 broad divisions of job satisfaction that was taken in the study, percentage of people in satisfaction zone is highest with respect to security and is closely followed by pay and promotion. The relative importance of job satisfaction factors as perceived by the tea garden executives ranked pay as the number one factor followed by security, work, environment, coworkers, supervision, promotion, benefits, recognition and authority. The study also revealed that there is no significant difference among age groups of executives in affecting job satisfaction relating to pay.

The organizational level of hierarchy also do not determine any significant impact on job satisfaction relating to pay. The study also revealed that there is no significant difference in pay, security and work environment of tea executive's in determining life satisfaction. The study also revealed that studying the correlation between all the variables, it indicates a high degree of association between job satisfaction and life satisfaction belonging to different age groups, i.e., higher the job satisfaction, higher is the life satisfaction. The study also states a positive correlation between job satisfaction and life satisfaction for executives belonging to different organizational levels; i.e. higher the job satisfaction, higher would be the life satisfaction.

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Innovations in Managing Work Stress-A Study among Faculty of Management Studies in TamilNadu

Submitted by

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ABSTRACT

Stress is an inseparable part of human life. It occurs when we depart away from the point of homeostasis or equilibrium. It is a mental imbalance resulting from the dominance of sympathetic activities and suppression of parasympathetic activities. The healthy and non stress state can be attained by maintaining a dynamic balance between sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system. The science of yoga is of paramount relevance to attain this neurological balance. The most powerful source of stress is our own mind and yoga helps to make our mind steady and stable. In the present research work an attempt has been made to explain the physiology of stress, level of stress and its implications. To carry out this study a sample of 150 respondents has been collected. On the basis of the opinion of 50 yoga experts, a yoga based stress management model has been developed. Finally it is concluded that the mitigation of stress is a serious challenge to modern world and it can be effectively managed through the science of yoga. Yoga is only a scientific and holistic approach for the management of stress to enhance efficiency, effectiveness and productivity in present complex global scenario.

Keywords:- Stress, Yoga.

INTRODUCTION

Today we are living in the age of industrialization ,urbanization and globalization in which the revolution in the area of information and technology made our life smooth and offer us ample opportunities on the one side and overloaded us with pressure, anxiety, conflict, depression and stress on the other side. There is a historical occupational shift of masses from agrarian economy to industrial economy. This occupational shift has brought new kinds of opportunities and threats in which each individual has to make adjustments and readjustments to lead happy, smooth and peaceful life. Many studies have proved that stress improves performance initially but beyond certain point it becomes distracting and affect efficiency, effectiveness and performance. While this relationship holds true under certain conditions, evidences of researches suggest that even prolonged or repeated exposure to mild level of stress may exert adverse and harmful impact on performance and health. The individuals who are employed in any organization or institution have to suffer from occupational stress in addition to other social and environmental stress. Under these complex circumstances the management of stress is prerequisites to enhance efficiency and performance to survive in this globalised era of cut throat competition. Every era of human being has been characterized by some debilitating diseases. It was a time when plague, small pox, polio, tuberculosis etc. has been the dominating diseases, which have adversely affected the well being of humanity. In the modern age, we too have the most dreadful socio-medical disease like stress, which is spreading like wild fire across the world. Stress in itself is always harmful and no one has ever been benefitted from it. It is a black plague, which is not easy to eliminate. The people of early times too suffer from the problem of stress but its intensity, duration, complexity, universality, and vulnerability was less as compared to modern urban, industrial and global society.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Human being is a power house of infinite potential. One can do wonder if this vast reservoir of potential is regulated and controlled in a systematic and disciplined ways. Yoga is scientific and holistic approach which is useful in the channelisation of energy. M.C. Dean (1998)¹, nasal breathing is the best means of warming and humidifying inhaled air in the preparation for the lungs. It also plays an important role in controlling brain temperature and may have important implications for the functioning of brain. There is substantial evidence that slow diaphragmatic breathing reduces adverse psychophysical effects of chronic stress and reduces reactivity in stressful situation. Sharma B.R.(1998)² in his research paper "yoga and global peace", made an attempt to establish relation between yoga and global peace. He has divided his study into two parts; first part deals with understanding the root cause of inner unrest, disharmony, discontentment and disturbances and the second part deals with the contribution of various yogic methods towards the removal of inner disturbances and attainment of peace. The author firmly believes that the problem of global unrest and discontentment cannot be solved by science only, to overcome this inner unrest the yoga of Patangali offers a systematic approach to understand inner disturbances like anxieties, tensions, fickleness of mind, hatred, passion, greed, anger depression etc. He has suggested that we have to reformulate our education system and along with scientific external education we should also impart internal subject oriented education. Udupa, K.N.(2000)³ in his book "Stress and its management by yoga" concluded that stress is the main cause behind various diseases and the yoga is a holistic approach which can be of immense help for the prevention and control of all diseases. Agarwal, Rita (2001)⁴, in her book "Stress in life and at work" made a comprehensive attempt to explain the several complex issues concerning stress. The book has been divided into three sections. Section one produce details of certain historical and theoretical facts, nature of stress, study of stress, concept, models of stress, source of stress, consequences of stress and physiology of stress. Section two is devoted to stress at work place, dynamics of work stress and man and woman and dual career. Section three focuses on the all important area of coping with stress. Finally, it is concluded that the most powerful contribution is the presentation of an integrated approach on stress, which is highly relevant in the age of globalization. Phil Nuernberger (2003)⁵ in his book entitled, Freedom from Stress- A Holistic Approach has divided his study into two parts i.e. Stress and Freedom from Stress. In the first part, author explained that the demon of stress born from within self. To elaborate the concept of stress, he scientifically explained how the disturbance in sympathetic and para sympathetic nervous system affect the level of stress. He further explained the phenomenon of mind and stress and relationship between our habits and prolonged stress. In the second part of book the author suggested that diet, exercises, pranayama, meditation play a significant role in the management of stress. Khare, K.C.(2003)⁶ in his research paper, "Role of yoga in management of stress induced geriatric problem" made an attempt to highlights various psycho-physiological mechanism of stress-induced disorders in Geriatric patients and suggests some non pharmacological remedies. The author, as a medical practitioner reveals that along with existing medical care for the patients suffering from geriatric disorders proper diet, exercise and a systematic yogic management system has an imminent contribution for prevention and treatment. The Maqbool Shahina and Khan Tabassum (2004)⁷ in their research paper "A study of job strain among female teachers" made as attempt to reveal the job strain among the teachers of college, senior secondary school and schools teachers. Findings of the study reveals that all teachers perceive the same level of job strain and all have same work load of same subjects. It is apparent that many teachers of college as well as secondary schools have difficulty in combining the demands of the both home and carrier. The job stress as experienced

by them must be minimized through the stress management techniques. The finding of study by Dr. Mathews and Sr. Alice(2005)⁸ reveals that stress is quite a personal matter and the perception of the situation enables one to cope with it effectively. The mental health of the teacher is a significant aspect in molding the personalities of the future generation. Therefore, regular practice of meditation and yoga by teachers, students and parents will be of much significant in this direction⁸. Shameem Akhtar (2006)⁹ concluded that stress changes the brain anatomy which eventually causes difficulties with concentration in many. Pandey, Madhu(2007)¹⁰ in her research paper "stress motivation force of power for female," reveals that "crises and stress in life" motivate woman to take up adverse situations in their stride and prepare them to act in a brave and powerful manner. The better-educated woman considers stress in life as a significantly important source of power in comparison to their counterparts. The latest scientific researches (2008)¹¹ have proved that when a normal individual interacts with the outside world through senses, he is gripped by the negative emotions like worries, angers, anxieties, fears, stresses etc. In this situation, the frequency of our brain waves ranges between 13 Hz to 30 Hz. Whereas, if same person achieves the relaxed, calm and tranquil state of conscious mind through the various yogic practices (meditation) then the frequency of brain waves in the same situation as mentioned above will dramatically reduced to 7 Hz. to 13 Hz.

TOI(2008)¹², The problem of stress can be analyzed from the recent study that globally, one million people commit suicide every year, mortality rate of 16 per 100000 or one death in every 40 seconds. Kauts and Sharma (2008)¹³ concluded that chronic exposure to stress has profound impact on our immune system which eventually has a adverse effect on performance. In addition to its physical impact it has psychological impact also. To cope with stress, yoga is the only effective scientific and holistic approach that helps to overcome negative thoughts and helps us to develop a positive attitude for sustainable shift.

NEED AND SCOPE OF THE STUDY

It has been observed from the above mentioned review of literature that many studies have been conducted on stress and its management by various techniques of yoga. But till date no specific study have been conducted on management of stress through yogi techniques of Patangali astang yoga in relation to teachers of Management Studies of Tamil Nadu. This research gap required to be filled with further research. Hence, the present study on stress management. The emphasis has been put on Patanjali Astang Yoga as stress tool of stress management intervention strategy. The scope of the study has been restricted to the teachers of Management Faculty of Tamilnadu. Though the entire population under study is scattered all over Tamil Nadu, yet it is difficult to use the census method to undertake this study. Therefore sampling methods has been adopted. In this study 10 per cent of the population has taken which consists of both teachers from Govt. Colleges and Self Financing Colleges of TamilNadu. There are many schools of thought on the yogic activities which may help the individual to control the perturbed mind. But for the purpose of study undertaken focus is only on Sage Patanjali's Astang yoga.

Objectives and Research Methodology

The present research work is undertaken to achieve the following objectives:-

- 1) To study the level of stress among respondents.
- 2) To analyze the implications of stress.
- 3) To devise a yoga based model for the management of stress.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is based upon the primary data . A questionnaire was prepared for the collection of data. The study has been divided into two parts. In the first part a sample of 150 teachers was chosen which consists of 92 male teachers and 58 female teachers. In the second part a sample of 50 experts of concerned field has been collected to study the coping techniques for managing stress through yogic activities. For the collection of primary data the multi stage random sampling, cluster sampling, quota sampling and convenience sampling methods were used. The data collected has been placed in the tabular form. Finally, various statistical tools like χ^2 , SD, skewness, kurtosis, coefficient of contingency, chi square and P value have been applied to evaluate and interpret the data. In addition to above mentioned sources, to pursue the present study, the data has been collected from the various books, magazines, journals, newspapers, various websites of internet. To test the reliability of the questionnaire Delphi method was used.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

From the present study, it is revealed that majority of the respondents of all age groups are either under medium or high or very high level of stress. Whereas very few respondents are under low or very low level of stress. The level of stress is increasing with the increase in the age. The value of contingency coefficient support the conclusion that there is a significant relationship between age and level of stress

YOGA-A STRESS BUSTER

With the help of analysis of experts' opinion the following model based on Patanjali Raja Yoga has been developed for the management of stress. The Raja Yoga consists of scientifically and systematically developed eight steps i.e. yama, niyama, asana, pranayama, pratyahara, dharna, dhayana and samadhi. This model is helpful in the attainment of sound health and calm, stable and sound mind. The following model of Raja Yoga is highly fruitful in the management of stress and development of right attitude for sustainable shift. (Astang yoga Model for stress management)

MANAGEMENT OF STRESS

Stress Management strategies may be categorized into two parts i.e. individual strategies and organizational strategies. In the present research work emphasis has been put on individual strategies specifically on Patanjali Astang Yoga. The opinion of experts have been collected in this regard and later on has been analyzed with the help of various statistically tools and expressed in Table 7. The opinion of experts is discussed in three sub parts. First part deal with ten social and personal commitment envisaged in Yama and Niyama. Though for the effective stress management, the observances of all commitments are essential yet in the present research work highest weightage have been assigned to truthfulness and contentment.

The second part of discussion i.e. regarding Asanas, Pranayama and Pratyahara is also effective in the process of stress management. The experts were of the opinion that after the proper conditioning of mind and body through these five steps of Astang yoga the next three steps such as Dharna, Dhayana and Samadhi help the individual to calm, cool stable and tranquilize his mental state. From the present research work it is observed that maximum weightage has been assigned to Dhayana (meditation) by the experts along with Dharna and Samadhi. Therefore, the entire analysis suggests us that Patanjali Astang yoga is the best effective and scientific tool for the management of stress.

YAMA

Yama represents moral conduct. These are universal rules for social behaviour. The adherence to these Yama is compulsory and obligatory under all circumstances. The five Yama or abstinence are non-violence, truthfulness, non-stealing incontinence and non-possessiveness.

NIYAMA

Niyama can be interpreted as "spiritual observances" and it represents individual's will power to adhere to these spiritual prescriptions. The regular practice of Niyama develops seeker's personality for the achievement of higher order. These five Niyama are purity of body and mind, contentment, self discipline, self study and surrender to ultimate reality. These are ethical ideal conduct, which are conducive to one's welfare and well-being.

ASANAS

It means position or postures that are essential for Pranayama, and Dhayana. For efficient yoga practice it is essential to have a, stable, comfortable and steady position while training the mind so that the mind is free from bodily interference, which normally force one to move or change position. There are two kinds of Asanas. First type of Asanas i.e. Asanas for physical well-being are practiced to make body prefect and free from diseases. These Asanas control specific muscles, nerves and have a great therapeutre value. The second form of Asana is meditative posture: such as padamasan, siddhasan, sukhasan suitable for Pranayama and Dhayana, ensuring that the head, neck and trunk are erect and in a straight line. These postures help to make body still and motionless without strain and tension.

PRANAYAMA

The doctrine of Pranayama is the most wonderful and brilliant discovery of the east. The word Pranayama consists of two words 'prana' and 'Yama', former means energy or life force where as latter means 'control and regulation of that energy'. Since there is a close connection between the flow of respiration and the dynamics of the mind, which help in maintaining some mental balance and enhancing its clarity and capacity for observations. This life force is the link between matter and spirit. Generally, there no qualitative difference between man and universe, the common factor between both of them is prana. Prana is the vital energy which sustains the body and mind. The grossest manifestation of this vital energy is the breath, so the

Pranayama is also called the science of breathing.

PRATYAHARA

Pratyahara means 'withdrawal of consciousness" from the senses. It is purely first step in the system of yoga, which is aiming at preparing the mind for the mental evenness and inner vision, that is essential prerequisites for the effective stress management. Mind is slave of senses and with the regular practice of pratyahara the slavery of senses can be managed effectively.

DHARNA

The first five steps are the preliminaries of yoga, the next three steps consists of dharna, dhayna and Samadhi is yoga proper. The process of yama, niyam, asanas, pranayama and pratyahara wash off all the impurities of body and mind and help in the channelisation of the dissipated energies to enter in the state of dharna.

Dharna means concentration and its aim is to bring one pointedness (ekagrata) of mind.

DHAYANA

Dhayana means meditation. The science of meditation was systematically developed in ancient India during upanishada period. It was latter elaborated in detailed by Sage Patanjali and the technique spread far and wide.

SMADHI

Prolonged and intense meditation leads to the last step of Raja yoga i.e. the super-conscious state or unification with universal consciousness. In this state man because one with the divine and transcends all imperfections and limitations. The state of ecstatic realization is also known as the "fourth state" of sleepless sleep (turiya) which transcends the three normal state of waking, dreaming, and dreamless sleep.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

It can be concluded from the present research work that there is positive and significant relationship between demographic variables and level of stress. Majority of the respondents suffer from medium level of stress, some suffer from high or very high level of stress whereas very few experience low and very low level of stress. But, till date the various studies confirm that even chronic mild level of stress interfere with efficiency and performance. Stress has physiological, emotional, behavioral, cognitive and social implications, which eventually adversely affect the efficiency, effectiveness, performance and immune system on the one side and relationship with family, friends, colleagues, relatives and neighbours on the other side.

Stress has an overall impact on human being, which is a motivating factor in short run, whereas, the chronic stress in long run proved as a demoralizing factor. Hence, it should be managed timely with suitable scientific techniques. Stress and Yoga have the same subject

matter i.e. the mind, former disturb the mind and later make the mind calm, stable and composed. Stress occurs due to activation of sympathetic nervous system whereas the perturbation can be controlled and regulated with the activation of parasympathic nervous

system for which yoga is an effective instrument. The regular practice of yoga will be helpful in the development of mental awareness and equanimity. It is further observed from the analysis

of expert's opinion that yoga is scientific and effective tool in the management of stress. The model which has been developed in the present study is not only fruitful to the teachers but also of paramount utility to all human resource in each organization whether public or private or social. Now time has come that our policy makers in Government organization and in corporate world should understand relevance of yoga and spirituality not only in the management of stress but also in the development of disciplined and responsible human resource.

LIMITATIONS AND SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

It is essential to accept certain inherent limitations in the present research work. Most of the part of the study undertaken is based upon primary data. Therefore the limitations of primary data may affect the results. Though, the study is confined to teachers in higher education yet it can be generalized to other sections of society. This generalization encompasses the scope for further research emphasis in the research work have been put on Patanjali Astang yoga as stress management techniques, whereas this also pave the way for the further research in other organizations. This research will especially be fruitful for the employees of corporate world, who are under the tremendous pressure of work due to increasing competition and demand. Hence, it is proved that yoga is a sustainable and permanent therapy for the management of stress.

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“Organizational Politics Bane or Boon ????”

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Abstract

The political nature of work environments has been discussed for quite some time; however, surprisingly little is known about the personal and situational factors that influence employees' perceptions of organizational politics. In this study, portions of a model of organizational politics perceptions proposed by Ferris, Russ, and Fandt (1989) were tested in two studies using samples reflecting considerable variability on jobs, age, sex, and education, as well as hierarchical level, across four different organizations. In Study 1, regression analyses, used to empirically examine a proposed model of organizational politics perceptions, demonstrated that feedback, job autonomy, skill variety, and opportunity for promotion contributed significantly to the explanation of variance in perceptions of organizational politics, after controlling for variance due to organization. In Study 2, a new expanded measure of organizational politics perceptions was used to provide a more refined analysis of the antecedents and consequences of politics perceptions. Directions for theoretical and empirical research on organizational politics are discussed in light of the present results.

KEY WORDS: OP, employees' perceptions, , regression analyses

Introduction

There is only one common thread, which stitches all types of organizations together. Whether it is a rustic school, a MNC with global reach or a teaching institute or a hospital, you will find lecturers trying to outdo the Principal, the manager trying to become the CEO, the surgeon trying to become the Director all at the cost of his or her peers. In all fairness, it can be said that no level in the organization is exempt from this phenomenon. The medium can create its own political agenda.

Why is playing politics in organizations so rampant and has such an overarching reach? There are perhaps two reasons for this. The first is of course the desire to move ahead whatever the cost. The second is the thrill of playing the game for its own sake. What do these statements imply? The first is of course self-evident.

The unfortunate part is that it is the truly good and capable people who get hit by the political players – the old days are long gone when an employee's good work could speak for itself; as someone said, if you expect that to happen, please also remember that it will speak in a very low voice.

This paper will now look at three randomly selected expositions on organizational politics to reinforce the point we are now making, and follow it up with two typical employee categorizations which are available to anyone looking for inputs in this area. Comments on the expositions are given in italics at the end of the section. It is emphasized that this paper is in way trying to put down or debunk the work put in by the theoreticians – the basic approach and stand taken in this paper is that theories of organizational politics are not of much help to the manager who is coping with the realities of day-to-day organizational politics. Regardless of the degree to which employees may be committed to the organization's objectives, there can be little doubt that, at least occasionally, personal interests will be incongruent with those of the organization.

Organizational politics arises when people think differently and want to act differently. In most organizational politicking occurs in the internal-vertical- legitimate realm. An example would be individuals trying to achieve personal gain by giving "voice" to their demands/needs. This could be done by complaining to supervisors, bypassing the chain of command, or obstructionism (ignoring requests or missing deadlines). In less autocratic organizations, political activity can be expected to occur most frequently in the internal-lateral-legitimate cell. This activity includes coalition formation, the exchange of favors, and reprisals.

The paper will now look at two types of employee classifications, the first one based on Transactional Analysis (TA), and the other classification typifying a variety, which is popular among theoreticians.

Transaction Analysis Related

This is a very popular classification and the topic of many workshops and executive development programs and divides employees into three categories based on the behaviors they exhibit. These are:

Parent

There are two forms of Parent we can play. The Nurturing Parent is caring and concerned and often may appear as a mother-figure (though men can play it too). They seek to keep the Child safe and offer unconditional love, calming them when they are troubled.

The Controlling (or Critical) Parent, on the other hand, tries to make the Child do as the parent wants them to do, perhaps transferring values or beliefs or helping the Child to understand and live in society. They may also have negative intent, using the Child as a whipping boy or worse.

Adult

The Adult in us is the 'grown up' rational person who talks reasonably and assertively, neither trying to control nor reacting. The Adult is comfortable with themselves and is, for many of us, our 'ideal self'.

Child

There are two types of Child which people play. The Natural Child is largely un-self-aware and is characterized by the non-speech noises they make (yahoo, etc.). They like playing and are open and vulnerable. The cutely named Little Professor is the curious and exploring Child who is always trying out new stuff (often much to their Controlling Parent's annoyance). Together with the Natural Child they make up the Free Child. The Adaptive Child reacts to the world around them, either changing themselves to fit in or rebelling against the forces they feel. The foregoing is a very condensed version of TA types. As can be seen, it definitely has tremendous value but is not what we were looking for. The paper will now examine a typical academic classification of employee types, popular with theoreticians.

Objective of study

1. To study the dysfunctional and functional politics of organization.
2. To study the dynamic behavior of new recruits in the organization.
3. To design strategies to cope with organizational politics.

Research Methodology

The hypothesis being tested was ' An understanding of employee types, if given at the B School level, will assist the new employee in his/ her career progression'. It was decided to see the 'levels' of understanding, which B School students possessed by the time they left their college, in terms of knowing the different types of people they will be working with soon in an organization. Draft questionnaires were prepared which had the express purpose of checking if new entrants to an organization (i.e. B School students on the verge of passing out):

Had any idea as to what to expect in terms of the types of employees they would interact with in the organization, and Were given in puts in B Schools from which they had passed out as to the practical aspects

of managing different types of employees when they transitioned to the corporate world.

These were pilot tested across 10 students and then refined to take into account some of the inputs, which came from the students. For example, the question, 'How would you react to an employee who professed willingness to help you tackle a time bound assignment, but later backed out?' was removed as it was felt that the question could not be fully understood in all its nuances by those who had no work experience. Again, the question, 'What type of employee would you naturally form a bond in the initial stages in a company?' was also removed, mostly for the same reason.

Sample

The final sample (judgment sample) consisted of 40 students, of whom only four had prior work experience, ranging from one to two years, in banking institutions and manufacturing companies. Ages varied from 24 years to 26 years. Ten questionnaires were dropped out of the sample as it was felt that the questions were not properly understood.

Analysis

What came out clearly was that the majority of the students did not have any idea on what to expect in terms of employee types when they joined a company. On a scale of 1 to 5 (where 1 stood for 'Have no idea' and 5 stood for 'Complete knowledge of what to expect'), 95% had indicated 1 or 2 as their choice.

Again, the majority (85%) of the respondents indicated that they did not possess the skills on how to tackle employees who were deliberately trying to mislead them. In fact, 74% indicated that they would not realize if they were being misled or not. An analysis of the coefficient of correlation showed the value of 0.44, which meant there was a significant correlation between a prior knowledge of employee types and career progression.

The same lack of the skills required to get along without major problems (especially in the initial stages) in an organization was evident in the response to the question, which asked the whether they would be able to distinguish between the genuine helpers and those who were trying to jeopardize their early career progression. What was evident was that the respondents possessed only a rudimentary idea of what to expect in terms of understanding their colleagues and superiors. These were evidently skills, which are not considered important to impart as part of their B School training. It was felt that this analysis was revealing insofar as the new recruits were evidently being 'thrown to the wolves' without the skills on how to survive, especially in a politically driven company.

Political 'Types'

In order to understand Organizational politics much better, the author has resorted to the dynamic characters of English literature on the basis of which new entrants can understand the political surrounding which includes different types of People (personalities) whose character are reflected and the strategies to cope with politics are as follows :-

1 Sherlock Holmes

Characteristics - Very rare to find in a company. The individual brings reasoning and common sense to the work place. May be taciturn and not easily approachable at all times. Will be impatient with those not intellectually up to the mark. However, there will not be any vindictiveness in the person and will have the potential to help and guide those in need. The person will have few friends but will be enormously respected in the system. Will not be reliant on anyone or anything in the system but will go his or her own route, which will almost in all cases be the right one. Can be a potential goldmine for finding out of the box solutions but

care has to be given to acknowledge the contributions with respect and due credit. Will be a repository of knowledge, which will be shared willingly. Opinionated but not in an offensive manner. Workplace will be a mess but will be able to find what is required without any problem. Fixed hours will be anathema and will work at a pace, which suits him or her. Has the potential to rise very high in the structure at a fast clip.

Recommendation - Latch yourself to this person's star and you will go places within the organization.

2 Prof Moriarty

Characteristics - The Napoleon of crime will, in the context of the organization, be the Napoleon of office politicking. The person will be the collector of information, which is the most precious commodity for this person, through various sources, and use it for someone's downfall at the appropriate time. Highly intelligent and negatively motivated, the sole purpose of this person's existence is the promotion (literally) of self. Will reward the coterie, which is invaluable to the success of this type of individual. A meticulous planner with the sole and ultimate objective of feathering his or her nest. Can be seen at all levels in the hierarchy and a few even make it to the top. Will tend to distance from the effects of his or her activities and will willingly let someone else take the blame. Do not try to engage in a battle of wits unless you want an assured exit from the company. Will keep long hours and expect the team to follow the same pattern because imitation will be taken as a virtue. Will tend to react emotionally to issues/ problems.

Recommendation - To be avoided at all costs, but if circumstances bring you in close contact with this type of person, use all your skills to protect yourself for the time being and get a transfer at the first opportunity and never mind the place to which where you are transferred.

3 Iago

Characteristics - This is a junior version of the Professor Moriarty type and tends to be more an executor of plans given by his superior than a creator of plans to do down employees. Most comfortable when casting innuendos and aspersions with regard to hapless victims. A time server with 'loyalty' only to his boss. Can be seen at all levels in the organization and, if sufficiently intelligent, will be a Moriarty in the fullness of time and even move up the organization. It will be difficult to gauge this person's actual stand on an issue as his or her perspective will keep changing depending on the consensus or what the boss is saying. Do not let your real feelings about anyone show in front of this character type as what you say will be promptly reported to the appropriate quarters and will boomerang on you fairly quickly. Most comfortable when putting down people and can be seen in the boss's residence at every opportunity. A timeserver par excellence with moving up the organization the only agenda in his or her immediate horizon.

Recommendation - Avoid whenever possible, but if you have to work with an Iago, keep your guard up to the fullest extent

4 Dr Watson

Characteristics - A thoroughly sincere and nice person, the Watsons of this world are a rare breed and not much seen in a company, especially one that is aggressive in its approach. This is because they would have been forced to leave reasonably early in their careers by more ambitious types. Will not carry tales or try and put down people and will be very loyal to the boss. This person is definitely intelligent, but what is lacking in them is plain and simple street smartness. Will not be able to see behind what is apparently being said and will land themselves in trouble by being too trusting and valuing the spoken word. A Watson will require a strong boss to carry him in the organization and will be at a loss with a boss who is a Moriarty or an Iago. Can be relied on to be a workhorse in the organization and will be a team player to the extreme. This person will speak his or her mind when under pressure and never mind the consequences.

Recommendation - Befriend the Watson and try and help them in their careers in the company. But avoid being a Watson if you want to move up the ladder. Consciously change your approach and mind set if you feel

you are one. Mid management is about the highest they can reach and that too with difficulty.

5 Bertie Wooster

Characteristics- Thoroughly amiable and friendly, the Woosters in a company will be liked by almost everyone. The problem is that mere liking will not carry a person far as it has to be coupled with intelligence and drive, which are factors, which Woosters do not possess in abundance. They can be termed as a disaster just waiting to happen and will land themselves wittingly or otherwise in one organizational crisis after another. Their good fortune may carry them for a while, but they require a strong and understanding boss even to manage day-to-day affairs, and such bosses are rarely seen. Woosters generally tend to fade away soon and old colleagues may miss them for a while but they are more remembered for the classic messes they created which will be told and retold.

Recommendation- If you are the sympathetic type, by all means try and help the Wooster but do not let people make an association between you and the Wooster as some of the negative traits in the latter may unfairly be perceived in you also.

6 Hamlet

Characteristics – This person will be very articulate and scholarly and will be an excellent sounding board for new ideas, which the company may wish to try out. He or she will do well in the strategic planning division, as they will have an enormous amount of data and wide ranging information on which they can base their conclusions. The problem will be that they will not work to a time schedule and will let extraneous matters intrude on their thought processes and delay the primary work on which they should focus. They are prone to having intense likes and dislikes (both of people and activities), and this will again come in the way of their work. Once they get going however, they are capable of churning out output of a high level; they will have to be carefully handled as otherwise they may start sulking and further slow down their time schedules. Prone to over analysis of a given matter and this is a tendency which will have to be carefully monitored and corrected by the boss.

Recommendation - The Hamlets of this world are basically extremely good people and will not harm anyone in the organization. If you have one as a subordinate, try and not to antagonize the person; all efforts should be made to bring out the best in him or her and to endure they are of use to you. A Hamlet as a boss on the other hand, is a very difficult proposition, and care will have to be taken to see that their negative traits are not seen by others as your own inadequacy especially when a time bound decision is required from your section.

7 Jeeves

Characteristics - This is a very rare individual in an organization. They are capable of rising to the top through sheer brainpower and will not be dependent on any kind of support system within or outside the organization. The closest they have as a parallel in the organization is the Sherlock Holmes, but without the latter's intellectual arrogance. In that sense, they will be more approachable especially when there is a crisis to be solved. The Jeeveses of this world are at their best when giving advice or solving knotty problems and are most satisfied when they get an opportunity to do this. They will also be superb mentors and have the potential to develop subordinates. They are essentially good people and will never think of harming anyone in the company in order to move up. They may not have many close friends within the system but this does not mean they are unsociable. They will not display the Holmes's extremes of activity but will proceed at a seemingly deceptively slow pace and let the end results speak for itself.

Recommendation – In line with what we said about his closest counterpart in the organization, if you come across a Jeeves, latch your wagon to him or her and find yourself going places. Whether you prefer working with a Holmes or a Jeeves will depend entirely on your own mental make up.

Conclusions

So where does all this leave us? Are organizational politics helpful and beneficial? Or are they simply something that cannot be ignored? Sometimes, it is felt that being good at organizational politics is a form of literacy, like computer literacy: not much good in and of itself, but just try ignoring it. We think one has to acknowledge that the political scene is there, and know how to work it to some degree. Even more important, one has to admit that it's fascinating, intriguing, and, if it hasn't turned on you, lots of fun. People are interesting; power is exciting. And both can turn against you and make you very, very unhappy.

One should be skeptical of those who get right into the politics, and equally skeptical of those who take the high moral road and deny any interest in or knowledge of the games that are taking place around them. The middle road is the best one: to be aware of politics and power as an inescapable fact of the environment and a source of fascination, but also to keep one's perspective, and to keep better, more important objectives at the center of one's agenda.

For, in the ultimate analysis, it is perhaps clear that by that by focusing strongly on your career objectives, keeping yourself up-to-date with knowledge and being a strong and fair executive, are the important factors, which have long lasting value. These are factors which will stand the test of time and be facets of your make up which the political player will find hard to hit against. And finally, when you leave a company, you should ensure that people are not breathing a collective and heart felt sigh of relief; there should be genuine regret that you have left and that the organization has lost a valuable employee.

Is that not accolading enough for anyone?

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HR services related to Cultural Sensitivity

Submitted by

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ABSTRACT

With the shift from national to international and global business, new challenges have emerged for managers engaged in transactional business activities. The complexity of the tasks involved in international marketing requires an approach that demonstrates cultural sensitivity. As a consequence, the question arises as to whether international marketing managers are well prepared to deal effectively with culturally overlapping situations.

While it is widely accepted that culture is substantially affecting international marketing decisions, pragmatic concepts of how to achieve cultural sensitivity in international marketing are lacking. This paper aims to narrow this gap. The importance of cultural sensitivity in international marketing is highlighted, training requirements are identified, and a recently introduced concept of culture is assessed for its usefulness and applicability in an international marketing context.

Author Keywords: Cultural standards; International management training; Cultural sensitivity.

Introduction

In today's multicultural workplace, it is vital that employers actively promote tolerance and acceptance of cultural and religious differences. Not only does tolerance maintain productivity and reduce turnover, it can also help companies avoid discrimination lawsuits. Cultural diversity can take many forms. Ethnicity, language and religion are a few prominent examples. It is a paradox that employers are supposed to be blind to cultural differences but must account for them in order to promote harmony in the workplace. The trick is to minimize differences between employees while simultaneously respecting their diverse backgrounds and lifestyles.

Generally, the differences between people are not as significant as the things they have in common. Open communication about cultural differences can defuse any tension by creating an atmosphere of understanding. Cultural differences can prompt curiosity, which can open the channels of communication.

If employees are focused on a common goal, that of their company, then they will have less time or reason to dwell on differences between themselves and their colleagues. Building a strong sense of mission and teamwork is one of the best ways to minimize

Cultural differences.

However, accommodating cultural differences can be a difficult balancing act. For instance, if the company gives one group of employees time off for religious holidays, it may provoke resentment among members of other groups. Sometimes, cultural traditions are in direct conflict with business priorities. For example, male members of the Sikh community are required by their religion to carry ceremonial daggers. This tradition can conflict with company policies about weapons in the workplace.

Dietary requirements of different cultures and religions are often easily accommodated. Kosher and halal meals can be ordered for company functions or stocked in flash-frozen form in the company cafeteria.

If a significant portion of the work force speaks a language other than English, it may be advisable to print memos, company newsletters and other communications in bilingual editions.

Celebrating Diversity

People appreciate recognition, including acknowledgment of their cultural heritages. Multicultural holidays can be recognized in company newsletters and after-work events. The company does not have to make a big production to show respect for such holidays; just a mention of these special occasions will suffice.

Some companies, particularly those who operate on an international scale, offer foreign-language courses and cultural-sensitivity training classes.

Intergenerational Differences

While some workers hail from different cultures, some of the youngest members of the work force may seem to be from a different planet. This younger generation may present the greatest difference of all: the generational difference.

Older workers may often be puzzled and frustrated by what they perceive as younger employees' lack of work ethic and selfishness. This can create a great deal of friction in the workplace. One way to defuse this type of situation is to partner younger and older workers in mentorship relationships.

Above all, cultural and religious sensitivity is based on respect for individuals. The best way for a company to exercise cultural sensitivity is to pay honest attention to each member of the work force, ask questions, and be prepared to accept and accommodate differences. This openness and tolerance must begin at the very top of the organization, and it should be visible to each and every employee.

Cultural sensitivity

Cultural sensitivity means being aware that cultural differences and similarities exist and have an effect on values, learning and behavior.

Works effectively with people from all backgrounds.

Avoids stereotypical responses by examining own behavior. Does not discriminate against any individual or group. Demonstrates respect for and

Understanding of diverse points of view in daily work and decision-making. Knows how and when to adapt personal behavior to manage or prevent conflict.

Components of Cultural sensitivity

Valuing and recognizing the importance of one's own culture Valuing diversity.

Realizing that cultural diversity will affect an individual's communication and participation in education in various ways.

A willingness to learn about the traditions characteristics of other cultures.

Interacting and communicating in cultural sensitive ways

Although Para educators may have contact with families, remember that primary communication should be the responsibility of the student's teacher and special educator.

Relationships with families are strengthened when you speak about children (and family members) in optimistic ways.

It is important for school personnel to indicate a willingness to listen to the child and the family. Active listening includes listening fully, without interrupting, clarifying, acknowledging, reflecting or expanding and building Effective communication is enhanced when empathy is conveyed. Empathy can be developed by consistently trying to put yourself in another's shoes. Some input on the best way to teach "sensitivity" in the workplace

The place where I work has a (not so) subtle air of discrimination and we are trying to change that. However, I'm at a bit of a loss as to what to do. I think that having some sort of workshop that both addresses some of the common issues that come up in our work environment and gets people talking about situations that make them uncomfortable would be fabulous. However, I've been told by a couple people that discussions just get people confused and it's better to have someone come in and simply state the policies on harassment to scare people into submission.

Global marketing presents a tremendous opportunity but is also a challenge. Most world trade either originates-or is purchased-in North America, Europe and the Middle East, and Japan and the Pacific Rim. To succeed in these markets, sales managers and sales teams need to understand how such factors as geography, culture, technology, and legal systems impact on business.

The subtlest of these influences is culture because we each perceive our own culture as normal and are puzzled when we meet unexpected behavior that stems from different cultural standards. By developing cross-cultural awareness we can begin to understand different perspectives, to adapt our own behavior so that we respect local cultures, to suspend judgment of what is normal or better and, using this knowledge, adapt our sales campaigns and business interactions to specific localities and situations instead of assuming that one approach will work everywhere.

Sales people need to:

Understand how culture affects behavior and business

Understand the key cultural dimensions

Raise their awareness of their personal culture

Understand how their cultural preferences can clash with others' behavior.

Identify key skills and competencies for international sales success

Be aware of the major traps and how to avoid them.

Sales management is heavily influenced by culture, and in the global business environment it is important to understand the cultural forces that shape and affect the interactions between salespeople and customers. Sensitivity to cultural differences can enhance the chances of success. If a salesperson approaches a meeting with knowledge of the customer's cultural background, then their words, actions, and body language can all be adapted to enhance the likelihood of a positive reception and the development of a long-term profitable relationship with that customer.

Global salespeople can, however, easily meet resistance from customers in different cultural. Often this is simply due to not understanding the 'dos' and 'don'ts' of interacting with different cultures. Understanding how to act in most cultures may be the difference between closing a sale and losing a customer. For example, gestures, facial expressions, the way you greet or address somebody can all have a negative effect as can not understanding how sales literature, advertising and branding are perceived.

Here are some specific mistakes to avoid in certain cultures. Of course, your hosts will probably make allowances for you as a foreigner, but if you can show that you have taken the trouble to learn and respect their standards of behavior, you will create a much more positive impression:

Arab countries. Greet people and use your right hand when eating and drinking. Do not use your left hand to hold, offer, or receive materials. Do not cross your legs when sitting or show the soles of your feet. The thumbs-up sign is rude. Do not inquire about a man's wife or female relations.

China. Never refuse to drink tea during business meetings, even if you are offered dozens of cups each day. Present materials in black and white because colors may have special meanings. Never eat or drink before your host.

France. The French normally do not meet until after 10:00 a.m. Do not offer to meet for a business breakfast. Meals are a ritual and should not be rushed.

Germany. Do not address a business associate by their first name unless you are invited to do so. Do not chew gum while talking to somebody. Don't be late as it is considered an insult.

Latin America. The clock is not taken seriously, so do not schedule more than two meetings during the day.

Japan. Do not blow your nose in public. Do not point. Do not raise business issues on the golf course unless your host initiates the conversation. The Japanese do not like to say 'no' directly, so even if they say 'yes', they may mean no'. Do not pour yourself a drink. Take special care in handling business cards that are given to you. Do not write on the card. Do not put the card in you pocket or wallet, as either of these actions will be viewed as defacing or disrespecting the business card. Examine the card carefully as a show of respect.

Mexico. Do not send red or yellow flowers as a gift; these colors are associated with evil spirits and death.

Philippines. Rather than disagree with someone, people will say 'Yes', but this can have many meanings. Criticism should never be direct, but should be offered as softly as possible.

Cultural gaffes can occur at any point in a sales campaign. Sales literature, advertising and brand names can be danger areas and can easily cause your product to fail:

Mitsubishi Motors of Japan tried marketing their popular Pajero car in the Spanish market but were baffled by their lack of success. Pajero is slang in Spanish for masturbation. Fiat found that they had to rename their Uno when selling it in Finland. Uno means garbage in Finnish.

When Toyota Motor Company released their popular MR2 sports car in France, they encountered a problem MR2 was pronounced as 'em er deux', which loosely translates to 'you little little shit'.

Pepsi Corporation's marketing slogan 'Come Alive with Pepsi' was first translated into the Chinese as 'Pepsi brings your dead ancestors back to life'. The same slogan was also translated into German as: 'Come out of the grave with Pepsi.'

FORD also learned the hard way when they introduced the Pinto car in Brazil, which was replaced by a different name when they learned that Pinto is Brazilian slang for tiny male genitals.'

Scandinavian vacuum manufacturer Electrolux used the following in an American campaign:

Nothing sucks like an Electrolux.

Using animals for product imagery is risky:

A U.S. deodorant found great success in the U.S. with their advertisement showing an octopus using the

product under each of its eight arms. When shown in Japan, however, it was a flop; the Japanese consider an octopus to have eight legs rather than eight arms.

A U.S. marketing firm found that while a deer was a sign of masculinity in the U.S., it conveyed a different image in Brazil, where deer' is slang for homosexual.

Another company erred when it chose an owl as part of its promotional efforts in India. Indians view the owl as a symbol of bad luck.

When we see the mistakes others have made we may well laugh, but we are not amused if we are the ones with egg on our faces. It is essential to research the culture before you localize your product information.

Ten Steps Toward Cultural Sensitivity

1. Take the initiative to make contact with the "international", the "outsider", the "foreigner" even if language is a problem at first.

2. Show respect for their culture and language. They may be in culture shock and grieving over the "loss" of their culture or at least the fear of losing their cultural identity. Ask, "How would I feel if I were in their shoes?"

3. Learn how to pronounce names correctly. Their name is as important to them as yours is to you. Practice saying it until you get close to how it should be pronounced.

4. Be sensitive to their feelings about their homeland. Developing nations are not as poor, backward or uneducated as North Americans tend to think.

5. When speaking English, do so slowly and clearly. Remember, raising your voice does not make English more understandable.

6. Be yourself. Show that you care about them as people and that you honestly want to help.

7. Take time to listen. If you don't understand, or you are not understood, take time to find out why. Explain or ask questions. A key question might be, "Would you help me understand?"

8. Be careful about promises. In English we express the subjunctive (possibility, probability or contingency) in a way that is sometimes misunderstood by internationals.

9. The key ingredient to developing and maintaining a long-term relationship with internationals is old-fashioned friendship built of mutual respect and a desire for understanding.

10. Don't allow cultural differences (preferences) to become the basis for criticism and judgments. Differences are neither good nor bad. What we do with them is the key.

A key to success for any organization will be the management of full operational HR service to all employees. Hence, it is imperative to manage a HR team of balanced complement with multi-cultural sensitivity as also lead and motivate the skilled team to deliver results. For this purpose a persuasive, passionate and politically astute disposition is essential. An HR must demonstrate experience at a senior level across national and international sphere to reinforce his views. He must have performed HR functions for multifaceted industries. As a strategic leader, motivated team player and conceptual thinker, he must be meticulously involved in development of HRM strategies and organizational design plan akin to current market realities and establishment of core competency strength for maintaining the business focus and future growth.

He must be endowed with strong interpersonal skills, with credibility at all levels, a pragmatic attitude with good understanding of strategic HR issues and have become a strong deliverer. He must have the ability to lead and manage the HR functions at Group Level through out India with strong Leadership qualities and Personal example coupled with excellent communications skill with a flair for human values and teamwork. In addition to that, he should be a committed achiever driven by results with high level of intellect and an outright team player. If he is confident and credible enough in advising executive and management colleagues on the broadest range of HR issues, then he would be instrumental in incorporating large scale outsourcing of facilities pertaining to utilities, maintenance, customer services and HR related functions without compromise of quality of output and services rendered.

The focus must be on maximizing operational efficiencies and creating result oriented performance through HR interventions necessary for sustaining the continued promotion of business venture by introducing structured and system driven...

Mcdonalds Cultural Sensitivity Since the mid-1980s, Indian society has undergone a dramatic shift in social values. The traditional caste-defined view of Indian life, which undervalues social and economic mobility, and the dominance of the Brahmanical culture's disdain toward commerce have been challenged by the middle class in contemporary Indian society. Getting rich and enjoying a good life has become the new mantra of social existence for the Indian middle class. With more income and more purchasing power, the status-

conscious Indian middle class now seek to buy good quality consumer products and spend more money on food and entertainment. In metropolitan cities, extensive foreign media exposure and the Internet revolution have contributed to the emergence of a new social attitude which accepts Western values and culture. The contemporary Indian society can be understood on the basis of a 70/30 dynamic. While 70% of Indians are still traditional, poor, and live in rural areas, 30% of Indians (more than 300 million people) have emerged as rich, modern, Western-exposed, English-speaking, urban dwellers. In India's metropolitan cities, the young and rich have embraced the spirit of American culture.²² America has come to be associated with success, productivity, and a good life. This growing acceptance corresponds to the big impact of the American influence on Indian business, education, and entertainment. The U.S. is India's largest trading partner, investor, and business collaborator. Top U.S. corporations like General Electric, General Motors, Ford, Citibank, Coca Cola, Pepsi, Microsoft, IBM, and Intel are entrenched in India. American universities in general, and a few in particular like Harvard, Wharton, Columbia, Princeton, and Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), are instantly recognized in India and have become the most preferred destinations for today's generation.

Sensitivity to cultural differences is generally agreed to be a highly desirable characteristic of sound practice in all human services. The terms "cultural competence," "cultural sensitivity," "cultural responsiveness," and "cultural appropriateness" are frequently seen in contemporary literatures (see Gollnick & Chinn, 2002; Lee, 2003; Shealey & Callins, 2007; Sleeter, 1999). Definitions of these terms are often not what behaviorists would consider operational. For example, Shealey and Callins (2007) state that "culturally responsive teaching refers to the extent to which educators use students' cultural contributions in transforming their lives and the lives of their families and communities by making education relevant and meaningful" (p. 195). They go on to say that demonstration of cultural sensitivity requires teachers to "learn about the cultures represented in their classrooms and translate this knowledge into instructional practice" (p. 196) and state that culturally mediated instruction is "characterized by the use of culturally mediated cognition, culturally appropriate social situations for learning, and culturally valued knowledge in curriculum content" (p. 196). As good as these ideas are, educators guided by them may be unable to identify a practice that is multicultural or culturally responsive or a practice that it is not. Teachers may also be unable to discriminate cultural sensitivity from cultural insensitivity.

Our purpose, therefore, was to seek evidence of responsiveness to behavioral interventions related to cultural identity. Thus, we reviewed behavioral literature related to three cultural markers--ethnicity, gender, and religion--to see whether we could find data supporting differences in behavioral interventions depending on cultural distinctiveness.

Some writers have suggested that behavioral interventions in education are inappropriate in or insensitive to some cultures. These writers find that the very characteristics that make behavioral interventions a practical tool for working in the scientific tradition may make them unacceptable for use with those who do not share the viewpoint of behavioral scientists. That is, they promote "culturally sensitive" practices that have little or no empirical support or urge teachers not to be "culturally insensitive" by using practices that do have considerable empirical support. For example, in his website on behavior management, McIntyre (2007) stated:

Behaviorist interventions are often inappropriate for, and sometimes even discriminatory against large numbers of culturally different youngsters with learning and behavioral disorders. Readers are asked to ponder whether behaviorism's practices, despite the empirical research demonstrating their effectiveness, should be implemented with youngsters who do not adhere to a Western European life view and orientation.

Conclusion

Behaviorists' research may be able to "prove" that behavioral change occurs, but at what cost? Is a method, despite its empirical validation, appropriate for everyone? Is it morally right to change culturally different behavior in culturally insensitive ways? One need only ask former students made to attend Bureau of Indian Affairs schools in decades past, or those youngsters who are willing to comply and love to learn, but refuse to do so in ways that they perceive to be "acting white" (identifying with a group they believe to be oppressors). While behaviorist practices may be "effective", we must

question if the means, or even the ends, are appropriate in all cases.

If data showing that effectiveness (regardless of how it is defined) is achieved with given methods, yet those methods are proscribed as culturally inappropriate, then we have no way to judge the effectiveness of interventions. Data showing better outcomes, even if desired by an individual, could be judged convincing only if the methods used to obtain them are judged culturally appropriate. Perhaps a judgment of cultural appropriateness should not trump data showing effectiveness for individuals, such that data showing better outcomes are subject to censure if the methods do not pass a test of cultural sensitivity.

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An Analysis of the Performance of
"Derivatives- Starter form of Investment" in Fostering Stock Market

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Abstract

"Derivatives are like aircraft: in the right hands, they are wonderful vehicles, but in the wrong hands, or incompetently handled they are dangerous"

As truly said, Apart from money market and capital market securities, a variety of derivatives have now become available for investment and trading and they are constituting a major part of the stock market transactions and continuously nurture Indian Stock Market. Derivatives or derivative securities are contracts which are written between two parties and whose value is derived from the value of widely held and marketable assets. Derivatives are also known as deferred payment Instruments. The exchange traded derivatives are quite liquid so indications are that derivatives have stabilizing effect and their introduction has led to decline in volatility of underlying assets. Due to the increased effects of globalization, last couple of years has seen the Indian Financial Market being increasingly exposed to global market factors and are faced by rising levels of complexity of risks. To mitigate the effect of those underlying risks, Indian markets are increasingly using highly complex hedging strategies with the help of exotic derivative instruments. The sheer explosive growth in volume of total derivative contracts outstanding validates the heightened interest of Indian markets for such products. To satiate this heightened interest for derivative instruments, banks have readily agreed to structure and offer these contracts to their corporate clients by focusing more on the returns rather than stressing on the potential down-side risks. However, banks should undertake derivative transactions, particularly with companies with a sense of responsibility and circumspection that would avoid, among other things, mis-selling. Under such circumstances, it has become imperative for Indian Financial Market to adopt and demonstrate a pro-active (but disciplined) approach towards financial risk management. The present paper evaluates the impact of introduction of derivative securities on volatility of underlying stocks and Index.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of derivatives in the last three decades can be attributed to the useful economic functions they perform and the numerous benefits they provide to the end users connected to Indian Stock Market. The values of derivatives and those of their underlying assets are closely related. Though derivatives are Off Balance Sheet Instruments, the fact is that obscure the leverage and financial might they give to the party. There are bewilderingly complex varieties of derivatives already in existence and the markets are innovating newer and newer ones continuously. The trading of first derivative security, i.e. the stock index futures commenced at the starting of the decade. The options and futures on individual stocks were introduced thereafter. Here is an attempt to test the efficiency or to check the performance of derivative securities traded in the Indian stock Market in managing market risk by comparing and examines the volatility of underlying assets and stock exchanges Index before and after the introduction of option and futures contracts. The market of derivatives took momentum very rapidly. Today the turnover in derivative segment has far exceeded the turnover in cash segment. According to SEBI bulletin, the average turnover of derivatives was more than two times of the turnover of cash segment in August, 2004. The individual stock futures accounted for fifty-seven percent of total market turnover. The derivatives contracts are used for arbitrage besides hedging and speculation. Although, arbitrage activities are helpful in eliminating mis-pricing in both the cash segment and the derivative segment of the market, but sometime they may lead abnormality in the market. Almost all the arbitrage strategies involving derivative contracts require taking simultaneous positions in the derivatives and the underlying securities. A number of studies have examined the performance before and after the introduction of derivative securities. The evidence is available for stock index options, stock options and stock index futures contracts in context of stock market all over the world.

Common derivative contract types and their share in total Derivative Turnover

Derivative contracts have several variants. The most common variants are forwards, futures, options and swap.

Forward Contracts

A forward contract is an agreement between two parties – a buyer and a seller to purchase or sell something at a later date at a price agreed upon today. Forward contracts, sometimes called forward commitments, are very common in everyone life. For example, an apartment lease is a forward commitment. By signing a one-year lease, the tenant agrees to purchase the service – use of the apartment – each month for the next twelve months at a predetermined rate. Like-wise, the landlord agrees to provide the service each month for the next twelve months at the agreed-upon rate. Now suppose that six months later the tenant finds a better apartment and decides to move out. The forward commitment remains in effect, and the only way the tenant can get out of the contract is to sublease the apartment. Because there is usually a market for subleases, the lease is even more like a futures contract than a forward contract. Any type of contractual agreement that calls for the future purchase of a good or service at a price agreed upon today and without the right of cancellation is a forward contract.

Future Contracts

A futures contract is an agreement between two parties – a buyer and a seller – to buy or sell something at a future date. The contract trades on a futures exchange and is subject to a daily settlement procedure. Future contracts evolved out of forward contracts and possess many of the same characteristics. In essence, they are like liquid forward contracts. Unlike forward contracts, however, futures contracts trade on organized exchanges, called future markets. For example, the buyer of a future contract, who has the obligation to buy the good at the later date, can sell the contract in the future market, which relieves him or her of the obligation to purchase the good. Likewise, the seller of the futures contract, who is obligated to sell the good at the later date, can buy the contract back in the future market, relieving him or her of the obligation to sell the good. Future contracts also differ from forward contracts in that they are subject to a daily settlement procedure. In the daily settlement, investors who incur losses pay them every day to investors who make profits.

Options Contracts

Options are of two types - calls and puts. Calls give the buyer the right but not the obligation to buy a given quantity of the underlying asset, at a given price on or before a given future date. Puts give the buyer the right, but not the obligation to sell a given quantity of the underlying asset at a given price on or before a given date. Options are contracts that give the owner the right, but not the obligation, to buy (in the case of a call option) or sell (in the case of a put option) an asset. The price at which the sale takes place is known as the strike price, and is specified at the time the parties enter into the option. The option contract also specifies a maturity date. In the case of a European option, the owner has the right to require the sale to take place on (but not before) the maturity date; in the case of an American option, the owner can require the sale to take place at any time up to the maturity date. If the owner of the contract exercises this right, the counterparty has the obligation to carry out the transaction.

Buyer of a Call Option

Swaps

Swaps are private agreements between two parties to exchange cash flows in the future according to a prearranged formula. They can be regarded as portfolios of forward contracts. The two commonly used swaps are interest rate swaps and currency swaps.

1. Interest rate swaps: These involve swapping only the interest related cash flows between the parties in the same currency.

2. Currency swaps: These entail swapping both principal and interest between the parties, with the cash flows in one direction being in a different currency than those in the opposite direction. More complex derivatives can be created by combining the elements of these basic types. For example, the holder of a swaption has the right, but not the obligation, to enter into a swap on or before a specified future date.

SERVICES PROVIDED BY THE DERIVATIVES

1. Increase the capability of the markets to absorb risk: To control, shift, avoid, reduce, eliminate, and manage efficiently various types of risks through hedging, arbitraging and acquiring insurance against them. In times of erratic trading, volatile interest rates and exchange rates, monetary chaos, national income turbulence and volatile markets, derivatives are said to enable investors to modify suitably the risk characteristics of their portfolios, or to shift the risk on to those who are willing to assume it for higher profits. They increase the capability of the markets to absorb risk, and this has a beneficial effect on the level of commercial and industrial activity. In their absence, the cost of risk to economy would be higher, and, it would worse off.

2. Barometers of future: To help in disseminating information which enables the society to discover or form suitable/ correct/true/ equilibrium prices. They serve as barometers of future trends in prices which result in the formation of correct prices on the spot markets now and in future. They provide for centralized trading where information about fundamental supply and demand conditions are efficiently assimilated and acted on. The economic and social benefits of accurate and equilibrium prices thus arrived at are many and one of them is superior allocation of resources.

3. Reduce Transaction cost: derivatives are there to enhance liquidity and reduce transactions cost in the market for underlying assets.

4. Assist in devise strategies: To enable the individuals and managers of large pools of funds to devise or design strategies for proper asset allocation, yield enhancement and achieving other portfolios goals. They provide opportunities for using certain kinds of special knowledge to obtain portfolio which offer higher expected returns than other portfolios comprising common stock, bonds, etc. with the same degree of risk.

5. Remove Price fluctuations: To smoothen out prices fluctuations, to narrow down the price spread, to integrate price structure at different points of time, and to avoid gluts and shortages in the markets. The existence of speculation, competitive trading, and differing risk taking preferences of the market operators help in achieving these results.

6. Catalyst to the growth of stock market: To act as starter form of investment which result in a wider participation in the securities markets. They attract young investors, who would not otherwise invest in stocks, to the securities industry. They act as the catalyst to the growth of stock markets.

7. Help in developing complete market: To offer important advantages of diversification and enable the society to reach the position of optimality by developing "complete market". The securities market is said to be complete if the patterns of returns of all additional securities are spanned by the already existing securities in it, or if it provides so many securities that no additional security can be created whose returns cannot be duplicated by a portfolio of existing securities.

NEED FOR A DERIVATIVE MARKET

The derivatives market performs a number of economic functions:

1. They help in transferring risks from risk adverse people to risk oriented people.
2. They help in the discovery of future as well as current prices.
3. They catalyze entrepreneurial activity.
4. They increase the volume traded in markets because of participation of risk adverse people in greater numbers.
5. They increase savings and investment in the long run.

World Wealth vs World Derivatives 1998-2007

FACTORS GENERALLY ATTRIBUTED AS THE DRIVING FORCE BEHIND THE GROWTH OF FINANCIAL DERIVATIVES IN NURTURING INDIAN STOCK MARKET

Particulars	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006
Stock Exchanges									
Cash Market	22	23	23	23	23	23	23	22	22
Stock Exchanges									
Derivatives Market			2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Brokers									
Cash Segment	9005	9069	9192	9782	9687	9519	9368	9128	9335
Sub Brokers									
Cash Segment	3760	4589	5675	9957	12208	13291	12815	13684	23479
Brokers									
Derivatives	-	-	-	519	705	795	829	994	1120
Foreign Institutional Investors	496	450	506	527	490	502	540	685	882
Custodians	-	-	15	14	12	11	11	11	11
Depositories	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2

Derivatives markets have had a slow start in India. The first step towards introduction of derivatives trading in India was the promulgation of the Securities Laws (Amendments) Ordinance, 1995, which withdrew the prohibition on options in securities. The market for derivatives, however, did not take off, as there was no regulatory framework to govern trading of derivatives. SEBI set up a 24-member committee under the Chairmanship of Dr. L.C. Gupta on 18th November 1996 to develop appropriate regulatory framework for derivatives trading in India. The committee recommended that derivatives should be declared as 'securities' so that regulatory framework applicable to trading of 'securities' could also govern trading of securities. SEBI was given more powers and it starts regulating the stock exchanges in a professional manner by gradually introducing reforms in trading. Derivatives trading commenced in India in June 2000 after SEBI granted the final approval in May 2000. SEBI permitted the derivative segments of two stock exchanges, viz NSE and BSE, and their clearing house/corporation to commence trading and settlement in approved derivative contracts.

Introduction of derivatives was made in a phase manner allowing investors and traders sufficient time to get used to the new financial instruments. Index futures on CNX Nifty and BSE Sensex were introduced during 2000. The trading in index options commenced in June 2001 and trading in options on individual securities commenced in July 2001. Futures contracts on individual stock were launched in November 2001. In June 2003, SEBI/RBI approved the trading in interest rate derivatives instruments and NSE introduced trading in futures contract on June 24, 2003 on 91 day Notional T-bills. Derivatives contracts are traded and settled in accordance with the rules, bylaws, and regulations of the respective exchanges and their clearing house/corporation duly approved by SEBI and notified in the official gazette. So, following are the different factors which contributed towards the growth of the stock market after introducing derivatives in different manners:

- (a) Increased Volatility in asset prices in financial markets.
- (b) Increased integration of national financial markets with the international markets.
- (c) Marked improvement in communication facilities and sharp decline in their costs.
- (d) Development of more sophisticated risk management tools, providing economic agents a wider choice of risk management strategies.
- (e) Innovations in the derivatives markets, which optimally combine the risks and returns over a large number of financial assets, leading to higher returns, reduced risk as well as transaction costs as compared to individual financial assets.

BENEFITS OF DERIVATIVES

Price Risk Management: The derivative instrument is the best way to hedge risk that arises from its underlying. Suppose, 'A' has bought 100 shares of a real estate company with a bullish view but, unfortunately, the stock starts showing bearish trends after the sub prime crisis. To avoid loss, 'A' can sell the same quantity of futures of the script for the time period he plans to stay invested in the script. This activity is called hedging. It helps in risk minimization, profit maximization, and reaching a satisfactory risk-return trade-off, with the use of a portfolio. The major beneficiaries of the futures instrument have been mutual funds and other institutional investors.

Price Discovery: The new information disseminated in the marketplace is interpreted by the market participants and immediately reflected in spot and futures prices by triggering the trading activity in one or both the markets. This process of price adjustment is often termed as price discovery and is one of the major benefits of trading in futures. Apart from this, futures help in improving efficiency of the markets.

Asset Class: Derivatives, especially futures, offer an exclusive asset class for not only large investors like

corporate and financial institutions but also for retail investors like high net worth Individuals. Equity futures offer the advantage of portfolio risk diversification for all business entities. This is due to fact that historically, it has been witnessed that there lies an inverse correlation of daily returns in equities as compared to commodities.

Derivatives Notionals by Type of User Insured Commercial Banks

Graph 1

High Financial Leverage: Futures offer a great opportunity to invest even with a small sum of money. It is an instrument that requires only the margin on a contract to be paid in order to commence trading. This is also called leverage buying/selling.

Transparency: Futures instruments are highly transparent because the underlying product (equity scripts/index) are generally traded across the country or even traded globally. This reduces the chances of manipulation of prices of those scripts. Secondly, the regulatory authorities act as watchdogs regarding the day-to-day activities taking place in the securities markets, taking care of the illegal transactions.

Predictable Pricing: Futures trading is useful for the genuine investor class because they get an idea of the price at which a stock or index would be available at a future point of time.

Conclusion

The derivatives would enhance further the speculative potential of the already highly speculative Indian stock market. The present research paper has revealed that there are many different aspects of the relationship between cash and derivative market namely, stabilizing effect, destabilizing effect or no effect. Derivative market in India has resulted in stabilizing prices by reducing volatility level. Thus it can be concluded that the introduction of derivatives has resulted in improving the quality of underlying asset market.

Customer expectations on services and responses from banking industry in India

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Abstract

The banking industries in India has undergone a major transformation due to changes in economic conditions and continuous deregulation- What was completely regulated and sellers market in the post is trying to graduate to completely deregulated market now.

The challenges faced by Indian Banking Industry presently are: Deregulation, New rules, Diffused customer loyalty, Competency Gap, Employees resistance to change due to up graduation of technology etc.

This research paper deals with customer expectations and the response from banking industry. The research finding reveal that customers feel that present banking sector in India is quite robust and their money is in safe hands and is satisfied. However the respondents have made a few suggestions on the possible areas of improvements .The bankers expressed their difficulty in meeting customers' requirements as many competent and devoted manpower is lost due to Bank's VRS Scheme and Competency Gaps now.

Key Words

Banking, Customer expectations, Deregulation.

1. Introduction

The banking industry in India has undergone a major transformation due to changes in economic conditions and continuous deregulation .What was completely regulated market in the past from sellers market is trying graduate to completely deregulated customer markets now.

The research paper deals with the customer expectations on services rendered and response from bankers in India.

2. Research objectives-

- a) To study various services offered by Indian banks
- b) To determine whether the bank customers are satisfied with the services offered by Indian banks and possible areas of improvements/ suggestions based on feedback from dis-satisfied customers of banks
- c) To find out investment priorities of bank customers
- d) To access the bank ratings in terms of services rendered to the customers.
- e) To study whether customers feel safe to keep money in bank
- f) To get banker's response based on customer expectations.

3. Market Survey

In order to find answers to the above objectives a market survey was carried out with 168 No of respondents in mainly the age group of 22-25years. A convenient sampling method was used and the replies to various questions are outlined below-

Q1 Your bank account is with:

1	Public sector Bank	109
2	Private sector Bank	63
3	Cooperative Bank	22
	Total	194

Note- As the respondents had accounts in more than one type on bank, the total number is more than the sample size

Findings- The majority of respondents are having saving accounts with Public sector banks.

Q2. What are the services offered by your bank?

Sr no	Services offered	Number of respondents
1	ATM Services	156
2	On-line banking	140
3	Cheque book facilities	151
4	Zero balance facility	62
5	Loan facility	136
6	Safe deposit lockers	93
7	Any other services	11
Total		749

Note – 1) As the respondents are availing more than one service, the total number of respondents are more than the sample size

Q3) Are you satisfied with the services offered by the bank?

Sr No	Satisfaction level	Number of respondents
1	Extremely satisfied	26
2	Satisfied	119
3	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	19
4	Dissatisfied	04
5	Extremely Dissatisfied	0

Findings-

- 1) The respondents are satisfied with the services offered by Indian Banks
- 2) Major reasons for dissatisfaction are :
 - a) Poor customer relationship management that is customer handling query and feed back is poor
 - b) High rate of interest on loans
 - c) ATM errors and less ATM machines
 - d) Zero balance not available with the bank.
 - e) Lost money in transaction

Q4 Rate banks in terms of services offered on a scale 1 to 5 (where 1 is the best and 5 is worst)

Sr No	Type of bank	Ranking
1	Nationalised Bank	04
2	Co-operative Bank	02
3	Private sector bank	03
4	Non financial Banking (NBFC)	01

Findings-

Surprisingly the target market has rated NBFCs and Co- operative Banks higher than private sector banks and co-operative Banks

Q5. What are your investment priorities?

Sr No	Investment options	No of Respondents
1	Shares	59
2	Gold	35
3	Real Estate	42
4	Mutual Funds	56
5	Fixed Deposits in Companies	51
6	Government Bonds	14
7	Public Provident funds PPF	02
	Total	259

Note- Since there is a multiple choice the total respondents are more than sample size.

Findings- The major options of respondents are shares, mutual funds and company fixed deposits.

Q6. Do you feel safe to keep money in Bank?

Yes	162
No	06
Total	108

Findings-

Majority of the respondents are of the opinion

Q7. When quizzed about additional services target market?

- 1) Lower interest rate for senior citizens deposits.
- 2) Foreign exchange facility.
- 3) Robust security for on line banking.

are suggestions from
higher interest rates on

- 4) 24 hour banking.
- 5) Cash deposit at ATM.
- 6) Proper communications.
- 7) Collection of money at doorstep.
- 8) Up gradation of technology.
- 9) Micro-finance.
- 10) Opening of additional counters during rush/ peak hours.
- 11) Demat account operations at all branches.
- 12) Operation of Public Provident Fund in all branches.

The response from bankers is given below-

- 1) Lower interest rate- Governed by RBI guidelines and Bank Policy.
- 2) Foreign exchange facility- Not possible.
- 3) Robust security for on line banking- Password provided.
- 4) 24 hour banking-ATM centers are available.
- 5) Cash deposit at ATM- Allowed up to particular limit at some banks
- 6) Proper communication- Lack of efficient manpower due to VRS Scheme.
- 7) Collection of money at doorstep- Some banks provide this facility to senior citizens.
- 8) Up gradation of technology- Being done on regular basis.
- 9) Micro- finance- Banks can provide.
- 10) Opening of additional counters during peak hours- Done as per the needs.
- 11) Demat account operation at all branches- Not feasible.
- 12) Operation of PPF account at all branches-Not possible. However, this facility is available at specified branches even now.

Limitations of the Study

- 1) The respondents contacted are generally in the age group of 22-25 years only.
- 2) Due to paucity of funds and time constraints, larger sample size could not be selected? Also, the research is carried out in Pune city only. The results obtained are therefore only indicative and not conclusive.
- 3) Only saving account holders were approached.

Conclusions

- 1) The Indian Banking sector is quite robust and the customers are satisfied with the present banking system
- 2) The customers feel safe to keep money in the Indian Banks
- 3) Some areas of dissatisfaction are: higher interest rates, poor communication, outdated technology, no personal touch.

Recommendations

- 1) Indian banks need to improve customer relationship management particularly handling queries and the customer problems.2) Bankers need to keep in touch with their customers as machines cannot replace to human touch.

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Abstract

Capital market reforms are a major constituent of the overall economic reforms in India. Major intermediaries in the securities market regulated by SEBI are brokers, sub-brokers, portfolio managers, merchant bankers, depository participants, bankers to an issue and share transfer agents. During 2007-08, there was an increase in the number of intermediaries registered. Quality service is an important consideration for the customer's satisfaction and their stay with the business. The research aimed to study the service quality conformance, level of customer's satisfaction about various services provided by the share broking institutions and, retention strategies of share broking institutions. In order to draw retention strategies, data has been collected from investors in Coimbatore- India. It is found from the research that investors are not very happy with the various services provided by the share brokers. The research reveals that the service quality deviation is very high for market exposure. In order to ensure desired service quality during the service delivery process a quality conformance model has been drawn. The customer retention model through CRM initiatives will help the share brokers to understand the customer's needs and wants and also the service providers.

Key Words: Service Quality, Customer Retention, CRM, share brokers, service delivery.

1.1 Introduction

The present challenging economy and competitive business world, customer retention is the critical for success of any business. Customer retention and satisfaction drive profits. The dramatic increase in competition among the organizations and declining loyalty among their customers has placed new emphasis on the value of customer retention. The customer retention is essential because capturing of new customers is so much more expensive than retaining old ones. Strong brands are built upon customer loyalty, and never is customer retention more relevant than in a time of economic downturn. If a company knows how much it really costs to lose a customer, they would be able to accurately evaluate investments designed to retain customers.

The financial services have been classified broadly in to four categories, fund based financial services, fee based financial services, commercial banks financial services, and securities related financial services. Reflecting the India's comparative advantage in the outsourcing market, the share of services exports in services sector GDP, which had increased from an average of 5.4 percent during 1995-2000 to 15.0 per cent in 2006-07, declined moderately during 2007-08 but rose sharply to 21.6 per cent in 2008-09. Similarly, net services exports also increased from 0.8 percent in 1995- 2000 to the peak of 6.6 per cent in 2008-09. In fact, India recorded the second largest growth after China in the services sector among the major emerging

market economies during the recent period

Indian stock markets had undergone structural transformation during nineties. The NSE had started its screen based on line trading in 1994 followed by BSE and other exchanges with the view to bring the participants closer.

According to the RBI s annual report 2008-09 the momentum of high growth in India has been the sustained because of the robust performance of the Indian services sector. The contribution of service sector to GDP has been 64.5% and it exhibited minimum growth of 9 percent in the recent five years. The significant progress made by the services sector has been partly possible because of the strong growth in services exports. The contribution of services exports in overall value added accelerated sharply from 6.9 per cent in 2000-01 to 21.6 per cent during 2008-09. Indian services sector has competitive edge in several knowledge based services segments viz., software, business processing and healthcare.

A share broker is a member of a recognized stock exchange who buys sells or deals in securities. A stock broker has to maintain high standard of integrity, promptness and fairness with due skills, care and diligence in conduct of all his business. The market intermediaries play an important role in the development of securities market by providing different types of services to their investors. Share brokers helps the clients to manage risk, they channels the funds from investors to fund seekers.

Market intermediaries are regulated by SEBI. During 2007-08, there was an increase in the number of intermediaries registered. As on March 31, 2008, the highest increase in absolute terms, was observed in case of depository participants (DPs) of CDSL (52) followed by portfolio managers (47). A decline was witnessed, in the number of underwriters followed by registrar to an issue and share transfer agent and debenture trustees as compared to 2006-07.

The Share brokers are providing excellent service, both to the investors and the fund seekers by connecting them. The survival of the share broking institution is depends on the strength of its investors. Customer retention can be made possible by considering the following three aspects:

- Customer satisfaction
- Service Quality
- Customer relationship management(CRM)

1.2 Customer satisfaction

It's a well known fact that no businesses can survive without customers. Customer satisfaction is a highly personal assessment that is greatly influenced by individual expectations as well as what they experience from the service institutions. The share broking institutions are at present providing excellent service to their customers. At present a share broker is providing more than 25 different services, like mobile trading, online trading, portfolio management, financing, etc. Measuring customer satisfaction is a relatively new concept to many of the share brokers but it is a must to retain customers. Competition in the share broking business and crowded markets with very little product differentiation necessities the institutions to be focused on customer satisfaction.

1.3 Service Quality

Service quality is very important both to the customers and service providers. Delivering quality service is an essential component of customer retention. The need, expectations and service received by the customers are crucial factors in assessing service quality. Service quality has been defined as the conformance of standards perceived by the customers. Parasuraman, Zeithamal, and Berry professor at various American

business schools has been identifies five criteria that customers relay on services quality: Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, Competence, and Tangibles. The present research also aimed to measure the service quality based on the mentioned service dimensions.

1.4 Customer Relationship Management (CRM)

CRM is technology that's used to improve the relationship between customer and organization. It is a process which retains the customers always. "Relationship marketing concerns attracting, developing, and retaining, customer relationships. Its central tenet is the creation of true customers - customers who are glad they selected a firm, who perceived that they are receiving value and feel valued, who are likely to buy additional service from, and who are unlikely to defect to a competitor". - Parasuraman, Zeithamal, and Berry. A good relationship is a reflection of greater propensity to buy the services from the particular service provider.

2.1 Review of related studies

Defining and measuring quality in services might be difficult due to the intangible nature of the service offering. Many of the researches on service quality have been carried out within the framework of widely accepted service quality model (SERVQUAL instrument) developed by extensive research by Parasuraman et. al. (1985, 1988, and 1991).

Customer satisfaction with quality and its link with service delivery have been explored in previous researches resulting in the identification of number of gaps. (Zeithml, VA, Parasuraman A and Berry L (1990)).Zeithml and Bitner (1996) have analyzed these gaps and have identified a number of service deficiencies or inadequacies within the service provider that would significantly contribute to sub optimization of the services and a higher probability of customer defection.

Kasper (1999) examined various alternative strategies for service marketing and gave emphasis to the need of a right service mix of services (product), people, system and technology. Many factors were identified as demanding attention in the triad of services, particularly the need of continuous interaction between the front office, the back office and the external customer.

Information systems (IS) technologies have become the enabling mechanisms behind a wide variety of customer-organisation service delivery interactions (Pitt et al., 1995). The emergence of Internet-based service encounters over the past ten years has seen the rise of new forms of online service encounters. As a result, there has been a proliferation of ServQual variants adapted to the Internet customer service setting (Parasuraman et al., 2005).

The quality of service is an important consideration in business. Customers perceptions of service quality are often influenced by the actual quality of the customer service delivered and received in relation to the product. Perceived quality is defined as a consumer's appraisal of a product's overall excellence or superiority (Zeithaml, 1988).

Consumers will notice something specific about that product, which will enable them to understand, in a particular way, its special quality. Therefore, perceived quality is an appraisal variable that might be added to models explaining behavioural intentions. This relationship is now well established identifying the processes of other variables (for example, customer satisfaction) and the positive behavioural intentions they have (Bagozzi, 1992).

According to Reichheld and Sasser (1990), a positive relationship between the customer and the company not only builds loyalty but also profitability. They found profits increased between 25 to 125 per cent

when a company retained just 5 per cent or more of its customers.

A study by Oliva, Oliver, and MacMillan, (1992) revealed customer satisfaction and loyalty increased dramatically with increased service quality but satisfaction declined as well as loyalty with minor changes to the same. Gould (1995), further helped consolidate interest in loyalty and satisfaction through his research with organisations marketers seeking information on how to build customer loyalty. Loyal customers serve as a "fantastic marketing force" by providing recommendations and spreading positive word-of-mouth (Raman 1999).

The success of a business enterprise is guided by the strategic orientation of the organization towards its customers, competitors and internal customers (employees) and the relationship between these significant components. External marketing addresses the relationship between the firm and its customers. Interactive marketing refers to the front end of the firm and the customer. Internal marketing refers to the relationship of the firm with its employees through its internal policies and interaction methods including the expectation – matching behavior and compensation planning. Substantial amount of research effort has been expended for understanding external customer behavior and developing tools and techniques for testing and interpreting the external consumer behavior (Parasuraman, A., Berry, L and Zeithaml (1998).

3.1 Significance of the study

Year	Grievances Received
1991-92	18794
1992-93	110317
1993-94	584662
1994-95	516080
1995-96	376478
1996-97	217394
1997-98	511507
1998-99	99132
1999-00	98605
2000-01	96913
2001-02	81600
2002-03	37434
2003-04	36744
2004-05	54435

Indian Share broking firms are playing significant role to bridge the investors and the capital market; the services rendered by the intermediaries are well appreciated and inevitable. The investors are facing number of problems and uncertainties to name a few: Regularity norms, Capital market trends, International financial market trends, Economic issues, Share market volatiles, Money market trends, Brokerages, Ineffective service facilities provided by the share brokers ,Reliability of information, Market rumors and so on.

2005-06	40485
2006-07	26473
2007-08	54933

According to the information reported in the Hand book of statistics on Indian securities market 2008, Securities & Exchange Board of India had been received about 33, 76,888 compliant from investors during the period 1991-92 to 2007-08. This is about an average of 1, 98,640 Compliant per year which is about 800 compliant per trading day. This statistics is about the compliant reported by the investors in fact the real number could be more than 4 to 5 times of dissatisfactions reported.

Share broking firms are also struggles to provide effective service to their customers because of difficulties in understanding investors needs, Complicated service standards ,Service satisfaction measurement issues, non availability of defined service models for different type of customers, Categorization of investors, Difficult to distinguish investors behavior, and Customers satisfaction and so on.

The study "Strategic Customer Retention of Indian Share Brokers" has been aimed to draw strategies to retain customers.

4.1 Research methodology

The research "Strategic Customer Retention of Indian Share Brokers" has aimed to study the service quality conformance, level of customer's satisfaction about various services provided by the share broking institutions and, retention strategies of share broking institutions. Primary data has been collected from 1000 selected investors from Coimbatore - India. Secondary data has been collected from various sources like journals, magazines, previous researches, books and websites. A well-structured questionnaire is developed to collect primary data from the investors. It is found sampling method is the most appropriate to do the research. The sampling plan for the study is stratified proportionate systematic sampling plan for selecting investors. List of investors has been obtained from the share brokers, from the list 83 investors from each share brokers has been selected for the researcher to collect data. Primary data has been collected with the help of a well structured questionnaire consisting of all appropriate questions for the research. In order to analysis the collected data various appropriate statistical tools were used.

5. Results and discussions

Table: 5.1 Service Quality Dimensions for Share brokers

Factors	Relevance		Importance	
	Mean relevance rating on 7-point scale	% of respondents indicating damnation is most relevant	Mean Importance rating on 7-point scale	% of respondents indicating damnation is most important
Reliability	5.464	34.5	6.229	63
Access	5.117	27.8	5.781	42.7
Security	6.722	86.5	6.726	84.8
Trustworthiness	6.527	78.5	6.107	59.4
Responsiveness	5.638	45.3	5.932	52
Competence	5.317	32.4	5.607	41
Empathy	4.529	21.2	5.275	32
Technology	5.842	56.4	6.6	78.1
Communication.	5.541	42.7	6.179	65.8

Source: Primary data

The customers perceptions of service quality are often influenced by the actual quality of the customer service delivered and received in relation to the services offered by the share brokers. The study has identified the following service quality dimensions; Reliability, Access, Security, Trustworthiness, Responsiveness, Competence, Empathy, Technology, Communication. It is found from the study that all the quality aspects mentioned are relevant to the share brokers for quality conformance. Among the above factors Security (86.5%) Trustworthiness (78.5%) and Technology (56.4%) are considered as most relevant to the share broking services.

It is found from the research that all the above factors are important for the share brokers while measuring quality conformance and investors satisfaction. The above table indicates the mean importance rating on 7 point scale and percentage respondents indicating that particular dimension is most important. Security (84.8%) is considered as most important factor for the service quality conformance by the customers; since the investor's hard earned money is invested and all the transactions are done through online the investors expect greater security. Technology (78.1%) and Communication (65.8%) are also important because both are very vital for speedy and correct decision making.

Table: 5.2 Service Institutions and Quality Conformance

Share brokers	Mean Quality Conformance rating on 10-point scale (n=1000)	Percentage of respondents indicating high degree of quality conformance (n=83)
ICICI Direct	7.62	28
Kotak Securities	7.92	42
India info line	8.14	58
karvy	7.12	26
Reliance Money	6.29	24
India bull financial	6.75	29
Angal broking ltd	6.84	28
Giojit Securities	7.59	32
Mothilal Oswal	6.81	27
Emkay Global Financial Services	6.72	26
Stock holding Corporation of India Ltd	6.1	21
Others	7.42	34 (n=87)

Source: Primary data

The success of service institution is determined by the customers and their survival in competitive environment, depends on quality of the service provided by them to their customers. In this context, qualities of service furnished by the share broking institutions are very important. The profitability of their business is closely connected to the quality of service they render to their customers.

The study has considered the above mentioned eleven service institutions. The study reveals that the service quality rendered by the service institutions are not reached excellent level; it is just above average level. In the case of India info line only the quality conformance has reached 8.14 in the 10 point scale and 58% customer's rated high degree of quality conformance. The share broking institutions has to give more importance to service quality not only in service delivery but also all other internal and external aspects. The success of a business enterprise is guided by the strategic quality orientation of the organization towards its customers, competitors and internal customers. Service quality conformance has to be ensured towards their own customers, against the competitor's customers and service providers (Service employees).

5.3 Service Quality Conformance Model

In order to ensure desired service quality during the service delivery process a quality conformance model has been drawn. This model identifies the service expectations of the customers, service providers and service institutions and actual service received by the customers and actual service delivered by the providers and institutions. The quality service delivery process is an important consideration for successful business.

Service customers perceptions of service quality are often influenced by the actual quality of the customer service delivered and received in relation to the service product. Perceived service quality is defined as a consumer's appraisal of a product's overall excellence or superiority in delivering excellent service to the investors. The customer expectations are not mere satisfactory service provided by the share brokers but what they promised, what the competitors promised and what you and others are not promised so far.

Table: 5.4 Investor's satisfaction

Factors	Mean Satisfaction on 5-point scale	Percentage of respondents indicating high degree of Satisfaction (n=1000)
Research report	3.4	42
Security news	3.1	41
Intraday call	3.5	29
Daily technical View	3.6	32
Morning Corporate News	2.9	26
Weekly tech Report	3.1	27
Sectorial report	2.7	25
SMA Alerts	3.2	41
Trinity Acc	3.8	49
Call & trade	3.4	41
Trading software	3.7	51
M-trade	2.4	34
Stock ideas	3.7	37
Derivative Report	2.1	32
Portfolio Advice	2.3	27
Com rep	2.5	21
Tech	2.6	26
IPO	4.2	59
After Market Orders	3.8	43
Market Exposure	2.4	21

Source: primary data

Share broking institutions should constantly monitor customer satisfaction in order to determine how it can increase their customer base, customer loyalty, revenue, profits, and market share. Customer satisfaction can be experienced in a variety of situations. In order to measure the customer satisfaction twenty service components has been identified and results are displayed in the above table. The investor's service satisfaction is based on the customer's experience of both contacts with the organization and their personal outcomes at various service levels.

To measure the service satisfaction a five point scale has been developed and investors are asked to rate the services components according to their preference. It is found that customer satisfaction is high in the case of IPOs (4.2 Mean Satisfaction on 5-point scale and 59 Percentage of respondents indicating high degree of Satisfaction out of 1000 respondents). The share broking services institutions have to work hard to identify,

the characteristics of the customers, and they have to consistently please their customers for sustainable growth. The share brokers need to develop tools for monitoring customer satisfaction, and to build continuous quality improvement systems that respond to the consumer reactions.

Table: 5.5 Service quality expectations and Service quality received
[Mean rating on 7-point scale (n=1000)]

Attributes	Service Quality Expectations(E) (Mean rating on 7-point scale)	Service Quality Received(R) (Mean rating on 7-point scale)	Quality deviations (R – E)
Research report	6.4	4.8	-1.6
Security news	6.1	4.1	-2.0
Intraday call	5.5	4.5	-1.0
Daily technical View	5.6	3.4	-2.2
Morning Corporate News	5.9	3.6	-2.3
Weekly tech Report	5.1	3.8	-1.3
Sectorial report	4.7	3.8	-0.9
SMA Alerts	6.3	5.2	-1.1
Trinity Accounts	5.3	4.9	-0.40
Call & trade	6.4	4.4	-2.0
Trading software	6.7	5.3	-1.4
M-trade	6.4	3.1	-3.3
Stock ideas	6.7	4.9	-1.8
Derivative Report	6.1	3.5	-2.6
Portfolio Advice	5.3	3.1	-2.2
Company report	5.5	4.7	-0.80
Technical report	5.6	3.4	-2.2
IPO	6.8	6.4	-0.40
After Market Orders	6.8	4.8	-2
Market Exposure	6.4	2.2	-4.4

Source: Primary data

The above analysis reveals the quality deviation between the customers' quality expectations and quality of service they received from the various services rendered by the share broking institutions. The research data is based on twenty attributes pertaining to service quality. The investors are asked to rate

service quality expectations and actual service received in a seven point scale based on their experience with the respective share brokers. The mean rating difference between actual and expected service is mentioned as quality deviations. The present research reveals that the service quality deviation is very high for market exposure (-4.4), M- trade (-3.3) and it is very low in the case of IPOs (-.40), trinity account (-.40). It is found from the research that service deviations are high in most of the services rendered by the share brokers. The share broking institutions need to take extra care to reduce the deviations to retain the customers.

5.6 Customer Retention Model through CRM Initiatives

A good relationship between the service providing institutions and customers will create excellent value over a period of time for both the parties. Customer acquisition is important for the newly established institutions, customer retention is vital for the established institutions, whether it is new or old brilliant CRM policy will serve the purpose. The above customer retention model through CRM initiatives will help the share brokers to understand the customer's needs and wants and also the service providers. The researcher has suggested some remedy to retain the customers through CRM initiatives. In order to implement successful CRM in an share broking institution the following suggestions has been recommended.

- + Service employee's involvement is very essential.
- + Internal marketing through proper and regular training to the service employees
- + Their must be a clear service policy.
- + Proper maintenance of customer's data base.
- + Innovative service technology
- + Regular events to approach customers.
- + Benefits to the customers for repeat usage of the service.
- + Management's commitment towards CRM activities.
- + Regular investors training
- + Regular investors meet to exit their problems and difficulties.

6.1 Concluding Remarks

Share broking institutions are providing brilliant service, both to the investors and the fund seekers, by connecting them. Customer retention is the need of the hour, it can be made possible by considering the following three aspects: Customer satisfaction, Service Quality, Customer relationship management (CRM). The recent developments in Information systems (IS) technologies have become the important mechanisms behind a wide variety of customer- service delivery interactions. The study reveals that the service quality has to be improved to a great extent by the share brokers. In order to improve the customer retention different models were also suggested. The research data has been collected from investors only share traders are not included to this research. The research data has been collected from Coimbatore this represent Indian customers, application to other nations are cautioned.

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IFRS- facts, basis and comparison to present Indian accounting standards

Submitted by

Himanshu Tiwari

“A common financial language, applied consistently, will enable the investors to compare the financial results of companies operating in different jurisdictions more easily and provide more opportunity for investment and diversification”

Sir David Twedie, Chairman, IASB

INDIA, being one of the emerging major economic superpowers, needs to strengthen its accounting structure to make it more transparent, concrete and comparable with rest of the world.

The objective of the IFRS is to provide a single set of accounting standards that would enable internationally to standardized training and assure better quality on a global screen. It would also permit international capital to flow more freely, enabling companies to develop consistent global practices on accounting problems. It would be beneficial to regulators too, to understand various reporting regimes.

What is IFRS?

International financial reporting standards (IFRS), together with the International accounting standards (IAS), are a “principles -based” set of standards that established board rules rather than dictating specific accounting treatments. From 1973 to 2001, international accounting standard committee (IASC) issued IAS. In April 2001 the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) adopted all IAS and begun developing new standards called IFRS. It is noteworthy that an IAS remains in effect unless replaced by an IFRS.

Objectives of IFRS

- To develop, in the public interest, a single set of high quality, understand and enforceable global accounting standards that require high quality transparent and comparable information in financial statements and other financial reporting to help participant in the world capital market and the other users make economic decision
- To bring about convergence of national accounting standards and international Accounting standards and IFRS to high quality solutions;
- To promote the use and rigorous application of those standards;
- In fulfilling the objectives associated with (1) and (2), to take account of, as appropriate, the special needs of small and medium-sized entities and emerging economics.

Structure of IFRS:

IFRS is considered a “principled-based” set of standards in that they establish broad rules as well as dictating specific treatments.

International Financial Reporting Standards comprise:

- International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS)- standards issued after 2001
- International Accounting Standards (IAS)- standards issued before 2001
- Interpretations originated from the International Financial Reporting Interpretation committee (IFRIC) issued after 2001
- Standing interpretation committee (SIC)- issued before 2001

There is no framework for the preparation and presentation of financial statements, which describes some of the principles underlying IFRS.

By the end of the fiscal 2008, it is expected that companies will be required to disclose plan for their IFRS transition and the expected impact of conversion on the financial statements. By the end of fiscal 2009, there will likely also be a requirement to provide a more detailed implementation plan and to quantify the conversion’s impact more precisely.

Another major challenge of the conversion will be the requirement to prepare 2010 comparative financial information, compliant with IFRS, for each 2011 interim reporting periods as well as the 2011 annual report. The first set of IFRS compliant financial information comprises will need to prepare will be for quarter 1, 2011.

What are the benefits of transition to IFRS?

- Inflow of foreign capital
- More efficient allocation of resources
- Greater comparability of financial information for investor
- Higher economic growth
- Greater willingness on the part of the investors to invest across borders
- Lower capital costs
- Global opportunities for accounting professionals.

What are the hurdles and impediments in fully converging with IFRS?

- Legal and Regulatory consideration.
- Shortage of resources.
- Alternative treatments prescribed by IFRS.
- Problem faced by small and medium sized firms and entities.
- Economic environment.
- Preparation level.
- Complexity of changes to be faced while interpreting and implementing IFRS.

What are the precautions that need to be taken?

In order to reduce the impediments to minimal level and maximize benefits, certain precautions need to be taken to ensure smooth transition to IFRS.

- Firstly, implementation of IFRS should be a gradual process. IFRS is not just an accounting exercise but is complete switch over or transition system that requires everyone concerned to adapt and adopt a new language and methodology. Therefore, implementation of IFRS especially in india due to diversities in terms of location, geography, social and economic environment must be gradual process.
- Secondly, proper and adequate methods should be adopted for addressing any differences or conflicts in the accounting requirements as per the law.
- Thirdly, effective guidance needs to be provide while implementation of IFRS. In order to be effectively implement the new system; the guidance should be effective. The standards must be accompanied with guidance notes and interpretation not only to facilitate the industry and entities to which it is applicable but also to provide assistance to auditors and other accounting professionals.
- Finally, capacity building is absolutely essential before issuing and implementing new standards corresponding to IFRS. Capacity building needs to be ensured in terms of training and guidance provided to auditors like organizing workshops, providing necessary assistance to small and medium scale entities, release of exposure drafts to make professionals aware of change in the standard etc.

Framework:

The framework states that the objective of financial statements is to provide information about the financial position, performance and changes in the financial position of the entity that is useful to a wide range of user in making economic decisions.

The framework can divide into the following sections:

- Purpose and status
- Scope
- Objective
- Underlying assumptions
- Qualitative characteristics of financial statements

IFRS: Standard of the future:

It is by now known enough that International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) would dictate standard-setting in the future. The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) – the standards-setter – is continuously making amendments to the standards to ensure that a single set of global accounting standards becomes the norm.

The Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB) has also amended some of its standards to bring them on a par with IFRS. India has announced that it would convert to IFRS effective 2011.

Towards this end, the Institute of chartered accountants of india (ICAI) has issued a Convergence Report for convergence to IFRS w.e.f. April1, 2011.

Underlying assumptions:

The underlying assumptions used in IFRS are:

- Accrual basis – the effect of transactions and other events are recognized when they occur, not as cash is received or paid
- Going concern – the financial statements are prepared on the basis that an entity is a going concern and will continue in operation for the foreseeable future

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Balance Sheet

Income Statement

Conceptual Framework Comparison

- Historical costing IAS & IFRS permits revaluation in contrast to historical cost convention. Only securities & derivatives can be valued at a fair value under IFRS.
- True & fair view: Under IFRS & IAS framework, there is an assumption that adoption of IFRS/IGAAP leads to a true and fair presentation.
- Prudence verses rules: There is common allegation against US GAAP, that they are ruled oriented & based on specific cases. However this is not true, as IAS are also more detailed & lay down detailed principles for application. No such allegation is leveled against IAF & IFRS.
- Overwriting of standards: IFRS permits that a company may withhold application in IFRS in extremely rare situation, where it is felt that application of IFRS would defeat the vary objective of financial reporting. Disclosure must be made for reason for override. No such override is permitted under IAS.
- Reporting elements: IFRS prescribes the minimum structure & content of financial statement including statement of changes in equity (in addition to balance sheet, income statement, cash flow statement, notes comprising significant accounting policy & other explanatory notes).

These statements are not required under IAS

Balance sheet... Comparison

- Format: IAS provides two formats of balance sheet horizontal & vertical & order of presentation as well. IFRS do not prescribes any formats.
- Order of line items: Under IFRS (if current & noncurrent order followed) & IAS, items in assets & liabilities are presented increasing order of liquidity. As under US GAAP in decreasing order of liquidity.
- Consolidation: Under IAS & IFRS consolidation of financial statements of subsidiaries is not compulsory until it is required under some other law or regulations.

Income Statement Comparison...

- Change in accounting policy: Under IAS effect if a change in accounting policy is given with prospective effect, if the same is material. Only in case of change in method of depreciation, the same has to be applied with retrospective effect. Other discloser required like need for change etc.
IFRS requires retroactive applications for the earliest period practical & adjustment of opening retained earning. Exemption given for prospective applications, if resulting adjustment is not reasonably determinable.
- Prior period items: IAS (AS 5.15, 19) requires separate discloser of prior period in the current financial statement either as part of current years result or as in alternative approach after determination of current net profit or loss.
No statement of retained earning is required however complete discloser of prior period & its impact on financial statements should be disclosed.
IFRS requires that a prior period item/error should be corrected retrospective effect by restatement of opening balance of assets, liabilities or equities for the earliest period practicable. Entity should also disclose nature of error & the amount of correction for each financial line item. IFRS also requires that such discloser should not be repeated in subsequent period.
- Discounting: IFRS provides that where the inflow of cash is significantly deferred without interest, discounting is needed. US GAAP also permit discounting in certain cases, While there is no concept of discounting under IGAAP.
- Consolidation: IAS & IFRS do not mandate consolidation of results of subsidiaries & VIEs as such except as required under law.
- Others: There are significant differences in the 2 GAAP on measurement & discloser of various heads of income & expenditure including forex losses extinguishment of debts, employ benefits, ESOP, dividend tax, loss on investments etc. leading to reconciliation issue between IGAAP results vis a vis IFRS.

IFRS vs Indian GAAP – Comparison

Acquisition and consolidated financial statements

Currently only listed Indian companies and banks are required to prepare consolidated financial statements. All other entities issued only standalone financial statements. Adoption of IFRS would require all defined entities (which include large –sized entities that are not listed on stock exchanges) to prepare and present consolidated financial statements.

Under Indian GAAP, there is no comprehensive standard that address accounting for acquisitions where one entity obtains control of another entity. The accounting for such transactions is largely dependent on the form of the acquisition. For example, the accounting treatment may differ dependent on whether the acquired company is retained as a separate legal entity, whether it is legally merged with the acquirer or whether a

group of assets constituting a business is acquired.

To add to the complexity and confusion, if the acquired company is merged with acquirer through a court-approved scheme, the scheme itself may prescribe accounting treatments that is required to be followed, which may be in variation with accounting standards.

Thus, depending on the form of the arrangement and other factors, goodwill may be computed based on the book value of the assets of the acquired company or the fair value of the assets of the acquired company.

Similarly, depending on the form of arrangement, the resultant goodwill may either be amortized over a period or not amortized, but tested for impairment. In certain cases, the court approved scheme may provide that the goodwill is adjusted against the reserves of the acquirer. Finally, Indian GAAP still permits the use of the pooling-of interest method whereby the entire transaction is accounted based on carrying values and no goodwill arises.

Under IFRS, all acquisitions are generally accounted for using the purchase method whereby the purchase price is compared to the fair value of all identifiable tangible assets, liabilities, contingent liabilities and intangible assets of the acquired company, with the excess being recognized as goodwill. This goodwill is not amortised, but is assessed for impairment annually. The limited exception to this principle relates to acquisition between entities under common control, whereby an entity can adopt an accounting policy choice of recognizing the acquisition either by the purchase method discussed earlier, or by the pooling -of-interest method.

For the most companies, application of the purchase accounting principles discussed above would result in an adjustment to the value of the assets and liabilities recorded recognition of previously unrecorded intangible assets and consequent adjustment of goodwill balances. These adjustments would subsequently affect the post-acquisition consolidated results, generally through increased amortization and depreciation . Additionally, the ability of companies to include ,in the consolidated financial statements,the revenues and profits of the acquired companies,prior to the date of the investment or prior to the date that control is obtained, would also be restricted.

Intangible assets acquired

Under Indian GAAP intangible assets are generally recognized only if they are acquired separately, All intangible assets are amortised over their useful lives (and tested for impairment) and there is rebuttable presumption that the useful life can not exceed ten years. Under IFRS, intangible assets are recorded either while accounting for acquisition using the purchase method, or when intangible assets are acquired separately. IFRS acknowledges that certain intangible assets may have identifiable useful lives (e.g. brands that demonstrate certain characteristics) and accordingly, such intangible assets are not amortized but tested for impairment annually, additionally , consistent with the treatment of all other depreciable assets, intangible assets are amortized over their estimated useful lives and there is no presumption that restricts the useful life.On adoption of IFRS, Indian companies that may acquire certain long-lived brands and similar intangible assets, may reach a conclusion that these intangible assets, which are amortised under Indian GAAP, are no longer required to be amortised or that these assets can be amortised over longer periods of time that represent their useful lives.

Financial instruments

Financial instrument where Indian GAAP differs significantly from IFRS include financial assets such as investments, financial liabilities such as convertible debt and preference shares and derivative instruments.

Under Indian GAAP, long- term investments are generally carried at cost, less impairment; and current investment are carried at lower of cost or market value. IFRS require that investment be categorised into three categories: trading on investment carried at fare value, held to maturity and available for sale. Except for held to maturity investment (where the entity has the intent and ability to hold the investment till maturity), all investment are carried at fare value. For investment categorasied as trading, all unrealized gains and losses are recorded in the income statements.

For investment classified as available for sale, the unrealized gains and losses are generally recorded directly as an adjustment to shareholders funds. Held to maturity investments are carried at amortised cost. It is likely that on adoption of IFRS, most investment securities held by Indian companies would be categorized as available for sale and accordingly would be carried at fare value. This would affect the reported value of the investment portfolio and net worth.

IFRS requires that a financial instrument should be classified in accordance with the substance of the contractual agreement rather than its legal form (substance over form). Thus, redeemable preference share would be a financial liabilities and dividend on redeemable preference share are recognised as interest expense under IFRS and impact the profit and loss for the year. This is different from the Indian GAAP classification of redeemable preference share as equity and the related presentation of dividends such preference shares as appropriation of profits. This would impact the financial structures and debt-equity ratio.

Similarly, under IFRS, a convertible debt is splits into a liabilities and equity portion whereby the proceeds from the insurance of debt are allocated to the two components. The liability components is recognized at fare value by a discounting at a market rate for a non convertible debts, while the balance proceed are allocated to the equity component and recoded directly in equity. This result is recognizing effective interest expense using rates applicable to non-convertible debt.

Under Indian GAAP, there is no specific accounting guidance for convertible debt and interest expenses generally recognized based on the stated rate of interest. Thus, if the stated rate of interest is lower than the market rate of non-convertible debt (due to the presence of the conversion feature), adoption of IFRS will result in additional interest based on this split-allocation approach.

Under IFRS, an entity must recognize all derivatives instruments at fare value on the balance sheet. Unless certain specific rules for hedge accounting are made, all charge in fare value are recoded through the income statements. Indian GAAP currently provides limited guidance on accounting for derivatives.

Thus except for certain specific forward exchange contracts, most derivatives instruments are currently not recoded on the balancesheet and do not affect the financial statements until realize/settled. The ICAI has already issued standards on presentation, recognition, measurement of financial instrument exactly on the basis of IFRS.

However this will be mandatory on April1, 2011. Adopting these standards in relation to derivatives

instrument hedge accounting will be a monumental shift in accounting for a large number of items on the balance sheet which will lead to recognition of many financial instruments which are currently kept off – balance sheet. Additionally, unless specific hedge accounting requirements are met, these standards will result in significant income statements volatility impacted by a change in fair value of the derivative instruments.

Presentation of financial statements:

Financial statements presentation formats under Indian GAAP are primarily driven by regulatory requirements specified in the Indian companies act and other regulation for specific industry (Banking insurance). Under IFRS, IAS 1 set out detailed requirement for presentation of financial statements, including their structure and minimum requirements for contents.

Under IFRS, in addition to balance sheet, income statements and cash flow statements, either a statements of changes in equity (SOCIE) or statements of recognize income and expenses(SORIE) with supplementary notes is required. A SORIE is a subset of SOCIE. An entity includes in SORIE revaluation, unrealized gain or losses on valuation of available- for-sale investments, which are not, reported the income statements, directly adjusted to the equity.

IFRS generally requires the balance sheet to clearly distinguished between current and non current assets and liabilities. Schedule VI to the Indian companies act follows current- non- current distinction only to a limited extent. Under IFRS, expenses can be classified by nature (salary, rent, power and fuel) or by function (cost of revenue, selling expenses, general and administrative). Schedule VI requires classification by nature companies would need to carefully evaluate the presentation requirement of IFRS to identify incremental disclosure and change to presentation requirement.

Conclusion:

Irrespective of various challenges involved in adoption & then converting all Accounting to IFRS with rapid liberalization process experienced in India, huge lot of multinational company are moving towards India

ICAI has taken a good initiative to bring the Indian Accounting standards at par with IFRS by bringing new ones and amend old ones . the move towards IFRS will transform the Landscape of accounting and will bring in benefits of an integrated global capital market regulated by single reporting standard.

HAPPY AND SUCCESSFUL TRANSITION.....

- CS KRISHNA RATHI

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The Industrial Restructuring – Mergers, Takeovers & Demergers- The Human Resource Perspective

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Abstract:

In a perfect world, mergers and acquisitions are as easy as two good companies coming together to form one bigger, better organization. Unfortunately, the reality is that as many as two-thirds of all mergers and acquisitions fail to achieve the anticipated benefits. Although the challenges posed by M&A projects are numerous and often unpredictable, there is at least one element that can be effectively managed to help reduce the risks and get the job done faster – workforce integration.

Several studies conducted across the globe that aimed at analyzing the true benefits of such strategies revealed that more than 60-70% of the acquisitions are financial failures. Whilst analyzing the reasons of the failures, research reports have assessed that Human Resource has a crucial role to play in steering the M&A strategy in the right direction. The prominence given to companies' human capital before and during M&A deals is critical to the success of the transaction. Lack of understanding of cultural issues and lack of involvement of the human resource in the M&A transaction are routinely cited reasons of failure of M&A transactions.

The study aims to examine the role of human resource in the entire M&A process to enhance its success. The study also provides an insight as to how transactions that place Human Resource considerations and capabilities centrally have a higher success rate than deals that neglect Human Resources.

Introduction:

Since Liberalization the world has been witnessing a wave of corporate mergers and acquisitions (M&A) that has been driven by dramatic changes in the global business environment. This fundamental economic restructuring is expected to continue for some time. Mergers and acquisitions are undertaken to fulfill various corporate objectives. They may be intended to reduce the likelihood of hostile takeovers, to diversify risk, or to achieve competitive advantage through synergistic efficiencies. They may involve merely integrating accounting functions and creating a new legal entity, or, at the other extreme, they may involve integration of capital assets, functional departments, and human resources (Shrivastava 1986). Although they are undertaken for good reasons, the research shows that many high-cost mergers and acquisitions fail to provide the anticipated rewards. Shrivastava (1986) suggests that one half to two-thirds of all mergers 'simply do not

work.' Buono and Bowditch (1989) reported that 30 percent of all acquired firms are sold off within five years and that 90 percent of mergers never live up to expectations.

Three converging trends, which can help explain why cultural issues have become so important: First, service companies increasingly dominate the largest global economies. That means the chief assets are not factories and equipment, but people - executives who develop client relationships and leverage a certain expertise. Consequently, mergers involve assets that can leave when things become uncomfortable. This was supported by Coffey et al (2003) who found that 47% of executives leave the company within the first year, and 75% leave within the first three years .Second, the sharp increase in cross border deals between global firms with operations in many different countries means that different national cultures become an additional challenge. Finally, deal rationales have become more complex. Many companies engage in mergers and acquisitions not just to squeeze out value or increase their size, but also to transform their business or industry..

Some Key M&A Statistics

- On the announcement of an M&A deal, company stocks rose in only 30% of cases (Coffey et al 2003)
- Synergies projected for M&A are not achieved in 70-80 % of cases (Coffey et al 2003)
- Routinely cited as problems are people and cultural issues in failing or failed integration (Coffey et al 2003)
- Almost 95% of all new products fail as a result of poor M&A management.
- 65% of strategic acquisitions and mergers result in negative shareholder value (Marcum 2003)
- Serial acquisitions are made in some instances to hide previous failed mergers and underlying financial problems (HRM Manager 2003, Vol 12)
- A Board making serial acquisitions will usually be more intent on focusing on the next deal than on integrating the business in hand. The Board enters into a vicious circle in order to keep shareholders sweet. (Deloitte & Touche 2001)
- New initiatives are launched with decisions stacking up but no one to make them (Webb 2002)
- Customers and staff are forgotten (Deloitte & Touche 2001)

As seen in the above mentioned statistics that most of them are concentrated on peoples Issues and cultural issues. Mergers and acquisitions often fail to meet pre-merger objectives, despite an efficient due diligence process at the outset, because not enough time and energy is devoted to post-merger relationships and the development of an emergent culture to support the new organizational form. The erroneous assumption is that once the financial issues are dealt with everything else will fall into place. But the case is reverse that once Peoples Issues are dealt with the financial issues will fall in place.

In an attempt to understand the reasons for the high failure rate, more recent M&A research has focused on human resource activities, particularly during the integration phase. Unfortunately, empirical studies relating to this topic seldom reach consistent conclusions. Furthermore, most studies do not explicitly link the various strategies pursued in mergers and acquisitions with the degree of success that is eventually obtained.

Nevertheless, it is clear that if human resource issues are dealt with, the financial issues will fall in place. Generally under-managed, poorly understood, and often discarded at the outset as irrelevant to the strategic planning process (Napier 1989; Buono and Bowditch 1989) a better understanding of human resource issues in the integration stage of mergers and acquisitions help M&A succeed.

Objectives of the Study:

The Research Objective include

- a) Examination of the role of human resource in the entire M&A process.
- b) Analysis of Human Resource Departments' capabilities that attribute to the success or failure of Mergers and Acquisitions transaction.
- c) Assessment of the data that Mergers and Acquisition transactions that put importance on Human Resource considerations and capabilities, required during the mergers and acquisition process, repeatedly have a higher success rate than deals that neglect Human Resources.

Research Methodology:

The Findings of the paper are based on a detailed analysis of data obtained by Questionnaires, observation and Interviews with Human Resource Professionals.

The Research Methodology comprised of three key initiatives.

- a) Online Detailed Questionnaires to a cross section of 78 senior human resource professionals that has undertaken Mergers and Acquisition activity during the past 36 months.
- b) In-depth interviews were conducted with senior human resource professionals of companies that had undertaken Mergers and Acquisition activity during the past 36 months
- c) Extensive desk research was conducted into the outcomes of 50 significant mergers and acquisition (M&A) deals involving Indian firms over the last 8 years.
- d) Surveys conducted by Research Organizations inquiring into the attitudes and Role of Human Resource executives during and after the Merger and Acquisitions.

This is a fact finding study. Based upon convenient sampling. Sample Size is based on 78 Human Resource professionals of firms that had undergone the Mergers and Acquisition activity during the past 36 months. Some of the Human Resource executives were also interviewed.

Limitations and Further Research:

This Study is confined only to selective Human Resources executives of those firms that have undergone mergers and Acquisitions during the past 36 months. The Information provided from the questionnaire by the respondents could be biased.

Some of the executives were less cooperative and unable to say boldly on fact finding due to hesitation.

To Analyze the subject in detail the survey needs to be extended to a detail mass of Human Resource executives. The study is also limited in terms of the merger period of 36 months. If the period of observation is extended to 5 years or more, the results provided would be more constructive.

Contacting the Human Resource executives was another difficulty. In spite of appointments taken very little time was given to interact with the human resource executives thus limiting the availability of information through personal interviews.

Literature Review:

Many independent studies have been conducted on Role of Human Resources with special reference to the success of Mergers and Acquisitions. McCann and Gilkey (1988) identified three types of fit—financial, business, and organizational fit—that must all be present if the merger or acquisition is to be successful. McCann and Gilkey suggests that organizational fit, which includes human resources and the two organizational cultures, is of primary importance, since it helps to determine how well the two firms can be integrated and that ‘the greater the differences between the two firms in these areas, the greater the difficulty in achieving the desired level of integration.. and in realizing business synergies which will ultimately show up in financial performance’.

A Delicate Balance Management of the transition stage requires a delicate balance between providing a stabilizing influence and creating a climate for change. Uncertainty and anxiety, anger, frustration, psychological withdrawal and family disruptions are pervasive during M&A activity (Schweiger, Ivancevich, and Power 1987). Since information is generally scarce in the transition stage, the employee's perceptions will be influenced predominately by rumour and speculation. Greenhalgh and Jick (1979) found a positive correlation between job insecurity and resistance to change (see also Staw, Sandelands, and Dutton (1981)) which shows that negative employee reactions and behaviors are more common in failed acquisitions than in successes.

Procedural integration is designed to standardize work procedures and improve productivity. Since each firm has its own systems and procedures, combining the two requires that some of the old ways are abandoned. Marks and Mirvis (1986) suggest that where the system of the dominant firm is adopted over that of the subdominant. Finally Buono and Bowditch (1989) point out that an active involvement of the Human Resources in the Mergers and Acquisitions deal will lead to achievement of the objective of the merger and thereby increase the success rate. Several studies have also emphasized the importance of the role and activities of the Human resource department in the Merger and Acquisitions process.

Analysis and Findings:

The survey is made up of a broad cross-section of business types from India. The respondents are from Mumbai (39%), Chennai (19%), Delhi (22%), Calcutta (8%) and rest of India (12%) (Refer Figure 1). The Respondents are from Industries led by financial services (34%), telecoms and technology (17%), service sector (16%) and manufacturing (10%) and others (23%). (Refer Figure 2).

Have the M&A Activity delivered the targeted objectives set for them:

M&A activity is undoubtedly complex, challenging and unpredictable. But this research finds convincing evidence to suggest that M&A deals are not nearly as prone to failure as is commonly supposed.

In the research, 71 % of respondents (see Figure 3) state that more than half of all merger-related activity in the company has delivered on targeted objectives.

Not only that, but the survey respondents believe that 62% of all employees perceive merger activity to be either successful or very successful.

Figure 3: Number of M&A-Related Activities that Delivered on the Objectives Set for Them

This isn't to suggest that M&A activity is easy. The research results still expose a fairly high failure rate—a candid 29% of respondents report that less than half their deals met the targets set for them. But success is certainly attainable.

An Analysis of 20 large mergers and acquisitions in India show that in 45% of the deals, the share price of the merged company outperformed the sector average in the year following the merger—the period of greatest upheaval and instability.

This is also evident by the fact of the number of deals completed by the respondents till date. (Figure 4) which goes to show why companies are unwilling to turn their back on M&A activity although they could turn to be failures.

Figure 4 :Number of deals completed by respondents

52% of the survey respondents said they had completed between one and three deals; 12% between four and six; 5% between seven to ten; and 7% eleven or more. Companies continued to believe that M&A activity is

central to their business. Asked how core M&A was to the success of the company's business strategies; 79% of survey respondents stated it was either "integral" or "important". Only 21% of respondents reported that it was "unimportant".

People-Related Issues are Critical to Achieving Success in Mergers and Acquisitions:

As part of the research process, a cross-section of senior human resource professionals were interviewed in Mumbai who had all recently experienced a merger (either as acquirer or target). From those interviews, the following critical HR-related factors to achieving success:

- Ensuring effective communications: A critical factor in getting employees from both "sides" to think in the same way is to assign responsibility quickly and clearly for communications to a very senior manager who knows what messages is being sent out and how they are being received.
- Achieving cultural alignment: Achieving the cultural alignment is important . In the survey conducted only 18% of the respondents were permitted to carry on task towards cultural alignment.
- Form a mobile team of transition executives: Use the skills of the human resource department fully. Set up immediate Internet access with your company. Link new employees with your people at similar levels who also joined your company through an acquisition. Practice full access and full disclosure. This team should research and study every single job at the acquisition and produce a map bringing that job into your firm's matrix..
- Do not kill the deal over price - Due diligence: Assessing the liabilities of the target company ensures the M&A transaction is accurately priced. The focus should not merely be on the inherited costs, but also on future additional costs associated with the integration of compensation and benefit integration.
- Move fast the day the deal is announced-Integration Phase: In acquisitions, studies show that there is direct correlation between speed of integration and the success of the deal.

The Research provides some insight into the positive impact that a deeper HR involvement in the M&A process can have. The vast majority of respondents (76%) who felt that their HR departments were fully capable met their objectives on 55% or more of their mergers. More than half of the respondents who said that their HR departments were not capable at all said that less than 45% of their M&A deals delivered on objectives.

In other words, it appears that there is a direct correlation between the capabilities of the HR department and the chances of M&A success.

Reasons for Failure in M&A Activity

What are the principal causes of M&A failure? "people issues" are at or near the top reasons for Failure of Mergers and Acquisition. Even if the business objective for a deal is the right one, the people in the system can support its success or cause its failure, through passive resistance, personal/political agendas, or a simple clash of working cultures."

The human aspects of M&A deals are paramount. The top five causes of M&A failure identified by the research respondents are all deeply rooted in the “softer” management issues of integrating different cultures, leadership teams and workforces (see Figure 5).

The respondents identified the people issues that have a critical impact on M&A activity and the roles entrusted to human resources professionals during the M&A process. (Figure 6) and the importance manager’s place on critical HR responsibilities (Figure 7).

Figure 6: The Most Critical People Issues for M&A Success (Percentage of Respondents*)

Figure 5: The Five Principal Causes of Failure in M&A Activity (Percentage of Respondents*)

- Respondents could choose up to four criteria.

**Figure 7: Responsibilities of HR Departments
(Percentage of Respondents*)**

Conclusion:

M&A deals are important to companies' strategies. People issues are critically important to M&A deals. If senior managers pay enough attention to human capital, if they enable HR to play a fully engaged and constructive role in the M&A process, and if they budget for outside help where it is needed, the M&A Activity would definitely be successful.

The Research adds analytical substance to the observations that the critical peoples issues that are essentially important for the success of the M&A Activity are:

- Involve HR professionals early—involve them when deciding a proposed deal.
- Finance departments often drive M&A processes. If HR departments want a seat at the M&A table, they must speak in financial terms.
- Ensure the due diligence process identifies the people liabilities.
- Focus on the top team and key talent.
- Speed and flexibility are essential in all aspects of the integration
- Be bold in integrating rewards and benefits.
- Communicate at all levels in the company—there's no such thing as too much communication.
- Pay as much attention to the people issues as the numbers; you won't get the benefit of the deal without the people.

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A Study of Current Trends in Service Industry with reference to Insurance Sector

Submitted By

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Introduction

The term “services” covers a heterogeneous range of intangible products and activities that are difficult to encapsulate within a simple definition. Services are also often difficult to separate from goods with which they may be associated in varying degrees.

“Services are the result of a production activity that changes the conditions of the consuming units, or facilitate the exchange of products or financial assets. These types of service may be described as transformation services and margin services respectively. Transformation services are outputs produced to order and typically consist of changes in the conditions of the consuming units realized by the activities of producers at the demand of the consumers. Transformation services are not separate entities over which ownership rights can be established. They cannot be traded separately from their production. By the time their production is completed, they must have been provided to the consumer. The changes that consumers of

Services engage the producers to bring about can take a variety of different forms as follows:

- a. Changes in the condition of the consumer’s goods: the producer works directly on goods owned by the consumer by transporting, cleaning, repairing or otherwise transforming them;
- b. Changes in the physical condition of persons: the producer transports the persons, provides them with accommodation, provides them with medical or surgical treatments, improves their Appearance, etc.;
- c. Changes in the mental condition of persons: the producer provides education, information, advice, entertainment or similar services in a face to face manner.”

“The changes may be temporary or permanent. For example, medical or education services may result in permanent changes in the condition of the consumers from which benefits may be derived over many years.

On the other hand, attending a football match is a short-lived experience. In general, the changes may be presumed to be improvements, as services are produced at the demand of the Consumers.

The improvements usually become embodied in the persons of the consumers or the goods they own and are not separate entities that belong to the producer.

Such improvements cannot be held in inventories by the producer or traded separately from their production services differ from goods in a number of ways, most commonly in the immediacy of the relationship between supplier and consumer.

Many services are non-transportable, i.e., they require the physical proximity of supplier and customer—for example, the provision of a hotel service requires that the hotel is where the customer wishes to stay, a cleaning service for a business must be provided at the site of the business, and a haircut requires that both hairstylist and client be present.

Distinctive characteristics of services

Service characteristics	Concept	Implications	Marketing Strategy
1 Intangibility	Services can't be seen ,touched and felt, tasted or smelled or even heard before they are purchased Dietician, counselor	Cannot be stored , no patents, no ready display, communication, pricing difficulties	Tangible clues, personal sources WOM Organizational image Cost accounting for prices
2 Inseparability	Services are produced distributed and consumed simultaneously e.g. a music program can take place only with the music provider.	Consumer involve in production No mass production Supply demand match	Selection and training of contact person Manage consumer Multi sight location
3 Heterogeneity	Services delivered generally vary in quality, time consumed in delivery at the extent of service provided e.g. for	Standardization difficult quality control difficult	Industrialize Customize

	instance , the vocal music of two musicians may be different but appealing		
4 Perish ability	Refers to the fact that if service is not availed on time that it is not available. e.g. for an airlines ,in particular flight , vacant seats remain unsold , where as in the case of manufactured goods, unsold items can be put into inventory and can be sold the next day.	no inventorization	Cope with fluctuating demand Better match through process

The GOODS and SERVICES Continuum

Operational skills

Dominant

Restaurants

Tourism

Transport

Waste disposal

Financial services(banking and insurance)

Consultancy

Tangibility

Intangibility

Medical health care

Professional advice(lawyers accountants etc)

Training

Objectivity Vs Subjectivity

Intellectual Property Dominant

The Services spectrum

SERVICES –Indian Economy

Service sector is the lifeline for the social economic growth of a country. It is today the largest and fastest growing sector globally contributing more to the global output and employing more people than any other sector.

The real reason for the growth of the service sector is due to the increase in urbanization, privatization and more demand for intermediate and final consumer services. Availability of quality services is vital for the well being of the economy.

In advanced economies the growth in the primary and secondary sectors are directly dependent on the growth of services like banking, insurance, trade, commerce, entertainment etc.

Services or the "tertiary sector" of the economy covers a wide gamut of activities like trading, banking & finance, infotainment, real estate, transportation, security, management & technical consultancy among several others.

The various sectors that combine together to constitute service industry in India are:

- Trade
- Hotels and Restaurants
- Railways
- Other Transport & Storage
- Communication (Post, Telecom)
- Banking
- Insurance
- Dwellings, Real Estate
- Business Services
- Public Administration; Defense
- Personal Services
- Community Services
- Other Services

Indian Service Sector

In alignment with the global trends, Indian service sector has witnessed a major boom and is one of the major contributors to both employment and national income in recent times. The activities under the purview of the service sector are quite diverse. Trading, transportation and communication, financial, real estate and business services, community, social and personal services come within the gambit of the service industry.

One of the key service Industry in India would be health and education. They are vital for the country's

economic stability. A robust healthcare system helps to create a strong and diligent human capital, who in turn can contribute productively to the nation's growth.

Post Liberalization

The Indian economy has moved from agriculture based economy to a knowledge based economy. Today the IT industry and ITE'S industry are the dominant industry in the service sector. Media and entertainment have also seen tremendous growth in the past few years.

Subsectors

Information Technology Industry

The Information Technology industry has achieved phenomenal growth after liberalization. The industry has performed exceedingly well amidst tough global competition. Being knowledge based industry; India has been able to leverage the global markets, because of the huge pool of engineering talent available and the proficiency in English language among the middle class.

ITES sector

The ITES sector has also leveraged the global changes positively to emerge as one of the prominent industries. Some of the services covered by the ITES industry would be:

- Customer interaction services -Non voice and Voice.
- Back office, revenue accounting, data entry, data conversion, HR services.
- Medical Transcription.
- Content development and animation.
- Remote education, market research and GIS

Retailing

Prior to liberalization, India had one of the most underdeveloped retail sectors in the world. After liberalization the scenario changed dramatically.

Organized retailing with prominence on self service and chain stores has changed the dynamics of retailing. In most of the tier I and tier II cities supermarket chains mushroomed, catering to the needs of vibrant middle class. This indirectly contributed to the growth of the packaged food industry and other consumer goods.

Financial Services-Banking And Insurance

Prior to liberalization these two sectors were controlled and regulated by the government. Nationalized banks and insurance companies had a firm grip over the market.

After liberalization the banking and insurance domain opened up for private participation.

Banking Sector

The three major changes in the banking sector after liberalization are:

- Step to increase the cash outflow through reduction in the statutory liquidity and cash reserve ratio.
- Nationalized banks including SBI were allowed to sell stakes to private sector and private investors were allowed to enter the banking domain. Foreign banks were given greater access to the domestic market,

both as subsidiaries and branches, provided the foreign banks maintained a minimum assigned capital and would be governed by the same rules and regulations governing domestic banks.

- Banks were given greater freedom to leverage the capital markets and determine their asset portfolios. The banks were allowed to provide advances against equity provided as collateral and provide bank guarantees to the broking community.

Insurance Sector

The Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority Act 1999 (IRDA Act) allowed the participation of private insurance companies in the insurance sector. The primary role of IRDA was to safeguard the interest of insurance policy holders, to regulate, promote and ensure orderly growth of the insurance industry. The insurance sector could invest in the capital markets and other than traditional insurance products; various market link insurance products were available to the end customer to choose from.

Some of the prominent insurance companies are:

- Bajaj Allianz Insurance Corporation
- Birla Sun Insurance Co Ltd
- HDFC Standard Insurance Co Ltd
- ICICI Prudential Insurance Co Ltd
- Max New York Insurance Co Ltd
- Tata AIG Insurance Co Ltd

.Reasons for growth of services in India

1 Economic Affluence- Affluence is one of the key factors for the growth of demand for services

The economic liberalization process initiated in the country during the last decade of the 20 th century had apposite impact on the Indian house holds. Their income as well as expenditure has been pushed up creating a demand for many goods and services.

2 Changing roles of women- Women constitute nearly 50% of the population. Indian women traditionally used to confine themselves to house hold activities. There has been change in the traditional way of thinking in the society, women were encouraged in education. Indian women proved to be more competent in work and, in some areas , proved to ne more efficient then their male counter parts .The changing role of women in the society crated market for a no of products, particularly a no of services .

3 Cultural changes- Change is the underlying philosophy of culture. During the last century the factors of change are prominent. There has been a marked change in the thought process relating to expenditure, investment, leisure time , perception children's education and so on, which ahs created a market for services.

4 IT Revolution-India has been occupying a vital position in the area of information technology for the last 15 years. Indians have proved their supremacy in the field to the world. It has become one of the key service business of the country.

5 Conservation of Natural Resources-The growths of population, greater industrialization and indiscriminate consumption have affected the natural resources, environment and ecological balance. Understanding the need the government and various social organizations have promoted several service organizations to take up social marketing so as to address the various environmental issues.

6 Development of Markets-The growth of the whole seller – retailer population during the last few decades in the country is sine qua non. For the development of markets in India. A breed of organization, offering marketing services for a no of products produced have also come up like SSI and SME

7 Unbundling Corporations -Manufacturing organizations identified the need for future orientation. to facilitates such requirements they have promoted staff function in the organization. The pressures in the market have further forced the manufacturing organizations to have marketing research, advertising, auditing etc divisions – all of these are services functions.

8 Increased Consciousness of Health Care -The health care market has grown substantially in India. The increased life expectancy is the result of the consciousness' of people regarding health issues. The growth of health centre, fitness club diagnostic centers, medical counseling psychological counseling, health related information sites are the reflection of the growing demand for health care services

9Economic Liberalization- The economic liberalization which started in1991 brought in many changes in Indian business scenario. Multinationals were permitted to enter the Indian Market. Liberal lending policies and lower interest rates motivated many people to become self-employed. The banking sector, insurance, telecommunications, hospitality services etc. Witnessed intense competition due to the entry of multinational companies.

10 Migration-Rural to urban and semi urban migration has been one of the reasons for the growth of services in India. Due to this, businesses like real estate, rentals, transportation and infrastructure services are expanding rapidly.

11 Export Potential-the export market for services has been on the rise throughout the world. India is considered to be a potential source of services. Services that are commonly offered to the international consumers are communication, data services, design engineering etc.

Tourism and software services are among the major foreign exchange earners of the country and their growth rate is also very high when compared to other sectors.

12 Service Tax-The growth in the services sector attracted the attention of the government as a tax generating resource. The Government of India introduced service tax for the first time in 1994.

The service tax as a proportion of GDP originating in the service sector however remained as a minuscule fraction.

Objectives: To identify the current trends which have helped in the growth of Services in India with reference to Insurance Sector

Methodology: The study will be carried out using secondary data. The secondary data is collected from various sources which includes the data provided by Insurance Companies and by IRDA(Insurance

Regulatory Development Authority of INDIA).

INSURANCE MARKETING

Insurance marketing is a sub set of Services Marketing.-

The term INSURANCE MARKETING refers to marketing of Insurance services with the motto of customer orientation and profit generation. The quality of services can be improved by formulating a fair mix of core and peripheral services. Since it is an intangible product the role of 3 more P's (i.e. People, Process, Physical evidence) besides the 4 P's becomes of vital importance.

Being a part of the service sector it involves high level of people Interaction and it is important to use this resource efficiently in order to satisfy customers and to have competitive edge in the market. Insurance marketing- Wherever there is uncertainty there is risk. The risk can't be averted. It involves multi faceted losses. Risk is uncertainty of financial /other losses. We don't have any command on uncertainties'. This makes it essential that we think in favor of a device that becomes instrumental in spreading the loss.i.e Insurance which is considered to be a social device to accumulate funds to meet uncertain losses. The main functions of insurance are to provide protection against the possible chances of generating losses. It eliminates worries and miseries of losses at destruction of property and death.

Brief history of Insurance Sector In India

The insurance sector in India has completed all the facets of competition –from being an open competitive market to being nationalized and then getting back to the form of a liberalized market once again. The history of the insurance sector in India reveals that it has witnessed complete dynamism for the past two centuries approximately.

Insurance sector in India is one of the booming sectors of the economy and is growing at the rate of 15-20 per cent annum. Together with banking services, it contributes to about 7 per cent to the country's GDP. Insurance is a federal subject in India and Insurance industry in India is governed by Insurance Act, 1938, the Life Insurance Corporation Act, 1956 and General Insurance Business (Nationalization) Act, 1972, Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) Act, 1999 and other related Acts.

The origin of life insurance in India can be traced back to 1818 with the establishment of the Oriental Life Insurance Company in Calcutta. It was conceived as a means to provide for English Widows. In those days a higher premium was charged for Indian lives than the non-Indian lives as Indian lives were considered riskier for coverage. The Bombay Mutual Life Insurance Society that started its business in 1870 was the first company to charge same premium for both Indian and non-Indian lives. In 1912, insurance regulation formally began with the passing of Life Insurance Companies Act and the Provident Fund Act.

By 1938, there were 176 insurance companies in India. But a number of frauds during 1920s and 1930s tainted the image of insurance industry in India. In 1938, the first comprehensive legislation regarding insurance was introduced with the passing of Insurance Act of 1938 that provided strict State Control over insurance business.

Insurance sector in India grew at a faster pace after independence. In 1956, Government of India brought together 245 Indian and foreign insurers and provident societies under one nationalized monopoly corporation and formed Life Insurance Corporation (LIC) by an Act of Parliament, viz. LIC Act, 1956, with a capital contribution of Rs.5 Crore.

The (non-life) insurance business/general insurance remained with the private sector till 1972. There were 107 private companies involved in the business of general operations and their operations were restricted to organized trade and industry in large cities. The General Insurance Business (Nationalization) Act, 1972 nationalized the general insurance business in India with effect from January 1, 1973. The 107 private insurance companies were amalgamated and grouped into four companies: National Insurance Company, New India Assurance Company, Oriental Insurance Company and United India Insurance Company. These were subsidiaries of the General Insurance Company (GIC).

In 1993, the first step towards insurance sector reforms was initiated with the formation of Malhotra Committee, headed by former Finance Secretary and RBI Governor R.N. Malhotra. The committee was formed to evaluate the Indian insurance industry and recommend its future direction with the objective of complementing the reforms initiated in the financial sector.

Important milestones in the Indian life insurance business

- 1912: The Indian Life Assurance Companies Act came into force for regulating the life insurance business.
- 1928: The Indian Insurance Companies Act was enacted for enabling the government to collect statistical information on both life and non-life insurance businesses.
- 1938: The earlier legislation consolidated the Insurance Act with the aim of safeguarding the interests of the insuring public.
- 1956: 245 Indian and foreign insurers and provident societies were taken over by the central government and they got nationalized. LIC was formed by an Act of Parliament, viz. LIC Act, 1956. It started off with a capital of Rs. 5 crore and that too from the Government of India.

Companies in India

- Life Insurance Companies
- Aviva Life Insurance
- Bajaj Allianz Life Insurance
- Birla Sun-Life Insurance
- HDFC Standard Life Insurance
- ING Vysya Life Insurance
- Life Insurance Corporation
- Max New York Life Insurance
- MetLife Insurance
- Om Kotak Mahindra Life Insurance
- Reliance Life Insurance
- Sahara India Life Insurance

- SBI Life Insurance
- TATA AIG Life Insurance

- General Insurance Companies
- Agriculture Insurance
- Amsure Insurance
- ANZ Insurance
- Bajaj Allianz General Insurance
- Cholamandalam General Insurance
- Employee State Insurance
- Export Credit Guarantee Corporation
- ICICI Lombard General Insurance
- IFFCO-Tokio General Insurance
- National Insurance
- Oriental Insurance
- Peerless Smart Financial
- Royal Sundaram Alliance
- TATA AIG General Insurance

MARKETING –MIX FOR INSURANCE COMPANIES:

The marketing mix is the combination of marketing activities that an organization engages in so as to best meet the needs of its targeted market. The Insurance business deals in selling services and therefore due weight-age in the formation of marketing mix for the Insurance business is needed. The marketing mix includes sub-mixes of the 7 P's of marketing i.e. the product, its price, place, promotion, people, process & physical attraction.

The above mentioned 7 P's can be used for marketing of Insurance products, in the following manner:

1. PRODUCT:

A product means what we produce. If we produce goods, it means tangible product and when we produce or generate services, it means intangible service product.

A product is both what a seller has to sell and a buyer has to buy. Thus, an Insurance company sells services and therefore services are their product.

In India, the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) and the General Insurance Corporation (GIC) are the two leading companies offering insurance services to the users. Apart from offering life insurance policies, they also offer underwriting and consulting services.

When a person or an organization buys an Insurance policy from the insurance company, he not only buys a policy, but along with it the assistance and advice of the agent, the prestige of the insurance company and the facilities of claims and compensation.

It is natural that the users expect a reasonable return for their investment and the insurance companies want to maximize their profitability. Hence, while deciding the product portfolio or the product-mix, the services or the schemes should be motivational. The Group Insurance scheme is required to be

promoted, the Crop Insurance is required to be expanded and the new schemes and policies for the villagers or the rural population are to be included.

The Life Insurance Corporation has intensified efforts to promote urban savings, but as far as rural savings are concerned, it is not that impressive. The introduction of Rural Career Agents Scheme has been found instrumental in inducing the rural prospects but the process is at infant stage and requires more professional excellence. The policy makers are required to activate the efforts. It would be prudent that the LIC is allowed to pursue a policy of direct investment for rural development.

Investment in Government securities should be stopped and the investment should be channelized in private sector for maximizing profits. In short, the formulation of product-mix should be in the face of innovative product strategy. While initiating the innovative process it is necessary to take into consideration the strategies adopted by private and foreign insurance companies. rice Dispersion of Life Insurance Products. Life insurance products like Whole Life or Endowment or Money Back policies have two components: saving and security. Specifically, there is an element that pays even when a policyholder survives the duration the policy is in force. Therefore, the "price" or the premium obscures the protection element offered by such policies. Hence, it is somewhat difficult to compare such products. Many insurance products have additional benefits (called riders). For example, buying bags of fertilizer in villages might include one-year term life benefits. Thus, if a product also riders, it becomes even more difficult to value them because of the embedded options.

The simplest product to compare across sellers is term life. It only has one element. It pays the beneficiary in case the buyer dies within a specific time period. The degree of price dispersion might be expected to decline as the market matures.

2. PRICING:

In the insurance business the pricing decisions are concerned with:

- i) The premium charged against the policies,
- ii) Interest charged for defaulting the payment of premium and credit facility, and
- iii) Commission charged for underwriting and consultancy activities.

With a view of influencing the target market or prospects the formulation of pricing strategy becomes significant. In a developing country like India where the disposable income in the hands of prospects is low, the pricing decision also governs the transformation of potential policyholders into actual policyholders.

The strategies may be high or low pricing keeping in view the level or standard of customers or the policyholders. The pricing in insurance is in the form of premium rates. The three main factors used for determining the premium rates under a life insurance plan are mortality, expense and interest. The premium rates are revised if there are any significant changes in any of these factors.

- Mortality (deaths in a particular area):

When deciding upon the pricing strategy the average rate of mortality is one of the main considerations. In a country like South Africa the threat to life is very important as it is played by host of diseases.

- Expenses:

The cost of processing, commission to agents, reinsurance companies as well as registration are all

incorporated into the cost of installments and premium sum and forms the integral part of the pricing strategy.

- Interest:

The rate of interest is one of the major factors which determines people's willingness to invest in insurance. People would not be willing to put their funds to invest in insurance business if the interest rates provided by the banks or other financial instruments are much greater than the perceived returns from the insurance premiums.

3.PLACE:

This component of the marketing mix is related to two important facets --
 i) Managing the insurance personnel, and
 ii) Locating a branch.

The management of agents and insurance personnel is found significant with the viewpoint of maintaining the norms for offering the services. This is also to process the services to the end user in such a way that a gap between the services- promised and services -- offered is bridged over. In a majority of the service generating organizations, such a gap is found existent which has been instrumental in making worse the image problem. The transformation of potential policyholders to the actual policyholders is a difficult task that depends upon the professional excellence of the personnel. The agents and the rural career agents acting as a link, lack professionalism. The front-line staff and the branch managers also are found not assigning due weight-age to the degeneration process. The insurance personnel if not managed properly would make all efforts insensitive. Even if the policy makers make provision for the quality upgrading the promised services hardly reach to the end users. It is also essential that they have rural orientation and are well aware of the lifestyles of the prospects or users. They are required to be given adequate incentives to show their excellence. While recruiting agents, the branch managers need to prefer local persons and provide them training and conduct seminars. In addition to the agents, the front-line staff also needs an intensive training programmer to focus mainly on behavioral management.

Another important dimension to the Place Mix is related to the location of the insurance branches. While locating branches, the branch manager needs to consider a number of factors, such as smooth accessibility, availability of infrastructural facilities and the management of branch offices and premises. In addition it is also significant to provide safety measures and also factors like office furnishing, civic amenities and facilities, parking facilities and interior office decoration should be given proper attention.

Thus the place management of insurance branch offices needs a new vision, distinct approach and an innovative style. This is essential to make the work place conducive, attractive and proactive for the generation of efficiency among employees. The branch managers need professional excellence to make place decisions productive.

4. PROMOTION:

The insurance services depend on effective promotional measures. In a country like India, the rate of illiteracy is very high and the rural economy has dominance in the national economy. It is essential to have both personal and impersonal promotion strategies. In promoting insurance business, the agents and the rural career agents play an important role. Due attention should be given in selecting the promotional tools for agents and rural career agents and even for the branch managers and front line staff. They also have to be given proper training in order to create impulse buying. Advertising and Publicity, organization of conferences and seminars, incentive to policyholders are impersonal communication. Arranging Kirtans, exhibitions, participation in fairs and festivals, rural wall paintings and publicity drive through the mobile publicity van units would be effective in creating the impulse buying and the rural prospects would be easily transformed into actual policyholders.

5. PEOPLE:

Understanding the customer better allows to design appropriate products. Being a service industry which involves a high level of people interaction, it is very important to use this resource efficiently in order to satisfy customers. Training, development and strong relationships with intermediaries are the key areas to be kept under consideration. Training the employees, use of IT for efficiency, both at the staff and agent level, is one of the important areas to look into.

6. PROCESS:

The process should be customer friendly in insurance industry. The speed and accuracy of payment is of great importance. The processing method should be easy and convenient to the customers. Installment schemes should be streamlined to cater to the ever growing demands of the customers. IT & Data Warehousing will smoothen the process flow. IT will help in servicing large no. of customers efficiently and bring down overheads. Technology can either complement or supplement the channels of distribution cost effectively. It can also help to improve customer service levels. The use of data warehousing management and mining will help to find out the profitability and potential of various customers product segments.

7. PHYSICAL DISTRIBUTION:

Distribution is a key determinant of success for all insurance companies. Today, the nationalized insurers have a large reach and presence in India. Building a distribution network is very expensive and time consuming. If the insurers are willing to take advantage of India's large population and reach a profitable mass of customers, then new distribution avenues and alliances will be necessary.

Initially insurance was looked upon as a complex product with a high advice and service component. Buyers prefer a face-to-face interaction and they place a high premium on brand names and reliability. As the awareness increases, the product becomes simpler and they become off-the-shelf commodity products. Today, various intermediaries, not necessarily insurance companies, are selling insurance. For example, in UK, retailer like Marks & Spencer sells insurance products. The financial services industries have successfully used remote distribution channels such as telephone or internet so as to reach more customers, avoid intermediaries, bring down overheads and increase profitability. A good example is UK insurer Direct Line. It

relied on telephone sales and low pricing. Today, it is one of the largest motor insurance operators. Technology will not replace a distribution network though it will offer advantages like better customer service. Finance companies and banks can emerge as an attractive distribution channel for insurance in India. In Netherlands, financial services firms provide an entire range of products including bank accounts, motor, home and life insurance and pensions. In France, half of the life insurance sales are made through banks.

In India also, banks hope to maximize expensive existing networks by selling a range of products. It is anticipated that rather than formal ownership arrangements, a loose network of alliance between insurers and banks will emerge, popularly known as banc assurance.

Another innovative distribution channel that could be used are the non-financial organizations. For an example, insurance for consumer items like fridge and TV can be offered at the point of sale. This increases the likelihood of insurance sales. Alliances with manufacturers or retailers of consumer goods will be possible and insurance can be one of the various incentives offered.

Insurance in the Rural Sector in 2003. There are two types of obligations of all insurance companies. Rural sector and Social sector obligations.

The requirements are different for life and general business. The requirements also differ depending on the number of years in business

Current Trends

While the insurance sector is seeking to maintain a balance between acquiring customers and developing existing ones, customer acquisition is vital, as no retention strategy will entirely stem customer defection.

That said, insurance companies are experiencing unacceptable levels of customer churn, thanks to which they are focusing on keeping the customers they already have in a bid to ensure a net growth in their customer base.

Today, the focus is on selling more products to existing customers to improve profitability. Customer-focused strategies require CRM (customer relationship management) to help acquire customers thorough various touch points and translate operational data into actionable insights for proactively serving customers.

Vikram G Shah, managing director, Talisma Corporation says, "CRM with BI (Business Intelligence) tools can help insurance firms monitor the ebb and flow of customer behaviour, giving them a holistic 360-degree view of their customers."

Spending on CRM is up

Insurance firms spend close to 12 percent of their IT budgets on CRM software and services. The cost includes operational CRM and spending on BI tools. If A spokesperson of an upcoming insurance firm adds, "Of our total IT budget, we are spending 14 percent on CRM applications." Industry pundits believe that insurance firms are looking for CRM initiatives with budgets ranging from Rs 50 lakh going right up to Rs 3 crore. The sector is busy compiling data on individuals, including their purchasing patterns and buying preferences of policies, pension plans and the like. In many cases, policy renewal marketing to existing customers remains an unsophisticated exercise, often amounting to little more than a request to renew, with no attempt at putting a value proposition before the customer. With a little help from CRM software, insurance firms can sell multiple insurance policies and pension plans to the same customer.

The opportunity is huge

Within the financial services sector, IT investment in insurance is expected to grow the fastest with a CAGR of 35 percent in the five-year forecast period (2001-02 to 2004-05). [Source: IDC India] Other sub-verticals of the financial services sector are expected to grow at a CAGR ranging from 21 to 25 percent. Much of this spending will be on CRM applications and integrating multiple delivery channels. IDC says that new delivery channels are evolving as the insurance market expands.

According to a report from Indian Info line (January 2004), India has the highest number of life insurance policies in force in the world. The industry is pegged at Rs 400 billion in India. Gross premium collections stand at 2 percent of the GDP and this has been growing by 15 to 20 percent per year from the Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) and other government-owned insurers. Privatization has led to new players entering this market and it is expected to grow at a rapid pace. George Varghese, head-Marketing, SAS says, "More than three-fourths of India's insurable population has no life insurance, pension cover and post-retirement protection cover." A substantial part of the insurance market—the portion dealing in pension plans and insurance as an investment option—is protected by a tariff and administered price regime. Competition in pricing is yet to emerge. Once that happens, as with all dynamic customer-oriented service industries such as banking and telecom, the race to gain and retain customer mind share will be on.

Business drivers for CRM

Margins are under pressure: A couple of years ago, LIC dominated the insurance market with the help of its sales force and channels and margins were reasonably high. Today, there are close to 20 companies offering both life and general insurance products. All of them have equally strong international and local partners; all are focusing upon similar geographies and target audiences. The new firms selling life insurance and non-life insurance [pensions, insurance as saving, etc] have failed to emulate the LIC model because margins are getting squeezed. There are several pain areas that new insurance firms face—acquiring new customers, retaining them, cross-selling products and controlling rising costs while providing comprehensive support.

Insurers have added a plethora of products and services to their kitty. These range from insurance as an investment option to pension plans. They target the younger generation in the 20 to 30 years age group. “The convergence of four factors—protection, saving (investment option), loans and pension—has compelled insurance companies to align with banks in reaching out to a larger audience,” says Tikoo. This trend has led to another—insurance companies are joining hands with banks by becoming channel partners for insurance. Tata AIG has a marketing alliance with HSBC, Birla Sun Life has one with Citibank and IDBI and LIC ally with Corporation Bank, while Kotak Life Insurance has an arrangement with Kotak Bank. This strategy helps insurance firms increase their footprint to cover a larger part of the customer base in the 20-30 years demographic. CRM helps connect a bank’s high net worth customers with insurance firms.

- Customer expectations are rising: Customers, faced with a dizzying array of insurance products expect customized offerings, value, ease of access, and personalization from insurers. Today, customers are expecting individual attention, responsiveness, customization and access. At the same time, they don’t want to pay a premium for these services. High customer expectations and lower exit barriers could lead to increased customer attrition.

Where to begin—operational CRM or analytical CRM?

The choice between operational and analytical CRM as a starting point depends upon the insurer’s needs. Gartner says that insurance companies with multiple financial products and a big customer base, such as integrated insurance solution providers, will leverage their customer base to cross- and up-sell different financial products, including insurance. Such providers will benefit from adopting analytical CRM. Market segmentation, campaign management and data mining applications will benefit them in many ways.

- Call centre text mining: This tool can help improve the customer experience by resolving complaints rapidly. Insurers are using these tools to mine text from call centre transcripts to identify issues faced by customers. Text mining tools also help detect and capture other useful pieces of information around a customer’s life stage, financial needs and product interests. These can be used to generate leads and trigger cross-selling. However, to be fully effective, customer service representatives must be trained to probe for information that will help in cross-selling during the text mining phase. Text mining tools are leading-edge today, but are predicted to take off quickly.
- Event-triggering and profiling: “Insurers can use event triggers to generate leads that can be acted upon quickly, usually within 24 hours,” says Tikoo. Event-triggering tools monitor incoming transaction and contact data in near-real-time to recognise changes in a customer’s behaviour or profile to trigger actions or alerts.
- Lead management gets sophisticated: Often the ability of an insurer to generate leads by means of event-triggering, re-engineered touch points and cross line-of-business referral can outstrip their ability to manage said leads. In such a situation, though the number of leads generated rises, the conversion rate does not. It may even drop. CRM can help provide sales representatives with a mechanism to prioritize and manage leads.

Pure insurance providers who do not have a large customer base will derive the maximum value from operational improvements, especially in integrating customer information from multiple channels and sales force automation.

Not all CRM deployments will involve packaged software: Kumar says, "Indian organizations in other verticals have used 'bespoke CRM' solutions and some insurance vendors will do likewise."

Most insurers will look to empower their agents by deploying partner-facing applications. Apart from making agents more productive, it will let insurers keep in touch with customers, otherwise difficult in a primarily channel-driven business.

Vendors and analysts agree that the need to acquire, retain and support customers will stimulate greater investment in CRM, covering customer life cycle management. Insurers who are in an IT catch-up mode have been relatively prosperous during the last 18 to 24 months. Now they are investing in CRM to lock in their gains.

2 Education –The education level i.e. bringing about awareness in the people about the importance of Insurance Companies have put in lot of efforts not only in urban area as well as rural sector.

For that giving detailed information through various Media is a good bet. Companies are also spending a hefty sum on Advertising and trying to convince the prospects through their various creative appeals.

3 Insurance of organs that we had never thought of-Even the stem cells of the womb, tooth can also be insured now. Not only that, there are other organs and parts which are being insured by various Insurance companies. Companies in nut shell are exploring all possible areas where Insurance can be a product to be offered.

4 Making it Affordable-Premium Price-The new concept that has been initiative of few Insurance Companies is that now we can pay the premium on daily basis can also be paid thereby gradually making insurance a product of affordability. Wherein a small sum like Rs3/4 can also be paid to cover certain amount of risks.

Future Trends

- Globally outsourcing industry would continue to grow.
- Following the success of US and UK, more countries in the European Union would outsource their business.
- Technological power shift from the West to the East as India and China emerge as major players.
- Political backlash over outsourcing would come down as companies reap the benefit of outsourcing.

Conclusions

- India is among the important emerging insurance markets in the world. Life insurance will grow very rapidly over the next decades in India.
- The major drivers include sound economic fundamentals, a rising middle-income class, an improving regulatory framework and rising risk awareness.
- The fundamental regulatory changes in the insurance sector in 1999 will be critical for future growth.
- Despite the restriction of 26% on foreign ownership, large foreign insurers have entered the Indian market. State-owned insurance companies still have dominant market positions.
- But, this would probably change over the next decade. In the life sector, new private insurers are bringing in new products to the market.
- They also have used innovative distribution channels to reach a broader range of the population. There is huge in the largely undeveloped private pension market. The same is true for the health insurance business.
- The Indian general insurance segment is still heavily regulated. Three quarters of premiums are generated under the tariff system. Reinsurance in India is mainly provided by the General Insurance Corporation of India, which receives 20% compulsory cessions from other general insurers.
- Finally, the rural sector has potential for both life and general insurance. To realize this potential, designing suitable products is important.
- Insurers will need to pay special attention to the characteristics of the rural labor force, like the prevalence of irregular income streams and preference for simple products.

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Investment Strategy through SIP

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Abstract

A mutual fund is a professionally managed type of collective investment scheme that pools money from many investors and invests it in stocks, bonds, short-term money market instruments.

If you are curious of investing in the stock market because of its unpredictability, it is advisable to play relatively safe with MFs. Output of mutual Fund can be stated as an Empirical Decomposition into Stock Picking Talent, Style, Transactions Costs, and Expenses. You will gain units of the MFs in proportion to the money put in. Each fund has a different approach and goal. In these times of recession, selecting a mutual fund seems to have become a very complex. It is necessary to make smart investment.

The most crucial factor in determining which one is better than the rest is to look at returns. The absolute return that a fund gives over a given period is just the percentage difference between the starting Net Asset Value and the ending Net Asset Value. A systematic Investment Plan is an investment strategy wherein you can invest into a mutual fund at specific intervals over a defined time frame.

This paper discussed about systematic Investment Plan as investment strategy for mutual fund and risk involved. It also discuss about "Multiply Your Wealth with Investors' Protection".

Keyword: mutual fund, SIP, investment, risk

Introduction:

The four-and-a-half decade old Indian Mutual Fund industry is still relatively young as compared to most other economies. The strong growth in Assets under Management (AUM) and the ever increasing number of international asset managers setting up funds in India are testimony to the increasing attractiveness of Indian markets as well as investor confidence in the overall India story. Mutual fund AUM has grown at a rapidly over 2003–08 touching a high of INR 7.2 trillion or USD 154 billion.

Yet, it is estimated that only about 7 percent of the households invest in Mutual Funds, as against more than 50 percent in developed markets like U.S.A. With 37 Asset Management Companies managing over 1000 schemes, the industry offers suitable investment vehicles to all types of investors to suit their requirements and risk-return profiles. With over 1 billion populations on path of economic development, with increasing disposable incomes and financial literacy, there is enough and more to look forward to a robust and sustained growth.

A Mutual Fund is a trust that pools the savings of a number of investors who share a common financial or investment goals which in turns buy assets. The money thus collected is then invested in capital market instruments such as shares, debentures and other securities.

The income earned through these investments and the capital appreciation realized is shared by its unit holders in proportion to the number of units owned by them. Thus a Mutual Fund is the most suitable investment for the common man as it offers an opportunity to invest in a diversified, professionally managed basket of securities at a relatively low cost.

How to invest

Retail investors may not have high risk-taking capacity or requisite acumen and expertise to analyze the stocks directly and regularly monitor the market and the company's performance on day to day basis. Thus MFs offer an opportunity to invest in a diversified well-researched basket of stocks at a relatively low cost hence investing through equity MFs should be the desirable route for retail investors.

One of key advantages that MFs offer includes professional management, affordability, liquidity and convenience. Besides, they are well regulated, transparent and tax efficient hence the investor need not track

the Net Asset Value (NAV) on a daily basis.

Mutual Fund Operation Flow Chart: Working of a Mutual Fund

Fig.1 Organization of a Mutual Fund

Fig.2

Success in the Indian Mutual Fund Industry, in the midst of all the growth that is evident, will depend upon strong distribution network and transparent approach towards trust building and client servicing at retail level will soon assume greater importance.

Types of Mutual Fund Schemes

Wide variety of Mutual Fund Schemes exists to cater to the needs such as financial position, risk tolerance and return expectations etc. below structure gives an overview into the existing types of schemes in the Industry.

- By Structure
 - Open Ended Funds
 - Close Ended Funds
 - Interval funds
- By Investment Objective
 - Growth Funds
 - Income Funds
 - Balanced Funds
 - Money Market Funds
- Special Schemes
 - Industry Specific Schemes
 - Index Schemes
 - Sectoral Schemes

Advantages of MF

The beauty of a mutual fund is that you can buy a mutual fund and obtain instant access to a hundreds of individual stocks or bonds. Otherwise, in order to expand your portfolio, you might have to buy individual securities, which exposes you to more potential volatility

By pooling a lot of stocks (in a stock fund) or bonds (in a bond fund), mutual funds reduce the risk of investing. If one company in that sector has a bad manager, or a losing strategy, it is balanced by other companies that are performing better. This lowers the risk, thanks to diversification.

For example, an energy fund in 2000 that included Enron stock would have declined with Enron's demise, but not nearly as much as those who only had Enron stock...they would have lost their entire investment.

Another example of leading Indian software company satyam's fall in early 2009 had shock the entire country which drastically reduced its stock price until government took the proper measure and then later took over by Mahindra to become satyam Mahindra, Investors would have lost their investment and might take year's to recover that early investment.

MF advantages are listed below

- Professionally Manage & Analysis
- Diversification & Divisibility across Companies & Sectors
- Convenient Administration with Record Keeping
- Potential Returns
- Low Costs of operations (Lower transaction cost)
- Liquidity availability during Entry & Exit at NAV
- Transparency with Regular disclosures
- Flexibility
- Choice of schemes
- Tax benefits
- Well regulated (By SEBI)

Many investors don't have the resources or the time to buy individual stocks. Investing in individual securities, such as stocks, not only takes resources, but a considerable amount of time. It is Mutual fund managers and analysts wake up each morning dedicating their professional lives to researching and analyzing current and potential holdings for their mutual fund. On the other hand, the availability of different types of mutual funds allows you to build a diversified portfolio at low cost and without much difficulty.

Also Mutual Funds Have Audited Track Records for each mutual fund and have them audited for accuracy, which ensures that investors can trust the mutual fund's stated returns. On the safer side, if a mutual fund company goes out of business, mutual fund shareholders receive an amount of cash that equals their portion of ownership in the mutual fund.

So-Called Disadvantages of Mutual Funds

- MF is subject to markets conditions. If your investment is 100% equity exposed and if market fall down

then the value invested will lead to losses. Comparing with other types of investment like PPF, NSC, Fixed/Recurring deposits, government securities, the risk factor is very high in MF. Of course, it depends upon individual risk appetite.

- All Mutual Funds Have High Capital Gains Distributions to investors as a taxable event but not all. ELSS MF allows tax deducted returns. With zero percent entry load from August, 2009 has motivated investors further to invest thru MF.

Systematic Investing and Withdrawals with Mutual Funds

SIP IS NOT MUTUAL FUND BUT ITS INVESTMENT STRATEGY. It's one of the method of investment in systematic way on regular periodic basis. It can be PF, FD, RD, NSC or any other form of investment. Recently the term is more associated with Mutual fund industry. Investor can invest lump sum amount once at a time in MF and/or they can start SIP at specific intervals over a defined time frame either monthly or quarterly.

Through SIP, fixed amount is invested on a regular basis you get more number of units in a falling market and fewer units when the market is on the rise. This will also help you to average out the market fluctuations and the investment will be low cost investment over a period of time. This strategy of investing is also called Rupee Cost Averaging.

SWP is the systematic way you can withdraw amount at specific intervals over a defined time frame either monthly or quarterly or at once. Investment in mutual funds is withdrawn within 12 months of investment then investor needs to pay the exit load of 1% as per the policy or as applicable.

SIP - Systematic Investment Plan and SWP - Systematic Withdrawal Plan

Multiply Your Wealth with Investors' Protection

With the objective of spreading better understanding of the Mutual Fund Industry as an appropriate investment avenue for wealth creation and best investment practices and investors' protection through SIP.

Following are the key points where MF industry needs to focus.

- ✓ Increase Awareness of Mutual Fund Industry through SIP.
- ✓ Protecting & promoting interest of Investors with high returns.
- ✓ Challenges before Asset Management Companies.
- ✓ Emerging Market trends & Opportunities in global market.
- ✓ Portfolio Diversification & Risks Associated with MF Investment.
- ✓ Evolving Principles of Fund Governance through SIP
- ✓ Asset Allocation – The model that suits the Investor.
- ✓ Mutual Fund – Basics Structure, Standards & Disclosures.
- ✓ Sustain Investor Confidence in Mutual Funds through SIP

How to invest in SIP and Multiply Your Wealth over a specific time frame

- It is simple to invest regularly in a mutual fund. The SIP option is available with all types of funds like equity, Debts, income. Fig.3
- Investors can invest as little as Rs.500 per month directly into a mutual fund
- If an investor wants to invest more than Rs.500 or Rs.1000 in any given month then he will have to fill a new a form for SIP intimating the fund that he is changing his SIP structure. Also he will be allowed to change the SIP structure only in the multiples of the SIP amount.
- The investor can get out of the fund i.e. redeem his units any time irrespective of whether he has completed his minimum investment in that scheme. In such a case his post-dated cheques will be returned back to him. Exit load as applicable.
- ECS (Electronic clearance service) option is easily available but if investor wants stop investing, investor has give in written to stop the ECS correspondence.

Example:

Following example shows how SIP work out in the period of recession.

Let's say, X person starts investing in SIP from January 2008 in ABC mutual fund –growth. Please find the

illustration as given below:

Date	SIP Amount	NAV	Units	Sensex
Jan 10, 2008	1000	94.17	10.62	20582
Feb 11, 2008	1000	74.59	13.41	16630
Mar 10, 2008	1000	73.51	13.6	15923
Apr 10, 2008	1000	72.73	13.75	15695
May 12, 2008	1000	77.32	12.93	16860
Jun 10, 2008	1000	71.2	14.05	14889
Jul 10, 2008	1000	66.7	14.99	13926
Aug 11, 2008	1000	72.7	13.76	15503
Sep 10, 2008	1000	70.03	14.28	14662
Oct 10, 2008	1000	56.22	17.79	10527
Nov 10, 2008	1000	54.99	18.19	10536
Dec 10, 2008	1000	51.21	19.53	9654
Jan 12, 2009	1000	51.07	19.58	9110
Feb 10, 2009	1000	52.82	18.93	9647
Mar 12, 2009	1000	48.64	20.56	8343
Apr 13, 2009	1000	57.77	17.31	10967
May 11, 2009	1000	58.57	17.07	11682
Summary				
Amount Invested				17000
Units Accumulated				270.34

Sensex Value (27/5/09)	14109
*NAV (27/5/09)	70.05
Investment Value (27/5/09)	18937.51
Absolute Return (%)	11.40%

* NAV: The Net Asset Value is the price of a unit of a fund

If you observe the above figure which is true. It's a real magic in spite of recession and market being down for some time, the X person was able to derived 11.40% returns on his SIP investment which is good financial achievement.

Fig.4 Chart showing returns on investment of MF via SIP)

Reviewing the Growing Market for Mutual Funds in India

The mutual fund industry has passed through many phases since UTI phase of 1964, public sector phase of 1987, emergence phase of 2003 when international players came to India and finally the new generation phase of 2007 where new players expanded the market.

Indian households have stepped up their exposure to the capital market. The contribution of funds in this asset class has increased. In fact, there has been more than 2000 per cent growth in the assets coming to MFs in the last 3 years

The scenario is most likely to change with everyone expanding and getting involved in SIP way. Changing investors profile has initiated many market players to innovate new products matching the investor's profile. As economy grows at a spectacular rate, there is a huge wealth creating opportunities surfacing everywhere

A recent study by Invest India reveals that there are about 32.18 crores paid workers in India. Of this only 53 lakh have an exposure to mutual funds? This is less than 2 per cent of the total workforce. Even more interesting fact is that 77 per cent of them reside in super metros and Tier I cities .Again, about 40 lakh come in the Rs 90,000 – Rs 5 lakh income bracket. The penetration among the less than Rs 90,000 and more than Rs 5 lakh income bracket is very low. The need for the hour is to expand the market boundaries and scope in Tier II and Tier III cities.

The need of the investor populace has changed, resulting in a change in asset management styles leading to the design of new and competitively-priced products, implying greater emphasis on higher quality resulting in an opportunity and a challenge.

Conclusion

Investment in mutual funds is key to multiple your wealth. Those who cannot invest lump sum and still expect financial growth has the option called SIP on monthly or quarterly basis.

We can say that in one time investment if you buy units of fund at high NAV and if the market dips after that, the value of your investments goes down and to get return of your investment you may have to wait for a long time. But, if you invest via a SIP, you don't have to worry because you do not commit the error of buying units when the market is at its peak. Through SIP you are buying small amounts of units continuously, therefore your investment will average out over a period of time. At the end you will have some units at a high cost and

some units a lower cost. Over time, your chances of making a profit are much higher when compared to a one-time investment.

SIP is one of the simplest, safe and most reliable ways for an investor to improve odds of investment and to get absolute returns. But investor should think for a period of at least for time frame of three years because it pays to invest in a longer run.

At the end, I would suggest and recommend "Investing in equity MFs through SIP is the best option".

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“An Analysis of Satisfaction Level of Customers with regards to Life Insurance Services”

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INTRODUCTION

The story of insurance is probably as old as the story of mankind. The same instinct that prompts modern businessmen today to secure themselves against loss and disaster existed in primitive men also. They too sought to avert the evil consequences of fire and flood and loss of life and were willing to make some sort of sacrifice in order to achieve security. Though the concept of insurance is largely a development of the recent past, particularly after the industrial era – past few centuries – yet its beginnings date back almost 6000 years.

Life Insurance in its modern form came to India from England in the year 1818. Oriental Life Insurance Company started by Europeans in Calcutta was the first life insurance company on Indian Soil. All the insurance companies established during that period were brought up with the purpose of looking after the needs of European community and Indian natives were not being insured by these companies. However, later with the efforts of eminent people like Babu Muttylal Seal, the foreign life insurance companies started insuring Indian lives. But Indian lives were being treated as sub-standard lives and heavy extra premiums were being charged on them. Bombay Mutual Life Assurance Society heralded the birth of first Indian life insurance company in the year 1870, and covered Indian lives at normal rates. Starting as Indian enterprise with highly patriotic motives, insurance companies came into existence to carry the message of insurance and social security through insurance to various sectors of society. Bharat Insurance Company (1896) was also one of such companies inspired by nationalism. The Swadeshi movement of 1905-1907 gave rise to more insurance companies.

The United India in Madras, National Indian and National Insurance in Calcutta and the Co-operative Assurance at Lahore were established in 1906. In 1907, Hindustan Co-operative Insurance Company took its birth in one of the rooms of the Jorasanko, house of the great poet Rabindranath Tagore, in Calcutta. The Indian Mercantile, General Assurance and Swadeshi Life (later Bombay Life) were some of the companies established during the same period. Prior to 1912 India had no legislation to regulate insurance business. In the year 1912, the Life Insurance Companies Act, and the Provident Fund Act were passed. The Life Insurance Companies Act, 1912 made it necessary that the premium rate tables and periodical valuations of companies should be certified by an actuary. But the Act discriminated between foreign and Indian companies on many accounts, putting the Indian companies at a disadvantage.

The first two decades of the twentieth century saw lot of growth in insurance business. From 44 companies with total business-in-force as Rs.22.44 crore, it rose to 176 companies with total business-in-force as Rs.298 crore in 1938. During the mushrooming of insurance companies many financially unsound concerns were also floated which failed miserably. The Insurance Act 1938 was the first legislation governing not only life insurance but also non-life insurance to provide strict state control over insurance business.

The demand for nationalization of life insurance industry was made repeatedly in the past but it gathered momentum in 1944 when a bill to amend the Life Insurance Act 1938 was introduced in the Legislative Assembly. However, it was much later on the 19th of January, 1956, that life insurance in India was nationalized. About 154 Indian insurance companies, 16 non-Indian companies and 75 provident were operating in India at the time of nationalization. Nationalization was accomplished in two stages; initially the management of the companies was taken over by means of an Ordinance, and later, the ownership too by means of a comprehensive bill. The Parliament of India passed the Life Insurance Corporation Act on the 19th of June 1956, and the Life Insurance Corporation of India was created on 1st September, 1956, with the objective of spreading life insurance much more widely and in particular to the rural areas with a view to reach all insurable persons in the country, providing them adequate financial cover at a reasonable cost.

Indian insurance sector is likely to register unprecedented growth of 200% and attain a size of Rs. 2000 billion (\$51.2 billion) by 2009-10, in which a private sector insurance business will achieve a growth rate of 140% as a result of aggressive marketing technique being adopted by them against 35-40% growth rate of state owned insurance companies. The aforesaid findings are made by The Associated Chambers of Commerce and Industry of India (ASSOCHAM) on 'Insurance in Next 2 Years', saying that in the last couple of years, the insurance sector has grown by CAGR of around 175% and the trend will emerge still better because of potential factor. Currently, the insurance sector size is estimated at Rs.500 billion (\$12.8 billion).

Releasing the ASSOCHAM findings, its President, Mr. Venugopal N. Dhoot said that on account of intense marketing strategies adopted by private insurance players, the market share of state owned insurance companies like GIC, LIC and others have come down to 70% in last 4-5 years from over 97%. The private insurance players despite the sector is still regulated has been offering rate of return (RoR) to its policy holders which is estimated at about 35% as against 20% of domestic insurance companies. This factor is mainly responsible for hike in private insurance market share which will grow further which is why the ASSOCHAM estimates that its growth rate could even exceed 140%.

Secondly, the state owned insurance companies such as LIC and GIC have limited number of policies to offer to their subscribers while in case of private insurance companies, their policy numbers are many more and the premium amount as well as the maturity period is much competitive as against those of government

insurance companies. Interestingly, said Mr. Dhoot that the private sector insurance players have started exploring the rural markets in which until recently, the state owned companies had the monopoly.

The Chamber has projected that in rural markets, the share of private insurance players would increase substantially as these have been able to generate a faith among their rural consumers. Estimating the potential of the Indian insurance market from the perspective of macro-economic variables such as the ratio of premium to GDP, ASSOCHAM reveals that India's life insurance premium, as a percentage of GDP is 1.8% against 5.2% in the US, 6.5% in the UK or 8% in South Korea. ASSOCHAM findings further reveal that in the coming years, the corporate segment, as a whole will not be a big growth area for insurance companies. This is because penetration is already good and companies receive good services. In both volumes and profitability therefore, the scope for expansion is modest. The Chamber has suggested that insurer's strategy should be to stimulate demand in areas that are currently not served at all. Insurance companies mostly focus on manufacturing sector; however, the services sector is taking a large and growing share of India's GDP. This offers immense opportunities for expansion opportunities.

Only 20% of the total insurable population of India is covered under various life insurance schemes (2008), the penetration rates of health and other non-life insurances in India is also well below the international level. These facts indicate the immense growth of the insurance sector. Innovative products, smart marketing, and aggressive distribution have enabled fledgling private insurance companies to sign up Indian customers faster than anyone expected. Indians, who had always seen life insurance as a tax saving device, are now suddenly turning to the private sector and snapping up the new innovative products on offer.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To evaluate satisfaction level of customers of life insurance service providers.
2. To know, how life insurance service providers can increase satisfaction level of customers.
3. To find out, how life insurance service providers can attract new customers.
4. To study the buying behaviour of customers of life insurance service providers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was based on both primary and secondary data.

DATA SOURCE

Secondary Data-

Secondary data were collected from books, journals, magazines, newspapers, websites and other published sources available in Pune.

Primary Data-

Utilizing the information from the secondary data, a questionnaire was prepared to study the satisfaction level of customers with regards to life insurance services. This questionnaire was tested by conducting a pilot study of a few customers on random basis. Utilizing the insight from pilot study, questionnaire was modified for the final study. This primary data was collected from customers of Life Insurance Corporation of India.

Type of Research-

Both Descriptive and exploratory research were used in compiling this study. While exploratory research helped in developing the hypotheses through the analysis of secondary data, descriptive research was used in order to study the satisfaction level of customers with regards to life insurance services.

Research Approach-

Survey method was employed to carry out this study through printed questionnaires.

Research Instruments-

A questionnaire was used to study the satisfaction level of customers with regards to life insurance services.

Contact Method- Personal Interview.

Location of Research-

Chinchwad and Akurdi region of Pune, Maharashtra, India.

Research Hypothesis-

- Customers are satisfied with different services rendered by life insurance service providers.
- Strategies of life insurance service providers are successful in attracting the customers.

Test Applied-

Kolmogorov-Smirnov One sample test is applied to know degree of satisfaction. It is similar to Chi Square Test, test of goodness to fit.

SAMPLING PLAN

Sampling Frame-

Customers of Life Insurance Corporation of India were selected on random basis from their customers when visited Premier Plaza Shopping Mall (Chinchwad) and Jay Ganesh Fame (Akurdi) on week days. The questionnaires were distributed simultaneously among 200 respondents during August 2009.

Sampling Procedure-

Survey was done in all seven days but, we specially surveyed on Saturday and Sunday.

Sample Size-

A sample size of 200 respondents has been taken randomly for the study the satisfaction level of customers with regards to life insurance services.

Sampling Technique

For the purpose of this survey, Random Sampling of Probability Sampling Technique has employed as it gives every unit of the population a known and non-zero probability of being selected.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- Study was limited to a few customers selected on random basis of life insurance service providers.
- Frauds/fault in giving the right information can not be neglected.
- For want of time and resources the study was confined to the only a selected region of Pune.

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATION/SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study can be justified in the following ways:

- The study provides information about the satisfaction level of existing customer of the life insurance service providers.
- The study provides information about the problem of customers and their possible solutions.
- The study provides information for the improvements required in the services provided by life insurance service providers.
- The study helps the management of life insurance service providers to formulate their strategies to attract new customers and to increase the satisfaction level of customers.
- The study will further prove to be of great help to the researchers/management students who want to do similar or related study in the future.

FINDINGS

The study indicated that:

- 56% respondents had the plan/policy of LIC. Because I found 200 positive response out of 356. These positive respondents hired the services of LIC due to the reasons like- Public sector company(73%), Good customer services(36%), Easy insurance process(41%), Variety of services(66%), Easy term and conditions of the policy(54%), Easy claim settlement(17%), After sale services(61%), Attitude and behavior of employees(78%), EMI of the policies(84%), and Benefits of the policy(67%).
- 66% of the total customers were male and 34% were female. Out of 66% of the male customers 89% customers were working and 72% customers took purchase making decision in their family. And out of 34% of the female customers 49% were working and 57% customers took purchase making decision in their family.
- Out of 76% working customers of LIC 37% were Govt. employee, 26% were Pvt. Employee, 32% had their own business and only 5% were in other group.
- 66% customers of the total customers of LIC were found under the age group 31 to 60. 85% customers of total customers were married. 71% customers of the total customers were graduate and postgraduate. 84% customers fell in annual income group of more than Rs. 1 lakh.
- 66% customers influenced their self, 77% by their family members, 70% by neighbors/friends/relatives, only 26% by advertising and only 5% by others like consultant.
- 68% of the total customers of LIC collected the information and remaining purchased randomly. 81% customers collected information about product & services from advertising, 75% from family members, 67% from neighbors, friends, and relatives, etc while making purchase decision. Out of 81% of total customers who collected information from advertising, 93% customers used television, 88% news paper, 50% magazines, 25% pamphlets and 19% other sources for collecting the information.
- 57% customers were brand conscious, 32% customers were price conscious and remaining were interested in discounts, schemes and others.

- 40% of the total customers of the LIC had policy of other company also. Out of this 40% 39% customers had a policy of Public Sector Company and remaining had policy of Private Sector Company. And 60% customers were loyal.
- Only 36% customers had health plans, 3% unit plans, 32% pension plans, 27% joint life plans, 7% term assurance plans, 9% whole life plans, 2% special money back plans for women, 4% money back plans, 18% endowment plans and 23% children's plans.
(Values in percentage are approximate)

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

In this study two hypothesis were used. First was "customers are satisfied with different services rendered by the insurance service providers." To find out the degree of satisfaction, Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample Test was applied on data collected from customers. Result indicated that with most of the services, customers were satisfied with different services provided by insurance service providers. So we can say that this hypothesis is proved to be positive. And second hypothesis was "strategies of insurance service providers are successful in attracting the customers." As I stated above with most of the services, customers were satisfied with different services provided by insurance service providers. This showed that- these insurance service providers were more efficient to attract the customers because they know customer satisfaction is important in reinforcing customers' trust, commitment, repurchase intentions and financial performance. So they formulated more attractive strategies for customers to be successful in their trade. That's why this hypothesis is also proved to be positive.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of this whole study, the following suggestions are made-

- In today marketing scenario customer in the king. And CRM is a key of success. These insurance service providers should use CRM approach.
- To make aware large number of customers insurance service providers should also use IMC tools. Still most of the insurance service providers are using only traditional promotional tools for the communication to the final consumers.
- Role of the women is changing a lot in the family because of increasing working women population, now they are not only managing house but also taking purchase making decision in their family. So insurance service providers should take care of them.
- In the study I observe that customers were not happy with some services like claim settlement period and procedure, information provided against their queries, term and conditions of the policy. So insurance service providers should pay more attention on these services for the improvements.

- Some innovative strategies are essential for effective delivery and targeting to the consumers like innovative product and services, smart marketing and aggressive promotion and distribution.

CONCLUSIONS

Insurance is one major sector which has been on a continuous growth curve since the revival of the Indian economy. Taking into account the huge population and growing per capita income besides several other driving factors, a huge opportunity is in store for the insurance companies in India. According to the latest research findings, nearly 80% of Indian population is without life insurance cover (2008).

Today, Insurance is much more than mere tax saving device. It is about reflecting customer's desires and aspirations, and forging long lasting relationship with them. The concept of hiring insurance services has undergone a change in terms of format and customer buying behaviour.

Insurance industry is going through a transaction, not only in India but also the world over. The recent development in insurance sector in India provides a new experience to both customers and insurance service providers. The industry is in for huge challenges in terms of targeting customers because of different and changing customer behaviour regularly. Ensuring the implementation of efficient and innovative strategies at right time, these insurance service providers can take better advantages of opportunities.

In the today marketing scenario consumer is the king. And his satisfaction should be prime goal/function of insurance service providers. They should not stop at the satisfaction level. They should regularly increase the satisfaction level to make the customers delighted. When customer will delight with the different services provided by insurance service providers, they will not be only loyal but also they will share their positive view with others. Role of the women is changing a lot in the family because of increasing working women population, now they are not only managing house but also taking purchase making decision in their family.

Some innovative strategies are essential for effective delivery and targeting to the consumers like innovative product and services, smart marketing and aggressive promotion and distribution. Customer's expectations are very high from the insurance service providers. Insurance service providers have to live up to these expectations in order to flourish, prosper and grow in the Indian market.

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On Foreign Exchange Risk Management

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Objective of the study

To understand how foreign exchange market— operates and the various types of risk involved in it.

To understand— the reasons for hedging and the techniques used to hedge the foreign exchange risk.

To understand what went wrong with Companies which made them to— take their bankers to Court

FOREIGN EXCHANGE MARKET IN INDIA

The foreign exchange market in India started in earnest less than three decades ago when in 1978 the government allowed banks to trade foreign exchange with one another. The foreign exchange market in India is growing very rapidly. The annual turnover of the market is more than \$400 billion. This transaction does not include the inter-bank transactions. According to the record of transactions released by RBI, the average monthly turnover in the merchant segment was \$40.5 billion in 2003-04 and the inter-bank transaction was \$134.2 for the same period. The average total monthly turnover was about \$174.7 billion for the same period. The transactions are made on spot and also on the basis of forward which include currency swaps and interest rate swaps. The Indian foreign exchange market consists of the buyers, sellers, market intermediaries and the monetary authority of India. The main center of foreign exchange transactions in India is Mumbai, the commercial capital of the country. There are several other centers for foreign exchange transactions in the country including Kolkata, New Delhi, Chennai, Bangalore, Pondicherry and Cochin. In past, due to lack of communication facilities all these markets were not linked. But with the development of technologies, all the foreign exchange markets of India are working collectively. The foreign exchange market India is regulated by the Reserve Bank of India through the Exchange Control Department. At the same time, Foreign Exchange Dealers Association (voluntary association) also provides some help in regulating the market. The Authorized Dealers (Authorized by the RBI) and the accredited brokers are eligible to participate in the foreign Exchange market in India. When the foreign exchange trade is going on between Authorized Dealers and RBI or between the Authorized Dealers and the overseas banks, the brokers have no role to play.

Apart from the Authorized Dealers and brokers, there are some others who are provided with the restricted rights to accept the foreign currency or travelers' cheque. Among these, there are the authorized money changers, travel agents, certain hotels and government shops. The IDBI and EXIM bank are also permitted conditionally to hold foreign currency. The whole foreign exchange market in India is regulated by the Foreign Exchange Management Act, 1999 or FEMA. Before this act was introduced, the market was regulated by the FERA or Foreign Exchange Regulation Act, 1947. After independence, FERA was introduced as a temporary measure to regulate the inflow of the foreign capital. But with the economic and industrial development, the

need for conservation of foreign currency was felt and on the recommendation of the Public Accounts Committee, the Indian government passed the Foreign Exchange Regulation Act, 1973 and gradually, this act became famous as FEMA.

Market size and liquidity

The foreign exchange market is unique because of

Its trading volumes

The extreme liquidity of the market,

Its geographical dispersion

Its long trading hours: 24 hours a day except on weekends (from 22:00 UTC on Sunday until 22:00 UTC Friday),

INTRODUCTION TO DERIVATIVES

A Derivative is a financial instrument that is derived from some other asset, index, event, value or condition (known as the underlying). Anything that can be measured can serve as the underlying to a derivative. These contracts are legally binding agreements, made on the trading screen of the stock exchanges, to buy or sell an asset in future. The asset can be a share, index, interest rate, bond, rupee dollar exchange rate, sugar, crude oil, soyabean, cotton, coffee etc. Rather than trade or exchange the underlying itself, derivative traders enter into an agreement to exchange cash or assets over time based on the underlying. A simple example is a futures contract: an agreement to exchange the underlying asset at a future date. Derivatives help to improve market efficiencies because risks can be isolated and sold to those who are willing to accept them at the least cost. Using derivatives breaks risk into pieces that can be managed independently. From a market-oriented perspective, derivatives offer the free trading of financial risks.

Derivatives are often leveraged, such that a small movement in the underlying value can cause a large difference in the value of the derivative. Derivatives can be used by investors to speculate and make a profit if the value of the underlying moves the way they expect (e.g. moves in a given direction, stays in or out of a specified range, reaches a certain level). Alternatively, traders can use derivatives to hedge or mitigate risk in the underlying, by entering into a derivative contract whose value moves in the opposite direction to their underlying position and cancels part or all of it out.

Derivatives are usually broadly categorized by:

The relationship between the underlying and the derivative (e.g. forward, option, swap)

The type of underlying (e.g. Equity derivatives, FX derivatives, credit derivatives)

The market in which they trade (e.g. exchange traded or over-the-counter)

Who are the operators in the derivatives market?

- Hedgers - Operators, who want to transfer a risk component of their portfolio.
- Speculators - Operators, who intentionally take the risk from hedgers in pursuit of profit.
- Arbitrageurs - Operators who operate in the different markets simultaneously, in pursuit of profit and eliminate mis-pricing

Derivatives Markets

Derivatives markets broadly can be classified into two categories, those that are traded on the exchange and those traded one to one or 'over the counter'. They are hence known as

- OTC Derivatives (Over The Counter).
- Exchange Traded Derivatives.

RISKS INVOLVED IN DERIVATIVE BUSINES INCLUDE:

Credit Risk

This is the risk of failure of a counterparty to perform its obligation as per the contract. Also known as default or counterparty risk, it differs with different instruments.

Market Risk

Market risk is a risk of financial loss as a result of adverse movements of prices of the underlying asset/instrument

Liquidity Risk

The inability of a firm to arrange a transaction at prevailing market prices is termed as liquidity risk. A firm faces two types of liquidity risks

1. Related to liquidity of separate products
2. Related to the funding of activities of the firm including derivatives.

Legal Risk

Derivatives cut across judicial boundaries, therefore the legal aspects associated with the deal should be looked into carefully.

Operational Risk

Operational risk is the risk arising out of some operational difficulties, like, failure of electricity, due to which it becomes difficult to operate in the market.

Hedging

A technique designed to eliminate or reduce risk.

Derivatives allow risk about the price of the underlying asset to be transferred from one party to another. For example, a wheat farmer and miller could sign a futures contract to exchange a specified amount of cash for a specified amount of wheat in the future. Both parties have reduced a future risk: for the wheat farmer, the

uncertainty of the price, and for the miller the availability of wheat. However there is still the risk that no wheat will be available due to causes unspecified by contract like the weather or that one party will renege on the contract. Although, a third party called a clearing house, insures a futures contract, not all derivatives are insured against counterparty risk.

From another perspective, the farmer and the miller both reduce a risk and acquire a risk when they sign the futures contract: The farmer reduces the risk that the price of wheat will fall below the price specified in the contract and acquires the risk that the price of wheat will rise above the price specified in the contract (thereby losing additional income

that he could have earned.) The miller, on the other hand, acquires the risk that the price of wheat will fall below the price specified in the contract (thereby paying more in the future that he otherwise would) and reduces the risk that the price of wheat will rise above the price specified in the contract. In this sense, one party is the insurer (risk taker) for one type of risk, and the counterparty is the insurer (risk taker) for another type of risk.

Hedging also occurs when an individual or institution buys an asset (like a commodity, a bond that has coupon payments, a stock that pays dividend, and so on) sells it using a futures contract. The individual or institution has access to the asset for a specified amount of time, and then can sell it in the future at a specified price according to the futures contract. Of course, this allows the individual or institution the benefit of holding while reducing the risk that the future selling price will deviate unexpectedly from the market's current assessment of the future value of the asset..

Speculation and arbitrage

Derivatives can be used to acquire risk, rather than to insure or to hedge against risk. Thus, some individuals and institutions will enter into a derivative contract to speculate on the value of the underlying asset, betting that the party seeking insurance will be wrong about the future value of the underlying asset. Speculators will want to be able to buy an asset in the future at a low price according to a derivative contract when the future market price is high, or to sell an asset in the future at a high price according to a derivative contract when the future market price is low.

Individuals and institutions may also look for arbitrage opportunities, as when the current buying price of an asset falls below the price specified in a futures contract to sell the asset

Tools of Exchange Risk Management

Risk management is met through internal and external hedging as under

Internal Methods

Currency of Billing

In this method risk is eliminated by contracting the sale transactions in the home currency.

Leading, Lagging and Matching

This is possible if the Corporate unit has a stream of exports & imports, resulting in both payment as well as receipt of foreign currency. It is possible to match the export and import schedules to provide for matching funds flow in either direction.

Currency Hold Accounts

It is a method of opening a foreign currency account and depositing export earnings and other exchange receipts in the said account, to generate risk-free funds for payment of the imports.

Lending and borrowing methods:

In this method a Company which has to make a foreign exchange payment at a future date and wishes to avoid a possible appreciation of exchange rate can buy Dollars at the current spot rate and invest the money by lending or depositing in a foreign currency account, up to the date of payment, to be used at the time of payment.

External Methods (Derivatives)

Forwards:

A forward contract is a customized contract between two entities, where settlement takes place on a specific date in the future at today's pre-agreed price. The rupee-dollar exchange rate is a big forward contract market in India with banks, financial institutions, corporate and exporters being the market participants.

Swaps:

Swaps are private agreements between two parties to exchange cash flows in the future according to a prearranged formula. They can be regarded as portfolios of forward contracts. The two commonly used swaps are:

- Interest rate swaps: These entail swapping only the interest related cash flow between the parties in the same currency.
- Currency swaps: These entail swapping both principal and interest between the parties, with the cash flows in one direction being in a different currency than those in the opposite direction.

Swaptions:

Swaptions are options to buy or sell a swap that will become operative at the expiry of the options. Thus a swaption is an option on a forward swap. Rather than have calls and puts, the swaptions market has receiver swaptions and payer swaptions. A receiver swaption is an option to receive fixed and pay floating. A payer swaption is an option to pay fixed and receive floating. For example, the holder of a swaption has the right, but not the obligation, to enter into a swap on or before a specified future date.

Futures:

A futures contract is an agreement between two parties to buy or sell an asset at a certain time in the future at a certain price. Futures contracts are special types of forward contracts in the sense that the former are standardized exchange-traded contracts.

Options:

Options are contracts that give the buyers the right (but not the obligation) to buy or sell a specified quantity of certain underlying asset at a specified price on or before a specified date. On the other hand, the seller is under obligation to perform the contract (buy or sell the underlying). Options are of two types - calls and puts. Calls give the buyer the right but not the obligation to buy a given quantity of the underlying asset, at a given price on or before a given future date. Puts give the buyer the right, but not the obligation to sell a given quantity of the underlying asset at a given price on or before a given date.

Options:

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Financial Turmoil & Derivatives

The beginnings of India's controversial derivatives muddle can be traced back to a period of extraordinary and beguiling calm in the global financial markets. But it was actually the calm before a storm that has sunk many ships.

The International Monetary Fund (IMF) had noted in the April 2006 edition of its Global Financial Stability Report: "Low nominal and real interest rates and the environment of low volatility...has continued to encourage risk-taking and leverage." A four-year global economic boom that was aided by low borrowing costs had lulled bankers, investors and company treasurers around the world into believing that a few extra risks would do no harm.

There was another factor at play in India. The sharp rise in the rupee after April 2007 had eaten into the profits of many small exporters. Exporters tried to protect their earnings by going in for exotic foreign exchange derivatives.

The sub prime crisis had already reared its ugly head in the US mortgage markets. But the overall outlook appeared sanguine. So it seemed safe to make all sorts of risky derivative bets.

And then a lot of things went horribly wrong. The credit crisis struck in August. By the end of the year, large parts of the Western financial markets were shut for business, central banks were doing stuff they had never done before to save embattled financiers, and currencies, bonds and equities were bouncing off in completely unexpected directions.

Twelve months later, in April, many Indian companies and banks are battling each other in the courts to decide whether various derivative deals are within the law.

Losses Suffered by Wockhardht due to the derivative instruments

The carry trade was officially unwinding, if not coming to an outright end; the result was that the Yen was belatedly joining the ranks of the rest of the world's major currencies, which have risen tremendously against the Dollar. The reason for the sudden weakness in the carry trade (i.e. Yen strength) was volatility. The US "credit crunch" began to significantly affect US bond and stock market valuations almost four months ago, but the full impact still hasn't been felt.

The low-yielding Japanese currency tends to do well in times of risk aversion because investors unwind carry trades that use cheaply borrowed yen to buy higher-yielding currencies. Strengthening of yen has affected Wockhardht In December 2006, Wockhardt had two contracts on outstanding currency swaps, in addition to forward exchange contracts, to hedge against fluctuations in changes in exchange rate and interest rate changes, one with a notional principal of 4,158million yen (Rs166.32 crore then) and the other with a notional principal of Rs154.87 crore. During 2006, Wockhardt had foreign currency exposure to the tune of Rs1,367 crore, which had not been hedged. Wockhardt's troubles began after it took a Rs 1,600-crore hit on foreign currency derivatives. As the company defaulted, some of the banks froze the derivative outstanding and initiated arbitration proceedings abroad .Of the Rs 1,600-crore derivative exposure, Rs 700 crore is with Indian banks and the balance with foreign banks. Till now, foreign banks have crystallised around Rs 500 crore of derivative exposure. Even though sources close to the company said these were crystallised at the highest rates, foreign banks complained they were treated worse than unsecured creditors. But local banks said their foreign counterparts have been given a similar treatment as Indian banks on derivative exposure. Besides the derivative liability, Wockhardt lenders also proposed to restructure Rs 1,500 crore of domestic loans, \$110 of million FCCBs and \$250 million of external commercial borrowing. According to the CDR terms, Wockhardt will sell assets and raise Rs 790 crore to be repaid to lenders by 2015. The Khorakiwala family, the promoters of Wockhardt, has also agreed to bring in Rs 70 crore in the next one year. Wockhardt has already sold its German subsidiary Esparma to Lindopharm in June this year. This was followed by the divestment of its animal healthcare business to French veterinary drug maker Vetsya for about Rs 200 crore in the same month. In August, Wockhardt promoters sold 10 hospitals (including two Greenfield projects under construction) to Fortis Healthcare for Rs 909 crore. Till date the company has brought in Rs 680 crore through sale proceeds of different units. Some of the lenders to the company include SBI, ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank, Punjab National Bank, Corporation Bank, HSBC, Citi, StanChart, Calyon, Abn Amro, DBS, Deutsche Bank and ING Vysya Bank. Debt-ridden pharmaceutical company Wockhardt Ltd and its Singapore-based lender DBS Bank Ltd have agreed to an out-of-court settlement of a dispute over loans Wockhardt had taken from DBS as on 30.11.09.

Wockhardt will settle the loan at a 19 per cent discount, paying Rs37 crore to DBS, according to the terms of

the consent decree signed on Saturday.

Derivative deal between Sundaram Multipap Ltd and ICICI Bank Ltd

Sundaram, which has no business in Switzerland, paid nothing on Oct. 24 when it bought a contract betting on the Swiss franc's value against the dollar. On that day, the franc traded for 1.17 to the dollar, according to data compiled by Bloomberg.

The contract guaranteed Sundaram \$36,000 as long as the franc was valued at more than 1.23 to the dollar within a month, according to the company's lawsuit. If the Swiss currency appreciated past 1.095, a record high, in three months, Sundaram would have to buy \$6 million at 1.23 francs to the dollar.

The franc rose to 1.08 on Nov. 20 as concerns about a U.S. recession lured traders to the Swiss currency. A second contract with a \$22,000 potential profit also turned into a loser, forcing Sundaram to buy an additional \$7.5 million at 1.23.

ICICI demanded 60 million rupees, more than Sundaram's annual profit, to cover the losses.

Refusal to Pay

After Chairman Amrut Shah refused to pay, the bank threatened to force Sundaram into bankruptcy and liquidate the company, Shah said in an interview.

In response, Shah filed his lawsuit accusing ICICI of not adhering to the central bank's guidelines about explaining the risks of derivatives.

While Mehta was removed from his post after the losses came to light, Shah doesn't blame his former finance chief for the possible closure of his firm, which he started as a bookbinder 25 years ago with a few thousand rupees

Payoff & summary of deal between ICICI Bank & Sundaram Multipap Ltd.:

	A	B	C	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q
1	Deal No	Trn Date	Expiry	B/S	C/P	PRC/STK	BRW_NOMU1	QTY. NOMINAL	BRW_NOMU2	BRW_NOM2	TYPE	BRW_SDTE	MARKET INDEX	Barrier	Pay Off	Unwind Date
2	196370	24.10.07	24.01.08	B	C	1.23	CHF	7380000	USD	6000000	BAR	28.01.08	USD/CHF	1.23 up & out 24 Oct '07 to 24 Jan '08	19700000	31.12.07
3	196372	24.10.07	24.01.08	S	C	1.23	CHF	7380000	USD	6000000	BAR2	28.01.08	USD/CHF	1.095 to 1.23, 24 Oct '07 to 24 Jan '08	0	
4	196374	24.10.07	22.11.07	S		0	USD	36000	CHF	42280.2	RBT	26.11.07	USD/CHF	1.23 No touch up 24 Oct 07 to 22 Nov 07	-1418760	26.11.07
5	202099	30.10.07	28.10.08	B	C	1.23	CHF	9225000	USD	7500000	BAR	30.10.08	USD/CHF	1.1693 up and out 30 Oct 07 to 28 Oct '08	9219600	31.12.07
6	202101	30.10.07	28.10.08	S	C	1.23	CHF	9225000	USD	7500000	BAR2	30.10.08	USD/CHF	1.10 to 1.1693, 30 Oct '07 to 28 Oct '08	0	
7	202103	30.10.07	28.02.08	S		0	USD	22000	CHF	25654.2	RBT	03.03.08	USD/CHF	1.1623 and 1.1693 double one touch 30 Oct '07 to 28 Feb '08	0	
9														Net ICICI to Receive	27500840	
10																
11																
12																
13																
14																
15																
16																
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Derivative Deal between Rajshree Sugars and Chemicals Ltd & Axis Bank Ltd

On 22 June 2007, the Swiss franc traded at 1.2355 to a dollar. That was the day when Rajshree Sugars and Chemicals Ltd entered into a complex derivatives deal with Axis Bank Ltd.

According to a foreign exchange adviser whom Mint interviewed by showing the documents, presented to the Madras high court by Rajshree Sugars and Chemicals, to a foreign exchange adviser who has requested anonymity. He explains that the deal was based on three scenarios.

First scenario: In case the dollar-franc rate moves by 30 basis points on either side of the spot price on 22 June 2007—either to 1.2385 or 1.2325—the bank pays the company \$100,000.

Second scenario: If the rate touches 1.2385, the deal gets “knocked out”. It ceases to exist and neither company nor bank has any liability.

Third scenario: If the exchange rate touches 1.1250/1.200, the company has to buy \$20 million from the bank at the rate of 1.33 francs for every dollar. Thus, 1.1250/1.200 is the rate at which the derivative deal “knocks-in”.

It is in the third scenario that the company loses money on the deal. It has to buy dollars at 1.33 to a franc from the bank, when the market rate is far lower. But, as we said earlier, the Swiss franc seemed unlikely to touch that rate against the dollar when the deal was signed at the end of June 2007, since it had moved in a tight corridor in previous months.

But the Swiss currency did leap outside this corridor against the dollar, as the US greenback fell after the US Federal Reserve slashed interest rates and the world’s largest economy headed into a recession.

The sudden drop in the value of the US dollar did not surprise economists who had been predicting this for quite some time. But the financial markets had taken a very sanguine view about the scars in the US economy—a huge fiscal deficit, a growing trade gap, a housing bubble and lax lending standards in the financial system. The drop in the dollar singed many investors, including Indian companies that had bet on its stability by looking at the recent past

Misselling by Banks:

Corporates are claiming they were misguide and sold unsuitable products which far exceeded their exposure to the foreign currencies. Companies also claimed that they were sold products they didn’t understand completely. Some companies say they were made to believe that Swiss franc movement will go in same direction by showing historical data over. It can be true to some extent that companies might have been cajoled into buying certain exotic products by showing historical data by over zealous salesperson of the bank to achieve their targets. Banks gave rosy picture of how they corporate could benefit from derivatives. Banks by passed and tweaked the regulations set by RBI and offered zero cost products to the companies. They made companies write options and gave them premium for that in the disguise of rebates. Thus by passing regulation of not passing on any premium to the companies

Misadventures by Companies

There are instances of severe over-hedging and over-leveraging. For instance, an over Rs 100-crore hit from unauthorised forex derivative trades undertaken by an official of software company Hexaware resulted in a Rs 81-crore loss for the quarter ended December 2007. The company’s net profit for FY07 was Rs 110.07 crore. A Hexaware spokesperson confirmed that it has fired the official.

Zero cost derivatives were the main culprits which wiped out the companies

In the basket of products, zero-cost derivatives turned out to be the hot pick as it allowed companies to get a

better exchange rate, far more lucrative than the simple forwards, from banks and sign deals with them at no expense. While the true purpose behind such deals was to hedge the risks that a company faced from fluctuations in foreign exchange rates, the products involved complex packaging and risks that few clients understood. Companies went in for these derivatives because they were not required to pay for the cover, and often the losses increased because of the leverage that was built in

The way a zero-cost derivative differs from other contracts is that a company simultaneously buys an option as well as sells another option to the bank; the deal is structured in a manner where the premium earned from selling an option is used to pay for buying the other option, making it zero cost for the company. Consider an exporter who is anticipating a payment of \$5 million from an overseas buyer six months later.

In this old-fashioned forward transaction, the exporter has the choice to sell the dollar forward to the bank at 45 a dollar when the present market rate could be, say 43.50. However, if the exporter does a zero-cost deal, the bank offers him a rate as high as 48, something he can't resist. But here the transaction is more complicated from a simple dollar receivable. In this case, the exporter buys one put option, which gives him the 'right' to sell dollar at 48 to the bank; at the same time he sells one call option, under which he is 'obliged' to sell the dollar at 48 to the bank. Now, if the dollar is 46 when he receives the payment from abroad, he exercises the put option to sell dollar at 48, thereby earning Rs.2 more than the market rate.

But what happens when the dollar is 50? Here, it makes no sense for the exporter to exercise the put option under which he will receive only Rs 48 a dollar. However, the banks to which he is obliged to pay (as per the call option) will not ignore the opportunity. They will buy dollar at 48, causing a loss of Rs 2 a dollar to the exporter.

In real life, zero-cost options are more complex. For instance, an exporter may have sold two or three or even five call options to buy one put option. In trade parlance, these are called as 1:2, 1:3 or 1:5 options. This is where a firm is leveraged and the losses would be higher when the exchange rate moves against the exporter. For instance, in a 1:2 option, the loss to the firm would be Rs 4, and not Rs 2, when dollar is at 50. This is because it has sold two call options. Similarly, the loss would be Rs 6 and Rs 10 per dollar when the greenback is at 50. As the leverage increases — from 1:1 to 1: 3 to even 1:5, the exchange rate offered to the exporter goes up. So, he is tempted to leverage.

"It is companies' birthright to speculate over foreign exchange and then cry over the ensuing losses," says Ajay Shah, a derivatives expert and senior fellow at Delhi-based government think-tank National Institute of Public Finance and Policy (NIPFP). "But it is not the job of the government or the regulator to help companies avoid mistakes. If they did not have the discipline to mark-to-market their positions daily to assess their losses, they deserve to burn."

The fact remains that the bulk of companies, pharma major Ranbaxy among them, have made huge trading gains on forex derivatives.

Steps taken by ICICI Bank after plethora of legal cases against it:

- 1) Appropriateness Questionnaire: Client is made to fill a questionnaire based on which understanding of the client of derivative products is determined. It's also checked whether client has experienced staff to deal in exotic products. (Appropriateness Questionnaire's copy collected from ICICI Bank will be attached in Annexure)
- 2) Confirmation of the details filled in Questionnaire: After receiving the filled form clients authorized signatory who has filled up the questionnaire is called up to from recorded line to reconfirm the inform filled in the form.
- 3) Labeling of client: Based on the questionnaire client id labeled and suitable product is sold to him.
- 4) Return on Equity calculator: ROE calculator has been created under which if a dealer is trying to generate undue profit from the deal is asked to take approval from Group Head, Sr. General Manager or above depending upon the percentage of ROE.
- 5) All the products sold to the client continue to be confirmed on recorded lines, in which all the points in the term sheet are narrated to the client by the dealer and clients Ok to all the points is taken before executing the deal.

Legal Cases in Court against ICICI Bank & Out of Court Settlement:

As on 06th Aug 2009 there where 50 cases filed by / against ICICI Bank.

List of which along with the status of the cases attached in Annexure 2

Many corporate have decided not take there bankers to court and settle the matter out of court. Few companies have opted for one time settlement of dues by agreeing to pay certain amount as per the agreement with bank in one shot after which the bank will let go interest accrued on the derivative losses and agreed upon portion of the derivative losses.

A number of companies have converted their derivative losses into short loans like Atlanta Ltd. has done.

Companies are doing this because once their name appears in defaulters list of banks it will become difficult for them to secure loans for their capex and working capital requirement.

Many banks have given loans to their clients to pay for derivative losses so to avoid big derivative losses of clients to be shown as NPA's in banks books.

Action taken By RBI:

Proposal to ban selling of zero cost derivative products to corporate clients, so as to avoid companies from getting into financial mess they can't handle and to restrict them from leveraging and taking up bigger bets than their exposure. RBI has also proposed allowing companies to sell options based on their exposure that also on the basis of an underlying or an irrevocable LC. If this proposal goes through there would be a considerable decline in the exotic products that are sold to the companies.

This will also arrest the greed of companies to earn extra profits from derivatives.

Lot many companies were using derivatives as means to earn profit and not to hedge their positions.

Recommendation

Banks should explicitly mention to the client the amount of loss they will incur if their bets go wrong.

RBI should like BSE and NSE offer some courses on dealing in derivatives to the finance staff of company and ask banks to contribute certain amount to fund such an initiative.

Banks on their part should see to it that they don't sell a company a product which will wipe out all the company's profit if the bet goes wrong. Banks should create and sell such a product that if any extreme movement happens in market then maximum 60% of company's profits are only eroded.

Instead of banning products in today's market the RBI should think of making Indian market more mature and increasing the financial acumen of companies. It should allow only those companies employing MBA, CA's,

CFA's etc to deal in exotic products.

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A Model Method Of
Investment Protection In A Crashing Market

Submitted by

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Stock markets have always remained unpredictable for the investors all over the world at all the times. No one knows the level at which the market will bottom out when it is falling continuously. Similarly, no one knows the level at which the market will peak out when it is rising continuously and start falling. Moreover, the unexpected fall in a stock market may be quite steep. This is a danger for which every investor wants to have some kind of protection.

The common method used by investors all over the world is in the form of a stop loss. It is a mechanism which minimises the potential loss that may be caused to an investor when the selected stock is falling individually or when the entire stock market is crashing. However, there is bound to be some loss, which an investor has to bear.

Obviously, everyone wants to have some kind of insurance protection against this possible loss in the stock market. The idea is well known. It is available in the form of 'Index Puts', which is a form of 'Index Options'. The knowledge of 'Index Puts', which are referred as 'Puts' in this article hereafter, seldom helps an ordinary investor in protecting his investments in the falling stock market. This is because the investors do not have an idea of the way in which they are to be used. A common investor needs to have a model for the use of 'Puts'. This article makes an attempt to provide a solution to the investors in the form of the desired model.

This model is based upon the following assumptions.

The amount to be invested is minimum Rs. 10,00,000.

It is to be invested in Nifty Index Stocks.

It is to be invested for a period of minimum 3 years.

The 'Puts' can be bought and sold in the lots of 50.

The 'Puts' for the near month can always be bought and sold.

The market has some volatility i.e. it has upward and/or downward movements. In other words, it does not remain at the same level for a long period of time.

The proposed model can be modified to suit the individual requirements and risk appetite of an individual investor. The advanced users can have modifications of their own choice to the proposed model. The assumptions for such users are as follows.

The user of this model understands the concepts of 'Support' and 'Resistance' and has a working knowledge of the same.

The user understands the concept of 'Trendlines', 'BreakDown' and 'Breakout' and has a working knowledge of the same.

The user of this model understands the concept of 'Market Volatility Index' and has a working knowledge of the same.

The Model Of Investment Protection

Start with a minimum fund of Rs. 10,00,000. Invest on the first day of a month, 95% of the fund (i.e. Rs. 9,50,000) in the Nifty Stocks in the same proportion in which they form the Nifty index. Keep the remaining 5% amount available for the insurance protection in the form of 'Puts'. Use 2% of fund to buy 'Puts' at a time. You may change this percentage to suit your requirements. In our example, this amount is Rs. 20,000 (10,00,000 * 2%)

Standard Procedure to buy 'Puts' on a trading day

Step 1: Find the Close of Nifty for the previous trading day.

(Initial Nifty Close = Nifty Close so calculated at the beginning of the investment plan)

Step 2: Calculate the strike price of 'Puts' of near month to be purchased.

Strike Price = $\text{Int}(\text{Nifty Close} * 0.95 / 100) * 100$ (See Note)

Step 3: Calculate the number of lots to be purchased

No. of lots = $\text{Int}(20000/\text{Put Premium}/50)$

This is because lot size is 50 shares.

If you use a different percentage to buy 'Puts', say 1.5%, the formula will be No. of lots = $\text{Int}(15000/\text{Put Premium}/50)$

Buy 'Puts' on the first day of investment in the manner explained above. Don't panic when the market is falling. Sell the 'Puts' if and when the Nifty falls below the strike price.

You will get a handsome amount, if the Nifty really falls below the strike price. The accompanying

example for 2008 shows that the 'Puts' are purchased for Rs. 74 each on 1st Jan. 2008 and are sold for Rs. 240 each on 18th Jan. 2008 fetching Rs. 60,000 against the premium of Rs. 18,500. Similarly, 'Puts' are purchased for Rs. 21.60 each on 18th Jan. 2008 and are sold for Rs. 499.50 each on 21st Jan. 2008 fetching Rs. 4,49,550 against the premium of Rs. 19,440. Thus, fall in Nifty results into a loss on one hand and the 'Puts' fetch you handsome returns on the other hand, if the market crashes badly and unexpectedly.

If you sell the 'Puts', buy on the next trading day, 'Puts' for a new strike price by using the standard procedure. Repeat these steps throughout the month. However, don't buy new 'Puts', if the Nifty falls 20% or more from its top in a single calendar month in the same month as in Jan. 2008.

Sell the 'Puts' on the expiry of the near month, if they have a realisable value. Otherwise, the premium paid for buying the 'Puts' is lost.

In any case, i.e. whether the 'Puts' fetch any value on the expiry or not, buy 'Puts' for a new strike price on the first trading day of the next month.

Repeat the same procedure every month without bothering about the fall in Nifty.

Calculate the Profit or loss in a month as follows.

Value Of Investments = Amount Invested (Rs. 9,50,000 in our example) * Nifty Close on the last day of the concerned month / Initial Nifty Close

Total Value = Value Of Investments + Cash Available

Profit = Total Value – Initial Total Fund (Rs. 10,00,000 in our example)

An accompanying file named 'Stock Protection.xls' has three sheets. The first sheet named 2% illustrates the abovementioned calculations for the year 2008, in which the Nifty crashed historically. This sheet shows that there was a **gain of Rs. 3,00,983** in the investment in this year by using this model of investment protection. The second sheet named 1.5% (in which the amount used to buy 'Puts' at a time is 1.5% of Rs. 10,00,000 i.e. Rs. 15,000) shows modified calculations resulting into a **gain of Rs. 88.183** during the same period with a lesser risk of loss of premium. The third sheet named 1.25% (in which the amount used to buy 'Puts' at a time is 1.25% of Rs. 10,00,000 i.e. Rs. 12,500) shows calculations for even lesser risk and results into a **loss of Rs. 36,722**. These three sheets are enough to illustrate how an individual investor can introduce modifications of his choice to this model. The third sheet shows that using as little as 1.25% of the total fund for the purchase of 'Puts' at a time may not necessarily result into desired gains.

Note: Strike Price = Int(Nifty Close * 0.95 / 100) * 100 (Normally)

However, the accompanying file shows calculations as follows.

Strike Price = Int(Nifty Close * 0.95 / 50) * 50

This is because currently, the strike price interval is 100 whereas it was 50 in 2008.

Limitations of the model

This model will protect your investments and even make gains for you when there are fluctuations in the stock market. There are four alternative situations.

Situation1 : The Nifty is rising continuously in a month.

You will lose all the 'Put' Premium in that month. However, there will be appreciation in the value of your investments. Finally, you don't lose.

Situation2 : The Nifty is falling continuously in a month.

You will gain a lot by selling 'Puts' in that month. However, there will be fall in the value of your investments. Finally, you don't lose.

Situation3 : The Nifty is rising and falling in a month.

You will gain by selling 'Puts' when the Nifty is falling in that month. However, there will be fall in the value of your investments during that period. You will lose all the 'Put' Premium when the Nifty is rising in that month. However, there will be appreciation in the value of your investments during that period. Finally, you don't lose.

Situation4 : The Nifty is almost at the same level in a month. You lose all the 'Put' premium in that month on one hand. On the other, there is no appreciation in the value of investments in that month. Finally, you have a loss of 'Put' premium paid by you.

If the situation remains like this throughout a year (which is unlikely), you keep on making losses every month in that year. Obviously, if you use 2% of the fund to buy 'Puts' at a time, you lose 24% of the fund in a year (2% every month). if you use 1.5% of the fund to buy 'Puts' at a time, you lose 18% of the fund in a year (1.5% every month). So, you have to decide how much of the fund you will use to buy 'Puts' at a time.

Possible Modifications to the model

You can calculate the strike price in a different way like $\text{Strike Price} = \text{Int}(\text{Nifty Close} * 0.96 / 100) * 100$ or $\text{Strike Price} = \text{Int}(\text{Nifty Close} * 0.97 / 100) * 100$ or $\text{Strike Price} = \text{Int}(\text{Nifty Close} * 0.90 / 100) * 100$. Remember that the closer the strike price to the Nifty, the higher is the 'Put' premium and higher are the chances of making gains as far as selling of 'Puts' is concerned. Also, the 'Put' premium is very low, if the strike price is far from Nifty and the chances of making gains out of the same are very thin.

Data Source Website : <http://www.nseindia.com/>

MODELING RISK AND INNOVATION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine through a modeling process whether the sources of risk management in project's innovation can be managed better. The diversity of theories over the nature of risk is a major problem to proactively manage 'risk' in the process of innovation, from conceptualization to commercialization. Several approaches to risk management have been proposed, although the relevance for innovation management is uncertain. This paper focuses the formation and management of uncertainties in a context and the deployment of risk management's techniques. The process of risk management is applied in a specific case using a general model of innovation to manage the parameters of risk creation.

Keywords: Innovation, management, risk, risk management

Conceptual paper.

1. Introduction

Establishing something new is the essence of product innovation. Since this process necessarily involves risk, an early risk identification and management is required in innovative firms. So the purpose of this paper is to explore methods for managing risk in the innovation projects. In the meantime, the proposal method for managing the risk in specific kind of innovation will be explained more. In the next section, definition of innovation and different types of innovations are described. Continuously, different stages of innovation are presented. Section three illustrates the definition of risk, sources of risk and risk management systems. Section four states the methodology of this research. Section five explains the proposal method for managing the risk in the innovation projects and includes the example of that and section six concludes this paper.

2. Innovation

Innovation is the main source of economic growth (Mokyr, 2002) and a key source of new employment opportunities as well as providing potential for realizing environmental benefits (Foxona et al., 2005). One of

the most important arguments is that, in the global economy, where economic actions can be more cheaply carried out in the low-wage economies such as China, the main way in which the other economies can compete and survive, is to find new and better products and processes, In other words, to innovate (Storey and Salaman, 2005). According to the Oxford Dictionary of Economics 'innovation refers to the economic application of a new idea. Product innovation involves a new or modified product; process innovation involves a new or modified way of making a product' (Black, 1997). According to Afuah (2003) innovation is the employing of new knowledge to provide a new product or service that the customers want. In another words, it is invention + commercialization. Van de Ven (1986) describes innovation in terms of a new idea, which may be a recombination of old ideas, a plan that challenges the present order, a formula, or an exclusive method which is perceived as new by the involved individuals.

Literature provides different categories of innovation classified by type, degree, competence, impact, and ownership (Narvekar and Jain, 2006). Innovation can be considered in both manufacturing and service sectors of different sizes (small, medium and large). Although there is a difference between these two sectors, the general definition and process of innovation are the same. Services have their own characteristics different from manufacturing. For instance, services are intangible, perishable and heterogeneous (John and Storey, 1997). Tidd et al. (2005) say innovation is not just about opening up new markets; it can also present new ways of serving older and established ones. He classifies the innovation into 4 groups (Product, Process, Position and Paradigm) each of which can happen along an axis, running from incremental through radical change. Incremental product innovation entails the introduction of an improved product, which, compared with its predecessor, has at least one additional desirable characteristic or is efficient with the same characteristics. In contrast, radical or fundamental product innovation takes place when a new market has opened up and the innovator begins to satisfy a hidden demand (Ferguson and Ferguson, 1994).

By considering the different kinds of innovation which is mentioned above, for this study three dimensions were selected to classify the innovation types. First one is based on kind of company (manufacturing or service).The other one considers the innovation based on product or service. Among different kinds of innovation which are mentioned in the literature like marketing, organization, position, and paradigm and so on, the product and process were selected. Since it seems in general point of view all of these different kinds of innovation can be categorized based on these two dimensions (product and process). Also these two kinds of innovation are more common in comparison with other ones. The last dimension assesses the innovation according to incremental or radical. The degree of novelty has an effect on this dimension. It means if the degree of novelty increases (based on the national or international consideration), the dimension is moving from incremental to radical situation. In general, the kind of risk management is more related to incremental or radical dimension. Radical innovation has high risk in comparison with incremental which has a low risk. So for managing the risk in the radical one (which sometimes this innovation is new in the world or country) the more complex risk management methods (e.g.: Risk Standard Model) are needed.

In incremental situation that are like the improvement, the simple risk methods (e.g.: risk log) can be used. It should be paid attention that the size of company can affect on amount and kind of risk

management. For example one small company may spend a lot of time and uses the different and precise method for managing the risk in one incremental innovation project, since it has a limited resources but a big company just uses the one and simple method for the same project. In this paper the proposal method -Risk Standard Model- for managing the risk in radical innovation will be explained.

It is suggested by several studies that there is usually a formal process for developing new products and services in firms with high performance in innovation (Griffin, 1997; Tatikonda and Rosenthal, 2000 and Shaw et al., 2001). In service firms, however, it does not appear to be common to use the formal process (Mitchell Madison Group, 1995). This formal process includes 'creativity and ideas management, selection and portfolio management and implementation management' (Oke, 2007). Tidd et al. (2005) argue that innovation is a general activity associated with growth and survival and a common fundamental process can be seen in all firms, which involve: Searching, Selecting, Implementing and Learning.

A stage-gate approach for managing the process of innovation (which has been adopted by many firms) is recommended by Cooper (1999); it allows the firms to manage, direct and control their innovation efforts. However, there is a major critique of Cooper's stage-gate approach, which focuses mainly on process factors. Other organizational factors which have an impact on innovation performance need to be considered. The Pentathlon framework (Goffin and Pfeiffer, 1999; Oke and Goffin, 2001) is a general one for managing innovation which addresses several soft organizational and process issues. Goffin and Pfeiffer (1999) declare that in order to achieve successful innovation management, companies should perform well in five areas and make sure that efforts in these areas are integrated. Narvekar and Jain (2006) point out another framework for considering innovation. This framework demonstrates an interactive innovation process which has three stages: ideation, incubation and demonstration.

The inputs to the process are the triggers through in-house R&D (human and structural capital), feedback from customer (relational capital) or through a serendipitous incident. The intuitive nature of those who involved in the innovation and the absorptive capacity of the organization, intervene here to have an influence on the production of the innovation process. Usually, the output of the process is a patent or a new process or a new product. In spite of having many models of the technological innovation process in literature, the process is not vivid (Narvekar and Jain, 2006). Innovations vary widely in terms of nature, scale, degree of novelty etc. However it can be seen that the same basic process is operating in each case (Tidd et al., 2005). In summary, each innovation projects (in all manufacturing or service industry) may have five following stages:

1- Creativity

Searching the external and internal environment and processing relevant signals about threats, opportunities and also ideation.

2- Selection

Preliminary assessment and deciding by considering a strategic view of how the organization can be

best developed; to know which of these signals to respond to.

3- Incubation

Transacting to the actual product development and producing the prototype production.

4- Implementation

Translating the potential idea into something new and launching it in an external or internal market.

5- Learning

Learning from progressing and building their knowledge base and improving the ways in which the process is managed.

3. Risk

For companies in order to launch new products speedily and successfully, taking risk is essential. The ability to identify and manage risk is considered to be vitally important in risky innovation. There is no single, universally employed definition of the word risk (Green and Serbein, 1983). Its definition is changing as it becomes interwoven with innovation and a rapidly globalizing world. Companies in order to survive must innovate at a previously unparalleled rate and within the framework of greater uncertainty. This means the risks they take are deepening (Taplin, 2005). In the more technical and specialized literature, as Ansell and Wharton (1992) say, the word risk is used to imply a measurement of the chance of an outcome, the size of the outcome or a combination of both. According to the standard definition of risk, it is "the combination of the frequency or probability of occurrence and the consequence of a specified hazardous event" (Edwards and Bowen, 2005). Some former writers in the field drew a distinction between uncertainty and risk. A risk situation is defined as one in which a probability distribution for consequences is made on a meaningful basis, agreed upon by the set of relevant experts, and therefore it is 'known'. Uncertain situations arise when an agreement among the group of experts cannot be gained, so there will be an undefined probability distribution on the set of outcomes (Hertz & Thomas, 1919).

Any factor affecting project performance can be a source of risk, and when this effect is both uncertain and significant in its impact on project performance, the risk arises (Chapman and Ward, 1997). Ackermann et al. (2007) argue that the categorization of risk in a simple way can be extremely unhelpful since the categories may be viewed as independent of each other. In addition to considering a wider range of risk categories, it is significant to consider more than just the risks themselves but also their impact on one another. In order to represent the different aspects of risk in an accurate way, it is important to consider risk as systemic. According to them the categorization of risk is: Political, Customer, Partner and Supplier, People, Reputation, Market and Financial. In other categorization of sources of risk based on Green and Serbein (1983), risk aspects of the enterprise may be considered under the following major headings: Property and personnel, Marketing, Finance, Personnel and production, Environment. So with paying attention to the different sources of risk and purpose of this paper, the best categorization of them, which suits for this study, could be found as follow:

- Environment (government policy, exchange rates, availability of skilled labor, weather, culture)
- Technical (new methods, technologies, materials)
- Resources (staff, materials, finance)
- Integration (software modules, new & old systems)
- Management (multiple parties' experience, use of project management techniques, HRM, set the tight goals, product transition management, organization structure, organization behavior)
- Marketing (customer, competitors)
- Strategy

Risk management means 'the process of understanding the nature of uncertain future events and making positive plans to mitigate them where they present threat or to take advantage of them where they present opportunities' (Taplin, 2005). By considering that one of the main features of innovation will always be 'risk', risk management needs to facilitate innovation rather than stifle it (Taplin, 2005). A methodical approach to risk management enhances the ability of an organization to manage risks at all stages. The important purpose of risk management is to improve project performance by means of systematic identification, appraisal and management of project-related risk (Chapman and Ward, 1997). A systematic approach to risk management has to encourage decision-making inside an organization which is more controlled, more consistent and yet at the same time more flexible (Edwards and Bowen, 2005). According to Edwards and Bowen (2005) it is safe to say that a good risk management system for a project should encompass these processes: Establishing the appropriate context(s), recognizing the risk of the project which the stakeholder organization will face, analyzing the identified risk, developing responses to those risks, controlling and Monitoring the risks during the project, and allowing post-project capture of risk knowledge. Chapman and Ward (1997) say that most specific risk management processes are explained in terms of phases (stages) which are decomposed in a variety of ways, some are related to tasks (activities), and some are related to deliverables (outputs/products). They present the nine-phase RMP that is more detailed than most specific process. This structure depicts an alternative approach to managing risk. Smith and Merritt (2002) provide the other process for managing the risk. This process consists of 5 steps for managing the risk.

In summary, it can be said that all risk management systems have the four following phases:

1. Identifying parameters (defining and focusing)
2. Analyzing (probabilities and prioritizing)
3. Solving (e.g.: Defer action for more information, Accept risk, Buy out risk (transfer to a third party), Parallel contingency development)
4. Monitoring and learning (New risk identification, Creating action plan for risks now above threshold, Concluding successful action plan and redeploying resources, Documenting the experience for use in future projects)

4. Methodology

By considering the different kinds of purpose of research and research strategy, also some criteria for selecting

the kind of research strategy (especially research questions), this research uses the case study as a strategy for research. As research project may have more than one purpose; this research is also placed between explanatory and exploratory research. This research concentrates more on the qualitative approach than quantitative, because finding the quantitative data during the innovation project is very difficult and at some points impossible (There are not any quantitative documents in different companies about innovation projects which they had done). Because of the importance of theoretical model in any kind of case study, this study started the research with a hypothesis model.

There are five decision points in this process. Each of these points need some information/criteria for approving the last stage and going to next stage (or back or abandon) and also should consider the parameters which create the risk in the next step. This is a dynamic diagram and there is an interconnection and overlap between different decision points. Based on hypothesis model, this structure is a method for better fitting the innovation process and risk management system together. These different stages of risk and innovation and elementary model for matching these two issues were considered in some cases from Iran and UK. Based on the purpose, strategy of research and method of gathering the data, also with considering the different definitions of analyzing method, the explanation building is the method for analyzing the data in this thesis. In this paper, the second step of risk management system (analyzing) will be explained more.

5. Method for Managing Risk in the Innovation Projects

Keizer et al. (1991) have been developing a novel method to diagnose and control risks in innovation projects: the Risk Diagnosing Methodology (RDM). This method lets a firm identify comprehensively and systematically the technological, organizational and business risks that a project might faces, and to formulate and implement appropriate risk management strategies. This method includes nine steps which are: 'initial briefing, kick-off meeting, individual interviewing of participants, processing the interviews (design of a risk questionnaire), answering the risk questionnaire, constructing the risk profile, preparing a risk management session, risk management session, drawing up and execution of a risk management plan' (Keizer et al., 2001).

In risk analysis, typically we are trying to understand, how risks are generated, assessing their probabilities and impact, ranking them and screening out minor risk (Emblemsvag and Kjolstad, 2006). Proper risk analysis lets an organization to achieve an understanding of the relative severity of its risks on a project (Edwards and Bowen, 2005). Different methods for analyzing risk from quantitative to qualitative, include: Monte Carlo simulation, Hazard identification methods, Failure modes and effect analysis, Fault tree analysis, Event tree analysis, What if' scenarios, Risk Mapping, Influence diagram etc.

Method which will be used in this research consists of four phases. In following, the summary of different stages of this method (how they work) will be described and in next section the case application will be explained for analyzing the risk. It should be emphasized that various parameters like kind of innovation,

industry and company have an effect on method, so therefore different methods may be appropriate for different conditions. Consequently this general method should be calibrated with different situations. For the first phase of risk management -Identifying Parameters- some of the parameters can be selected as parameters that create risks based on the kind of industry, size of companies, the countries which the companies are located in and situation of company. In the second phase -Analyzing- the company should estimate probabilities of events and the impact of their consequence and also prioritize these different risk factors in order to solve them, because, the company cannot solve all the risks (limited recourses, time etc.) and also the innovation is inherently risky, and if the company wants to manage all risks, it may cause to stifle the innovation. With considering the conditions of radical innovation, standard risk model would be a good method for this purpose (figure1). Based on this method, expected loss for each of the risks could be calculated, and the risks could be prioritized based on the expected loss. Risk events are the parameters which are recognized as risk. But for calculating the probability of risk event and probability of impact, the following method can be used. For instance, it can be assumed that the Technical is the risk event. Based on different parameters which are mentioned as a risk, technical risk includes three risk event drivers which create this risk. These risk events are: new methods, technologies and new materials.

Figure 1 - Standard risk model (Smith and Merritt, 2002) (Expected loss $(L_e) = L_t * P_e * P_i$)

For each of these risk events, different scenarios could be written with different probabilities of success (Table 1) (In different situations these scenarios and their probabilities could be changed). So after calculating the probabilities of success, P_e can be calculated as: $P_e = 1 - P_{\text{success}} = 1 - (P_1 * P_2 * \dots)$

Table 1 - Risk event probability

Risk event: Technical			
Risk event drivers			Probability of success
new methods (P_1)	technologies (P_2)	new materials (P_3)	
			0.9
			0.7
			0.5
			0.3
			0.1

To find the reasons for each of the risk events drivers, the scenario method could be used. Same method could be applied for impact. Each of these parameters which create the risk is more effective in one or some of the stages of innovation project, and cause the problem(s) in these stages. Although in general, they affect the whole stages; separating them is also possible. According to Table 2, if each of the risk events affects different stages of innovation, they would have different probability of success. If they affect more than one stage, the probability of success is equal to multiplying them. So the probability of failure for impact (P_i) equals one minus the probability of success.

Table 2 - Impact probability

Impact	Probability of success
learning	0.9
creativity	0.7
selection	0.5
incubation	0.3
implementation	0.1

For calculating the expected loss, total loss should also be found. But it could be assumed that the total loss for all risk is equal, because all of these risks will cause the reduction of success in the market and losing the profit. So if the total loss were the same for all risk events and impact, it does not have an effect on prioritizing the risk. Thus all risk could be prioritized based on result of multiply P_e and P_i , because the L_i in all is equal. In phase three, the company should find different methods for solving these risks in different stages of innovation and in phase four, the company should monitor the process and also learn for future risk management system.

6. Case application

In this section the proposed method for analyzing the risk in risk management system will be applied for one case. January 2003, lightweight Medical³ directors Neil Tierney and Neil Farish were considering the options open to their Edinburgh-based industrial design company. The commercialization fund upon which the development of their Lightweight Incubator for Neonatal Transport (LINT) product depended on to secure patenting had failed to materialize. According to parameters which create the risk during the innovation project and also information based on case, it can be said that environment, marketing and resources are three parameters which are creating the risk during this case. So in second phase these parameters should be considered and prioritized.

Tables 3, 4 and 5 suggest these three risk event (marketing, resources and environment) with their risk drivers. In the Lightweight case, for Resources risk, just finance plays a role as a risk event driver. In Marketing risk all three drivers (customer, competitor and market) exist and in Environment risk event, intellectual property is as a risk event driver. For each risk event the $P_e * P_i$ for prioritizing them are calculated as shown bellow.

Marketing (

Table 3)

$$\begin{array}{l}
 P_1 = 0.7 \\
 P_2 = 0.5
 \end{array}
 \left. \vphantom{\begin{array}{l} P_1 = 0.7 \\ P_2 = 0.5 \end{array}} \right\}
 P_{\text{success}} = 0.7 * 0.5 * 0.5 = 0.175 \quad \Rightarrow \quad P_e = 1 - P_{\text{success}} = 0.825$$

$$P_3 = 0.5$$

Marketing has an effect on implementation stage of innovation $\Rightarrow P_i = 1 - 0.1 = 0.9$

$$P_e * P_i = 0.7425$$

Table 3 – Risk event drivers for marketing

Risk event: Marketing			
Risk event drivers			Probability of success
(P ₁) Customer †	(P ₂) Competitor ‡	(P ₃) Market	
Product is different and best in all attributes and satisfy all of the new demands of customers	There is not any competitor product and entrance to this market is difficult	The company is in this market and has a relation with customer and also supplier and buyer are in coordination with the new idea	0.9
Product is different and best in some attributes and satisfy some new demands of customers	There is not any competitor product and entrance to this market is easy	The company is in the similar market but has a relation with customer and also supplier and buyer are in coordination with the new idea	0.7
Product is different and has advantages in one or two attributes but it can't satisfy the new demands of customers	Products with low capabilities of competing and difficulty for entrance to this market	The company is not in this market but has a relation with customer and also supplier and buyer are in coordination with the new idea	0.5

Product just has advantage in comparison with present products	There are competitors product and entrance to this market is difficult	The company is in this market just as a "niche" and does not have a direct relation with customer and also supplier and buyer are not in coordination with the new idea	0.3
Product is different and has advantages in one or two attributes but it is worse in other attributes and can't satisfy new demands of customers	There are powerful competitor products and entrance to this market is easy	The company is not in this market or the similar and does not have a relation with customer and also supplier and buyer are not in coordination with the new idea	0.1

† Intervener Parameter: introducing the future innovation before the maturity in life cycle of the previous innovation in the market, would have a negative effect on the probability of success.

‡ Intervener Parameter: if the competitors advertise about their future products which is not yet in the market, but with good attributes of competitions, this would have a negative effect on the probability of success.

Resources (Table 4)

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \\ \\ \end{array} \right\} P_{\text{success}} = 0.5 \implies P_e = 1 - P_{\text{success}} = 0.5$$

$$P_1 = 0.5$$

Resources has an effect on implementation and incubation stages of innovation

$$\implies P_i = 1 - (0.1 * 0.3) = 0.97$$

$$P_e * P_i = 0.485$$

Table 4 - Risk event drivers for resources

Risk event: Resources	
Risk event drivers	Probability of success
(P ₁) Financet	
Financial resources for innovation is enough within the company	0.9
Financial resources for innovation should be supplied with external and some available external resources and good proposal is accessible	0.7
Financial resources for innovation are not in the company and they should be supplied from available external resources and a good proposal is accessible	0.5
Financial resources for innovation are not in the company but the familiarity with external sources is available and a relatively good proposal is accessible	0.3
Financial resources for innovation are not in the company and for consuming the external resources, researches should be done as there is no familiarity with them and a relatively good proposal is accessible	0.1

† Intervener Parameter: broad range of innovation would have a negative effect on the probability of success.

Environment (Table 5)

$$P_1 = 0.7 \quad \left. \vphantom{P_1} \right\} \quad P_{\text{success}} = 0.7 \quad \Rightarrow \quad P_e = 1 - P_{\text{success}} = 0.3$$

Environment has an effect on implementation, incubation, selection and creativity stages of innovation $\Rightarrow P_i$

$$= 1 - (0.1 * 0.3 * 0.5 * 0.7) = 0.9895 \quad P_e * P_i = 0.297$$

Table 5 - Risk event drivers for environment

Risk event: Environment	
Risk event drivers	Probability of success
(P ₁) Intellectual property	
intellectual property rules are done completely and within the short time	0.9
intellectual property rules are done completely but within the relatively long time	0.7
intellectual property rules are done partially complete and within the short time	0.5
intellectual property rules are done partially complete and within the relatively long time	0.3
intellectual property rules are done incomplete and within the long time	0.1

So with pay attention to these results the company at first should consider the marketing risk after that, resources and in the last one environment. Also company based on their abilities should find the methods for solving some or all of these risks.

6. Conclusion

On the one hand companies need innovation to endure in the market competition but on the other hand one of the most important aspects of innovation is risk. If the companies do not consider the risk, the project will be failed and if they apply a lot of risk management systems, these methods could stifle the innovation. This research attempts to provide the system for managing the risk in the innovation projects and also to create a method for prioritizing different risks factors and to manage the most important ones in second stage of this risk management system for some kind of innovation.

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